

Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers from 0 to 10000 Using Square Function

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Abstract

*This work brings natural numbers from 0 to 10.000 written in two different forms. Increasing and decreasing orders of 1 to 9 and 9 to 1. This is done using **square function** along with basic operations. Previously, the author also worked [7]-[27] with numbers up to 300.000 using only basic operations along with **square-root, factorial**, etc. For more details refer author's work in reference list. Similar kind of work is given with **Triangular numbers** [40] and **Fibonacci sequence values** [?]. This kind of work using **square function** is never seen before in the literature.*

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1 Introduction

First we shall give some different ways of representing natural numbers using the digits 0 to 9 or 1 to 9. See the subsections below

1.1 Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers

In this section natural numbers are* represented in three different types.

1.1.1 Increasing and Decreasing

In 2014, author [7] wrote natural numbers in increasing and decreasing orders of 1 to 9 and 9 to 1. See examples below:

$$\begin{aligned}100 &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 \times 9 = 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\101 &:= 1 + 2 + 34 + 5 + 6 \times 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\102 &:= 12 + 3 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\103 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 34 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4 + 3 + 21 \\104 &:= 1 + 23 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 65 + 4 \times 3 + 2 + 1 \\105 &:= 1 + 2 \times 3 \times 4 + 56 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\106 &:= 12 + 3 + 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\107 &:= 1 \times 23 + 4 + 56 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 76 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 \times 1 \\108 &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 78 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 76 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1.\end{aligned}$$

See more examples,

$$\begin{aligned}786 &:= 1 + 23 + 4 + 56 + 78 \times 9 = 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 \times 4 \times 3 \times 2 + 1 \\999 &:= 12 \times 3 \times (4 + 5) + (67 + 8) \times 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 654 + 321 \\2535 &:= 1 + 2345 + (6 + 7 + 8) \times 9 = 9 + 87 \times (6 + 5 \times 4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\2607 &:= 123 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + (7 + 8) \times 9 = 987 + 6 \times 54 \times (3 + 2) \times 1 \\10483 &:= 1 + 23 \times 456 - 7 - 8 + 9 = (9 \times 87 \times 6 + 543) \times 2 + 1 \\10549 &:= 1^2 + 34 \times 5 \times (6 + 7 \times 8) + 9 = 9 + (87 \times 6 + 5) \times 4 \times (3 + 2) \times 1 \\10550 &:= 1^2 + 34 \times 5 \times (6 + 7 \times 8) + 9 = 9 + (87 \times 6 + 5) \times 4 \times (3 + 2) + 1 \\10553 &:= 1 \times 23 \times 456 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times 5 \times 43 + 21) \\10554 &:= 1 + 23 \times 456 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) \times 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\11807 &:= 1 \times 234 \times (5 + 6 \times 7) + 89 = -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3)^2 \times 1.\end{aligned}$$

For more details refer [7]-[27]. These works brings the representations of natural numbers from 1 to 300.000. Soon, we shall extend it to half-milion, i.e., 500.000.

2 Triangular Numbers and Fibonacci Numbers

Triangular numbers are very much famous in the literature of mathematics [?]. These are given by

$$1, 3, 6, 10, 15, 21, \dots$$

The general formula to write these numbers is given by

$$T(n) = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots = \frac{n+1}{2} = C(n+1, 2)$$

The letter "C" represents as "**binomial coefficient**" as seen in subsection ??.

In this paper our aim is to bring **selfie numbers** by used of **triangle numbers**. This we have done in subsequent sections. Due to high quantity of numbers, we restricted our work up to four digits, i.e., from 1 to 9999. There are different ways of calling these numbers, such as, **tri-gonal**, **triangular** or **triangle selfie numbers**. For simplicity, we shall call them as **triangular selfie numbers**.

2.1 Natural Numbers in Terms of Fibonacci Sequence and Triangular Values

Below are few examples of natural numbers written in terms of **Fibonacci sequence** and **Triangular number** values.

1 := $F(2)$	1 := $T(1)$	22 := $F(2) + F(8)$	22 := $T(1) + T(6)$
2 := $F(3)$		23 := $F(3) + F(8)$	
3 := $F(4)$	3 := $T(2)$	24 := $F(4) + F(8)$	24 := $T(2) + T(6)$
4 := $F(2) + F(4)$	4 := $T(1) + T(2)$	25 := $F(2) + F(4) + F(8)$	25 := $T(4) + T(5)$
5 := $F(5)$		26 := $F(5) + F(8)$	26 := $T(1) + T(4) + T(5)$
6 := $F(2) + F(5)$	6 := $T(3)$	27 := $F(2) + F(5) + F(8)$	27 := $T(3) + T(6)$
7 := $F(3) + F(5)$	7 := $T(1) + T(3)$	28 := $F(3) + F(5) + F(8)$	28 := $T(7)$
8 := $F(6)$		29 := $F(6) + F(8)$	29 := $T(1) + T(7)$
9 := $F(2) + F(6)$	9 := $T(2) + T(3)$	30 := $F(2) + F(6) + F(8)$	30 := $T(2) + T(3) + T(6)$
10 := $F(3) + F(6)$	10 := $T(4)$	31 := $F(3) + F(6) + F(8)$	31 := $T(2) + T(7)$
11 := $F(4) + F(6)$	11 := $T(1) + T(4)$	32 := $F(4) + F(6) + F(8)$	32 := $T(1) + T(2) + T(7)$
12 := $F(2) + F(4) + F(6)$		33 := $F(2) + F(4) + F(6) + F(8)$	
13 := $F(7)$	13 := $T(2) + T(4)$	34 := $F(9)$	34 := $T(3) + T(7)$
14 := $F(2) + F(7)$	14 := $T(1) + T(2) + T(4)$	35 := $F(2) + F(9)$	35 := $T(1) + T(3) + T(7)$
15 := $F(3) + F(7)$	15 := $T(5)$	36 := $F(3) + F(9)$	36 := $T(8)$
16 := $F(4) + F(7)$	16 := $T(1) + T(5)$	37 := $F(4) + F(9)$	37 := $T(1) + T(8)$
17 := $F(2) + F(4) + F(7)$	17 := $T(1) + T(3) + T(4)$	38 := $F(2) + F(4) + F(9)$	38 := $T(4) + T(7)$
18 := $F(5) + F(7)$	18 := $T(2) + T(5)$	39 := $F(5) + F(9)$	39 := $T(2) + T(8)$
19 := $F(2) + F(5) + F(7)$	19 := $T(1) + T(2) + T(5)$	40 := $F(2) + F(5) + F(9)$	40 := $T(1) + T(2) + T(8)$
20 := $F(3) + F(5) + F(7)$			
21 := $F(8)$	21 := $T(6)$		

For more details refer author's work [35].

2.2 Selfie Numbers: Palindromic-Type

This section brings *selfie palindromic numbers* by use of triangular numbers. The idea of starting the work with palindromic numbers is as they are symmetric in itself, i.e., remains the same by changing the order of digits. Below are *selfie palindromic numbers*:

$$66 := T(T(T(6)))/T(6)$$

$$171 := T(17+1)$$

$$222 := T(T(2))^{T(2)} + T(T(2))$$

$$232 := -2 + T(T(T(3))) + T(2)$$

$$242 := T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(4) + T(T(T(2)))$$

$$252 := (T(T(2)) + T(T(5))) \times 2$$

$$525 := 5 \times T(T(T(2))) \times 5$$

$$666 := T(-6 + T(6) + T(6))$$

$$696 := T(T(6)) + T(9 + T(6))$$

$$777 := T(7) \times T(7) - 7$$

$$969 := T(T(9)) - T(6) - T(9)$$

$$2222 := (T(T(2))^{T(T(2))} + T(T(2)))/T(T(T(2)))$$

$$2332 := T(2^{T(3)}) + T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(2)))$$

$$2442 := (-T(T(2)) + T(T(4) \times 4)) \times T(2)$$

$$2552 := (T(T(2))^5 - T(T(5)))/T(2)$$

$$2662 := 2 \times (T(T(6))/T(6))^{T(2)}$$

$$2772 := -T(2) + T(77 - T(2))$$

$$3003 := T(T(T(T(3)))/003)$$

$$3333 := T(T(T(3))) + T(T(3)) + T(T(T(3) + T(3)))$$

$$3773 := T(T(T(3))) - T(7) + T(T(7) \times 3)$$

$$3993 := -T(3 \times 9) + T(93)$$

$$4224 := T(42) + T(T(2)^4)$$

$$4334 := T(T(T(4))) \times 3 - T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4))$$

$$4884 := (-T(T(4)) + T(T(8))) \times 8 - 4$$

$$5445 := T(54) \times T(T(4))/T(5)$$

$$5665 := T(5) \times T(T(6) + 6) - 5$$

$$5775 := T(5) \times 77 \times 5$$

$$5995 := 5 \times T(T(9)) + T(T(9) - 5)$$

$$6336 := (T(6) + T(T(3 \times 3))) \times 6$$

$$9339 := T(9) \times T(T(T(3))) - T(T(3)) - T(T(9))$$

For more examples of similar type refer author's work [?].

2.3 Selfie Numbers: Symmetric Representations

In this section, we shall give **selfie numbers** in terms of **triangular numbers** along with basic operations. These representations are in symmetric way, i.e., all is same except the digits 0 to 9. This happens in both ways, i.e., in digit's order and in reverse order of digits. In some cases numbers can written in both the ways. Below are examples of numbers written in digit's order and its reverse:

$$120 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 0 = 0 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$121 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 1 = 1 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$122 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 2 = 2 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$123 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 3 = 3 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$124 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 4 = 4 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$125 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 5 = 5 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$126 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 6 = 6 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$127 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 7 = 7 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$128 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 8 = 8 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$129 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 9 = 9 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$210 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 0 = 0 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$211 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 1 = 1 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$212 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 2 = 2 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$213 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 3 = 3 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$214 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 4 = 4 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$215 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 5 = 5 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$216 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 6 = 6 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$217 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 7 = 7 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$218 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 8 = 8 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$219 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 9 = 9 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$990 := T(T(9)) - T(9) + 0 = 0 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$991 := T(T(9)) - T(9) + 1 = 1 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$992 := T(T(9)) - T(9) + 2 = 2 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$993 := T(T(9)) - T(9) + 3 = 3 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$994 := T(T(9)) - T(9) + 4 = 4 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$995 := T(T(9)) - T(9) + 5 = 5 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$996 := T(T(9)) - T(9) + 6 = 6 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$997 := T(T(9)) - T(9) + 7 = 7 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$998 := T(T(9)) - T(9) + 8 = 8 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

$$999 := T(T(9)) - T(9) + 9 = 9 + T(T(9)) - T(9)$$

For more examples of similar type refer author's work [?].

2.4 Selfie Numbers: General Representations

$$\begin{aligned} 15 &:= T(1 \times 5) \\ &:= T(5) \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21 &:= T(T(1+2)) \\ &:= T(T(2+1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23 &:= 2 + T(T(3)) \\ &:= T(T(3)) + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24 &:= T(T(2)) \times 4 \\ &:= 4 \times T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34 &:= -T(T(3)) + T(T(4)) \\ &:= T(T(4)) - T(T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36 &:= T(3) \times 6 \\ &:= 6 \times T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39 &:= -T(3) + T(9) \\ &:= T(9) - T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45 &:= T(4+5) \\ &:= T(5+4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 49 &:= 4 + T(9) \\ &:= T(9) + 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55 &:= T(5+5) \\ &:= T(5+5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 63 &:= T(6) \times 3 \\ &:= 3 \times T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 105 &:= T(-1 + T(05)) \\ &:= T(T(5) - 01) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 132 &:= (1 + T(T(3))) \times T(T(2)) \\ &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(3)) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 135 &:= T(-1 + T(3)) + T(T(5)) \\ &:= T(T(5)) + T((T(3) - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 136 &:= T(T(1+3)) + 6 \\ &:= T(6 + T(3+1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 147 &:= T(T(-1+4)) \times 7 \\ &:= 7 \times T(T(4-1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 152 &:= -1 + T(T(5) + 2) \\ &:= T(2 + T(5)) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 154 &:= T(T(T(-1+5)))/T(4) \\ &:= T(T(T(4)))/T(5-1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 167 &:= -1 + 6 \times T(7) \\ &:= T(7) \times 6 - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 168 &:= 1 \times T(6) \times 8 \\ &:= 8 \times T(6 \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 176 &:= 1 + T(T(7)) - T(T(6)) \\ &:= -T(T(6)) + T(T(7)) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 185 &:= (1 + T(8)) \times 5 \\ &:= 5 \times (T(8) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 186 &:= -T(1+8) + T(T(6)) \\ &:= T(T(6)) - T(8+1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 221 &:= -T(1 + T(2)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(2) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$223 := -2^{T(2)} + T(T(T(3)))$$

$$:= T(T(T(3))) - 2^{T(2)}$$

$$:= T(7) + T(54 \times 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 224 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(2) - 4 \\ &:= -T(4) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1462 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(6) - 2 \\ &:= -T(2 \times 6) + T(T(T(4 \times 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 225 &:= T(2 + T(2)) \times T(5) \\ &:= (5 \times T(2))^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1463 &:= 1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(6 + T(3)) \\ &:= -T(T(3) + 6) + T(T(T(4))) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 226 &:= -2 - T(2) + T(T(6)) \\ &:= T(T(6)) - 2 - T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1464 &:= T(T(T(1 \times 4))) - T(6) - T(T(4)) \\ &:= T(T(T(4))) - T(6) - T(T(4 \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1446 &:= T(-1 + 4) \times (T(4) + T(T(6))) \\ &:= (T(T(6)) + T(4)) \times T(4 - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1472 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - 7 - T(T(2)) \\ &:= -T(T(2)) - 7 + T(T(T(4)) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1447 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(4) - T(7) \\ &:= -T(7) - T(4) + T(T(T(4)) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1474 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - 7 - 4 \\ &:= T(T(4)) \times T(7) - T(T(4) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1448 &:= -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(4)) - T(8) \\ &:= -T(8) + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(4)) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1479 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(T(-7 + 9)) \\ &:= -T(T(9 - 7)) + T(T(T(4)) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1449 &:= -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(4) \times 9 \\ &:= -T(9 + 4) + T(T(T(4 \times 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1482 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(8 - T(T(2))) \\ &:= T(T(2)) + T(8) \times 41 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1455 &:= T(14) \times T(5) - T(T(5)) \\ &:= -T(5) - T(5) + T(T(T(4)) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1483 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - 8 + T(3) \\ &:= -T(T(3)) - T(8) + T(T(T(4 \times 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1456 &:= (1 + T(T(4))) \times (5 + T(6)) \\ &:= T(T(6)) + T(5 \times T(4) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1484 &:= -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8 - 4)) \\ &:= T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8 - 4)) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$1457 := T(-T(1 + T(4)) + T(T(5))) - T(7)$$

For more examples of similar type refer author's work [?].

3 Crazy Representations from 0 to 10000 Using Square Function

In this work we have written natural numbers from 0 to 10000 in terms of increasing and decreasing orders of 1 to 9 and 9 to 1 by use of **square function** along with basic operations. The same numbers are also written before by author [7] without use of **Fibonacci sequence** and **Triangular numbers**. In [39, 40], the author wrote numbers from 0 to 10000 using **Fibonacci sequence** and **Triangular numbers** respectively, without use of any extra operations just with basic operations. Here we have done it by using **square function values**. Still there are few numbers written without use of **square function**. To be more clear, below is a definition of square function:

$$Q(n) = n^2, n \geq 0$$

$$0 := Q(Q((Q(-1-2+3) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$1 := (-1+2)^{3456789}$$

$$2 := ((-1-2+Q(Q(3)))/(4+5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$3 := (-1 \times (Q(2 \times 3) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$4 := (Q((-1-2+Q(Q(3))))/Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$5 := (-1 - (Q(2+3) + (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$6 := (-1 \times (Q(2+3) + (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$7 := (-1-2 - (Q(3) + (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8 := ((-1 + (Q(2+3) + Q(Q(4))))/(5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$9 := Q((-1 \times (Q(2 \times 3) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$10 := (Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) - (4+5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$11 := ((-1-2+Q(3+4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$12 := (((-1-2) \times Q(3)) + 4+5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$13 := (-1 - (Q(2+3) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$14 := (-1 \times (Q(2+3) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$15 := ((-1+2+Q(3+4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$16 := ((-1+Q(Q(2+3)))/(4+5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$17 := (-1+2-3 - (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$18 := (Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) + (4 - (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$19 := (-1-2 - (Q(3) + (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$20 := (-1 - (2 \times Q(3) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$21 := (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + 4+5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$22 := (((-1+2) \times 3) - (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$23 := ((-1+2+3) - (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$24 := ((-1+Q(2^3)) - (4+5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$25 := Q(1 \times 2^3) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$26 := 1 + Q(2^3) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$27 := (-1-2 - (Q(3) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$28 := ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$29 := (Q((-1 + (2+3+4))) - (5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$30 := (1-2) \times Q(3) + (4+5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$31 := (-1+2 - (Q(3) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$32 := 1 \times 2 - Q(3) + (4+5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$33 := 1+2 - Q(3) + (4+5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$34 := -1+2 \times Q(3) + 4 - 56 + 78 - 9$$

$$35 := (-1+2)^{34} \times (5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$36 := (-1+2)^{34} + 5+6+7+8+9$$

$$37 := -\sqrt{-1+2+3+4+5+6+7+8+9}$$

$$0 := Q(Q(Q(-9+8+7-6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$1 := 9 - Q(8) - Q(7+6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$2 := 9 \times 8 - Q(7) - (6+5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$3 := 9 + (8-7)^6 + 5 - 4 - 3 - Q(2) - 1$$

$$4 := (((-9-8) \times (7+6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$5 := (-9 - (((8-7)^6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$6 := (-9 + (((8-7)^6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$7 := (9-8 - Q(7))/6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$8 := 9 - (8-7)^{654321}$$

$$9 := Q(((9 \times (8-7-6))/(5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$10 := 9 + (8-7)^{654321}$$

$$11 := \sqrt{Q(-16+7+6+5+4+3+2 \times 1)}$$

$$12 := 9 \times (8 \times 7 - Q(6))/(5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$13 := -Q(9) + 87 + 6 + (5-4)^{321}$$

$$14 := 98 + 7 - 65 + 4 - Q(3!) + (2+1)!$$

$$15 := (Q((-9+8+7)) - (6+5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$16 := Q((((9-8) \times (7+6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$17 := (-9 - ((Q(8) - Q(7+6+5))/(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$18 := (((9 \times Q(8))/(Q(7) - Q(6+5))) + 4+3+2+1)$$

$$19 := (Q((-9+8-7+6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)$$

$$20 := (9-8+Q(7)) \times 6/(5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$21 := 9 \times (Q(8) + 7 - Q(6))/(5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$22 := ((-9+8 - (7 \times (6+5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))$$

$$23 := (-9 - (Q(8)/(7+6 - (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$24 := (-9-8 - (Q(7) - (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$25 := ((-9+Q((8-7+6))) - (5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$26 := (9+8+Q(7))/6 + (5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$27 := \sqrt{Q(-9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1)}$$

$$28 := ((-9+Q(8)) - ((7 \times 6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$29 := (((9 - Q(8)) \times 7) + (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$30 := \sqrt{Q(-9 \times (8-7-6) - (5+4+3+2+1))}$$

$$31 := 98 + 7 - Q(6) - 54 + Q(3+2-1)$$

$$32 := (-9-8+Q((7 \times (6+5 - (4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$33 := (-9-8+(Q(7) + (6+5 - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$34 := 9 - Q(8+7)/(6 - (5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$35 := ((-9 + (8 \times (7+6+5))) - Q(4+3+2+1))$$

$$36 := ((-9 \times (8+7+6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$37 := (Q((-9+8+7)) + (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$38 := \sqrt{Q(-1 + (-2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))}$$

$$39 := 1 \times 23 - 4 + Q(5) + 67 - 8 \times 9$$

$$40 := 1 + 23 - 4 + Q(5) + 67 - 8 \times 9$$

$$41 := (((-1 + Q(2 + 3))/4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$42 := (1 + 2) \times (Q(3 + 4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$43 := -Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$44 := (12 - 34) \times (5 - 6) + \sqrt{7 \times Q(8) + Q((\sqrt{9})!)}$$

$$45 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$46 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$47 := (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$48 := (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$49 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$50 := (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$51 := (Q((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$52 := (-1 + 2)^3 + Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$53 := 1 - 2 + 3 + Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$54 := 1 - 2 + Q(Q((3!)) - Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$55 := (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$56 := (-1 + (2 \times Q(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$57 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$58 := (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$59 := (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$60 := ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$61 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$62 := ((-1 + (2 \times Q(3 + 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$63 := (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$64 := (Q((-1 + 2 \times 3)) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$65 := (Q(((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$66 := ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$67 := (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$68 := ((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$69 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$70 := \sqrt{(-1 - 2 + 3 + 4) \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)}$$

$$71 := Q(Q((2 - 3 + 4)!)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$72 := 1 + (2 \times 3)^4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$73 := ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times Q(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$74 := (-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$75 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$76 := (-1 \times (Q(2^3) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$38 := 9 \times 8 - Q(7!/6!) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$39 := (-9 - 8 - (Q(7 + 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$40 := (-9 - ((8 \times Q(7)) - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$41 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$42 := (-9 + (Q((8 - 7) \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$43 := (-9 + 8 - 7 + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$44 := (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$45 := (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$46 := 9 + Q(8) - 7 \times 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$47 := (-9 - 8 + Q(((7 + 6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$48 := (-9 + 8 + Q((7 \times (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$49 := Q((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$50 := ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7)))/((6!)/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$51 := -Q(-9 + Q(8 + 7 - 6 - 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$52 := ((-9 - 8 + (Q(7) \times 6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$53 := (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$54 := -9 \times (8 - 7) + Q(6) + 5 + 43 - 21$$

$$55 := (-9 + 8 - (Q(7 + 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$56 := ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7 + 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$57 := (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$58 := \sqrt{Q((9 + 8) \times (-7 + 6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))}$$

$$59 := (Q((-9 + Q(((8 + 7) - (6 + 5)))))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$60 := (9 - 8)^7 \times 6 \times 5 + 4 + Q(3 + 2) + 1$$

$$61 := ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$62 := -Q(-9 + Q(8)) + 7 \times Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$63 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) - Q(7 + 6)))/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$64 := ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$65 := ((-9 - (8 + 7 + 6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$66 := -9 \times 8 + 76 + Q(5) + 4 + 32 + 1$$

$$67 := (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$68 := (9 + 8) \times 7 - Q(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$69 := (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$70 := (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$71 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$72 := 9 \times (8 + Q(7)) - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$73 := (-9 + 8 + (Q((7 + 6 - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$74 := (-9 - (Q(8) - (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$75 := 9 + Q(8) - 7 - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$76 := -Q(-9 - 8 + Q(7)) + (6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
77 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
78 &:= (-1 + (((2 + Q(3)) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
79 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
80 &:= (Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
81 &:= Q(Q((-1 \times (Q(2 \times 3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
82 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3 + 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
83 &:= 1 + Q(2 + Q(3)) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
84 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
85 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3 + 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
86 &:= (Q(((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
87 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
88 &:= (Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
89 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + Q(3)) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
90 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
91 &:= 1 + (Q(2 + Q(3)) + 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
92 &:= -1 + 2^{3+4} - \sqrt{Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)} \\
93 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - ((4)! - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
94 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
95 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
96 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
97 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
98 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
99 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
100 &:= Q((Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
101 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
102 &:= (-1 + (Q(2^3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
103 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
104 &:= 1 + Q(2^3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
105 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3)))/(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
106 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((3 \times 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
107 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((3 \times 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
108 &:= 1 - 2 + (Q(3 \times 4) - 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
109 &:= (Q((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
110 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((3 \times 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
111 &:= (Q((-1 - (2 - (3 + (4 + 5)))))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
112 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
113 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
114 &:= 1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)) - 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
115 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3) \times Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
116 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
77 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
78 &:= (9 + Q(8 + 7))/6 + 54/3 + 21 \\
79 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7)))/Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
80 &:= \sqrt{Q(-10 + 8 \times (7 + 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 \times 1))} \\
81 &:= Q(Q((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6))/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
82 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q(7 + 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
83 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
84 &:= ((Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) - Q(6))/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
85 &:= ((-9 + Q(8 + 7)) - (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
86 &:= ((Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) - 6)/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
87 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
88 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) + (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
89 &:= (((Q((-9 + Q(8))) - Q(Q(7)))/6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
90 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 + 7))/6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
91 &:= (-9 + Q((8 - (7 + 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
92 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7)^{65}) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
93 &:= ((-9 - (8/(7 - 6 - 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
94 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
95 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
96 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 + Q(4) + 32 \times 1 \\
97 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
98 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
99 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
100 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 + 6) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
101 &:= ((-9 - (8 - (7 + 6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
102 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
103 &:= 9 + Q(8 + 7) - Q(6 + 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
104 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
105 &:= (((-9 + Q((8 + Q(7))))/Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
106 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7) - Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
107 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
108 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) - (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
109 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
110 &:= (9 - Q(8)) \times (7 + 6 - 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
111 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
112 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
113 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
114 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - Q(6))) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
115 &:= ((-9 + Q(8 + 7)) - ((6 - 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
116 &:= 9 + 8 \times 7 + Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
117 &:= 1 + Q(2 + 3 + 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
118 &:= (1 - 2 + 3) \times (4! + \sqrt{Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)}) \\
119 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
120 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
121 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
122 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
123 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
124 &:= (Q(((((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) + Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
125 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
126 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
127 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
128 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
129 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
130 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
131 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
132 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(3 + 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
133 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
134 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
135 &:= (Q(((((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
136 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 \times 3)) + (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
137 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
138 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)!) - (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
139 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
140 &:= Q(Q(3)) \times (1 - 2) + Q(Q(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
141 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
142 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3 + Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
143 &:= 1 + 2 - Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
144 &:= Q(((((-1 - 2) \times Q(3)) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
145 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! / \sqrt{Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)} \\
146 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
147 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
148 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 \times 3))) \times 4) / (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
149 &:= (Q(((((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
150 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
151 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
152 &:= ((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
153 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
154 &:= 1 - (2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
155 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3) \times 4! + \sqrt{Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)} \\
156 &:= 123 - 45 - 67 + Q(8) + Q(9) \\
117 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7 + 6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
118 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) - (7 \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
119 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) \times (7 + 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
120 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) / 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
121 &:= Q((-9 - (8 - (7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
122 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
123 &:= (9 \times 8 - Q(7)) \times 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
124 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) - (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
125 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
126 &:= Q(98 / 7 - 6) - 5 + 4 + 3 \times 21 \\
127 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) \times Q(7)) / Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
128 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(Q(7)) - Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
129 &:= (Q((-9 + (8 + 7 + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
130 &:= 9 - 8 \times (7 + 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
131 &:= (Q(((((-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) + Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
132 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
133 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7 + 6)) - (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
134 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) / (7 - 6 - 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
135 &:= (Q((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6))) / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
136 &:= (Q(((((-9 + 8 \times 7) - Q(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
137 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(7 + 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
138 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
139 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (7 + 6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
140 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7 - 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
141 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) / 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
142 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
143 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
144 &:= Q((-9 + ((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
145 &:= 9 - Q(8) - Q(Q(7)) + Q(Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
146 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 + 65 + 4^3 + Q(2 + 1) \\
147 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
148 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) - (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
149 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(((8 + 7) - (6 + 5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
150 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) + (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
151 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + ((7 - 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
152 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - Q(((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
153 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7 + 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
154 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + 6) / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
155 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
156 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + Q(6)) / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
157 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q(3)) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
158 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
159 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + Q(3)) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
160 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times (3 + 4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
161 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2 - 3) + Q(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
162 &:= 1 + Q(2 \times (3 + 4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
163 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3))/\sqrt{4}) + \sqrt{Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)} \\
164 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
165 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 \times 3)) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
166 &:= (-1 - 2 + Q(((3 \times Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
167 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3 + 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
168 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) \times (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
169 &:= Q((-1 - (Q(2 + 3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
170 &:= (-1 + 2 + Q(((3 \times Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
171 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
172 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) \times (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
173 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(3) - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
174 &:= 1 - 2 + (Q(3) - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
175 &:= (1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) / Q(4) \\
176 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(3) - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
177 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
178 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2 \times 3) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
179 &:= (Q((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
180 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((3 \times 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
181 &:= 1 \times 2 + Q(3 \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
182 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
183 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
184 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q(Q(Q(3))) - Q(4)) / (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
185 &:= -Q(Q(-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
186 &:= 1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) - Q(4)) / (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
187 &:= ((Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - Q(4)) / (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
188 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(Q(Q(3))) - Q(4)) / (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
189 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2 - 3) + Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
190 &:= (Q((-1 - ((2 - 3) \times Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
191 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) / 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
192 &:= ((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - 4) / (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
193 &:= (-1 - 2 + Q((Q(3 + 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
194 &:= 1 + 2 \times Q(Q(3)) + (-4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
195 &:= 1 \times 2 \times Q(3 + 4) + 56 / 7 + 89 \\
196 &:= Q((-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
157 &:= 9 - Q(8) - 7 - 6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
158 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
159 &:= (Q((-9 + (8 + 7 + 6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
160 &:= (Q(((-9 + 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
161 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
162 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 + 6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
163 &:= (((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(Q(7)))) / 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
164 &:= (-9 + (8 \times Q(7) + (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
165 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 + 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
166 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + 7 + 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
167 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7 + 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
168 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
169 &:= Q((-9 + 8 - (7 - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
170 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) + (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
171 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7) \times 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
172 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) - (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
173 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 + 6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
174 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - Q(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
175 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) / 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
176 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
177 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7) \times 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
178 &:= (9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) / 6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
179 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) - (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
180 &:= 9 \times (8 - 7 - 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
181 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
182 &:= ((-9 + 8 - (7 \times 6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
183 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
184 &:= (-9 \times 8 + Q(((7 - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
185 &:= (-9 - (Q((8 + 7 + 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
186 &:= (((-9 - Q(8 + 7)) / 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
187 &:= (-9 + Q(((8 + 7) - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
188 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6 - 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
189 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - Q(7)) \times 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
190 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
191 &:= (-9 - ((8 / (7 - 6 - 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
192 &:= ((-9 + ((Q(8) + 7) \times 6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
193 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
194 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
195 &:= ((-9 + Q(8 + 7)) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
196 &:= Q(((-9 + 8) \times (7 - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
197 &:= (-1 + 2 + Q((Q(3+4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
198 &:= (((-1 + Q((Q(2+3) + 4)))/5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
199 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
200 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
201 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(3) + 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
202 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(3) + 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
203 &:= (-1 + (Q(2^3) + (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
204 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times (3+4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
205 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) - (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
206 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2^3) - ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
207 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
208 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
209 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
210 &:= (((-1 + Q(2+3))/4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
211 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
212 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times 3) + Q(Q(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
213 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
214 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4)))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
215 &:= (((-1 - (2+3)) + Q(Q(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
216 &:= (((-1 \times (2+3)) + Q(Q(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
217 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
218 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
219 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + Q(Q(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
220 &:= (-1 - ((2-3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
221 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - (2 - (3+4)))))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
222 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
223 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - (4 - (5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
224 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
225 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
226 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times 3) + Q(Q(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
227 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
228 &:= ((-1 - 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
229 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) \times Q(4)) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
230 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times (3+4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
231 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2 - 3) + Q(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
232 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 + Q(Q(4)) + 5 - (6+7+8+9) \\
233 &:= 1 + 2 + Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) - 5 - (6+7+8+9)) \\
234 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(3)) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
235 &:= (-1 - (Q((2 \times Q(3))) - (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
236 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 \times Q(3))) - (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
197 &:= ((-9 - (8+7)) + (Q(6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
198 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + 6))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
199 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(Q(7)) - Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
200 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(Q(7)) - Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
201 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times Q(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
202 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 \times (6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
203 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7+6) + (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
204 &:= ((-9 \times ((8+7) - Q(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
205 &:= ((Q((-9 \times (8-7-6))) + Q(5))/(4+3+2+1)) \\
206 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (Q(7) + 6))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
207 &:= (-9 - (Q(8+7) - Q(6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
208 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q((7+6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
209 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7+6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
210 &:= ((-9 - (8-7) \times 6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
211 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
212 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7+6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
213 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + (Q(6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
214 &:= (((-9 - 8 - Q(7))/6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
215 &:= -Q(-9 + Q(8)) + Q(7+6+5) \times (4+3+2+1) \\
216 &:= (98 - 76 + 5) \times 4 + Q(3!) \times (2+1) \\
217 &:= (-9 + (((8-7)^6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
218 &:= ((-9 + Q(8) \times 7) - (Q(6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
219 &:= (Q((-9 + (8+7+6))) - (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
220 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times Q(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
221 &:= ((-9 - (8-7-6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
222 &:= ((-9 + (8-7) \times 6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
223 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 + 6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
224 &:= ((-9/(8+7-6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
225 &:= Q((Q((-9+8+7)) - (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
226 &:= (((-9+8+7)/6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
227 &:= ((-9+8+7) + (Q(6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
228 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7+6) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
229 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7+6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
230 &:= (-9 + Q(8)) \times (-7+6+5) + 4+3+2+1 \\
231 &:= ((Q((-9+8+7))/6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
232 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 \times (6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
233 &:= (((-9+8+Q(7))/6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
234 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - Q(7+6+5)))/(4+3+2+1)) \\
235 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7+6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
236 &:= ((-9+8+(7 \times Q(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
237 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
238 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
239 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + 4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
240 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(3))) + (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
241 &:= ((-1+2^{Q(3)}) - ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
242 &:= -Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) + Q(Q(4)) + 5 + (6+7+8+9) \\
243 &:= -Q(-1 + Q(2+3)) - Q(4+5) + Q(6+7+8+9) \\
244 &:= (-1 + (((2+Q(3)) - 4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
245 &:= (-Q((-1+2) \times 3) + Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9) \\
246 &:= Q(1 \times 2 + 3) + Q(Q(4)) - 5 - (6+7+8+9) \\
247 &:= 12 \times Q(3) + Q(4) + 5 + Q(6) - 7 + 89 \\
248 &:= ((-1+2-Q(3)) \times (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
249 &:= ((-1+Q(((2+3) \times 4))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
250 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
251 &:= (-1 - (2 \times Q(3) - ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
252 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q((3 \times 4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
253 &:= (((-1-2) \times (Q(Q(3)) \times 4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
254 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times (Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
255 &:= (-1 + Q(((2+Q(3+4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
256 &:= Q(((-1 + Q(Q(2+3))) / (4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
257 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
258 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) + (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
259 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2-3) + Q(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
260 &:= (Q((-1 - ((2-3) \times Q(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
261 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3) - (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
262 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) - (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
263 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
264 &:= (((-1-2) \times Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
265 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+3) - (Q(Q(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
266 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+3) - (Q(Q(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
267 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((Q(3) + 4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
268 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (Q(Q(3) + 4) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
269 &:= 1 + 2 \times (Q(Q(3) + 4) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
270 &:= (Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
271 &:= (((-1+2)^3) + ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
272 &:= (-1 - ((2-Q(3)) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
273 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
274 &:= 1 + (-2 + Q(3)) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9) \\
275 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) - (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
276 &:= (-1-2 - (Q(3) \times (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
237 &:= (-9 + (Q(8+7) + 6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
238 &:= (9-8) \times (7+6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1) \\
239 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7+6) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
240 &:= ((Q((-9+8+Q(7))) + Q(Q(6))) / (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
241 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7+6+5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
242 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q(7+6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
243 &:= ((-9+8+Q(7+6)) - (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
244 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) / (7-6-5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
245 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + Q(6+5))) / (4+3+2+1)) \\
246 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8) \times (7-6-5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
247 &:= (-9 + Q((Q(Q(8)) / Q((7 - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))))))) \\
248 &:= (((Q(Q((-9+8+7))) - 6) / 5) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
249 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((Q(7)+6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
250 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7+6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
251 &:= ((-9-8+7) + (Q(6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
252 &:= (-9 + (Q((8-7) \times 6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
253 &:= (-9+8-7 + (Q(6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
254 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + (Q(6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
255 &:= (Q((-9+8+7)) - (6 - Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
256 &:= Q(Q(((-9 - 8) \times (7+6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
257 &:= (Q((-9+8+7)) + (Q(6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
258 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) - (6+5+Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
259 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) - ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
260 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) - (6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
261 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times 6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
262 &:= ((-9-8 + (Q(7) \times 6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
263 &:= (-9-8 + (Q(7) + (6+Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
264 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) - 7+6))) / (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
265 &:= (-9 + (Q((8-7+6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
266 &:= ((-9+8+7 \times 6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
267 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - (7+6 - Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
268 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7 - Q(6))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
269 &:= (-9+8 + (Q(7) + (Q(6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
270 &:= ((-9 \times (8-7-6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
271 &:= (((Q((-9+Q(8))) - Q(7)) / 6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
272 &:= (-9-8 + Q(((Q(7) + Q(6+5)) / (4+3+2+1)))) \\
273 &:= (((-9+8+Q(7)) \times 6) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
274 &:= (((-9+Q(8)) \times 7) - (6+5+Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
275 &:= (((-9+Q(8)) \times 7) - ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
276 &:= (((-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q(7))) / (6+5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
277 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 277 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
278 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + Q(3)) + (Q(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 278 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) \times 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
279 &:= Q((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (-4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 279 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
280 &:= (-Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 280 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + Q(((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
281 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 281 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 - 6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
282 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 282 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 - 6 - 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
283 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 283 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 + (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
284 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 284 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (7 \times (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
285 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 285 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
286 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 286 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6) + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
287 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 287 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(7) - (6 + 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
288 &:= (-1 + Q((Q(2 \times 3) + (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 288 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) / (7 + 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
289 &:= Q((-1 + 2 - 3 - (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 289 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) / Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
290 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 290 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7 + 6)) \times Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
291 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 291 &:= 9 + 8 \times Q(7) - (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
292 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 292 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((Q(7) \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
293 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 293 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 + 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
294 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 294 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
295 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 295 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
296 &:= (Q(((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) / Q(4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 296 &:= (((-9 + Q(Q(8)) - Q(Q(7))) / 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
297 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 297 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
298 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 298 &:= 9 + Q(8) + Q((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
299 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 299 &:= (Q((-9 + (8 + 7 + 6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
300 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 300 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - Q(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
301 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 301 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
302 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 302 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 - 6 - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
303 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 303 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
304 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 304 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
305 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 305 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
306 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 306 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7 - 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
307 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 307 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
308 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 308 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
309 &:= (-1 \times (Q(((2 + 3) + Q(4))) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 309 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
310 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times Q(Q(4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 310 &:= (-9 + (((8 + Q(Q(7))) / (6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
311 &:= (1 + 2 + 3) \times Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 311 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + Q((7 - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
312 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 312 &:= 9 + (Q(8 + Q(7)) + Q(Q(6))) / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
313 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) - Q((3!))) \times (4!)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 313 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7 + 6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
314 &:= 1 - 2 + Q(3!) / 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 314 &:= (Q(((-9 \times 8) / (7 - 6 - 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
315 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 315 &:= (((-9 + Q((8 + Q(7)))) / Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
316 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 316 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + ((Q(6) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$317 := (((-1 - 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$318 := (-1 + (Q(((2^3) + (4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$319 := (Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$320 := (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$321 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$322 := (-1 + ((2 \times Q(3 \times 4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$323 := (-1 + Q(((2 - 3) - (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$324 := (Q(((((-1 + 2)^3) + Q(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$325 := (Q((-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) + (4 + 5)))))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$326 := (Q((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$327 := ((-1 + 2 + Q(3 + Q(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$328 := (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$329 := (-1 + ((2 + (Q(Q(3)) / (4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$330 := 1 + 2 + Q(Q(3!)) + Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$331 := (Q((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - Q(4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$332 := (-1 + (((2 - Q(3)) \times Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$333 := ((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$334 := (Q(Q((-1 + 2 \times 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$335 := (-1 - ((2 \times ((3 + 4) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$336 := (((-1 \times 2) \times ((3 + 4) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$337 := (-1 + (2 \times Q(((3 \times Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$338 := (((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$339 := (Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$340 := (-1 - ((2 + Q(3)) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$341 := (((-1 \times 2) - Q(3)) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$342 := ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) \times (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$343 := (-1 - (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$344 := (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$345 := (((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times (4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$346 := (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$347 := (((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$348 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$349 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$350 := (((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$351 := (Q(((((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$352 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$353 := (-1 + ((Q(2 \times 3) \times (4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$354 := ((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$355 := (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$356 := (-1 - 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$317 := (-9 - 8 + (Q(7 + 6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$318 := ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) - (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$319 := (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$320 := (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$321 := (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7 + 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$322 := (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$323 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$324 := (-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$325 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$326 := (-9 + (Q(8 + 7) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$327 := (-9 + (Q(8 + 7) + (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$328 := (-9 \times 8 - ((7 - 6 - 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$329 := (((Q((-9 + Q(8))) - Q(Q(7))) / 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$330 := ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - Q(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$331 := ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7 + 6) - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$332 := ((-9 + (8 \times Q(7))) - (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$333 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7))) + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$334 := (((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) - (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$335 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$336 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$337 := (-9 + (Q((8 + 7 + 6)) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$338 := (((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times 6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$339 := (-9 - 8 - (Q(7 + 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$340 := (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$341 := (Q(((((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) - (6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$342 := 9 \times (Q(8) - 7 + 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$343 := (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$344 := (-9 + (Q(8) + Q(((Q(7) + Q(6 + 5)) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$345 := ((((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) / (6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$346 := (Q(((((-9 + 8 \times 7) - Q(6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$347 := (-9 + (Q(Q(((8 + 7) - (6 + 5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$348 := ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$349 := ((-9 + Q(8) \times 7) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$350 := (-9 + (8 \times (7 + Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$351 := (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7 + 6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$352 := (-9 - (Q((8 + Q(7))) / (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$353 := (-9 \times 8 + (((7 + 6) \times Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$354 := ((-9 + ((Q(Q(8)) + 7) / (6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$355 := (-9 + 8 - (Q(7 + 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$356 := (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
357 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((3 \times 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
358 &:= (-1 + ((Q(Q(2 \times 3))/4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
359 &:= ((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
360 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
361 &:= Q((-1 - 2 - (Q(3) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
362 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
363 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
364 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2 + 3) \times 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
365 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + 3) + Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
366 &:= (-1 + (((2 + Q(Q(3))) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
367 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
368 &:= (((-1 - Q(Q(2 + 3))) + 4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
369 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
370 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
371 &:= ((-1 + 2^{Q(3)}) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
372 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
373 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
374 &:= ((-1 + Q((Q(2 \times 3) + 4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
375 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + Q(4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
376 &:= 1 + Q(Q(2 \times 3) + 4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
377 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
378 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
379 &:= (-1 \times (2^{Q(3)} + (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
380 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q((2 + 3 + 4)))/5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
381 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
382 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
383 &:= (-1 - (Q((Q(2 + 3) + 4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
384 &:= (-1 \times (Q((Q(2 + 3) + 4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
385 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
386 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2 \times 3))) - ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
387 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) - ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
388 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{Q(Q(3))/(4+5)} - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
389 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(4)) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
390 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
391 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q((Q(3 + 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
392 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) + (Q(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
393 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
394 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3 + Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
395 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times (Q(3) + (4 + 5)))))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
396 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
357 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
358 &:= (((Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) - 6)/5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
359 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q((Q(7) + (6 + 5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
360 &:= (-9 + ((8 - Q(7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
361 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (7 - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
362 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
363 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((7 - Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
364 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
365 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
366 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((Q(7) \times (6 + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
367 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) \times (6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
368 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
369 &:= (Q((-9 + (8 + 7 + 6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
370 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) - (7 + 6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
371 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((7 \times Q(6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
372 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(6))/5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
373 &:= (((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(Q(7))))/6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
374 &:= (-9 + (8 \times Q(7) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
375 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
376 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
377 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7 + 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
378 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
379 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) - (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
380 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7 - 6)) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
381 &:= ((-9 + Q(((8 - 7 - 6) + Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
382 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times Q(7))) - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
383 &:= (-9 + (8 \times Q((7 \times (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
384 &:= (-9 + (8 \times Q(7) + (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
385 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7)))/6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
386 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) \times (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
387 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
388 &:= ((-9 + Q(8) \times 7) - (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
389 &:= (Q((-9 + (8 + 7 + 6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
390 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
391 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
392 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
393 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7 + 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
394 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
395 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (Q(7) - (6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
396 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - ((7 + 6 - 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
397 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3 + Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
398 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
399 &:= (-1 + Q((2 - ((3 + (4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
400 &:= Q((-1 - (2 \times Q(3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
401 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
402 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3+4})) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
403 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
404 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 \times 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
405 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2 + 3) + Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
406 &:= (Q(((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
407 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
408 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
409 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (Q(3 + 4) \times 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
410 &:= ((-1 - Q((2 + 3 + 4))) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
411 &:= 1 - 2 \times (5 \times Q(3 + 4)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
412 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q((2 + 3 + 4))))/5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
413 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3) \times Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
414 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
415 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
416 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - (Q(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
417 &:= 1 + Q(2 + 3 + Q(4)) + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
418 &:= -Q(-1 + Q(2 + 3)) + 4^5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
419 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
420 &:= ((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
421 &:= 1 - 2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
422 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (Q(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
423 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
424 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
425 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times Q(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
426 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((3 + Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
427 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + (Q((Q(4) + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
428 &:= (-1 + ((2 + Q(3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
429 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
430 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) + Q(Q(4)))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
431 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
432 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(4 + 5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
433 &:= (-1 - (Q(((2 + 3) + Q(4))) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
434 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2 + 3) \times 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
435 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2 + 3) + Q(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
436 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
397 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 + 7 + 6))) - (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
398 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) \times 6) + (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
399 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7)))/6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
400 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + 7 \times 6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
401 &:= (-9 + ((Q(Q(8)) - 7 + 6 + 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
402 &:= ((-9 + ((Q(8) + 7) \times 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
403 &:= (((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(Q(7))))/6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
404 &:= (-9 + (8 \times Q(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
405 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
406 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
407 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7 + 6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
408 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
409 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times 7) + (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
410 &:= ((-9 - (Q(8) + (7 - Q(6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
411 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6) \times 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
412 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + 7 \times (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
413 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
414 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - Q(6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
415 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7)))/6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
416 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (Q(7) + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
417 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
418 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
419 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) - (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
420 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
421 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
422 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (Q(7) \times (6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
423 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7 + 6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
424 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
425 &:= 9 - 8 + Q(7 + 6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
426 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7 + 6)) + Q(Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
427 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + 7 + 6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
428 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times (6 + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
429 &:= (Q((-9 - (8 \times (7 - 6 - 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
430 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times 7) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
431 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
432 &:= (-9 + Q(((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
433 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
434 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
435 &:= ((-9 + Q(8 + 7)) - (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
436 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
437 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((Q(3) + Q(Q(4+5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
438 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+Q(3)) - (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
439 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+Q(3)) - (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
440 &:= (-1 + Q(((2 \times (Q(3) - Q(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
441 &:= Q((((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + 4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
442 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2+3))) + (Q(4) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
443 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
444 &:= ((-1+2+3) \times (Q(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
445 &:= (((-1+Q(2+Q(3))) \times 4) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
446 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) + (Q((4 \times 5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
447 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3+Q(Q(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
448 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3+Q(Q(4)))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
449 &:= (Q((-1-2+(Q(3)+Q(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
450 &:= (((-1+Q(2+3)) - 4-5) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
451 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3+4) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
452 &:= (-1-2 - ((3-Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
453 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((3-Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
454 &:= (-1-2 - ((3 \times Q(Q(4))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
455 &:= ((1-2) \times 3 + Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9) \\
456 &:= ((Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3))))/4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
457 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
458 &:= (-1+2 - ((3 \times Q(Q(4))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
459 &:= (Q(((1+2) \times 3)) \times (Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
460 &:= (-1+2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
461 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
462 &:= 1+2+Q(3) \times (Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
463 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
464 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) \times (4 - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
465 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2+3))) - (Q(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
466 &:= (-1 - ((2^{3+4}) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
467 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{3+4}) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
468 &:= (((-1-2) \times Q((3+(4+5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
469 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{Q(3)}) - (Q(4+5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
470 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - Q(Q(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
471 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - Q(Q(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
472 &:= ((-1+2^{Q(3)}) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
473 &:= ((-1+Q(Q(2+3))) - (Q((Q(4)-5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
474 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+3) \times (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
475 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2+3) + Q(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
476 &:= (-1-2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
437 &:= (-9 + (Q(8+7) + (Q(6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
438 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + 6))) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
439 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (Q(7+6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
440 &:= (-9+8 - (Q(7) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
441 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times Q(7)) - Q(6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
442 &:= (-9+8-7 - (6 \times (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
443 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) - (6 \times (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
444 &:= ((-9 + ((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times 6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
445 &:= (-9+8 - (Q(7+6) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
446 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
447 &:= ((-9+8+7) + Q(6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
448 &:= ((-9+Q(8) \times 7) - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
449 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7+6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
450 &:= ((Q((-9+8+7)) - 6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
451 &:= (Q(((9-8+7) + Q(6))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
452 &:= (((-9-8+Q(7)) \times (6+5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
453 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
454 &:= (-9+8 + ((7+6) \times (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
455 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7) - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
456 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((Q(7) \times (6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
457 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) \times (6+5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
458 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) - (6+5 - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
459 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
460 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times 7) + 6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
461 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7) + (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
462 &:= (-9 - (((8 - Q(7)) \times 6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
463 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((Q(7) - (6-5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
464 &:= (-9 + (((Q(Q(8)) + 7)/(6+5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
465 &:= (-9+8 - (Q(7+6) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
466 &:= ((-9+8) \times (Q(7+6) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
467 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (Q(7) - Q(6+5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
468 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + Q(6)))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
469 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8+7)) - (6 - Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
470 &:= ((Q((-9+8+7)) + (6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
471 &:= (((-9 - (8+7)) \times 6) + Q(Q(5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
472 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times Q(7))) - (6+5 - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
473 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + Q(6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
474 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7) - (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
475 &:= (-9 + Q((8 - (7 - (6+5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
476 &:= (-9+8 + (7 \times Q(6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
477 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
478 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2+3)) + (4 - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
479 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2+3) - 4 - 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
480 &:= (-1+2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
481 &:= (-1-2 + Q((3 - (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
482 &:= (-1 \times 2 + Q((3 - (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
483 &:= (-1 + Q(((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
484 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2+3))) - (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
485 &:= (-1+2 + Q((3 - (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
486 &:= (-1+2 - ((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)) \times (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
487 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
488 &:= ((-1 - (2+3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
489 &:= Q(1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) + Q(Q(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)) \\
490 &:= (((-1+2-3) + Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
491 &:= (((-1 - Q(2+3)) \times 4) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
492 &:= (-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
493 &:= ((((-1+2) \times 3) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
494 &:= ((-1 - Q(2+3)) \times (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
495 &:= (-1 - (Q((2 + (Q(3) + Q(4)))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
496 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 + (Q(3) + Q(4)))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
497 &:= (((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))/4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
498 &:= ((-1+2+3) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
499 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times (3 + (4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
500 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 + (Q(3) + (4+5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
501 &:= (((-1+2)^3) - (Q((4 \times 5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
502 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q(3+Q(4))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
503 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3+Q(4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
504 &:= ((-1+2+3) - (Q((4 \times 5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
505 &:= (((-1 + ((2+3) \times 4)) \times Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\
506 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2+3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
507 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
508 &:= (((-1-2) \times Q(3+4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
509 &:= (-1 - ((Q(2^3) - Q(4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
510 &:= ((-1+2+Q(3)) \times (Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
511 &:= -1 + 2^{Q((Q(3)+Q(4+5))/Q(6+7+8+9))} \\
512 &:= (-1+2 + (Q(3+Q(4)) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
513 &:= ((-1-2) \times (Q(3) \times (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
514 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2 \times 3))) - (Q(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
515 &:= (((-1 + Q(2+Q(3))) \times 4) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
516 &:= (((-1-2+Q(3)) \times Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
477 &:= (Q((-9+8+7)) + Q(6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
478 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7 - Q(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
479 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7+6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
480 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) + (6+5+Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
481 &:= (((Q((-9+Q(8))) - Q(7))/6) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
482 &:= (-9 + (Q((8+7+6)) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
483 &:= (-9 + ((Q(Q(8)+7) - Q(6+5))/(4+3+2+1))) \\
484 &:= (Q((-9-8+Q(7))) - (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
485 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - Q(6+5))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
486 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - (7+6+5+Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
487 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (Q(7) - (6+5+Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
488 &:= ((-9+8 \times 7) + Q(6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
489 &:= (-9+8 + (Q(7) + Q(6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
490 &:= (((-9+Q(8)) \times (7+6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
491 &:= ((-9+8) \times (Q(7) - (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
492 &:= (-9 + (((8-7)^6) + (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
493 &:= (-9 + (8 \times Q(7) + ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
494 &:= (-9 + (8 \times Q(7) + (6+5+Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
495 &:= 9 + Q(8+7) + Q(6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1) \\
496 &:= ((-9+Q(8)) - (Q(7) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
497 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q((Q(7) + (6+5))) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
498 &:= ((-9+8-7+6) + (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
499 &:= ((-9/(8+7-6)) + (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
500 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (6+5))) \times Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
501 &:= (9 \times 8 + Q(7)) \times 6 - Q(5+4+3+2+1) \\
502 &:= (-9-8 + ((Q(7) \times 6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
503 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 + Q(6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
504 &:= (-9 - ((8+Q(7)) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
505 &:= ((Q((-9 \times (8-7-6)))/5) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
506 &:= (((-9+Q(Q(8)) - Q(Q(7)))/6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
507 &:= (((-9+8 \times 7) \times 6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
508 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7 - Q(6))) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
509 &:= ((Q((-9+8+Q(7)))/6) + (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
510 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + (7-6-5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
511 &:= (((Q((-9+Q(8))) - Q(7))/6) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
512 &:= ((-9-8 + (Q(7) \times (6+5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
513 &:= (((-9+8+Q(7)) \times 6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
514 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
515 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) - (Q((Q(7) + (6-5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
516 &:= ((-9 - (8+7)) + (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$517 := (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$518 := (-1 + (Q(((2 \times 3) + Q(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$519 := (Q((-1-2+(Q(3)+Q(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$520 := ((-1+2+3) \times ((4 \times Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$521 := (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3) - ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$522 := ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) - ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$523 := (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) - (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$524 := (-1 + (((2-3) + Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$525 := (Q((-1+Q(2+3))) - (Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$526 := (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$527 := (-1 \times ((2^{3+4}) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)))$$

$$528 := (-1 - ((2 \times (Q(3) - Q(Q(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$529 := Q((-1+2+3) - (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$530 := ((-1+2^{Q(3)}) - (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$531 := (Q(Q((-1 - (2 - (3+4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$532 := ((-1+2^{Q(3)}) - (4+5 - (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$533 := (((-1-2) \times Q(3)) + (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$534 := (-1 - (Q(2+3) - (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$535 := (-1 \times (Q(2+3) - (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$536 := (-1 - (((2 - Q(3)) \times Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$537 := (Q((-1+Q(2+3))) - (4+5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$538 := (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(3) + (4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$539 := (-1 + (2 \times (Q((Q(3) + Q(4+5)))/(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$540 := ((-1+Q((2 \times (3 \times 4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$541 := ((Q((-1-2+Q(3))) \times Q(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$542 := -1 + 2^{Q(3)} - 4+5+6+7+8+9$$

$$543 := (-1 - 2 - (Q(3+4) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$544 := (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$545 := (Q((-1+Q(2+3))) + (4 - (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$546 := ((-1 - Q(2+3)) \times (4+5 - (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$547 := (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$548 := (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) - (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$549 := ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) - (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$550 := (-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + 4+5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$551 := (((-1-2) \times 3) + (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$552 := (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$553 := ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$554 := ((-1 - (2+3)) + (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$555 := ((-1 \times (2+3)) + (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$556 := (-1 - ((2 \times Q(3+4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)))$$

$$517 := (((-9-8) \times Q(7)) + (6 \times Q(5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$518 := (-9+8 + ((Q(7) \times 6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$519 := (Q((-9 - (8 \times (7-6-5)))) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$520 := (-9 + Q((8 + ((7-6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$521 := ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (6+5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1))$$

$$522 := ((-9 - Q((Q(8) - 7 - 6)))/(5 - (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$523 := 9 - 8 - Q(7) + Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)$$

$$524 := (((-9)/(8+7-6)) + Q(Q(5))) - Q(4+3+2+1)$$

$$525 := (((-9 + Q((8 + Q(7))))/6) - (5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$526 := ((-9 + Q((8 \times 7))) - Q((Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$527 := 9 \times Q(8) - Q(7 \times (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$528 := ((-9+8 + (Q(7) \times (6+5))) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$529 := Q((-9 - (Q(8)/(7+6 - (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$530 := ((-9-8+7) + (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$531 := (-9 + (Q(((8+7) \times 6)))/(5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$532 := (-9+8-7 + (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$533 := (((-9+8) \times 7) + (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$534 := (Q((-9+Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$535 := (Q((-9+Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) - (6+5 - Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$536 := ((-9 \times (8+7+6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$537 := (((-9 + (8+7+6)) + Q(Q(5))) - Q(4+3+2+1))$$

$$538 := (((-9+8+Q(7)) \times (6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)$$

$$539 := (Q((-9 - (8 \times (7-6-5)))) + 4+3+2+1)$$

$$540 := 9 \times (Q(8) + 7 - Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$541 := (Q((-9-8+Q(7)) - (6+5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))$$

$$542 := (-9 - (((8 - Q(7)) \times (6+5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$543 := (-9 + (8 \times ((Q(7) \times 6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$544 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$545 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) + Q(6+5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$546 := ((-9+8+7) + (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$547 := (((-9 - (8+7)) + Q(Q(6))) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$548 := (-9+8 + ((Q(7) \times (6+5)) + 4+3+2+1))$$

$$549 := (-9 \times (8 - ((Q(7) \times 6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$550 := ((-9-8 - (Q(7) - Q(6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1))$$

$$551 := (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7) + 6+5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$552 := ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$553 := (-9+8-7 + (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$554 := ((-9 \times (8+7-6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1))$$

$$555 := (((-9 + Q((8 + Q(7))))/6) + 5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$556 := ((-9+8) \times (Q(7+6) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$557 := (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$558 := ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$559 := (-1 - ((2 - 3) \times (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$560 := (Q((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$561 := (((-1 + 2)^3) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$562 := (-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$563 := (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$564 := ((-1 + 2 + 3) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$565 := ((-1 + 2 \times 3) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$566 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$567 := (((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$568 := (-1 - 2 - ((Q(Q(3)) \times 4) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$569 := (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$570 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$571 := (-1 - (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$572 := (-1 \times (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$573 := ((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) - (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$574 := (Q(Q((-1 + 2 \times 3))) - (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$575 := (-1 + Q(((2 + 3) - (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$576 := Q(((-1 + Q(2^3)) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$577 := (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) \times 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$578 := ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4)) / (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$579 := (-1 + 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$580 := (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$581 := (((-1 \times (2 \times (3 + 4))) + Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$582 := ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (Q((4 \times 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$583 := (-1 - (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$584 := (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$585 := ((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$586 := (Q(Q((-1 + 2 \times 3))) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$587 := ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(3) + Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$588 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(3) + Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$589 := 1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3) + Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$590 := (Q(Q((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$591 := ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(3) + Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$592 := (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$593 := (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$594 := (Q(Q((-1 + 2 \times 3))) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$595 := (-1 - (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$596 := (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$557 := (-9 - (Q(8) - (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$558 := (-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$559 := (Q((-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$560 := (-9 + (8 \times (7 + Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$561 := 9 \times Q(8) - (7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$562 := (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$563 := ((-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(Q(6))) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$564 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((7 - Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$565 := -Q(-9 + Q(8)) + Q(Q(7) + 6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$566 := (-9 - (Q(8) - ((Q(7) \times (6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$567 := (-9 + Q(((8 + 7) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$568 := ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + (6 + 5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$569 := ((-9 - 8 + 7) - (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$570 := ((-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$571 := (-9 + ((8 \times (Q(7) + (6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$572 := (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$573 := (-9 \times 8 + ((7 + Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$574 := (((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) - (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$575 := ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - Q(6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$576 := (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$577 := (-9 - ((8 \times (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$578 := 9 \times Q(8) - 7 - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$579 := (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + ((6 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$580 := (9 - Q(8) + Q(7 + 6)) \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$581 := (((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$582 := (((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times (6 + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$583 := (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$584 := (-9 + (Q(8) + ((Q(7) \times (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$585 := 9 + Q(8 + 7 - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$586 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$587 := ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$588 := (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$589 := (((-9 - Q(8)) \times 7) + ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$590 := ((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$591 := (-9 + ((Q(8) + (7 - 6 - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$592 := ((-9 + 8 - (7 \times 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$593 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (((7 + 6) + Q(Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$594 := ((-9 - 8 - Q(7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$595 := ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - Q(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$596 := ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
597 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q((Q(3) + Q(4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
598 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q((Q(3) + Q(4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
599 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
600 &:= (-1 \times (((2 + 3)^4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
601 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q((Q(3) + Q(4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
602 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) + Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
603 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
604 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
605 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
606 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 \times 3))) + (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
607 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
608 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) + Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
609 &:= (Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
610 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times (3 \times 4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
611 &:= ((Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) \times Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
612 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) \times 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
613 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
614 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
615 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
616 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
617 &:= ((-1 + ((2^3) \times Q(4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
618 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times Q(Q(4))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
619 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((4^5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
620 &:= (Q(Q((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
621 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + Q(3))) - Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
622 &:= (-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
623 &:= (-1 + (Q(2^3) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
624 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
625 &:= Q((-1 - ((2 + 3 + 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
626 &:= (-1 + 2 + Q(Q(((3 + 4) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
627 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
628 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - ((4 - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
629 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
630 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
631 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times 4) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
632 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(3) \times 4) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
633 &:= (((-1 - Q(2 \times 3)) \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
634 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
635 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
636 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
597 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
598 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) \times (7 + 6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
599 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) + (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
600 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 - 7 + 6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
601 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) + Q(Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
602 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times Q(7))) - (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
603 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
604 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) - (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
605 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7 + 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
606 &:= (-9 - 8 - (7 \times (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
607 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
608 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + Q(7)) \times (6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
609 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7)))/6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
610 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + 7 \times 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
611 &:= 9 \times Q(8) - 5 \times (7 + 6) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
612 &:= (-9 \times ((Q(Q(8))/(7 + Q(6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
613 &:= 9 \times (-8 + 7 \times 6) - 5 + 4 \times (Q(Q(3)) - 2 - 1) \\
614 &:= (-9 + (8 \times Q(7) + (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
615 &:= (9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
616 &:= (Q((((-9 + 8) \times 7) + Q(6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
617 &:= 9 \times Q(8) - Q(7) + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
618 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times Q(7 + 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
619 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
620 &:= ((Q((-9 + (8 + 7 + 6))) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
621 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
622 &:= (-9 + 8 - (7 \times (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
623 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
624 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - Q(Q((7 \times (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
625 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7)))/6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
626 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times Q(6 + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
627 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (7 - (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
628 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 + Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
629 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + Q(Q(5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
630 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) - 7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
631 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7))! + (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
632 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
633 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
634 &:= ((-9/(8 + 7 - 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
635 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) - (6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
636 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (7 + 6 - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
637 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
638 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
639 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
640 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times (Q(3) + 4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
641 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
642 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
643 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) - (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
644 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 \times 3))) - (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
645 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
646 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 \times 3))) - (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
647 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3 + 4) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
648 &:= (-1 - (Q((2 \times (3 \times 4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
649 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 \times (3 \times 4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
650 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3 + 4)) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
651 &:= (-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
652 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((Q(3 + 4) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
653 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((Q(3 + 4) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
654 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
655 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
656 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 \times 3))) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
657 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(3) + Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
658 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(3) + Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
659 &:= 1 - 2 + Q(Q(3) + Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
660 &:= (Q(Q((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
661 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(3) + Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
662 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
663 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
664 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 \times 3))) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
665 &:= 1 + Q(Q(2 + 3)) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
666 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
667 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - (4 - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
668 &:= (-1 - (Q((2 + 3 + 4)) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
669 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 + 3 + 4)) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
670 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times (Q(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
671 &:= (Q((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
672 &:= (((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
673 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
674 &:= (-1 - ((Q(2 + 3) \times (4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
675 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
676 &:= Q((-1 \times ((2 + 3 + 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
637 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) + Q(Q(6))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
638 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) \times (6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
639 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 + Q(7)))) - Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
640 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + 7 \times 6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
641 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) - Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
642 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) + 7) \times 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
643 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) \times 7 - ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
644 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
645 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
646 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) + (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
647 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6 + 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
648 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + 6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
649 &:= 9 - (Q(8) - 7 - Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
650 &:= (((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) - 6) \times Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
651 &:= ((((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6) + Q(Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
652 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7 + 6) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
653 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(Q(6))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
654 &:= ((-9 + ((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
655 &:= 9 - 8 - 7 + Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
656 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - Q(((7 \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
657 &:= (-9 + (Q(8 + 7) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
658 &:= ((-9 + Q(8) \times 7) - (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
659 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((7 + 6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
660 &:= 9 \times (Q(8) + 7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
661 &:= (Q(((-9 - 8 + 7) + Q(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
662 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((7 + 6) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
663 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
664 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
665 &:= (((-9 + Q(Q(8)) - 7) / 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
666 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + 7 + 6 + 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
667 &:= (-9 + Q((Q(((8 + 7) - (6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
668 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7 + 6) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
669 &:= (Q((-9 + (8 + 7 + 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
670 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times 7) + (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
671 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) - 7 + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
672 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
673 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (Q(7 + 6) \times 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
674 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 \times Q(6 + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
675 &:= 9 + Q(8 + 7) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
676 &:= Q(((-9 + 8 \times 7) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
677 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times Q(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
678 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3 + 4) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
679 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3)))) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
680 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + Q(3)) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
681 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
682 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(Q(3)) \times 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
683 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) \times (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
684 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 \times 3) \times (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
685 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
686 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(3 + Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
687 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
688 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q(3) \times 4) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
689 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) - (Q(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
690 &:= (1 + 2) \times (Q(3) + Q(Q(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
691 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3)))/Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
692 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(3 + 4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
693 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + (Q(3) + Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
694 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (Q(3) + Q(Q(4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
695 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) + Q(Q(4)))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
696 &:= (-1 - (2^{Q(3)} + (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
697 &:= (-1 \times (2^{Q(3)} + (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
698 &:= ((-1 + Q((Q(2 \times 3) - 4 - 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
699 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3 \times Q(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
700 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) + Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
701 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
702 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3 + 4) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
703 &:= ((-1 - Q(2 \times 3)) \times (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
704 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 + (3 + (4 + 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
705 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3 + 4) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
706 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - Q(Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
707 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (3 + Q(Q(4)))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
708 &:= (-1 - (2^{Q(3)} + (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
709 &:= (-1 \times (2^{Q(3)} + (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
710 &:= ((-1 + (Q(2 + Q(3)) \times Q(4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
711 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(3) + Q(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
712 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(3) \times (4 - Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
713 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) \times Q(Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
714 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times Q(Q(4)))) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
715 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
716 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
677 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + 7 + 6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
678 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
679 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(6))) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
680 &:= (9 + 8) \times (Q(7) + 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
681 &:= 9 - 8 + (Q(7) - 6 + Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
682 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + 7 + 6)) + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
683 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
684 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
685 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
686 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
687 &:= -Q(-9 + Q(8)) + Q(Q(7)) + Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
688 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
689 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - Q(6))) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
690 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(6)) \times Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
691 &:= (Q(((9 - 8 + 7) + Q(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
692 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
693 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
694 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((Q(7) \times (6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
695 &:= (((-9 + Q(Q(8)) - 7)/6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
696 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (Q(7) + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
697 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
698 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (7 - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
699 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((Q(7) + Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
700 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (7 + 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
701 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) - (6 \times (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
702 &:= (-9 \times (((Q(8) - Q((7 \times 6)))/Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
703 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((Q(7) - Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
704 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (7 \times (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
705 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
706 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
707 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
708 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + Q(6)))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
709 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(6))) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
710 &:= ((-9 + 8 - (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
711 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - Q((7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
712 &:= (-9 \times 8 + Q((7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
713 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) + (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
714 &:= (Q(-9 + Q((8 - 7) \times 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
715 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) + Q(6)) \times Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
716 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times Q(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
717 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{Q(3)}) - (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
718 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q((Q(3) + 4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
719 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3 - Q(Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
720 &:= 1 + 2 \times (3 - Q(Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
721 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
722 &:= (-1 - 2 - (((3 + 4) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
723 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (((3 + 4) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
724 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - Q(Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
725 &:= (-1 \times ((Q(2 + 3) + 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
726 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
727 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
728 &:= (-1 - ((2^{Q(3)}) - (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
729 &:= Q((-1 - 2 - (Q(3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
730 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (3 \times Q(Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
731 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times Q(Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
732 &:= (-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
733 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times Q(Q(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
734 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) + Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
735 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((Q(3) - Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
736 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
737 &:= (((-1 - Q(2 + Q(3))) \times 4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
738 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) \times Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
739 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
740 &:= (-1 - (Q(((2 \times 3) + Q(4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
741 &:= (-1 \times (Q(((2 \times 3) + Q(4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
742 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + (Q(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
743 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
744 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (3 + 4)) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
745 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
746 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
747 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
748 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3 + 4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
749 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
750 &:= ((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + (4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
751 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{Q(Q(3+4))}) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
752 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3 + 4) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
753 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q((3 + (4 + 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
754 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q((3 + (4 + 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
755 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
756 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(3 + Q(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
717 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
718 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - Q(6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
719 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((Q(7) - Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
720 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - Q(7 + 6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
721 &:= (((Q((-9 + Q(8))) - Q(7))/6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
722 &:= (-9 + (Q(8 + 7) + (6 + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
723 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - Q((Q(7) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
724 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7 + 6) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
725 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
726 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 - 7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
727 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6 - 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
728 &:= (-9 + 8 + Q(((7 \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
729 &:= Q((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
730 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
731 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
732 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
733 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(7))/6) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
734 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
735 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
736 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times Q(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
737 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7 + 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
738 &:= (-9 \times (((8 + 7) \times 6)/5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
739 &:= (Q((-9 + Q((((8 - 7)^6) + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
740 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(7 + 6)) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
741 &:= 9 + Q(Q(8)) - Q(Q(7) - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
742 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 + (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
743 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
744 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8 - 7) \times 6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
745 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
746 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times Q(6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
747 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
748 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
749 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
750 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7 + 6)) \times Q(Q(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
751 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) - (7 + 6 - Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
752 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((Q(7) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
753 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((Q(7) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
754 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
755 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
756 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
757 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q((3 + (4 + 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
758 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2 \times 3) - 4 - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
759 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times (3 \times (4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
760 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((3 \times (4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
761 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (Q(4) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
762 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - (4 - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
763 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + (Q(3) + Q(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
764 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
765 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 \times 3))) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
766 &:= (Q((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
767 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{3+4}) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
768 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
769 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) + Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
770 &:= (((-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
771 &:= (((-1 - Q(2 + 3)) \times 4) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
772 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q((Q(3) + (4 - 5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
773 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3)) - (Q((Q(4) - 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
774 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + 3) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
775 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
776 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - Q(Q(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
777 &:= (((-1 - Q(2 \times 3)) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
778 &:= (-1 - (Q((2 + (Q(Q(3)) / (4 + 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
779 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 + (Q(Q(3)) / (4 + 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
780 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times Q(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
781 &:= (-1 - 2 + Q((Q(3) - (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
782 &:= (-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(3) - (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
783 &:= (-1 + Q((2 \times (Q(3 + 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
784 &:= Q(((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
785 &:= (-1 + 2 + Q((Q(3) - (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
786 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) - (Q((4 + Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
787 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + Q(3)) - ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
788 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + Q(3)) - ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
789 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + 4)) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
790 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times (3 + 4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
791 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3 + Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
792 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3)) - (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
793 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q((3 \times 4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
794 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - Q(Q(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
795 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + 4) \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
796 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3 + 4) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
757 &:= (((-9 + Q(((8 \times 7) + 6))) / 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
758 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
759 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 - 6 - 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
760 &:= 9 \times Q(8) + Q(7 + 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
761 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
762 &:= (((-9 + ((Q(8) + 7) \times (6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
763 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
764 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 \times Q(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
765 &:= (((-9 + Q((8 + Q(7)))) / 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
766 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8) - 7 - 6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
767 &:= (-9 - 8 + Q((7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
768 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
769 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
770 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times 7) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
771 &:= (Q(((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
772 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7 + 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
773 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7 + 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
774 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
775 &:= (-9 + Q((Q(8) - Q((7 - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
776 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
777 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + Q(Q(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
778 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
779 &:= (Q((-9 + (8 + 7 + 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
780 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times ((6 \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
781 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
782 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times (6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
783 &:= (-9 + 8 + Q((7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
784 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + Q(((7 \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
785 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 \times Q(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
786 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
787 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
788 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8) \times (7 + 6))) - (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
789 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((7 + 6) \times (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
790 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (7 + 6)) - (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
791 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
792 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - 7 + 6 + 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
793 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) - (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
794 &:= (-9 + (((8 + Q(Q(7))) / ((6 \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
795 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - Q((Q(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
796 &:= (-9 + ((8 - Q(7 + 6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$797 := (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$798 := (-1 + 2 - 3 - ((4 \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$799 := (Q(((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$800 := (Q((-1 - 2 + (3 \times Q(4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$801 := (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times Q(Q(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$802 := (-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$803 := ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times Q(Q(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$804 := (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times Q(Q(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$805 := ((-1 + Q((Q(2 + 3) + 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$806 := ((-1 - Q(2 + 3)) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$807 := (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$808 := 1 - 2 \times Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$809 := (((-1 - Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$810 := -Q(Q(3)) \times (-1 + 2) - 4 - 5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$811 := Q(1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$812 := ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) - (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$813 := ((-1 - (2 + 3)) - (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$814 := ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) - (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$815 := (((-1 + 2 - Q(Q(Q(3)))) / Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$816 := (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$817 := (-1 + 2 - 3 - (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$818 := (-1 + ((2 - 3) \times (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$819 := (Q((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + 4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$820 := (((-1 + 2)^3) - (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$821 := (((-1 - Q(2 + 3)) \times 4) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$822 := ((-1 + ((2^3) \times Q(Q(4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$823 := ((-1 + 2 + 3) - (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$824 := (-1 - (Q(((2 + 3) \times 4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$825 := (-1 \times (Q(((2 + 3) \times 4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$826 := ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) - ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$827 := (-1 \times (Q(2^3) + (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$828 := (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$829 := (-1 + 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$830 := (-1 + (Q((2 + 3 + 4)) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$831 := ((((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$832 := (-1 + 2 + ((3^4) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$833 := (-1 - (Q(2 + 3) + (Q(4) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$834 := (((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times (Q(4) - 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$835 := (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$836 := (-1 \times (Q((2 - (3 - 4 - 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$797 := (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$798 := ((-9 \times (8 + Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$799 := (Q((-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$800 := (((-9 - Q(8)) \times 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$801 := 9 + 8 + Q(7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$802 := (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 \times Q(6 + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$803 := (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$804 := ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$805 := (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$806 := (-9 - (((8 - Q(7 + 6)) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$807 := ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$808 := ((-9 + (Q(8) \times (7 + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$809 := (-9 - ((8 \times Q(7)) - (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$810 := ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$811 := (-9 + ((Q(8) + 7 + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$812 := (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$813 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$814 := ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7 + 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$815 := 9 \times Q(8 + 7) - Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$816 := (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + Q(6 + Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$817 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$818 := (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$819 := (Q((-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(6))) + (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$820 := ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times Q(6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$821 := (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$822 := (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$823 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$824 := (-9 + (8 \times Q(7) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$825 := ((-9 + Q(8)) \times ((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$826 := (((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$827 := (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) - (Q(6 + Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$828 := (-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$829 := (Q((-9 + Q((((8 - 7)^6) + 5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$830 := (((-9 + 8 + Q(7 + 6)) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$831 := (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$832 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 \times (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$833 := (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (6 - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$834 := ((-9 + 8 + (Q(7 + 6) \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$835 := (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$836 := ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times Q(6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
837 &:= ((-1-2) \times (Q(3) \times (4 - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
838 &:= (-1+2 + ((3 \times (4 - Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
839 &:= -Q(-1+Q(2+3))/Q(4) - Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9) \\
840 &:= ((-1-2+Q(3)) \times (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
841 &:= Q((Q((-1+(2+3+4))) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
842 &:= (((-1+2)^3) + Q((4 - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
843 &:= ((-1+Q(2+3)) - (Q(4+5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
844 &:= (Q((-1+2 \times 3)) - (Q(4+5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
845 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2+3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
846 &:= ((-1-2) \times (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
847 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
848 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
849 &:= (Q((-1+(2 \times Q(3)))) + (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
850 &:= (((-1 - (2+3+4)) \times 5) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
851 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - (2 - (3+4)))))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
852 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3+4) - Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
853 &:= (-1-2 - (Q(3+4) - (5+Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
854 &:= ((-1 - ((2+3) \times (4+5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
855 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2+3)) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
856 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2+3)) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
857 &:= (-1+2 - (Q(3+4) - (5+Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
858 &:= (((-1+2-3) \times (Q(4)+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
859 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+Q(3)) - (Q(4+5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
860 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+Q(3)) - (Q(4+5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
861 &:= (-1-2 - (Q(3+Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
862 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3+Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
863 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (Q(3) + (4+5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
864 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3 - (Q(Q(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
865 &:= (-1+2 - (Q(3+Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
866 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+3) + (4+5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
867 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2+3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
868 &:= (Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) - (Q(4+5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
869 &:= -Q(-1+2+Q(3)) - Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9) \\
870 &:= (-1-2 + (3 \times (Q(Q(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
871 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (Q(Q(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
872 &:= (-1-2 + ((Q(3) + Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
873 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
874 &:= (-1+2 + (3 \times (Q(Q(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
875 &:= (Q((-1 \times (2 - (3+4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
876 &:= (-1+2 + ((Q(3) + Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
837 &:= (-9 - (Q(8+7) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
838 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (7+6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
839 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + Q((7+6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
840 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + (7-6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
841 &:= Q((((-9 - Q(8)) \times 7) + (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
842 &:= (((-9-8) \times 7) + Q((Q(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
843 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
844 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (7 \times (Q(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
845 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (Q(6+5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
846 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
847 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7+6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
848 &:= (-9+8 + (Q(7) + (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
849 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8) + Q(7))) \times 6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
850 &:= (Q((-9-8+7 \times 6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
851 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
852 &:= (-9 - ((8 - Q(7)) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
853 &:= ((-9+8-7+Q(6+Q(5))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
854 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) \times 7 - (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
855 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) - Q(6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
856 &:= (Q((((-9+8) \times 7) + Q(6))) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
857 &:= (-9 + (Q(8+7) + (6 + (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
858 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) - (6+5))) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
859 &:= (Q((-9+8 \times 7)) - (6 \times Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
860 &:= (((-9-8+Q(7+6)) \times 5) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
861 &:= (Q(((((-9+8+7) \times 6) - 5) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
862 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 + Q((6 \times 5))) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
863 &:= ((-9-8+Q(Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
864 &:= (-9 \times (((8+7) - (6+5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
865 &:= (Q((Q((-9+8+7)) - 6)) - (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
866 &:= (-9 - (Q(8+7) - ((6+5) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
867 &:= ((((-9+Q(8)) \times Q(7+6)) - Q(Q(5)))/(4+3+2+1)) \\
868 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q((Q(7) - (6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
869 &:= (Q((-9 + (8+7+6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
870 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - Q(7+6))) + (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
871 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) - ((7-6) - Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
872 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) + 7) \times (6+5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
873 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (7+6)) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
874 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 \times Q(6+5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
875 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 \times Q(6+5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
876 &:= (-9 - ((8 + Q(7+6)) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
877 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3 + 4) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
878 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3 - (4 \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
879 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) + (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
880 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
881 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times Q(Q(3)))/(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
882 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
883 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
884 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
885 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
886 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
887 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q((Q(3) + 4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
888 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((Q(Q(3)))/(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
889 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
890 &:= ((-1 + ((2 - 3) \times (4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
891 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3 + 4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
892 &:= (-1 - (((2 + Q(Q(3))) \times 4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
893 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) - Q(Q(3))) \times 4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
894 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
895 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
896 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
897 &:= (-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
898 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((Q(Q(3)) \times 4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
899 &:= (-1 + Q((2 - ((3 + 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
900 &:= Q(((((-1 - 2) \times 3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
901 &:= (-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
902 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((Q(Q(3)) \times 4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
903 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + 3) - 4 - 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
904 &:= (-1 - (Q((2 \times Q(3))) - (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
905 &:= (((-1 + 2 - Q(Q(3))) \times 4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
906 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q(Q(3)))/(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
907 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
908 &:= (-1 + (((2 - Q(Q(3))) \times 4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
909 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 - Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
910 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (Q(3) + Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
911 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 - 4 - 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
912 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times (3 + (4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
913 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 \times Q(Q(4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
914 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((3 \times Q(Q(4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
915 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
916 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
877 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
878 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) - (6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
879 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
880 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times 7) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
881 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((Q((7 \times 6)) \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
882 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
883 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) + Q((6 \times 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
884 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7)))/6) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
885 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7) - 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
886 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 + 6 - Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
887 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) \times (7 - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
888 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) \times 5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
889 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(6))) + (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
890 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (7 + 6 + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
891 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - 7)^{65}) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
892 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 \times Q(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
893 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) \times 7 - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
894 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
895 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - Q(7 + 6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
896 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
897 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
898 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
899 &:= (-9 + 8 + Q((((Q(Q(7) + 6)) - Q(5))/Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
900 &:= Q(((((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
901 &:= (Q(((((-9 - 8 + 7) + Q(6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
902 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6))) - 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
903 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6))) + 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
904 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((Q(7) \times (6 - Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
905 &:= (((-9 + Q(Q(8)) - 7)/6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
906 &:= ((-9 + (((8 - 7) + Q(6)) \times Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
907 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + Q(7 + 6))) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
908 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
909 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) + (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
910 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
911 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + Q(Q(6))) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
912 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 \times Q(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
913 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) - (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
914 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
915 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7) - 6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
916 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
917 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 \times Q(3))) - (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
918 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
919 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) + ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
920 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
921 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times Q(3))) \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
922 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(3 + 4)) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
923 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + (4 + 5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
924 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (3 \times (4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
925 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
926 &:= (Q(((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) - 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
927 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times (3 \times (4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
928 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times (4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
929 &:= ((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
930 &:= ((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) \times (4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
931 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3)))/Q(4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
932 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
933 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 \times 3) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
934 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
935 &:= (Q(((-1 + Q(2 + Q(3)))/4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
936 &:= ((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
937 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q((3 \times 4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
938 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
939 &:= ((-1 + Q(2 + Q(3))) - (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
940 &:= (Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) - (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
941 &:= (Q((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
942 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
943 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + 3) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
944 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
945 &:= ((-1 - ((2 - Q(3)) \times 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
946 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + (Q((4 \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
947 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(3 + 4) - Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
948 &:= (((Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) - Q(4))/5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
949 &:= (Q((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - 4 - 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
950 &:= (-1 - (2 \times Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
951 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
952 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3 + 4) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
953 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 + 5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
954 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3)) + (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
955 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + 3) - (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
956 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) - (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
917 &:= (((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
918 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + Q(6)))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
919 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
920 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + Q(7 + 6)) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
921 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + ((6)! + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
922 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
923 &:= (-9 + (8 \times Q(7) + (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
924 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7 + 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
925 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) + (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
926 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + (Q((6 \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
927 &:= (((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
928 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
929 &:= ((((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7 + 6)) - 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
930 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - Q(7 + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
931 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((Q(7) \times 6) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
932 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + 7 + 6)) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
933 &:= (((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times Q(Q(6))) + 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
934 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
935 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
936 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + Q(Q(6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
937 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + Q((Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
938 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (7 - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
939 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) - (6 \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
940 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
941 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
942 &:= ((-9 + Q(((8 - 7) + 6 \times 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
943 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7 + 6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
944 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - Q(6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
945 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
946 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 \times Q(6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
947 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (Q(6 + Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
948 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
949 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times Q(7)) - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
950 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
951 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) \times ((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
952 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7 + 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
953 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + Q((Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
954 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
955 &:= (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) + (Q(6) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
956 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
957 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
958 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
959 &:= (-1 \times 2 + Q(((Q(Q(Q(3)))/Q(Q(4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
960 &:= (-1 + Q(((2 - 3) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
961 &:= Q((-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
962 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
963 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
964 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
965 &:= (((-1 - Q(2^3)) \times 4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
966 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(Q(3))) - (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
967 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
968 &:= (-1 + ((2 - 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
969 &:= (Q(Q(Q(Q(Q(-1 - 2 + 3)))))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
970 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
971 &:= (-1 + (((2^3) \times (4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
972 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
973 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
974 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
975 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
976 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
977 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3^4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
978 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
979 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
980 &:= ((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
981 &:= (Q((-1 - (2 - (3 + (4 + 5)))))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
982 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3^4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
983 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - ((4 - 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
984 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(3 + 4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
985 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
986 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
987 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
988 &:= ((-1 + Q((Q(2 \times 3) - 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
989 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times Q(Q(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
990 &:= ((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + (4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
991 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
992 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(((3 + 4) + Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
993 &:= ((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
994 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
995 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(((3 + 4) + Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
996 &:= (Q(((-1 + Q(2 \times 3) - 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
957 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
958 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((7 + 6) \times (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
959 &:= (-9 + (8 \times Q(((7 - 6)^5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
960 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - Q(7 + 6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
961 &:= Q((-9 + (((8 + 7) - (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
962 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
963 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((7 \times 6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
964 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - Q(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
965 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
966 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + (7 - 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
967 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + Q((Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
968 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) - (6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
969 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7) + (6 - Q(Q(5)))))) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
970 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) + Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
971 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 \times (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
972 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
973 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
974 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 + 6) \times (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
975 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) \times (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
976 &:= (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) - (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
977 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + (Q(6 + Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
978 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
979 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
980 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (7 + 6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
981 &:= 9 \times (8 - Q(7)) + 6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
982 &:= (((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) \times (6 + Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
983 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
984 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7 + 6) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
985 &:= (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) + (6 - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
986 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) - ((6 + Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
987 &:= (9 - 8) \times 7 \times (Q(6) + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
988 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
989 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 - 7 + (Q(6) + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
990 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - (7 + 6 + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
991 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) + (7 - Q(6)))))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
992 &:= (((-9 \times 8 - 7) + Q(Q(6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
993 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
994 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
995 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - Q(7 + 6))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
996 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) - (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
997 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) + (Q(4+5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 997 &:= (Q((-9+8+7)) + Q((Q(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
998 &:= (((-1-2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 998 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8) + 7) - 6) / (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
999 &:= (-1 - (Q(((2-3) + Q(4))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 999 &:= (Q((-9+8 \times 7)) - (Q(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1000 &:= (-1 \times (Q(((2-3) + Q(4))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1000 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times Q(6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
\\
1001 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 1001 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + (7+6 \times 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1002 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(3+4)) + (5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1002 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 \times Q(6+5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1003 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + ((4 \times Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1003 &:= (Q((-9-8+Q(7))) - (6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1004 &:= ((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1004 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7+6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1005 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1005 &:= (-9-8 - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1006 &:= (Q((-1+2 \times 3)) + (Q(4+5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1006 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + Q(Q(6))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1007 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(3+4) + 5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1007 &:= (Q((-9+8+7)) + (Q(6+Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
1008 &:= (-1 - ((2^{Q(3)}) - Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 1008 &:= ((-9+8+Q(7)) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1009 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{Q(3)}) - Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 1009 &:= (Q((-9+8-7+Q(6))) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1010 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + (4 + (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 1010 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1011 &:= ((-1 + Q(2+Q(3))) - (4+5 - Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1011 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + (Q(7) - (6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1012 &:= (((Q((-1+Q(2+3))) - Q(4))/5) + Q(6+7+8+9)) & 1012 &:= (-9-8 + (Q(7) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1013 &:= (((-1+2-3) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1013 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1014 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2+3) + 4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) & 1014 &:= (-9+8 - ((7 - Q(6)) \times (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1015 &:= ((Q((-1+2 \times 3)) + 4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) & 1015 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) \times (7 - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
1016 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) + (Q(4+5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1016 &:= ((Q((-9+8+7)) \times (6+Q(5))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
1017 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(3))) + (Q(4+5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1017 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1018 &:= (Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1018 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1019 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2+3) + (4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 1019 &:= ((-9+8) \times (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) \times (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1020 &:= ((Q((-1+2 \times 3)) + (4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9)) & 1020 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + 7+6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1021 &:= (Q((-1 - (2 \times (3-4-5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9)) & 1021 &:= (-9+8 - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1022 &:= (-1 \times 2 + Q(((3+4) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) & 1022 &:= ((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 - (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1023 &:= (-1 + Q((2 - (Q(3) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)))))) & 1023 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1024 &:= (Q((-1 - ((2 \times 3) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1024 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q((Q(7) + (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1025 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2 \times 3))) - ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 1025 &:= (Q((-9-8+Q(7))) + (6+5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1026 &:= (Q(Q((-1-2+Q(3)))) - ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 1026 &:= (-9 - ((8+7) \times (Q(6) - (5+Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1027 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q((Q(3) + (4-5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1027 &:= (-9 - (Q(8+7) - (Q(6) + Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1028 &:= (-1 - (Q((2 \times (3+4))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1028 &:= (-9+8 + (Q(7) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1029 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 \times (3+4))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1029 &:= ((-9+8+Q(Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1030 &:= (((-1-2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1030 &:= ((-9+Q(8)) - ((7+6) \times (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1031 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1031 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8+7) - Q(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1032 &:= ((-1 + Q(2^3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1032 &:= (-9-8 + (Q(7) + (Q((6 \times 5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1033 &:= (((-1-2 - Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1033 &:= (Q((-9-8+Q(7))) - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1034 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(3+4) - 5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) & 1034 &:= ((-9-8+Q(Q(7))) - (6 \times Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1035 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) - (Q((Q(4) - 5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1035 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) - (Q(6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1036 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4 + 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1037 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(3 + 4) - 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1038 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1039 &:= (Q((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - 4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1040 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1041 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((3 + (4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1042 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((3 + (4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1043 &:= (((-1 + Q(2^3)) \times Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1044 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times (3 + (4 + 5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1045 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((3 + (4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1046 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1047 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1048 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1049 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1050 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1051 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1052 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1053 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q((Q(3) + 4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1054 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(3) \times 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1055 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) + 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1056 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - Q(4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1057 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q((Q(3) + 4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1058 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2 \times 3) - 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1059 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times Q(Q(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1060 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1061 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(Q(Q(3)))/Q(4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1062 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1063 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (3^4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1064 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1065 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + Q((Q(4) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1066 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1067 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1068 &:= (((-1 + Q((Q(2 + 3) + 4)))/5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1069 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1070 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - 4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1071 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1072 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((3 + 4) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1073 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((3 + 4) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1074 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2 \times 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1075 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1036 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q((7 \times 6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1037 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1038 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(Q(6))) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1039 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7 + 6) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1040 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - Q(7 + 6))) - (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1041 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 \times (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1042 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + 7)) + Q((Q(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1043 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) \times (7 + 6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1044 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - ((7 + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1045 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1046 &:= (Q(((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6)) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1047 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) + Q(Q(6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1048 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (7 + 6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1049 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((7 + 6) \times (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1050 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1051 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) - Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1052 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (6 - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1053 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + (Q(6 + Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1054 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - Q(6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1055 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(7 + 6) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1056 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7 + 6) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1057 &:= (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1058 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1059 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((7 \times 6) \times Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1060 &:= ((((-9 + Q(8)) - 7 - 6) \times Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1061 &:= (((-9 - 8 + 7) + Q(Q(6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1062 &:= -9 + Q(Q((8 - 7) \times 6)) - Q((5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1063 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(Q(6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1064 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) + Q(Q(6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1065 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1066 &:= (Q((((-9 + 8) \times 7) + Q(6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1067 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + ((7 - Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1068 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((7 - Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1069 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1070 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - Q(6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1071 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1072 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + Q(Q(6))) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1073 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1074 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + (6 \times Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1075 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1076 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((3 \times Q(4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1076 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1077 &:= (((-1 - Q(2 \times 3)) \times 4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1077 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1078 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3 + 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1078 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1079 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times 4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1079 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) \times ((Q(7) + Q(6 + 5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1080 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((3 \times Q(4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1080 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(7 + 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1081 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1081 &:= 9 + 8 - 7 + Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1082 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q((3 \times 4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1082 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (Q(6) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1083 &:= (-1 - (Q(((2 + 3) + Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1083 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1084 &:= (-1 \times (Q(((2 + 3) + Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1084 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1085 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1085 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((Q(7 + 6) + Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1086 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1086 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) - (6 \times (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1087 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + Q(3)) + (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1087 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + Q(7))) + Q(((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1088 &:= (-1 + Q((Q(2^3) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1088 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1089 &:= Q((-1 - ((2 + 3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1089 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 + 6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1090 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times (3 + 4)))) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1090 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (7 + 6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1091 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3 + 4) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1091 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1092 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3 + 4) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1092 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1093 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q((3 \times 4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1093 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1094 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1094 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1095 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1095 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7) - (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1096 &:= (-1 - ((2^{3+4}) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1096 &:= (((-9 - Q(8 + 7)) \times 6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1097 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{3+4}) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1097 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + (Q(6 + Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1098 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1098 &:= ((-9 - (Q(8) + Q(7))) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1099 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + Q(3)) + (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1099 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1100 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + Q(3)) + (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1100 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) + Q(5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1101 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3) - (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1101 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + ((7 \times 6) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1102 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) - (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1102 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1103 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1103 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1104 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1104 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + ((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1105 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1105 &:= 9 \times Q(8) + Q(7) \times (6 + 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
1106 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1106 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1107 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + Q(3)) - (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1107 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1108 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + Q(3)) - (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1108 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1109 &:= -Q(-1 + 2 + Q(3)) - Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1109 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) - ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1110 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1110 &:= (((-9 - 8 + 7) + Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1111 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times 4))) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1111 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (Q(7) + (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1112 &:= (-1 + (((2 - Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1112 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1113 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1113 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) - (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1114 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1114 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1115 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1115 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8))/(7 - 6 - 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1116 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 \times 3) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1117 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) \times 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1118 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2 + Q(3)) \times (4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1119 &:= Q(1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (4 + 5) + (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1120 &:= ((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1121 &:= (((-1 - Q(2 + 3)) \times 4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1122 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3 + 4) - Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1123 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1124 &:= (-1 - ((Q(2 + 3) \times 4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1125 &:= (-1 \times ((Q(2 + 3) \times 4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1126 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q(3 + 4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1127 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3 + 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1128 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3) \times Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1129 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1130 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1131 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1132 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1133 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1134 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - Q(4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1135 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(3 + 4)) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1136 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1137 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) + (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1138 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) + (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1139 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1140 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 \times Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1141 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(Q(3)) + (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1142 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((3^4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1143 &:= (-1 - (Q((2 + 3 + 4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1144 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 + 3 + 4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1145 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1146 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) - (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1147 &:= ((-1 - Q(2 \times 3)) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1148 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((3^4) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1149 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1150 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) + Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1151 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q((3 - (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1152 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (Q(3) \times 4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1153 &:= (-1 - 2 + Q((3 - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1154 &:= (-1 \times 2 + Q((3 - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1155 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (Q(3) \times 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1116 &:= (-9 - ((8 - 7 - 6) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1117 &:= (((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6)) - (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1118 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times Q(7 + 6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1119 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1120 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1121 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1122 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1123 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((7 - Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1124 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1125 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) - 6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1126 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) \times (6 + Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1127 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + ((7 + 6 - Q(5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1128 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((7 + 6 - Q(5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1129 &:= (Q(((9 - Q(8)) - 7 - 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1130 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1131 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7) + (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1132 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1133 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 + Q(Q(6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1134 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1135 &:= ((-9 + Q(((8 - 7) + Q(6)))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1136 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1137 &:= (((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1138 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1139 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 - Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1140 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) + Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1141 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8 + 7) \times 6) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1142 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1143 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) \times (7 + 6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1144 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7) - (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1145 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1146 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + 7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1147 &:= (-9 + Q((Q((8 - 7 + 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1148 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1149 &:= (Q(((9 - Q(8)) - 7 - 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1150 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1151 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(Q(8)) - Q((7 + 6) \times 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1152 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) \times (7 + 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1153 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (7 + 6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1154 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8) + Q(7))) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1155 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1156 &:= Q((-1 \times ((2+3) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1156 &:= Q(((-9 - 8) \times (7+6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1157 &:= (-1+2+Q((3 - (4 - (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1157 &:= (-9 + (Q((8+7+6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1158 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1158 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((7+Q(6)) \times Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1159 &:= ((-1+2-3) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5+Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1159 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1160 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1160 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1161 &:= (-1+2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1161 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) - (Q(7+Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1162 &:= (((-1+2+Q(Q(3))) \times Q(4)) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) & 1162 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7+6) \times Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1163 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1163 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((7+6) \times (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1164 &:= ((-1+2+3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) & 1164 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1165 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2^3) - (4+Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1165 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) - (Q(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
1166 &:= (Q(Q((-1-2+Q(3)))) - ((4 \times Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)) & 1166 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + 7+6) + Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1167 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + (Q(4) - (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1167 &:= 9+8+7 \times 6 \times Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1) \\
1168 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3+Q(4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1168 &:= ((-9 \times (8+Q(7))) + Q((Q(6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1169 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (3+4)) + Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 1169 &:= ((-9+8+Q(Q(7))) - (6+Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
1170 &:= (((-1+Q(2+Q(3))) - Q(4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9)) & 1170 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - Q(7+6))) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1171 &:= ((-1+2+(3 \times Q((4 \times 5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 1171 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - Q((Q((7+6-5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1172 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) + (Q(4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1172 &:= ((-9+8) \times (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1173 &:= (-1-2 - (Q(3+4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1173 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((7 \times 6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1174 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3+4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1174 &:= (((-9+Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1175 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((3 \times Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1175 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1176 &:= (Q(Q(((-1+2) \times (3+4)))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1176 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1177 &:= (-1+2 - (Q(3+4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1177 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) + (6 - (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1178 &:= (-1+2 - ((3 \times Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1178 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1179 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((Q(3) + Q(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1179 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - ((7+6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1180 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (4 - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1180 &:= ((-9 \times (8-7-Q(6+5))) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
1181 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) - Q(3)) \times 4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1181 &:= (-9+8-7 - (Q(6) - Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
1182 &:= (((-1-2) \times Q(3)) - (Q(4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1182 &:= ((-9+8 - (7 \times 6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1183 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+3) + (Q(4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1183 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((7+6 - Q(5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1184 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+3) + (Q(4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1184 &:= ((((-9+8) \times 7) + Q(Q(6))) - (5 + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1185 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2 \times 3))) + (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) & 1185 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) - (6+5+Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1186 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2 \times 3))) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)) & 1186 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) - ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1187 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (3+Q(4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1187 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1188 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2^3) + (4+5))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1188 &:= (-9 + ((8+Q(7)) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1189 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3 \times 4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1189 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1190 &:= (-1+2 - ((Q(3) \times 4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1190 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1191 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) - (Q(4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1191 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) - (Q(7+Q(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1192 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) - (4+Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1192 &:= (((-9-8) \times 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1193 &:= (((-1+2-3) \times Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1193 &:= (-9+8-7 + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1194 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2 \times 3))) + (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))) & 1194 &:= (((-9+Q((Q(8) + 7+6)))/5) + 4+3+2+1) \\
1195 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+3) + (4 - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1195 &:= ((-9+Q(8)) - ((7 - Q(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1196 &:= (-1 - (Q((2 \times Q(3))) - Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1197 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 \times Q(3))) - Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1198 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) + (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1199 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) + 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1200 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) - (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1201 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times 4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1202 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3)) + (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1203 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) - (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1204 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1205 &:= ((-1 \times ((2 + 3) \times 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1206 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) + (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1207 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1208 &:= (-1 + ((2 - 3) \times (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1209 &:= (Q(Q(Q(Q(-1 - 2 + 3)))) - (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1210 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 + 4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1211 &:= ((-1 \times (2 \times (3 + 4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1212 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1213 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) - (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1214 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (3 \times 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1215 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3 + 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1216 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3 + 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1217 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) \times 4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1218 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1219 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (3 + 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1220 &:= (((-1 + 2 - Q(Q(3)))/Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1221 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1222 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) - (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1223 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + 3) - 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1224 &:= (-1 + Q((((2 + 3) - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1225 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{Q(Q(3+4))}) \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1226 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{Q(Q(3+4))}) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1227 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (3 - 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1228 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1229 &:= ((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1230 &:= ((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1231 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3))/4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1232 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1233 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1234 &:= (Q(((-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1235 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) + (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1196 &:= (Q(((-9 + 8 \times 7) - (6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1197 &:= (-9 \times (((8 \times 7) + Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1198 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 \times (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1199 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 + 6 - Q(5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1200 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) + (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1201 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) + (7 - Q(6)))))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1202 &:= (((-9 \times 8 - 7) + Q(Q(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1203 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((7 \times 6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1204 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1205 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - Q(7 + 6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1206 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1207 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1208 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 + Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1209 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1210 &:= (Q(((-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) + Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1211 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7) + Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1212 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1213 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1214 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1215 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7))! + ((6)! - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1216 &:= (-9 + Q(((8 \times 7) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1217 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7)^6) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1218 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((7 + 6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1219 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + 6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1220 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (Q(7 + 6) + Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1221 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7 - 6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1222 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) + Q(Q(6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1223 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7 + 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1224 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7 + 6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1225 &:= Q(((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1226 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + ((6 \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1227 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (Q(6) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1228 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1229 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1230 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) + (Q(6 + Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1231 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1232 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1233 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1234 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1235 &:= (Q(((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7)/(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1236 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1236 &:= ((-9 - (8+7)) + (Q(6) \times (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1237 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) - (4 - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1237 &:= ((-9 + (8+7+6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1238 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3+4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1238 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times Q(7+6))) - (5 + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1239 &:= ((-1+2-3) + (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1239 &:= (Q(((9+Q(8)) - 7-6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1240 &:= (-1 - ((2-3) \times (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1240 &:= (((-9+Q(8)) \times (7+6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1241 &:= (Q((-1 - (2 - (3+4)))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1241 &:= (-9 - ((8-7-6) \times (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1242 &:= (((-1+2)^3) + (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1242 &:= (-9 - (((8-Q(7)) \times Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1243 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2+3))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1243 &:= (Q((-9-8+Q(7))) - (6 - Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1244 &:= ((-1 + ((2+3) \times 4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1244 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8) + Q(7))) \times (6+5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
1245 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) + (4 + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1245 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + Q(6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1246 &:= (((-1-2) \times (Q(3) - Q(4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1246 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) - (Q((7 \times 6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1247 &:= (-1-2 + (Q(3) + (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1247 &:= (-9 + (Q(((8+7-6) + Q(5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1248 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1248 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times Q(7+6)) + (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1249 &:= (((-1-2+Q(3)) \times 4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1249 &:= (-9+8 + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1250 &:= (Q((-1 \times (2 - (3+4)))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1250 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (7 \times (Q(6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1251 &:= (-1+2 + (Q(3) + (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1251 &:= 9 \times (Q(8) + (7+6) \times 5+4+3+2+1) \\
1252 &:= (-1 - (((2-Q(3)) \times 4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1252 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) + (6 - (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1253 &:= (-1 + (Q(2+3) + (4 + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1253 &:= (-9+8-7 + (Q(6) + Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
1254 &:= (Q((-1+2 \times 3)) + (4 + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1254 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + (Q(6) + Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
1255 &:= (((-1+Q(2+Q(3)))/4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1255 &:= (Q((-9-8+Q(7))) + (6 + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1256 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2 \times 3))) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)) & 1256 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) + Q(7+6)) \times 5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1257 &:= (Q(Q((-1-2+Q(3)))) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)) & 1257 &:= (((-9 - (8+7)) + Q(Q(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1258 &:= (-1-2 + ((Q(3) \times 4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1258 &:= (-9-8 + ((Q(7) + Q(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1259 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(3) \times 4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1259 &:= (-9+8 - (7 \times (Q(6) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1260 &:= ((Q((-1+Q(2+3)))/Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) & 1260 &:= ((-9+8 + (Q(7) + Q(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1261 &:= ((Q((-1+Q(2+3)))/Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1261 &:= (-9+8 - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1262 &:= (-1+2 + ((Q(3) \times 4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1262 &:= ((-9+8) \times (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1263 &:= ((-1 - (2+3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1263 &:= (-9-8 + ((7+Q(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1264 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2 \times 3))) + 4+5+6+7+8+9) & 1264 &:= (Q(((9+Q(8)) - 7-6) - (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1265 &:= (-1 + (Q(2+3) + (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1265 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) - (Q(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1266 &:= (Q((-1+2 \times 3)) + (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1266 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) + (6 \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1267 &:= (-1+2-3 - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1267 &:= ((-9+Q(8)) - (7+6 - Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
1268 &:= (-1 + (((2+Q(3)) \times 4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1268 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times Q(7+6)) + (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1269 &:= ((Q(((9+2) \times 3)) \times (Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)) & 1269 &:= (Q(((9+Q(8)) - (7+6+5))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
1270 &:= (-1-2 + ((3 \times Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1270 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (7 - (6 \times Q(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1271 &:= (-1-2 + (Q(3+4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1271 &:= (((-9-8+7) + Q(Q(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1272 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3+4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1272 &:= ((-9+Q(Q(8-7) \times 6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1273 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9) & 1273 &:= ((-9+8-7+Q(Q(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1274 &:= (Q(((9+2) \times (3+4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1274 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + Q(Q(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1) \\
1275 &:= (-1+2 + (Q(3+4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1275 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) - (6+5+4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1276 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) + (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1277 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1278 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1279 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1280 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(3 + 4)) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1281 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1282 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q((2 + 3 + 4))))/5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1283 &:= (((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1284 &:= ((-1 + Q(2^3)) - (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1285 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1286 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times 4)) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1287 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1288 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1289 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1290 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1291 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1292 &:= (-1 + (Q(2^3) + (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1293 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) \times 4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1294 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) + (Q((4 \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1295 &:= (-1 + Q(((2 + 3) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1296 &:= Q(((((-1 + 2)^{Q(Q(3+4))}) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1297 &:= (-1 + 2 + Q(Q(((Q(3) \times (4 \times 5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1298 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(Q(3))) \times Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1299 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1300 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1301 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3)))/Q(4))) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1302 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1303 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1304 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1305 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + 3 + 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1306 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1307 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3^4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1308 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1309 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1310 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1311 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1312 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (Q(3^4)))/(Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1313 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 \times Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1314 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times Q(Q(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1315 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1276 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q((7 \times 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1277 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) + Q(Q(6))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1278 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) - ((Q(6) \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1279 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1280 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times Q(7)) - Q((Q(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1281 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1282 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (Q(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1283 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (Q(7 + 6) + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1284 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7) - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1285 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1286 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7) - (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1287 &:= (-9 + Q((8 + (7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1288 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1289 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7)))/Q(6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1290 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - ((7 + 6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1291 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) - (7 \times (6 + 5))) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1292 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 + 6) \times (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1293 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times Q(7 + 6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1294 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) + Q(Q(6))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1295 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1296 &:= Q((-9 \times (8 + 7 + 6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1297 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1298 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) \times (6 \times 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1299 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (((7 + 6) \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1300 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(7) - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1301 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1302 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1303 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1304 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1305 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1306 &:= (-9 - 8 - (7 \times (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1307 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1308 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times Q(7 + 6))) - (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1309 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1310 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) - (Q(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1311 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1312 &:= (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1313 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1314 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (Q(7 + 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1315 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (6 \times Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1316 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2 \times 3))) - (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1316 &:= (-9 + (Q(8 + 7) + ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1317 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) - (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1317 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1318 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1318 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6))) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1319 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1319 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + 6))) - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1320 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1320 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + (7 \times (6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1321 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times 4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1321 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7 + 6) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1322 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(3 + 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1322 &:= (-9 + 8 - (7 \times (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1323 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1323 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1324 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2 + 3) \times 4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1324 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1325 &:= (Q(((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1325 &:= (Q((((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) / (6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1326 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2 \times 3))) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1326 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1327 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1327 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1328 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1328 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times Q(7 + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1329 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1329 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1330 &:= 1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 1330 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((Q(7) + Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1331 &:= (Q((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) / Q(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1331 &:= (Q(((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6)) + (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1332 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1332 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + (7 + 6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1333 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1333 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(6 + Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1334 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1334 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) \times (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1335 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1335 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 + Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1336 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(3)) \times Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1336 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + ((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1337 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1337 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (Q(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1338 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + ((3 + 4) \times 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1338 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times Q(7 + 6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1339 &:= (Q((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - (4 - Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1339 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1340 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(((3 \times 4) + Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1340 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1341 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1341 &:= (9 \times 8 + Q(7)) \times (6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
1342 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q((2 + 3 + 4)))) / 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1342 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1343 &:= (-1 - (Q(2^3) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1343 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1344 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2^3) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1344 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7 + 6))) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1345 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1345 &:= ((-9 + Q(((8 - 7) + Q(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1346 &:= (Q(((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1346 &:= (Q(((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1347 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1347 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1348 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1348 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times Q(7 + 6))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1349 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + Q(3)) + (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1349 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1350 &:= ((Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + (4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1350 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) / 6) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1351 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3)))) \times Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1351 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (Q(7) + (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1352 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3+4}) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1352 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1353 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times Q((Q(4) + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1353 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(6 + Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1354 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1354 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7 + 6))) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1355 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) / (4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1355 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) - (Q(6) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$1356 := (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$1357 := (Q(-1+2+3) + (Q((Q(4)+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$1358 := (-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$1359 := (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$1360 := (-1 \times (Q(2+Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$1361 := (-1 + (Q(2+Q(3)) + (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$1362 := (-1 + (((2 + Q(Q(3))) \times Q(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$1363 := ((((-1+2) \times 3) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$1364 := ((Q(-1+2+3) \times (4+Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9))$$

$$1365 := ((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$1366 := (-1 - 2 + (Q((3 \times 4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$1367 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q((3 \times 4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$1368 := (-1 + Q(((2 \times 3) - (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))))))$$

$$1369 := Q((-1+2 - (3 - (4+5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$1370 := (-1+2 + (Q((3 \times 4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$1371 := ((-1-2) \times ((3 \times Q(Q(4))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$1372 := (-1-2 - ((Q(3) - 4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$1373 := ((-1 \times 2) - ((Q(3) - 4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$1374 := (-1 + ((2 - (3+4)) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$1375 := ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(3+4)))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$1376 := (Q((-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) + Q(4)))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$1377 := (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(3+4) + Q(Q(5)))) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$1378 := (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - 4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$1379 := (-1 + (((2 + Q(3+4)) - 5) \times (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$1380 := (((-1 + Q(2+3)) \times (4 \times 5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))$$

$$1381 := (((-1 + Q(Q(2+3))) / 4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$1382 := ((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$1383 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) \times (4 + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))))))$$

$$1384 := (Q(((-1 \times 2 + Q(3+4)) - Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9))$$

$$1385 := (((-1+2+Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$1386 := (-1 + ((2 \times (3^4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$1387 := (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$1388 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)))$$

$$1389 := (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(3+4) \times 5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$1390 := (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + (4 + Q(5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$1391 := (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(3) + 4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$1392 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(3) + 4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$1393 := (((-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + Q(Q(4)))) / 5) + 6+7+8+9)$$

$$1394 := (Q((-1 + (2 \times (3+4)))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$1395 := (-1+2 + (Q((Q(3) + 4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$1356 := ((-9+8+7) + (6 \times Q(5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$1357 := (((-9+8 \times 7) \times (6+Q(5))) - Q(4+3+2+1))$$

$$1358 := (-9 + ((8 \times Q(7+6)) + 5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$1359 := (-9+8 + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$1360 := (-9 + Q((Q(8) - ((7 \times 6) - (5+4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$1361 := (-9 + ((8 \times (Q(7) + Q(6+5))) + 4+3+2+1))$$

$$1362 := ((-9 \times 8 + Q((Q(7) - (6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$1363 := ((-9+8-7 + Q(Q(6))) - (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$1364 := (-9+8 + ((7+6) \times (5+Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$1365 := (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) - (Q(6) - (5+Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$1366 := (-9 + (((Q(8) - 7 - 6) \times Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$1367 := (-9 - (8 \times (Q(7) - (Q(6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$1368 := (-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + (6+5+Q(4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$1369 := Q((Q((-9+8+7)) + (6+5 - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$1370 := ((-9 - (Q(8) - (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) \times (4+3+2+1))$$

$$1371 := (-9 + (((8 \times 7) + Q(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$1372 := ((-9+8) \times (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$1373 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 + (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$1374 := ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7+6))) + (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$1375 := (Q((-9+Q((8-7+6)))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$1376 := ((Q((-9+8+7)) \times (Q(6)+5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))$$

$$1377 := (((-9-8+Q(7)) \times Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$1378 := ((-9+Q(8)) - (7 \times (Q(6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$1379 := (Q(((-9 + Q(8)) - (7+6+5))) + 4+3+2+1)$$

$$1380 := (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + (Q(6) - Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$1381 := (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q((Q(7) - (6+5))) + 4+3+2+1)))$$

$$1382 := (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + (6 \times Q(5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$1383 := (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7+6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$1384 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - Q(6+5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$1385 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$1386 := (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$1387 := (-9 + (Q(8+7) + (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$1388 := (((-9+8+Q(7)) \times (6+Q(5))) - Q(4+3+2+1))$$

$$1389 := (((-9 - Q(8)) \times 7) - ((6 - Q(5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$1390 := ((Q((-9 + (8+7+6))) - 5) \times (4+3+2+1))$$

$$1391 := (Q(((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6)) - (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$1392 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8-7) \times 6) + (5+Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$1393 := (-9+8 + (Q(7+6) + Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1))))$$

$$1394 := ((-9-8) \times ((7+6+5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$1395 := (-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(7+6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1396 &:= (-1 - ((2^{3+4}) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
1397 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1398 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1399 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+Q(3)) - Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1400 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+Q(3)) - Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1401 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1402 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1403 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1404 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(3))) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1405 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2+3) + Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
1406 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + (Q(4+5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
1407 &:= (Q(Q((-1-2+Q(3)))) + (Q(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
1408 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times (3 + Q(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1409 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2+3))) \times 4) + (5 - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
1410 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (Q(3+4) - Q(5)))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
1411 &:= (-1 + ((2^{Q(Q(3))/(4+5)}) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
1412 &:= (((-1+2+Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4)))/5) + Q(6+7+8+9) \\
1413 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times (Q((Q(4)+5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
1414 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times (3+4))) + Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9) \\
1415 &:= ((Q((Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) + 4))/5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
1416 &:= (-1 - (Q(2^3) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1417 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2^3) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1418 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1419 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3)))) \times (4+5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
1420 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times (3+4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1421 &:= (Q((-1+2-3) + Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1422 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) + (Q((Q(4)+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
1423 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\
1424 &:= (-1 - ((Q(2+3) \times (4 - Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
1425 &:= (-1 \times ((Q(2+3) \times (4 - Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
1426 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q(3+4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
1427 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q((3 \times (4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
1428 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2 \times (3-4)) + Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
1429 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times (3 + (4+5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
1430 &:= (((-1 + (Q(2+3) + Q(Q(4)))) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9) \\
1431 &:= (-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + ((4 \times 5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
1432 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1433 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - (4 - Q(Q(5)))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
1434 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2+3) + Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1435 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1396 &:= (Q(((-9 + 8 \times 7) - (6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1397 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1398 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1399 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1400 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1401 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7 + Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1402 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1403 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (Q(7 + 6) - 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1404 &:= (-9 \times ((Q(8) \times (7 - 6 - 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1405 &:= ((-9 + Q(8 + 7)) - (Q(6) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1406 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1407 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1408 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 \times (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1409 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1410 &:= (Q((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1411 &:= 9 + 8 + Q(7 + 6) + Q(Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1412 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1413 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((7 \times 6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1414 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1415 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1416 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times (Q(6) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1417 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) - (6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1418 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1419 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1420 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 + 6) \times (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1421 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1422 &:= (-9 \times (((8 \times 7) + Q(6)) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1423 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((Q(7 + 6) - Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1424 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + Q((7 - (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
1425 &:= 9 + 8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1426 &:= (-9 + (Q(8 + 7) + (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1427 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1428 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))/5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1429 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1430 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(7 + 6)) - Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1431 &:= 9 \times 7 \times Q(8) - Q(Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1432 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(Q(7)) - ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1433 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q((Q(7) - (6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1434 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7 + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1435 &:= ((-9 + Q(8 + 7)) - (6 - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1436 &:= (Q(Q((-1-2+Q(3)))) + (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))) & 1436 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) + (6 \times Q(5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1437 &:= (-1-2-(Q(Q(3))-Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 1437 &:= (-9+Q(Q(8))-(Q(7)+Q((Q(6)+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1438 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) - Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 1438 &:= ((-9+(8 \times Q(7+6))) - (5-Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1439 &:= (-1+(2 \times ((Q(3+4)-Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 1439 &:= (-9+8+((Q(7+6)-Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1440 &:= (((Q(Q(-1+2+3))-Q(4))/5) \times (6+7+8+9)) & 1440 &:= ((-9-(Q(8)-Q(7+6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1441 &:= (-1+2-(Q(Q(3))-Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 1441 &:= (-9+(Q((Q(8)+(7-Q(6))))+Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1442 &:= (-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(3) + (4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 1442 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1443 &:= (-1 + Q((2 - (3 - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 1443 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (Q(7+6) + Q(5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
1444 &:= Q((-1 - ((2-3) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1444 &:= Q((-9 + ((8 \times 7) + (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1445 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 \times 3) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1445 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - Q(7+6))) + (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1446 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2 \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))) & 1446 &:= (((-9 \times (8+7)) + Q((Q(6)+5))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
1447 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2+3))) - ((4+Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1447 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (Q(7) - (6+Q(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1448 &:= ((-1+Q((2 \times (3+Q(4)))) - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))) & 1448 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + Q(6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1449 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2-3) + Q(4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1449 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - Q(((7-6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1450 &:= (Q((-1 - ((2-3) \times Q(4)))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1450 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + Q(6)) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
1451 &:= ((Q((-1-2+Q(3))) \times Q(4)) - (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1451 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (Q(7) + Q(6+5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1452 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q((Q(3) + 4)) + (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1452 &:= (-9 - (((8 - Q(7)) \times Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1453 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) \times 4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1453 &:= (-9+8+(Q((Q(7)-(6+5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
1454 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9))) & 1454 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (6 \times Q(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1455 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+3) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1455 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q(7+6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1456 &:= (-1 - (Q(2^3) - Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 1456 &:= (Q((-9+8+7 \times 6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1457 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2^3) - Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 1457 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) + (Q(6) + (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1458 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(4) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) & 1458 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - (7-6+Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1459 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(3+4))) - (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 1459 &:= (Q((-9-8+(Q(7)+6))) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
1460 &:= (-1 \times ((Q(2 \times 3) + Q(Q(4))) \times (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 1460 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (7 \times (6 - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1461 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(3+4))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)) & 1461 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (7 \times (6 - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1462 &:= (-1 - (2 \times Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1462 &:= (-9 + (Q(8+7) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1463 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1463 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7+6) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1464 &:= (-1 - (Q(2^3) - (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))))) & 1464 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7+6))) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
1465 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) - (Q(4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1465 &:= (Q((-9-8+Q(7))) + Q(6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1466 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(3)) \times Q(4+5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1466 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q((7 \times 6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1467 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2+3))) - (4+5 - Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1467 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q((7 \times 6))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1468 &:= ((-1+2-3) \times (Q(4) - (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 1468 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + Q(6+5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
1469 &:= (-1-2-(Q(3)-(Q(Q(4))+Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1469 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8)) - (7+6+5))) + Q(4+3+2+1) \\
1470 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1470 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + (7 + Q(6)))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1471 &:= (-1+2+(Q(((3 \times 4) - 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 1471 &:= (-9+8-(Q(7)-(Q(Q(6))+Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1472 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1472 &:= ((-9+8) \times (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1473 &:= (-1+2-(Q(3)-(Q(Q(4))+Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1473 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7 - (6 \times 5))) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1474 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1474 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (7 \times (Q(6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1475 &:= ((-1 - (2+3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1475 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (Q(6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1476 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1476 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - (7 + (Q(6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1477 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) - (4 - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1477 &:= (-9 + (Q(8+7) + (Q(6) + Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
1478 &:= ((-1 + Q((Q(2 \times 3) + Q(4)))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1478 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 \times (Q(6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1479 &:= ((-1+2-3) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1479 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 + Q((Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1480 &:= (-1 - ((2-3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1480 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1481 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - (2 - (3+4)))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1481 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q((Q(7) - (6+5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1482 &:= (((-1+2)^3) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1482 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + 7) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1483 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2+3))) - (Q(4) + (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1483 &:= (-9 + (8 \times Q(7) + ((6+5) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1484 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) - Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 1484 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7+6))) + (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
1485 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 \times 3) - Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 1485 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) - (Q(6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1486 &:= (Q(((-1 + Q(Q(2+3))) / Q(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 1486 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q((7 \times 6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1487 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1487 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 - (Q(6) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1488 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1488 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times (Q(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1489 &:= (((-1 - (2+3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + Q(Q(5)+6+7+8+9)) & 1489 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q((Q(7) - (6+5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1490 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1490 &:= ((Q((-9 + (8+7+6))) + 5) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
1491 &:= (-1+2 + (Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1491 &:= (-9 + ((8+7) \times Q(((6-5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1492 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - ((4+5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1492 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times (6 - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1493 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3+4))) - (5 + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1493 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - Q((Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1494 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3)) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)) & 1494 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (Q(7+6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1495 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+3) - Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 1495 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((Q(7+6) - Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1496 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+3) - Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 1496 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1497 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1497 &:= ((-9 - (8+7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1498 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1498 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1499 &:= ((-1 + ((2+3)^4)) - (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1499 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7+6))) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1500 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times Q(Q(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 1500 &:= ((-9 + (8+7+6)) \times (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1501 &:= (((-1 - 2 + Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 1501 &:= (-9 - ((8 + (Q(7) \times 6)) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1502 &:= (-1 - (2 \times Q(3) - Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 1502 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) \times (Q(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1503 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)) & 1503 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1504 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3+4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1504 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7+6) - 5))) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
1505 &:= (-1 + (Q(2+3) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1505 &:= (Q((-9 + Q((8-7+6)))) + (5 - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1506 &:= (Q((-1+2 \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1506 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) + (6 \times (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1507 &:= (-1+2 + (Q(Q(3+4)) + (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1507 &:= (-9 + (Q(8+7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1508 &:= (-1 + ((2-3) \times (Q(4) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1508 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1509 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) - Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 1509 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q((Q(7) - (6+5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1510 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) - Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 1510 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times 7) + (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1511 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q((3+(4+5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1511 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1512 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)) & 1512 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7) \times (Q(6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1513 &:= (-1+2 - (Q(3) - Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 1513 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1514 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)) & 1514 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1515 &:= ((-1 - (2+3)) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)) & 1515 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) - (6 - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1516 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)) & 1516 &:= (-9-8-(7 \times (6-Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1517 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1517 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) + (Q(6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1518 &:= (Q((-1+(2 \times Q(3)))) + (4+Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1518 &:= (-9+8+(Q(7) \times (Q(6) + (5-(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1519 &:= ((-1+2-3) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)) & 1519 &:= (Q((-9-8+(Q(7)+6))) - (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1520 &:= (-1 - ((2-3) \times Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 1520 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - Q(((7+6) \times 5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1521 &:= Q((-1 - (2 - (3+4+5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1521 &:= Q((-9-8 - (Q(7+6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1522 &:= (((-1+2)^3) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)) & 1522 &:= ((-9-8+Q((7 \times 6))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1523 &:= (-1-2+(Q(Q(3+4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1523 &:= ((-9-8+Q(Q(7))) - (Q(6+Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1524 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)) & 1524 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7+6))) - (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1525 &:= ((-1+2+3) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)) & 1525 &:= (Q((-9 \times (8-7-6))) - (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1526 &:= ((-1+2 \times 3) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)) & 1526 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times Q(Q(6))) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1527 &:= (-1-2+(Q(3) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 1527 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) + (6+Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1528 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 1528 &:= (-9 \times 8 + Q((Q(7) + (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1529 &:= ((-1 - (2 - (3+4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1529 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1530 &:= (Q(((-1+2) \times 3)) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)) & 1530 &:= (-9-8+(7 \times (Q(6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1531 &:= (-1+2+(Q(3) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 1531 &:= (-9+8-(Q(7) - (Q((Q(6)+5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1532 &:= ((-1+Q((2 \times Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1532 &:= (-9+8-(7 \times (6-Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1533 &:= (-1+(Q(Q(2+3)) + ((4+5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1533 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) \times (6-Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1534 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2 \times 3))) + ((4+5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1534 &:= (-9-8-(Q(7) - Q(((6 \times 5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
1535 &:= (((-1+(2^{3+4})) \times 5) + Q(6+7+8+9)) & 1535 &:= (-9+(Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) - Q((Q(6)+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1536 &:= (-1-2-(Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1536 &:= ((-9+8+7) \times (6+(Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1537 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)) & 1537 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times ((7-6) - Q(5))) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1538 &:= (-1+(2 \times Q(3) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 1538 &:= ((-9+8+Q((7 \times 6))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1539 &:= (-1 + ((2+Q(3)) \times (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1539 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8)) - 7-6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1540 &:= (-1+2-(Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1540 &:= ((-9+Q(8)) \times (7+6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1541 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times 4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1541 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(((5+4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
1542 &:= (((-1+2)^3) + (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1542 &:= (-9 - (((8-Q(7)) \times Q(6)) + (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1543 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3) - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1543 &:= (-9+8+(Q((Q(7) - (6+5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1544 &:= ((-1+Q((2 \times Q(3)))) - (4 - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1544 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (7 \times (6+Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1545 &:= (-1+(Q(2+3) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 1545 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (6+Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1546 &:= (Q((-1+2 \times 3)) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)) & 1546 &:= (-9+8+(7 \times (Q(6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1547 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times 4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1547 &:= (-9 - (Q(8+7) - (Q((Q(6)+5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1548 &:= (-1 + ((Q(Q(2 \times 3))/4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1548 &:= 9-8+7 \times (Q(6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
1549 &:= ((Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) \times 4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1549 &:= (Q((-9-8+(Q(7)+6))) + (5+Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1550 &:= (-1+2+((Q(Q(3)) \times 4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1550 &:= (((-9+Q(8+7)) - (Q(6)+Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
1551 &:= (Q(((-1+Q(2+Q(3))) - Q(4+5))) + 6+7+8+9) & 1551 &:= 9 \times 8 \times (7+6) + Q(Q(5)) - 4-3-2-1 \\
1552 &:= (-1+(Q((2 \times Q(3))) + (4+Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1552 &:= (-9+Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7+6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1553 &:= (((-1+2+Q(Q(3))) \times 4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1553 &:= (-9-8+(Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1554 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(3+4))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)) & 1554 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7+6))) + (5+Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1555 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2+3)) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1555 &:= (-9+Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1556 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) + Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1557 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1558 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (Q((Q(4) - 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1559 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1560 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1561 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3)))/Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1562 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1563 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1564 &:= ((-1 + Q((Q(2 \times 3) + 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1565 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1566 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1567 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q((Q(3) - (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1568 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1569 &:= ((-1 + Q((Q(2 + Q(3)) - Q(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1570 &:= (Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) + Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1571 &:= (((-1 - 2 + Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1572 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3 + 4) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1573 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1574 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1575 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (3 \times Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1576 &:= (-1 - ((2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1577 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1578 &:= (Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) + (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1579 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q((4 + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1580 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1581 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1582 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1583 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3 + Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1584 &:= (-1 + (Q(2^3) + Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1585 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times Q(Q(4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1586 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times 4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1587 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3 + Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1588 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1589 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1590 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1591 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times 4) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1592 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1593 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1594 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 \times 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1595 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3 + 4))) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1556 &:= ((-9 \times (Q((8 + 7 + 6)) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1557 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1558 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + Q(6 + 5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1559 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 - (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1560 &:= (((Q((-9 + Q(8))) - Q(Q(7)))/6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1561 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) - ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1562 &:= (-9 + (Q(8 + 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1563 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7 - (6 \times 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1564 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1565 &:= (((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) \times 6)) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1566 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - ((7 + 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1567 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((Q(7 + 6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1568 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times Q(7 + 6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1569 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1570 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1571 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q((Q(7) - (6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1572 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q((8 - 7) \times 6) + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1573 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 + Q((Q(6) + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1574 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 + 6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1575 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + 7 \times 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1576 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1577 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q((Q(7) + (6 - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1578 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1579 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) + (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1580 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - Q(7 + 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1581 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + 7 \times 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1582 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (Q(6) + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1583 &:= (-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1584 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (Q(7 + 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1585 &:= (Q((-9 + Q((8 - 7 + 6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1586 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7 \times 6)) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1587 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - Q((Q(7) + (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1588 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - (7 \times (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1589 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1590 &:= (Q(((9 - 8 - 7 - 6) - 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1591 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (Q(Q(7)) - Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1592 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1593 &:= (-9 + (8 \times Q(7) + (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1594 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1595 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1596 &:= ((-1 - 2 - Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1597 &:= (-1 - 2 + Q((Q(3) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1598 &:= (-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(3) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1599 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1600 &:= Q((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1601 &:= (-1 + 2 + Q((Q(3) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1602 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1603 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1604 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) + (4 \times Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1605 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times Q(Q(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1606 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 \times 3))) + (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1607 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3^4) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1608 &:= ((-1 - 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1609 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1610 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(3 + 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1611 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1612 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times Q((Q(4) + (5 + 6)))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1613 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + Q(4)))) - ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1614 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(3 + 4))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1615 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (Q(Q(3)) \times 4)) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1616 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1617 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q(3 + 4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1618 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(3 + 4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1619 &:= 1 - 2 + (Q(3 + 4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1620 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(3)) \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1621 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1622 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(3 + 4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1623 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times Q((4 + Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1624 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2 + 3) \times 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1625 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + 3) + Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1626 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((3 \times (4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1627 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((3 \times (4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1628 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2 \times 3) - 4 - 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1629 &:= (Q((-1 + 2) \times (3 \times (4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1630 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((3 \times (4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1631 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 + Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1632 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((3 + Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1633 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1634 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2 \times 3) + 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1635 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + Q(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1596 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1597 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1598 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7 + Q(6))) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1599 &:= (-9 + 8 + Q((Q(7) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1600 &:= Q((-9 - ((8 \times Q(7)) - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1601 &:= ((-9 + (Q(((8 + 7) \times 6)/5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1602 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 \times (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1603 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6)) - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1604 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1605 &:= (Q((-9 + Q((8 - 7 + 6)))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1606 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 \times 7))) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1607 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(7 + Q(6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1608 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 + 6) \times (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1609 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7)))/6) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1610 &:= (Q((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) - 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1611 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (Q(7) + Q(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1612 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) - Q(((7 - 6) \times 5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1613 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1614 &:= (-9 + (8 \times Q(7) + (6 + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1615 &:= (Q((-9 + Q((8 - 7 + 6)))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1616 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1617 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + (Q((Q(6) + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1618 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) \times (6 + Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1619 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + (6 \times Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1620 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(7 + 6) - (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1621 &:= (-9 + ((Q(((8 + 7) \times 6)/5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1622 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7 - Q(6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1623 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7 + Q(6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1624 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1625 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1626 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1627 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((Q(7) + Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1628 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((Q(7) + Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1629 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1630 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(7 + 6)) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1631 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7 + 6) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1632 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) \times (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1633 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6)) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1634 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (6 \times (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1635 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1636 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - ((4-5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
1637 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((Q(Q(Q(3)))/Q(4+5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
1638 &:= ((-1+2-3) \times (Q(4+5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
1639 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + ((4-5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
1640 &:= ((-1+2-3) \times ((Q(4) \times 5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
1641 &:= (-1 + (Q(2+Q(3)) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1642 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1643 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 - (Q(4+5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
1644 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q(3+4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1645 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(3+4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1646 &:= ((Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3))))/4) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1647 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times (4 \times 5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
1648 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3+4))) - (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1649 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2^3) - 4 - 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1650 &:= ((-1 - (Q(2+3) - Q(4+5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
1651 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2) \times (3+4))) - (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1652 &:= ((-1+2+Q(Q(3+4))) - (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1653 &:= ((-1-2) \times (Q(3) - (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1654 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + Q((Q(4) + Q(5)))) - (6+7+8+9) \\
1655 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - ((4+5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
1656 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - ((4+5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
1657 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q((4+Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
1658 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1659 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1660 &:= (((Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 5) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
1661 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) - (4 \times Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1662 &:= ((-1+2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1663 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times Q(Q(4))) - (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
1664 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times (Q(4) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
1665 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2+3) + Q(4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1666 &:= (Q((-1-2) \times (Q(3) - Q(4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1667 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
1668 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((Q(Q(3)) \times (4 - Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
1669 &:= (Q((Q(-1+2+3) - 4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
1670 &:= (((-1+2+Q(Q(3))) \times (4 \times 5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\
1671 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3 - (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1672 &:= (-1+2 - ((Q(Q(3)) \times (4 - Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
1673 &:= (-1+2 - (Q(3) - Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
1674 &:= (-1+2 + ((3 \times Q(Q(4))) + (5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
1675 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(3+4)))) - (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
1636 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1637 &:= (-9 + (Q(8+7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1638 &:= ((-9+8+Q((7 \times 6))) - (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1639 &:= (-9+8+((Q(7+6) - 5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1640 &:= (((-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + 7+6))/Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
1641 &:= 9+8+Q(7+Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1) \\
1642 &:= ((-9+8) \times (Q(7) - (Q((Q(6)+5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1643 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (Q(7+6) + Q(5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1644 &:= (-9 - ((8 + Q(7)) \times (6 - (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
1645 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1646 &:= ((-9 \times (Q((8+7+6)) - Q(Q(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1647 &:= (((-9 - (8+7)) + Q((Q(6)+5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1648 &:= (-9+8+(Q(7)+Q(((6 \times 5)+4+3+2+1))) \\
1649 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times 7) + (Q(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1650 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1651 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (Q(7+6) + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1652 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times ((7-6) - Q(5))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
1653 &:= (((-9+8+Q(7)) \times Q(6)) + (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1654 &:= (Q((-9-8+Q(7))) + (6 \times (5 + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1655 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + Q((Q(7) + (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1656 &:= (-9 + ((8+7) \times (6+5+Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1657 &:= (-9 + (Q((8+7+6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
1658 &:= ((-9+8+Q((7 \times 6))) - (5+Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1659 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7+6)) - Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1660 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) - ((7+6) \times (5+Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1661 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1662 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q((8-7) \times 6) + 5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1663 &:= ((-9+8-7+Q((Q(6)+5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1664 &:= (-9 + (8 \times Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1665 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + 6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1666 &:= (Q((-9+8+7 \times 6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1667 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((Q(7+6) + 5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1668 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) - (7 + (6 \times Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1669 &:= (Q((-9-8+(Q(7)+6))) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1670 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((7+6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1671 &:= (Q((-9 - (Q(8) + (7 - Q(6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1672 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 \times (6 + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1673 &:= (-9+8-7+Q((Q(6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1674 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7+6))) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1675 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) + (6 - (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

1676 := $((-1 \times (2+3)) + Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))))$
1677 := $(-1 - 2 + (3 \times (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))))$
1678 := $(-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))))$
1679 := $(-1 + ((Q(2^3) - Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$
1680 := $(((-1+2) \times 3) \times (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$
1681 := $Q(((-1 + Q(2+3)) / 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$
1682 := $(-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)))$
1683 := $((((-1+2) \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4) + 5))) + Q(6+7+8+9))$
1684 := $(Q((-1+2+(3 \times (4+5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9))$
1685 := $((-1+2+3) + Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))))$
1686 := $(-1 \times (Q(2+3) - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9)))$
1687 := $(((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) / 4) - (5+6+7+8+9)$
1688 := $(-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))))))$
1689 := $(Q((-1 + (Q(2+3) + 4))) + (5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))$
1690 := $(Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))))$
1691 := $(-1 - (2 \times (Q(3+4) + (5 - Q(6+7+8+9))))$
1692 := $((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3+4) + (5 - Q(6+7+8+9))))$
1693 := $((((-1+2) \times 3) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$
1694 := $(Q((-1 + (2 \times (3+4)))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$
1695 := $((-1 + Q((2 + Q(3+4)))) - (5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))$
1696 := $(Q(-1+2+3) \times (Q(Q(4) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))))$
1697 := $(Q(-1+2+3) + Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))))$
1698 := $(-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) \times (4+5 - (6+7+8+9))))$
1699 := $((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) \times (4+5 - (6+7+8+9))))$
1700 := $((Q(-1+2+3) + Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)$
1701 := $((Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) \times (4+5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))$
1702 := $(-1+2 - (Q(Q(3)) \times (4+5 - (6+7+8+9))))$
1703 := $(-1+2 - (Q(3) - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9)))$
1704 := $((-1 + Q(2+3)) \times (Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))$
1705 := $(((-1 + Q(2 + Q(3))) \times 4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))$
1706 := $((-1 \times (2+3)) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9))$
1707 := $(Q((-1 + Q(2+3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9))))$
1708 := $(-1 + (Q(((2 \times 3) + Q(4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))$
1709 := $(Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + Q(4)))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))$
1710 := $(((-1+2+Q(3)) \times Q(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))$
1711 := $(Q((Q((-1 - (2 - (3+4)))) + Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9)$
1712 := $(-1 - 2 + (Q(3+4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$
1713 := $(-1 \times 2 + (Q(3+4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$
1714 := $(-1 + (Q(((2 + Q(3)) - 4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$
1715 := $(Q(((-1 + 2) \times (3+4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))$

1676 := $(-9 - (Q(8) - (Q((7 \times 6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))))$
1677 := $(-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))))$
1678 := $(((-9+8+Q(7)) \times Q(6)) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))$
1679 := $(-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7+Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))))$
1680 := $((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1))$
1681 := $Q((-9 + (Q(8) + (7 - (6+5+4+3+2+1))))$
1682 := $(Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 - (6 \times Q(5+4+3+2+1))))$
1683 := $9 + (Q(Q(8)) - Q(Q(7)) - (6+5+4+3+2+1))$
1684 := $((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7+6) + Q(5)))) + 4+3+2+1)$
1685 := $(-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (6+5 - (4+3+2+1))))$
1686 := $(-9 + Q(Q(8)) - Q(Q((7 \times (6+5 - (4+3+2+1))))))$
1687 := $(-9 - (8 \times (7+6 - Q(5+4+3+2+1))))$
1688 := $(-9+8 + (Q((7 \times 6)) + (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1))))$
1689 := $(Q((-9 + Q(8)) - 7 - 6) + (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))$
1690 := $((-9+8 + (Q(7) + Q(6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1))$
1691 := $(Q((-9 - (Q(8) + (7 - Q(6+5)))) + 4+3+2+1)$
1692 := $(-9 \times (((8-7) + Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))$
1693 := $(((-9+8+Q(7)) \times Q(6)) - (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1))$
1694 := $(-9 + (8 \times Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)))$
1695 := $(-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))))$
1696 := $(Q((-9+8+7 \times 6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)$
1697 := $((-9+8+7) + (Q((Q(6) + 5)) + 4+3+2+1))$
1698 := $(-9+8 - (Q(Q(7)) - ((Q(6) + 5) \times Q(4+3+2+1))))$
1699 := $(-9+8 + ((Q(7) + Q(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))$
1700 := $((-9 + (8+7+6+5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1))$
1701 := $(-9 \times (Q((8-7) \times 6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))$
1702 := $(Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times (Q(6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))))$
1703 := $(-9 - (8 \times (7 - (Q(6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1))))$
1704 := $((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - Q((6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1))))))$
1705 := $((Q((-9+8 \times (7+6))) / 5) - Q(4+3+2+1))$
1706 := $(-9 - (Q(8) - (Q((7 \times 6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)))$
1707 := $(-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - (6+5+4+3+2+1)))$
1708 := $(((-9+8) \times 7) \times (6 - (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1))))$
1709 := $((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + (6 \times Q(5)))) - (4+3+2+1))$
1710 := $(-9 \times (Q(8) + (7 - (Q(6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))))$
1711 := $(-9 + (((8 + Q(7+6)) - 5) \times (4+3+2+1)))$
1712 := $((-9+8 - 7) \times (Q(6) - (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1))))$
1713 := $(((-9+8+Q(7)) \times Q(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))$
1714 := $((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6+5+Q(4+3+2+1))))$
1715 := $((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))))$

$$\begin{aligned}
1716 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3 + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1717 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1718 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (Q(3) - Q(Q(4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1719 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) - Q(Q(4)))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1720 &:= ((-1 + 2^{Q(3)}) - (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1721 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2 - 3) + Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1722 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1723 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + (Q((4 + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1724 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1725 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(3 + 4))) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1726 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) + (Q((4 \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1727 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3 + Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1728 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3 + Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1729 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 + 4) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1730 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - Q(Q(4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1731 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - Q(Q(4)))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1732 &:= ((-1 + 2^{Q(3)}) - (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1733 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - (Q((4 + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1734 &:= (Q(((-1 \times 2 + Q(3 + 4) - 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1735 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (((3 + 4) + Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1736 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (((3 + 4) + Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1737 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1738 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (Q(4) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1739 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (Q((4 + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1740 &:= (-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1741 &:= (Q(((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1742 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 + Q(Q(4)))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1743 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - Q(Q(3))) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1744 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3 + 4))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1745 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1746 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1747 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3 + 4))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1748 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + (Q((4 + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1749 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3 \times Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1750 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(3 + 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1751 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3 + 4) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1752 &:= (-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1753 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 + (4 \times 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1754 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4)))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1755 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1716 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(6) + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1717 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + Q((Q(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1718 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) - (6 - 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1719 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) \times ((7 \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1720 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times 7) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1721 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 - (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1722 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7 - Q(6))) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1723 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((Q(7 + 6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1724 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1725 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1726 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 - 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1727 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 + 6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1728 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - Q((7 - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1729 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - Q(Q((7 - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1730 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (Q(7 + 6) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1731 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7 \times 6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1732 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q((7 \times 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1733 &:= (-9 + (8 \times Q(7) + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1734 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (6 \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1735 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1736 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1737 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1738 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) - (6 - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1739 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7 + 6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1740 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times 7) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1741 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1742 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q((7 \times 6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1743 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1744 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(((6 \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1745 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 + Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1746 &:= (-9 \times (Q((8 + 7 + 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1747 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1748 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q((7 \times 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1749 &:= (Q(((-9 + Q(8)) - 7 - 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1750 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1751 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1752 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1753 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7 + Q(6)) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1754 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (7 \times (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1755 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1756 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1757 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1758 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3 + 4) - Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1759 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
1760 &:= ((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + Q(4)) \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1761 &:= (-1 - 2 + Q((3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1762 &:= (-1 \times 2 + Q((3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1763 &:= (-1 + Q(((2 + Q(3)) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1764 &:= Q(((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1765 &:= (-1 + 2 + Q((3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1766 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1767 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1768 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q((3 - (4 - 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1769 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1770 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1771 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + ((4 - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1772 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1773 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1774 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1775 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1776 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1777 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1778 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (Q(4) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1779 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1780 &:= (((-1 + 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(4)))) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1781 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((Q(Q(3)) / (4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1782 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1783 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3) + ((4 - 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1784 &:= (-1 + ((2 + Q(3 + 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1785 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) - (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1786 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (((3 \times 4) - 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1787 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 - 4 - 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1788 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - 4) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1789 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3 - 4) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1790 &:= (-1 + (((2 + Q(3)) \times Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1791 &:= ((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times (Q(4) - 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1792 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1793 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1794 &:= (Q(((-1 \times 2 + Q(3 + 4)) - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1795 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (((3 + 4) - 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1756 &:= ((-9 \times (Q((8 + 7 + 6)) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1757 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (Q((Q(6) + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1758 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q((7 \times 6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1759 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8)) - 7 - 6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1760 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) - (Q(6) - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1761 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7 + Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1762 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q((7 \times 6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1763 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1764 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1765 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) + Q((6 \times 5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1766 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) + (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1767 &:= (((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1768 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1769 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8)) - 7 - 6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1770 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (Q(7 + 6) + Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1771 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) - (7 - Q(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1772 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1773 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + (Q((Q(6) + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1774 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1775 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1776 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1777 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 \times 7))) - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1778 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q((7 \times 6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1779 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8)) - 7 - 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1780 &:= (Q((-9 \times 8 + 7 + 6) + Q(5 + 4)) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1781 &:= (Q((-9 - (Q(8) + (7 - Q(6 + 5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1782 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times Q(6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1783 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) \times (7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1784 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1785 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) - (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1786 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7 \times 6)) + (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1787 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 + 6) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1788 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1789 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1790 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 + 6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1791 &:= (-9 + (8 \times Q(((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1792 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7 + Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1793 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1794 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1795 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6))) / 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1796 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (((3+4) - 5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
1797 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2+3))) - (4 - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1798 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((Q(Q(Q(3)))/Q(Q(4+5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
1799 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q((Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1800 &:= ((-1-2) \times (Q((Q(3)+Q(4))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1801 &:= ((Q((-1-2+Q(3))) \times Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1802 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((Q(Q(3)) \times 4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1803 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3+4) - 5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
1804 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1805 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2+3))) + (4+Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1806 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2) \times (3+4))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
1807 &:= ((-1+2+Q(Q(3+4))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
1808 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2 \times 3) + Q(4))) + (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
1809 &:= (Q(((-1+2) \times 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
1810 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1811 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3-4-5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
1812 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((3-4-5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
1813 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3 \times 4) - 5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
1814 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2+Q(3)) \times 4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1815 &:= (((-1 \times (2+3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
1816 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1817 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2+3))) + (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1818 &:= ((-1-2) \times (Q(3+4) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
1819 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2 \times 3) + Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1820 &:= ((Q((-1-2+Q(3))) + Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1821 &:= ((-1-2) \times ((3 \times Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
1822 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) + (Q((4+Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
1823 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3+(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
1824 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1825 &:= (((-1+2+(Q(3) \times 4)) \times Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
1826 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1827 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
1828 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) - (4 \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1829 &:= (Q((Q((-1-2+Q(3))) + Q(4))) + (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
1830 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2+3) + Q(4))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1831 &:= ((Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3))))/4) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1832 &:= (-1-2 + ((Q(3+Q(4)) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
1833 &:= ((-1+Q(Q(2+3))) - (Q(4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1834 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2 \times 3))) - (Q(4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1835 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) \times (Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1796 &:= ((-9 + ((8+7) \times Q(6+5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1797 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - (6+5+Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1798 &:= ((-9+8+Q(7+Q(6))) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1799 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7-6+Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1800 &:= (Q((-9 \times (8-7-6))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1801 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + (7 \times Q(6+5)))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1802 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (((7+6) \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1803 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (((7+6) \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1804 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1805 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1806 &:= ((-9+8+7) + (Q(6) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1807 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + 7+6)) + Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1808 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) - (7 + (Q(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1809 &:= (-9 \times (Q((8-7+6)) - (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1810 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (Q(6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1811 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (Q(7+6) + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1812 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8-7) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1813 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (7+6 - Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
1814 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 \times (6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1815 &:= (Q(((-9+8 \times 7) - Q(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1816 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1817 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(7+Q(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1818 &:= ((-9 + ((8+Q(7)) \times Q(6))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1819 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7+6) \times 5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1820 &:= (((Q((-9+8+Q(7)))/6) \times 5) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
1821 &:= (Q(((-9+8+7) \times 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1822 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (7 - (Q(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1823 &:= (((-9+8+Q(7)) \times Q(6)) - (5 - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1824 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1825 &:= (Q((-9+Q((8-7+6)))) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1826 &:= (-9+8+(7 \times (Q(6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1827 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - ((7 \times 6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1828 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) - (6-5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1829 &:= ((-9+8+Q(Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1830 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + (7+Q(6+5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
1831 &:= (-9 - ((Q((8+7+6)) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1832 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7 - Q(6))) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1833 &:= ((-9+8+Q(7+Q(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1834 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1835 &:= ((-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) \times 6))) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1836 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(3))) \times (Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9)) & 1836 &:= (-9 \times ((8+7+6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1837 &:= (((-1-2+Q(Q(3))) \times 4) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1837 &:= ((-9-8+Q(7+Q(6))) - (5-(4+3+2+1))) \\
1838 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - ((4 \times Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1838 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7-Q(6+5))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
1839 &:= (Q((-1-2+(Q(3) \times 4))) + (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 1839 &:= (Q((-9-8+(Q(7)+(6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1840 &:= (((-1+2+Q(3+Q(4))) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9) & 1840 &:= (-9+Q(((8-(7+6) \times 5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1841 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2+Q(3))) - (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) & 1841 &:= ((-9+Q(((8+7) \times 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1842 &:= ((-1+2-3) \times (4 - (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1842 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7-Q(6))) - (5-(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1843 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + Q((4 - (5 - (6+7+8+9))))))) & 1843 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times Q(7+6)) + (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1844 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3)) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 1844 &:= ((-9-8+Q(Q(7))) - (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1845 &:= ((-1+Q(Q(2+3))) - (4 - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1845 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (Q(6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1846 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2 \times 3))) - (4 - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1846 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + 6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1847 &:= (-1-2+(Q((Q(3)+Q(4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1847 &:= (-9-8+(Q(7+Q(6))+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1848 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(3)+Q(4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1848 &:= (-9+8+(Q(7)+(Q(6) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1849 &:= Q((-1+(2+(3+4+5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1849 &:= Q((-9+8-7+(Q(6)+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1850 &:= (Q(Q((-1 \times (2 - (3+4)))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1850 &:= (((-9+Q(8+7)) - (6+Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
1851 &:= (-1+2+(Q((Q(3)+Q(4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1851 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (Q(7+6) + Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1852 &:= (((-1+2+Q((Q(Q(3))+Q(4))))/5) - (6+7+8+9)) & 1852 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7-Q(6))) + (5-(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1853 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2+3)) + (4+Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1853 &:= ((-9+8+Q(7+Q(6))) - (5-(4+3+2+1))) \\
1854 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2 \times 3))) + (4+Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1854 &:= (-9 \times ((8+7) - (Q(6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1855 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1855 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7+6+5) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1856 &:= (Q(Q((-1-2+Q(3)))) + (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) & 1856 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1857 &:= ((((-1+2) \times 3) \times (4+Q(Q(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 1857 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) + (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1858 &:= (-1+2-(3 \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1858 &:= (-9-8-(((7+6) \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1859 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q((Q(3) + (4-5)))) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 1859 &:= (Q((-9-8+(Q(7)+(6+5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
1860 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times Q(3) - Q(4+5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) & 1860 &:= ((-9+8+Q(Q(7))) - (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1861 &:= (Q(((((-1+Q(2+3))/4) + Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)) & 1861 &:= (-9+8-(Q(7)-(Q(Q(6))+(Q(Q(5))-(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1862 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1862 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7-Q(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1863 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3+4) + (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1863 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) - Q(6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1864 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2 \times 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1864 &:= (Q(((9 \times 8 - 7) + Q(6+5))) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
1865 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2+3)) + (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1865 &:= (-9-8+(Q(Q(7)) + (6 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1866 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2 \times 3))) + (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1866 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) - (6 \times (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1867 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(Q(3))) - ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 1867 &:= ((-9+Q((Q(8)-7-6))) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1868 &:= (-1 - (Q((2 \times Q(3) + Q(4))) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) & 1868 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((Q(7+6) + Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1869 &:= (((-1+(2 \times Q(Q(3)))) \times 4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1869 &:= (Q(((9+Q(8))-7-6)) + (5+Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1870 &:= ((((-1+Q(Q(2+3))) - Q(Q(4))) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9) & 1870 &:= ((-9+Q(((8+7)-(6-5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
1871 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times (3+(4+(5+6)))) + Q((7+8+9)))) & 1871 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7+Q(6)) - (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1872 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(Q(3)) \times 4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1872 &:= (-9-8+(Q((7 \times 6)) + (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1873 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times 4) + (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1873 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1874 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2+3)) - Q(((4 \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)))) & 1874 &:= (-9+8-(((7+6) \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1875 &:= (((-1+Q((2 \times (3+4)))) \times 5) + Q(6+7+8+9)) & 1875 &:= (-9+Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1876 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + (Q((4 \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1876 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1877 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(((3 \times Q(4)) - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1877 &:= (((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1878 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2^3) + (4 - Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1878 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - Q(((7 \times 6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1879 &:= (-1 + ((Q((2 \times (3 + 4))) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1879 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1880 &:= ((Q(((-1 + 2 - 3) + Q(4))) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1880 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q((7 - (6 - 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1881 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1881 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1882 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1882 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 \times (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1883 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3 + Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1883 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7 + Q(6)) + (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1884 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2 + Q(3)) \times 4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1884 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1885 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + Q(3))) \times Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1885 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 - Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1886 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times 4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1886 &:= (-9 - (Q(((8 + 7) \times 6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1887 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) \times (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1887 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1888 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1888 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q(Q(7))) - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1889 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q(3)) \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1889 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7 + Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1890 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 - (3 - 4 - 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1890 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) \times (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1891 &:= (Q((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3)))/Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1891 &:= (-9 - (Q((Q(8) + (7 - 6 + Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1892 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1892 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 - Q(6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1893 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1893 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) - ((6 - Q(5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1894 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 \times (4 - Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1894 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (6 + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1895 &:= (((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - 4) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1895 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1896 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) - 4) \times Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1896 &:= (-9 - ((Q(((8 + 7) \times 6)) - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1897 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3)) + ((4^5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1897 &:= (-9 + (Q(8 + 7) + Q((Q(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1898 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4)))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1898 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7 + Q(6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1899 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 + Q(3 + 4))) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1899 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (Q(7 + 6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1900 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times (Q(3) + 4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1900 &:= (Q((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6))) - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1901 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(3) + Q(4)))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1901 &:= (Q(((-9 - 8 + 7) + Q(6))) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1902 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q((4 + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1902 &:= -9 + Q(Q((8 - 7) \times 6)) + Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1903 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(3 + 4) - 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1903 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((Q(Q(7)) - (6 + 5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1904 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(3 + 4) - 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1904 &:= (-9 + (8 \times Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1905 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3 + 4))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1905 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1906 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1906 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7 \times 6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1907 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(3 + 4) - 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1907 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1908 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - 4) - Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1908 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) \times (Q(6) + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1909 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 + 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1909 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7 + Q(6)) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1910 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1910 &:= ((((-9 + 8 + 7) \times Q(6)) - Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1911 &:= (Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1911 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + (7 + Q(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1912 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))))/5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1912 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) \times Q(7))/6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1913 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - Q(3)) + ((4^5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1913 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((7 \times 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1914 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1914 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1915 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + ((4^5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1915 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1916 &:= ((Q(Q(-1+2+3)) \times (Q(4)-5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)) & 1916 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q((7 \times 6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1917 &:= (-1 - ((2^{Q(3)}) - (Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 1917 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q((7 \times 6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1918 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{Q(3)}) - (Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 1918 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) - (7 + ((6+5) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1919 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1919 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7+Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1920 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1920 &:= (Q((-9 \times (8-7-6))) - (5 + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1921 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q(((Q(Q(Q(3)))/Q(Q(4+5))) + 6+7+8+9)))) & 1921 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times Q(7)) - 6) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1922 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3+4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1922 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times (Q(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1923 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((3+4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1923 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) \times (Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1924 &:= (Q(((((-1+2) \times (3+4)) + Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)) & 1924 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q((Q(7) + (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1925 &:= (-1+2 + (Q(((3+4) + Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)) & 1925 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) - (6 - (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1926 &:= (-1+2 - ((3+4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1926 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) + 7+6) \times Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
1927 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + ((4^5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1927 &:= (-9 + Q(((8 \times (7+6+5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1928 &:= ((-1+2+3) + ((4^5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1928 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7 - Q(6+5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1929 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times Q(Q(4))) + (5 + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1929 &:= ((-9 + Q((8+Q(7)))) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1930 &:= ((-1-2+Q(3)) + ((4^5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1930 &:= ((-9+8 + (Q(7+6) + Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
1931 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3+Q(Q(4))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1931 &:= (Q(((9+8+7) \times 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
1932 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((3+Q(Q(4))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1932 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (7 - ((6+5) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1933 &:= (-1-2 + Q((Q(3+4) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 1933 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - 7+6)) + Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1934 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(3+4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1934 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + (6-5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
1935 &:= (-1 + Q((2 + (3+4+5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1935 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1936 &:= Q((-1 + ((2 \times 3) + 4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 1936 &:= Q((((9+8) \times 7) + (Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1937 &:= (-1+2 + Q((Q(3+4) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 1937 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((7+6) + Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1938 &:= ((-1+2-3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1938 &:= ((-9-8) \times (7 - Q((6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1939 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4) - (5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1939 &:= (-9+8 + ((Q(7+6) + Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1940 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) + ((4^5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1940 &:= (((-9+Q(8)) \times (7+6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1941 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 1941 &:= (-9 + ((8+7) \times ((6 \times 5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1942 &:= (((-1-2) \times Q(3+Q(4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)) & 1942 &:= (((-9-8+Q(7)) \times (Q(6) + Q(5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1943 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1943 &:= ((-9-8 + Q(Q(7))) - Q(6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1944 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) - (Q(4+5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1944 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8+7) - Q(6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1945 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(3+4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)) & 1945 &:= (((-9 + Q(((8 \times 7) - Q(6)))) \times 5) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1946 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(3+Q(4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1946 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + Q((6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1947 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3+4) + (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 1947 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1948 &:= ((-1 + Q(2+3)) + ((4^5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1948 &:= (Q((-9+8 \times 7)) - (Q(6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1949 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 1949 &:= (Q((-9-8 + (Q(7) + (6+5)))) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
1950 &:= (-Q(-1+2+3) + Q(4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9) & 1950 &:= (Q((-9 \times (8-7-6))) + (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1951 &:= (Q((Q((-1+Q(2+3)))/Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)) & 1951 &:= (-9 + (Q(((8+7) - (6-5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1952 &:= (-1+2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9))) & 1952 &:= ((-9+8-7) \times (6 - (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1953 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + (Q(3) + Q(4)))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1953 &:= (((-9+8+Q(7)) \times Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1954 &:= (Q((-1 - ((2 - Q(3)) \times 4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1954 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8-7) \times 6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1955 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1955 &:= (((-9+Q(8)) - Q(Q(7)))/6) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1956 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - (Q(4+5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
1957 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q((3 + (4 \times 5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
1958 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{Q(3)}) - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1959 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + ((4-5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
1960 &:= (((Q((-1 + Q(2+3))) - 4) \times 5) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
1961 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((Q(Q(Q(3)))/Q(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
1962 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((Q(Q(3)) \times (4-5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
1963 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(3+4) - 5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
1964 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(3+4) - 5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
1965 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((Q(3+4) \times 5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
1966 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - Q(Q(4)))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1967 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (Q(4+5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
1968 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
1969 &:= ((-1 + ((2+3) \times Q((4 \times 5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
1970 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2+Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1971 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 \times Q(4+5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
1972 &:= (Q((-1 \times (2 - (3 + (4+5)))) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q((7+8+9)))) \\
1973 &:= (Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) + ((4^5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
1974 &:= (((-1 + Q(2+3)) \times Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\
1975 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2+3)) - Q((Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1976 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2+3)) - Q((Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1977 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
1978 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
1979 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + ((4+5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
1980 &:= (((-1 + Q(2+Q(3))) \times (4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
1981 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) \times (4 \times (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
1982 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) - ((4 \times Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
1983 &:= (-1 - (Q(2^3) \times (4 - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1984 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2^3) \times (4 - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1985 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
1986 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1987 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1988 &:= (((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1989 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1990 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1991 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times Q(Q(4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1992 &:= (-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1993 &:= ((((-1+2) \times 3) \times Q(Q(4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1994 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times Q(Q(4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1995 &:= (Q((Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + (4+5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
1956 &:= (-9 + ((8+7) \times (Q(6+5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1957 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) - 7 - 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
1958 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times Q(7+6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1959 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - Q(6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1960 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1961 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1962 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - 7 + 6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1963 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
1964 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - (6 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1965 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (((7 \times 6) \times Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
1966 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1967 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
1968 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times (Q(6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1969 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7+6) - Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
1970 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8+7) + (6 - Q(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
1971 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - 7) \times 6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1972 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q((7 \times 6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1973 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7+Q(6)) + (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1974 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1975 &:= (Q((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6))) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1976 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7) - Q((Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1977 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) - 7 - 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1978 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) - (6 + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1979 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
1980 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q((7 - (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1981 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times Q(7) + 6) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1982 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (Q(7) \times (Q(6) + 5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1983 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 - 6) - (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1984 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(Q(7))) - Q(((6 \times 5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1985 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) - (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1986 &:= (-9 - ((8+7+6) \times (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1987 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1988 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q((7 \times 6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1989 &:= (Q(((-9 + Q(8)) - 7 - 6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1990 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) + (6 - Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1991 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7 - 6) + Q(5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
1992 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times Q(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1993 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + Q(7))) + (6 + Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1994 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - ((6 + Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1995 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((Q(7+6) + Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1996 &:= (((-1 - Q(Q(2+3))) \times 4) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\ 1997 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) \times (Q(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\ 1998 &:= ((-1-2) \times ((3+Q(Q(4))) - (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\ 1999 &:= (-1 - ((2+3) \times (Q(4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))))) \\ 2000 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) \times (Q(4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2001 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\ 2002 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) + ((4^5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\ 2003 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) + ((4^5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\ 2004 &:= (((-1 + Q(2+3)) \times Q((Q(4) - 5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\ 2005 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(3+4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\ 2006 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) + ((4^5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\ 2007 &:= (((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) \times (4+5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\ 2008 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\ 2009 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2+3) + 4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\ 2010 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\ 2011 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\ 2012 &:= ((-1 + ((2^3) \times Q(Q(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\ 2013 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(3+4) + 5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\ 2014 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(3+4) + 5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\ 2015 &:= ((-1 - Q(2^3)) \times (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\ 2016 &:= ((Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) \times Q(4+5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\ 2017 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(3+4) + 5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\ 2018 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\ 2019 &:= (((-1 + 2^{Q(3)}) \times 4) + (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\ 2020 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (3^4)) \times Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\ 2021 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\ 2022 &:= (1+2) \times (3+Q(4) + Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\ 2023 &:= (1 - 2 + Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4)) + 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 2024 &:= (-1 + Q(((2 \times 3) + 4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\ 2025 &:= Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + 4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\ 2026 &:= 1 + Q(2 \times 3 + 4+5+6+7+8+9) \\ 2027 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((3 \times Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\ 2028 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2^3) - Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\ 2029 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))))) \\ 2030 &:= (((-1 + Q((2+3+4))) \times Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\ 2031 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - (Q((4 \times 5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\ 2032 &:= (-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\ 2033 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1996 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\ 1997 &:= ((-9 - (8+7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\ 1998 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) \times (Q(6) + 5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\ 1999 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 - 6 + (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2000 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) - Q(5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1)) \\ \\ 2001 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7 + Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2002 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7 + Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\ 2003 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2004 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (6 \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2005 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1))))) \\ 2006 &:= ((-9 + Q(((8 \times 7) - (6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\ 2007 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\ 2008 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) \times (Q(6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))))) \\ 2009 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(6))) + Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\ 2010 &:= (Q((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\ 2011 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (Q(7+6) + Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\ 2012 &:= (-9 + (Q(8+7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1))))) \\ 2013 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\ 2014 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2015 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) - Q(6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2016 &:= (-9 - (Q(8+7) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2017 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2018 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (7 - Q((Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2019 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) + ((6 - Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\ 2020 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) + (Q(6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\ 2021 &:= (Q(((9 - 8 + 7) \times 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\ 2022 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) \times Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\ 2023 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (Q(6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2024 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) + Q(6)) \times Q(5))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\ 2025 &:= Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2026 &:= (-9 + (Q(((8 \times 7) - (6+5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\ 2027 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 \times 7))) - ((6+5) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\ 2028 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\ 2029 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) + (Q(6) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2030 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 + Q(7)))) - (Q(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\ 2031 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times Q(7) + Q(6)) \times 5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\ 2032 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 + Q((Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2033 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times (6 - Q(Q(5))))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$2034 := ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2035 := ((-1 + 2 + (Q(3) \times 4)) \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2036 := (-1 - ((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$2037 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2038 := ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$2039 := ((Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(4) + Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$2040 := ((-1 - 2 - (Q(3) - (Q(4) \times 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2041 := ((-1 + Q(Q(2 \times 3))) - (4 - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2042 := ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2043 := (-1 - 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2044 := (Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) - (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$2045 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2046 := (Q(((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3)))/Q(4))) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2047 := (-1 + (2 \times Q(((3 + 4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$2048 := ((-1 + Q((Q(2 \times 3) + Q(4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2049 := ((Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2050 := ((-1 - Q((2 + 3 + 4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$2051 := (-1 - ((2 \times (Q(3 + 4) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$2052 := (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3 + 4) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2053 := (((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) \times 4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2054 := (-1 + (Q(((2 + 3) \times (4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$2055 := (-1 + (Q((Q(2 + 3) + (4 + 5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2056 := (Q((Q((-1 + 2 \times 3)) + (4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2057 := (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$2058 := ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2059 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(3 + 4))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$2060 := (Q((-1 - 2 + (3 \times Q(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$2061 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3 + 4))) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2062 := ((-1 + 2 + (Q(3)^4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$2063 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2064 := (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + (Q((4 + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2065 := (-1 + (Q((Q(2 + 3) + 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$2066 := (Q((Q((-1 + 2 \times 3)) + 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2067 := (((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$2068 := (-1 - ((2^{Q(3)}) - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2069 := (((-1 + 2^{Q(3)}) \times 4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$2070 := (-1 - (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2071 := (-1 \times (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2072 := ((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2073 := (((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - Q((4 \times 5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2034 := (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2035 := (((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q(7 + 6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2036 := (-9 + (Q((8 + Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2037 := (-9 + (Q(8 + 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2038 := (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - Q(6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$2039 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8))/(7 + 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2040 := (Q((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$2041 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) - 7 - 6)) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2042 := (-9 + (((8 \times 7) \times Q(6)) + (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2043 := (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2044 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q((7 \times 6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2045 := ((-9 - Q(((8 \times 7) - Q(6)))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2046 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2047 := ((-9 \times 8 + Q(7)) \times (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2048 := (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (7 + 6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2049 := (-9 - (Q(8) \times 7 - (6 + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2050 := (((-9 + Q(8 + 7)) - (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$2051 := (-9 + ((Q(8 + 7) + (6 - Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2052 := (((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) \times (Q(6) + Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$2053 := (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2054 := (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - ((6 \times Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2055 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(7) \times 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$2056 := ((-9 + Q((8 \times 7))) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2057 := (-9 - 8 + (Q(7 + Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2058 := (-9 + (((8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$2059 := ((-9 \times Q((8 - 7 + 6))) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2060 := (((-9 + Q((8 + 7 + 6))) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$2061 := (-9 \times (8 - ((7 \times Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2062 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2063 := (-9 - (8 \times Q(7) + (Q(6) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2064 := ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7 + 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2065 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(7) \times 6))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2066 := (-9 + ((Q(8 + 7) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2067 := (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2068 := ((-9 \times 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2069 := (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2070 := (-9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2071 := (-9 + ((Q(8) + (Q(7 + 6) - Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2072 := (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7 - Q(6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2073 := (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2074 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(3 + 4)) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2075 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(3 + 4)) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2076 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2077 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(((3 + 4) + Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2078 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2079 &:= (((-1 + 2^{Q(3)}) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2080 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) \times ((4 \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2081 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3 + 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2082 &:= (-1 + (((2^3) \times Q(Q(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2083 &:= (1 - 2 + Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
2084 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) - (Q(4) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2085 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2 + Q(3 + 4)) - 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2086 &:= (Q(((-1 - (Q(2 + 3) - Q(Q(4)))) / 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2087 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((3 + (4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2088 &:= (-1 - ((2^{Q(3)}) - Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2089 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{Q(3)}) - Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2090 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2091 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3 + 4))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2092 &:= ((-1 - 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) + 4) \times Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2093 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) + 4) \times Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2094 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) + (Q((Q(4) - 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2095 &:= (((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + 4) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2096 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3 + 4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2097 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2098 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times Q((4 \times 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2099 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2100 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) - Q(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2101 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times Q((4 \times 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2102 &:= 1 + 2 - Q(Q(3 + 4)) + 5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2103 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3 + 4) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2104 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) - (Q(4) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2105 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2106 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2107 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(((3 + 4) + Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2108 &:= ((-1 + Q((Q(2 \times 3) + Q(4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2109 &:= ((Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2110 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2111 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q((Q(3) + 4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2112 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q((Q(3) + 4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2113 &:= (-1 - 2 + Q(((3^4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2074 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2075 &:= (Q((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2076 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - Q(((Q(6) \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2077 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 + Q(6)) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2078 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) - (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2079 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - Q(7)) \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2080 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7) - (6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2081 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) - (7 \times 6)) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2082 &:= (-9 - ((8 - Q(7)) \times (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2083 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2084 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7 + 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2085 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2086 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2087 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(Q((7 + 6 - (5 + 4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2088 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + Q(7))) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2089 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (6^5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2090 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times 7) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2091 &:= (-9 - (((Q(8) - Q(7 + 6)) / 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2092 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) - 7 - 6))) - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2093 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2094 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (6 \times (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2095 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2096 &:= ((-9 + (Q((8 + 7 + 6)) \times 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2097 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2098 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q((7 \times 6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2099 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2100 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) + Q(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2101 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times Q(6)))) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2102 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 - Q(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2103 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times (7 - Q(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2104 &:= (((-9 - 8 - Q(7)) \times 6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2105 &:= ((-9 - (Q(8) \times 7 - Q(6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2106 &:= ((-9 - Q(8 + 7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2107 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2108 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2109 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2110 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2111 &:= ((-9 + ((Q(8) + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2112 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 - Q(6))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2113 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) - Q((Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2114 &:= (-1 \times 2 + Q(((3^4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2114 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + ((6 - Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2115 &:= (-1 + Q((Q((2 + 3 + 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2115 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2116 &:= Q((-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2116 &:= Q((-9 - 8 - (7 \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2117 &:= (-1 + 2 + Q(((3^4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2117 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) - (7 + 6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2118 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (Q(4) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 2118 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (Q(7) \times 6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2119 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(3) \times 4))) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2119 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2120 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4)) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 2120 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) + (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2121 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3 + 4))) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2121 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) + 7) \times (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2122 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(((3 + 4) \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2122 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 - Q(6))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2123 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2123 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2124 &:= ((-1 + Q((Q(2^3) - 4 - 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 2124 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2125 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + Q(3)))/4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 2125 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) - 6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2126 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(((3 + 4) \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2126 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + ((7 \times 6) + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2127 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2127 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2128 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((Q(3) - (Q(4) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2128 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (6 + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2129 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) \times Q(4)) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 2129 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7 + Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2130 &:= (1 - 2 - Q(3) + Q(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 2130 &:= (Q((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6))) + (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2131 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2131 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8 + 7) - (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2132 &:= (-1 - 2 - (((Q(3) - Q(Q(4))) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2132 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 - Q(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2133 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) - (Q(4) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2133 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - Q(6))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2134 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) + ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2134 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((Q(7) + Q(6)) \times Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2135 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times ((3 + 4) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2135 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7) - (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2136 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times ((3 + 4) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 2136 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2137 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) + Q((4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2137 &:= (-9 \times 8 + Q(((7 \times 6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2138 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(Q(3))) \times Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2138 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times (7 - Q(6))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2139 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times Q(4)) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2139 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2140 &:= ((((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) - Q(4)) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 2140 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2141 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3 + 4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2141 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7) \times 6) \times Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2142 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 2142 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q((8 - 7 + 6)))) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2143 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2143 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(6) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2144 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) \times (Q(4) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2144 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) \times 7 - Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2145 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2145 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2146 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 \times 3))) + Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 2146 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (7 - 6 + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2147 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((3 - 4) + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2147 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(7 + 6) + Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2148 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(3) + Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2148 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2149 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3 + 4) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2149 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + Q(6)) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2150 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(3 + 4)) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 2150 &:= (((-9 + Q((8 + 7 + 6))) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2151 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3 + 4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 2151 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7) + (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2152 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times ((3 - 4) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 2152 &:= (-9 - ((Q(((8 \times 7) + Q(6))) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2153 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2153 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2154 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(3 + 4))) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2155 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2156 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((Q(Q(3)) + 4) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2157 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((3 \times Q(4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2158 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((Q(3) - Q(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2159 &:= 1 + 2 \times (Q(3 \times Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2160 &:= ((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2161 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q((3 \times 4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2162 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q((3 \times 4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2163 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((3 + 4) + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2164 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) - (Q(4) + Q(Q(5)))))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2165 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2166 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((3 - Q(Q(4))) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2167 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) - ((4 + Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2168 &:= ((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times ((4 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2169 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (3 \times (4^5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2170 &:= (((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2171 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3 + 4))) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2172 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (4^5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2173 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times (4^5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2174 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(3 + 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2175 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((3 + 4) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2176 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2177 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q((3 - ((4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2178 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2179 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times (Q(3 + 4) - Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2180 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2181 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2182 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2183 &:= (-1 - (Q((Q(2 + 3) + 4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2184 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(3 + 4))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2185 &:= ((((-1 + 2)^3) + Q(Q(4))) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2186 &:= (Q(((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) - 4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2187 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) - (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2188 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4))) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2189 &:= (-1 - (((2^3) - Q(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2190 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - Q(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2191 &:= (Q((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3)))/Q(4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2192 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4))) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2193 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q((3 \times 4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2154 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) \times (7 \times 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2155 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2156 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) \times (6 - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2157 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (Q(6 + Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2158 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) - (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2159 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(Q(7))) - Q(((6 \times Q(5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2160 &:= (Q((-9 + (8 + 7 + 6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2161 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times (6 - Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2162 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(7) + 6) \times (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2163 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2164 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (6 \times Q(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2165 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2166 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 \times 7))) - Q((Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2167 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q((8 - 7 + 6)))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2168 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 \times Q(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2169 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2170 &:= (((-9 + Q((8 + 7 + 6))) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2171 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + Q((Q((7 - (6 - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2172 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7 + 6) + Q(5 + 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2173 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2174 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7 + 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2175 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times Q(7)) - (6^5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2176 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8 - 7) \times 6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2177 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7 - (Q(6) + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2178 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 \times Q((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2179 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2180 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2181 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2182 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(((7 \times 6) + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2183 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7 + 6) + (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2184 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + Q(7))) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2185 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (6 - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2186 &:= ((-9 + (Q((8 + 7 + 6)) \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2187 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) - (6 - 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2188 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2189 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((Q(7) \times 6) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2190 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2191 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2192 &:= (-9 - 8 + Q(((7 \times 6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2193 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$2194 := (Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$2195 := (-1 + (Q((2 \times (Q(3) + (4 + 5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$2196 := (Q(((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2197 := (-1 + 2 - (Q((3 \times Q(4))) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2198 := (-1 - 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2199 := (-1 - 2 - (3 \times (Q(4) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2200 := (((-1 + 2 + 3) + Q(Q(4))) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2201 := (Q((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3)))/Q(4)) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2202 := (-1 + 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2203 := (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (Q(4) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2204 := (-1 - ((2 - (Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$2205 := (((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2206 := (-1 - 2 + Q(((3 \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$2207 := (-1 \times 2 + Q(((3 \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$2208 := (-1 + Q(((2^3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$2209 := Q((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2210 := (-1 + 2 + Q(((3 \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$2211 := ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) + (4 - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2212 := (((-1 + Q(Q((2 + 3 + 4))))/5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2213 := (((Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + 4)/5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2214 := ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2215 := (-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + ((4 \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2216 := (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) + ((4 \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$2217 := (-1 - 2 + ((Q(3 + 4) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$2218 := (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(3 + 4) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$2219 := (-1 + ((2 - (Q(3) - Q(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$2220 := (((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + Q(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2221 := (-1 + 2 + ((Q(3 + 4) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$2222 := (-1 + 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2223 := (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times Q((Q(4) + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2224 := (-1 - (((2 - (3 + 4)) \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$2225 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3 + 4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$2226 := ((-1 + 2 + ((Q(3) - 4) \times Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2227 := (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$2228 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2229 := ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + 4) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2230 := (((-1 + Q((2 + 3) + Q(4))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$2231 := (Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$2232 := (((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (4 + Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2233 := (((-1 + Q(2^3)) \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$2194 := (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2195 := (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2196 := (-9 - (Q((8 + 7 + 6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2197 := (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2198 := ((-9 \times 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$2199 := ((-9 \times ((8 - Q(7)) \times 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$2200 := (-9 + Q(((8 \times 7) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2201 := (((-9 - Q(8 + 7)) \times Q(6)) + Q(Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2202 := (-9 - 8 + (Q(((7 \times 6) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$2203 := (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - ((6 - 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2204 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) \times (7 - 6 - 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$2205 := (-9 \times (Q(8) - ((Q(7) \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2206 := (-9 + ((Q((8 + 7 + 6)) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$2207 := (-9 + (Q((Q(8) - (7 + 6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2208 := (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2209 := Q((-9 - 8 + Q(((7 + 6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2210 := (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) + (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2211 := (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2212 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (((7 + 6) \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2213 := (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(6) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2214 := (-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2215 := (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2216 := (-9 + 8 - 7 - (6^5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2217 := (((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$2218 := (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2219 := (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + (6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$2220 := (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2221 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2222 := ((-9 \times 8 + Q((Q(7) - (6 - 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$2223 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$2224 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + 6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2225 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2226 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2227 := ((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7) + (Q(6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2228 := (((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6)) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$2229 := ((-9 \times ((8 - Q(7)) \times 6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$2230 := (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$2231 := (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7) + (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2232 := (-9 \times (8 - Q((7 - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$2233 := (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2234 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(3 + 4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2235 &:= ((-1 + Q((Q((2 + 3 + 4)) - Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2236 &:= (Q((-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) - Q(4 + 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2237 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times Q(4)) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2238 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2239 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times (Q(3 + 4) - Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2240 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2241 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2242 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q((4 + (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2243 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2244 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(3 + 4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2245 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (4 + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2246 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((3 \times Q(4)))) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2247 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(3 + 4) + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2248 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2 \times 3) - 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2249 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times Q(Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2250 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2251 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2252 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3 + 4))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2253 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - 4) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2254 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2 + 3) + Q(4)) \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2255 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2256 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2257 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2258 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 \times Q(Q(4))) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2259 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2260 &:= (((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + Q(Q(4))) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2261 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2262 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (4 + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2263 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (4 + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2264 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2 \times 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2265 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2266 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((3 \times Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2267 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((3 \times Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2268 &:= ((-1 + Q((Q(2^3) - Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2269 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2270 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((3 \times Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2271 &:= (Q(((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) / Q(4)) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2272 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2273 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2234 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2235 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2236 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (Q((Q(7) + 6 \times 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2237 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2238 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2239 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2240 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - Q(7 + 6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2241 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - Q((7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2242 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q((Q(7) - (6 - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2243 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + Q(6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2244 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (6 \times Q(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2245 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2246 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times Q(6)))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2247 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2248 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 \times (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2249 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - ((7 + 6) \times Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2250 &:= (Q((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2251 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8 + 7) + (6 - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2252 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) + ((7 + 6)^{5+4-(3+2+1)})) \\
2253 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2254 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2255 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2256 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) - (6^5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2257 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + Q((Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2258 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7 + 6) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2259 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7 + 6) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2260 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2261 &:= (-9 - (((Q(8) \times 7) + 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2262 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8 + 7) + Q(6))) \times (5 + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2263 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2264 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8)) - 7 - 6) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2265 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2266 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2267 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2268 &:= (-9 + (((8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2269 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2270 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8 + 7) + (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2271 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + (Q(7 + 6) - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2272 &:= (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) - (6 + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2273 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2274 &:= ((Q(Q(-1+2+3)) \times (4+5)) - (6+7+8+9)) & 2274 &:= ((-9-8+Q(Q(7))) - ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2275 &:= ((Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) - Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) & 2275 &:= (Q((-9 \times (8-7-6))) + (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2276 &:= (-1+2+((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) & 2276 &:= (((-9+Q(8+7)) \times (6+5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
2277 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 \times Q(3))) - Q((Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2277 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6)+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2278 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2^3) - Q(4))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) & 2278 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(6)+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2279 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + (4 - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2279 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7+6)) + Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2280 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) + (4 - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2280 &:= ((-9-8+Q(7+6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2281 &:= 1 - 2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + 4 - Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 2281 &:= ((-9 \times Q((8+7+6))) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2282 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2+3)) - (4 + (Q((5+6)) \times (7+8+9)))) & 2282 &:= (((-9+Q(8+7)) \times Q(6)) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2283 &:= ((-1-2) \times (Q((3 \times 4)) - (5+Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 2283 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) - (6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2284 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3 - Q(Q(4)))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 2284 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) - ((6 \times 5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2285 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times Q(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 2285 &:= ((-9+Q((8 \times (7 - (6-5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2286 &:= (((-1-2+Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)) & 2286 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) - ((Q(6) \times 5)/(4+3+2+1))) \\
2287 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3^4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2287 &:= (-9+Q(Q(8)) - ((7+6+5) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
2288 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((3^4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2288 &:= (-9+8 + (Q((7 \times 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2289 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((Q(3+4) \times 5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 2289 &:= ((-9+8+Q(Q(7))) - (6+5+Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
2290 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - (Q(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)) & 2290 &:= ((-9+8+Q(Q(7))) - ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2291 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (4 - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) & 2291 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6 - (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2292 &:= (((-1-2+Q(Q(3))) \times (4+Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9) & 2292 &:= ((-9+Q(Q((8 - ((7-6)^5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
2293 &:= ((((-1+2) \times 3) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 2293 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) - (6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2294 &:= (-1 - ((2+3) \times (Q((Q(4)+5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 2294 &:= ((-9-8+Q(Q(7))) - (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2295 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - (4+Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2295 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) + (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2296 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - (4+Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2296 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) - Q(((7 \times 6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2297 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((3 \times Q(4))) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 2297 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2298 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2298 &:= (Q((-9+8 \times 7)) - (6+5 - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
2299 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2299 &:= (Q((-9+8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2300 &:= (((-1 + (Q(2+3) + Q(Q(4)))) \times 5) + Q(6+7+8+9)) & 2300 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7-6-5))) \times Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
2301 &:= (-1 - 2 + Q((Q(3) + 4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 2301 &:= (Q(Q((-9+Q(((8+7) - (6+5)))))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
2302 &:= (-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(3) + 4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 2302 &:= (-9 - (Q(8+7) - (Q(6) + Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2303 &:= (-1 + Q(((2 + (3^4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2303 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) - (6+5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2304 &:= Q((Q((-1+2) \times 3) + 4+5+6+7+8+9)) & 2304 &:= Q((-9+8+Q((7 \times (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2305 &:= (-1+2+Q((Q(3) + 4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 2305 &:= (Q((-9-8+Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2306 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2 \times 3))) + Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) & 2306 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q((7 \times 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2307 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 - (Q(4) \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 2307 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - (6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2308 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+Q(3)) - (Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 2308 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2309 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+Q(3)) - (Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 2309 &:= (Q((Q((-9+8+7)) + (6+5))) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
2310 &:= (((-1+2+Q(Q(3))) - Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) & 2310 &:= ((-9+8+Q(Q(7))) - (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2311 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q((3 - (4 - (5+6+7+8+9)))))) & 2311 &:= (-9+8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (6+5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2312 &:= (-1+2 - (Q(3) - (Q(4) \times (Q((5+6)) + 7+8+9)))) & 2312 &:= (((-9+8-7) \times Q(6+Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
2313 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + Q(4)) \times ((5+6) - (7+8+9)))) & 2313 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2314 &:= (Q((-1-2+(Q(3)\times 4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2315 &:= (-1\times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5\times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2316 &:= (-1-2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4)\times (5\times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2317 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2+3))) + (Q((4+Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2318 &:= ((-1-Q(2+Q(3)))\times (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2319 &:= (-1 - (2\times (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4)+Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2320 &:= ((-1\times 2)\times (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4)+Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2321 &:= ((Q(-1\times 2+Q(3))\times (4+Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
2322 &:= ((-1 + ((2^3)\times Q(Q(4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2323 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2\times 3)) - (4\times (5+Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2324 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4)\times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2325 &:= (-1 + (Q((2+Q(3+4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2326 &:= ((-1-2+Q((3\times Q(4)))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2327 &:= (-1 + ((2^3)\times (Q(Q(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2328 &:= ((-1+Q((Q(2^3) - Q(4)))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2329 &:= ((Q((-1+Q(2+3)))\times 4) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2330 &:= ((-1+2+Q((3\times Q(4)))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2331 &:= (((-1-2)\times 3)\times (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2332 &:= (-1+2 - (Q(3)\times (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2333 &:= (-1 + (Q((2\times (Q(3+4) - Q(5)))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2334 &:= ((Q(Q(-1+2+3))\times (4+5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\
2335 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2+3) + Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2336 &:= (-1-2 + (Q((3\times Q(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2337 &:= (-1\times 2 + (Q((3\times Q(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2338 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2^3) - Q(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2339 &:= ((Q((-1+Q(2+3)))\times 4) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
2340 &:= (-1+2 + (Q((3\times Q(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2341 &:= (-1+2 - ((3-Q(4+5))\times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2342 &:= (-1-2 + ((Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4))/5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2343 &:= ((-1-2+Q(Q(3+4))) - (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2344 &:= (-1 + (((2+Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))\times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2345 &:= (((-1+Q((2\times Q(3)))) - Q(Q(4)))\times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2346 &:= (-1-2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4+5)\times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2347 &:= ((-1\times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4+5)\times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2348 &:= (((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))\times (4+Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2349 &:= (((-1+(2\times Q(Q(3))))\times (4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
2350 &:= (Q(Q(-1\times 2+Q(3))) - (Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2351 &:= (-1 - (2\times (Q(3+4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2352 &:= ((-1\times 2)\times (Q(3+4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2353 &:= (-1 - (2\times ((3\times Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2314 &:= ((-9\times (Q(8)\times (7-6-5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2315 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) + (6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2316 &:= (Q((-9+8+7\times 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
2317 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2318 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) - (Q(6) - (5\times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2319 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2320 &:= (-9\times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2321 &:= ((-9\times ((8-7-Q(Q(6)))/5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2322 &:= ((-9 + ((Q(8)+7)\times Q(6))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2323 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8)+7))) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2324 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) + ((6\times 5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2325 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) + 6+5+4+3+2+1) \\
2326 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6))\times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2327 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2328 &:= ((-9 + (8\times (Q(7)\times 6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2329 &:= (-9\times 8 + Q(Q((7\times (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2330 &:= ((-9\times (Q(8) - Q(7+6+5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2331 &:= (-9\times ((8 - (7\times 6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2332 &:= (-9\times 8 + (Q((Q(7) - (6-5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
2333 &:= ((-9-8+Q(Q(7))) - (Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2334 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) - (6\times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2335 &:= (Q((-9-8+Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2336 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) - (Q(6)\times (5\times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2337 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2338 &:= ((-9\times 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2339 &:= ((-9\times (Q(8) - ((7+6)\times Q(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2340 &:= (-9\times (8-7 - (Q(6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2341 &:= (-9 + (((8+7)\times 6)\times Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
2342 &:= (((-9-Q(8))\times (7-Q(6))) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2343 &:= (-9 + (8\times (Q(7+6) + (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2344 &:= ((-9+8+Q(Q(7))) - (6 + (5\times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2345 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6+5+Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2346 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) - ((6+5)\times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2347 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(7+6)+5)\times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2348 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) - (6 - (5\times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2349 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + 6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2350 &:= (-9\times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + 6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2351 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8+7) + (6+5))\times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2352 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8)+7)\times (6+(5+4))) + Q(Q((3+2+1)))) \\
2353 &:= ((-9-8+Q(Q(7))) - (Q(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2354 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((3 \times Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2355 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+3) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2356 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((3 \times Q(4))) + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2357 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q((3 \times (4+5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2358 &:= (((-1-2) \times Q(Q(3))) + Q((Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2359 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(3+4))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2360 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((3 \times Q(4))) + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2361 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2362 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2363 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3+4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2364 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3+4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2365 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(((2 + Q(3)) - 4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2366 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2) \times (3+4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2367 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3+4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2368 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(((3 \times 4) - 5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2369 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (Q(Q(Q(3)))/Q(4+5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2370 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2371 &:= (Q(Q((Q(-1+2+3) - 4 - 5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2372 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(((3 \times 4) - 5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2373 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3+4)) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2374 &:= ((-1 + Q((Q(2^3) - 4))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2375 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+3) - (Q(4) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2376 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2) \times (3+4))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2377 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((Q(3) \times 4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2378 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((Q(3) \times 4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2379 &:= (-1 + ((Q((2 \times Q(3))) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2380 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) \times (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2381 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) \times 4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2382 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2383 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2+3)) + (Q(4) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2384 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2385 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2386 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2387 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2388 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) - (Q(4) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2389 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(((3+4) \times 5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2390 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2391 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3+4))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2392 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - (Q(4) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2393 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) - (Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2354 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) + (6 \times Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
2355 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) + (Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2356 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) - (Q(7+6) + (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2357 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) + (Q(6+Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
2358 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (Q(7) \times 6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2359 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + Q((Q(7) - (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2360 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) + (6 + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2361 &:= (-9+8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2362 &:= (-9-8 + (Q((7 \times 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2363 &:= ((-9-8+Q(Q(7))) - (6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2364 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2365 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2366 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2367 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) - 7 - 6))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2368 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (7 + (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2369 &:= ((-9+8+Q(Q(7))) - (Q(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2370 &:= (-9+8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2371 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + (Q(7+6) + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2372 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2373 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) - (Q(6) - (5 + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2374 &:= (Q((-9-8+Q(7))) + (6 \times Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2375 &:= (-9-8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2376 &:= ((-9 + Q(8+7)) \times (6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2377 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q((8-7+6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2378 &:= (-9+8 + (Q((7 \times 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2379 &:= ((-9+8+Q(Q(7))) - (6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2380 &:= ((-9-8) \times (Q(7) + (Q(6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2381 &:= ((-9-8+Q(Q(7))) - ((6 \times 5)/(4+3+2+1))) \\
2382 &:= ((-9+8+Q(Q(7))) - ((Q(6) \times 5)/(4+3+2+1))) \\
2383 &:= ((-9-8+Q(Q(7))) - (6+5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2384 &:= (-9-8 + Q(Q((7 \times (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2385 &:= (-9-8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2386 &:= (((-9 + Q(8+7)) \times (6+5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2387 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(7) + Q(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2388 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7))/Q(6)) + Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2389 &:= ((-9+8+Q(Q(7))) - (6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2390 &:= (((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7+6))) \times Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2391 &:= (-9+8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2392 &:= (-9 + Q(Q((Q(8) \times 7 - Q(6+5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2393 &:= ((-9-8+Q(Q(7))) - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2394 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 \times 3) - (Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2395 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times Q(3+4))) \times Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2396 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2397 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2398 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (Q(4) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2399 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3) + (Q(4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2400 &:= (-1 + Q(((2 \times (3+4)) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2401 &:= Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(3) + 4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2402 &:= (-1 + 2 + Q(Q(((Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(4)))/(5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2403 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3)) + (Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2404 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+3) - (Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2405 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+3) - (Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2406 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2) \times (3+4))) - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2407 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3+4))) - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2408 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (4 + Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
2409 &:= (Q((-1+2) \times 3) + (Q(4) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2410 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) + (Q(4) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2411 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 + Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2412 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((3 + Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2413 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) \times (4 + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
2414 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2415 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2+3)) - (Q(4) + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2416 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) + (Q(4) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2417 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q(3) + (Q(4) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2418 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (Q(4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2419 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) - (Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2420 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2421 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2422 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - (Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2423 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3) + (4 - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2424 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) + (4 - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2425 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 \times 4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2426 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((3 \times 4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2427 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) \times ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2428 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2429 &:= (-1 - ((2 - 3) \times (Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2430 &:= (-1 + ((2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2431 &:= (Q(Q(Q(-1+2+3) - 4 - 5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\
2432 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2433 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3+4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2394 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2395 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2396 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2397 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2398 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) - (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2399 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2400 &:= (-9 + 8 + Q(Q((7 \times (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2401 &:= Q(Q((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2402 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2403 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7 + 6) - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2404 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) \times (7 - 6 - 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2405 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2406 &:= (-9 - ((8 - Q(7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2407 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q((8 - 7 + 6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2408 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (6 - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2409 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2410 &:= (((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7 + 6))) \times Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2411 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + Q(((8 + 7) - (6 + 5))))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2412 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2413 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q(7) - (6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2414 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2415 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2416 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + 6))) - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2417 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2418 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2419 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2420 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 - Q(6)) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2421 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2422 &:= (-9 - (Q((Q(8) - (7 - (6 \times 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2423 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + 6 - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2424 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2425 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((Q(7) + (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2426 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7) \times (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2427 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) \times (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2428 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) - (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2429 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (6 - (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2430 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(7 + 6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2431 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2432 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 \times 6) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2433 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (Q(7) - (6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2434 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3+4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2435 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3+4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2436 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2) \times (3+4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2437 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3+4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2438 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2439 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2440 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2441 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2+3))) \times 4) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2442 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2443 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3)) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2444 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2445 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3+4))) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2446 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) - (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2447 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3-4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2448 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2449 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3-4)) \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2450 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (3-4)) \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2451 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3-4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2452 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((3-4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2453 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3+4)) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2454 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) + (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2455 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 \times 3)) + (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2456 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2) \times (3+4))) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2457 &:= ((-1 + Q(2^3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2458 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2459 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) - (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2460 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))/Q(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2461 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2+3))) \times 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2462 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4) + Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2463 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3+4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2464 &:= ((-1 + (Q(Q(2+3)) \times 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2465 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3+4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2466 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) + (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2467 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(3) + (Q(4) + Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2468 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + (4 \times Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2469 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2470 &:= (((-1 - (2 - (3+4))) \times Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2471 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2+3))) \times 4) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2472 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3^4) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2473 &:= (((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2434 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2435 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2436 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) + (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2437 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q((Q(7) + (6 - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2438 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2439 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - Q(7)) \times 6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2440 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) + (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2441 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + 7 + 6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2442 &:= (-9 - (Q((8 - 7 + 6)) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2443 &:= (((-9 - 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(6) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2444 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (6 - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2445 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) + (6 - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2446 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) - ((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2447 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2448 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2449 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q(((7 + 6) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2450 &:= ((((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7))/ (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2451 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2452 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7) \times 6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2453 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2454 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) \times (7 \times 6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2455 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2456 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8 + 7) \times (6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2457 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2458 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2459 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2460 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2461 &:= (((-9 - Q(8 + 7))/6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2462 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2463 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2464 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2465 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2466 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2467 &:= ((-9 \times ((Q(8) \times (7 + 6)) + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2468 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (Q(7) \times 6)) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2469 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + 6) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2470 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) + (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2471 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7) + (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2472 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2473 &:= (((-9 - 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2474 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q((Q(3) + Q(4)))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2475 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) + (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2476 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2477 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2478 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3 + 4) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2479 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + Q(3)) - Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2480 &:= ((-1 + 2 - Q(Q(3))) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2481 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (Q(4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2482 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2483 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2484 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2485 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) \times 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2486 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2487 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2488 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2489 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2490 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (4 - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2491 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times 4) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2492 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - Q(((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2493 &:= (-1 + (Q(2^3) + (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2494 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2^3)) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2495 &:= (-1 + (Q(2^3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2496 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - Q((4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2497 &:= (-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2498 &:= (-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2499 &:= (-1 + Q((2 + (Q(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2500 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2501 &:= (-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2502 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) \times (4 - Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2503 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + Q(((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2504 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times Q(Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2505 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2506 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + Q(((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2507 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2508 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2509 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2510 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) + Q(((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2511 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2512 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(Q(3)) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2513 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) \times Q(Q(4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2474 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2475 &:= (((-9 + 8 \times 7) - Q(6)) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2476 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 + 7 \times 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2477 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2478 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 + (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2479 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) - Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2480 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) - Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2481 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + Q(Q(((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2482 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2483 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times Q(7 + 6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2484 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2485 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) - (Q(6) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2486 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2487 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - Q((Q(7) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2488 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q((7 \times 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2489 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2490 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2491 &:= (-9 + Q((Q(8) + (7 - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2492 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 - (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2493 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2494 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2495 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2496 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((Q(7) \times (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2497 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) - 7 - 6)) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2498 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) \times (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2499 &:= (-9 + 8 + Q((Q(7) + (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2500 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) - (6 + 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2501 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + Q(((8 + 7) - (6 + 5)))))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2502 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7 + Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2503 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7 + 6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2504 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + (6 \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2505 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + Q((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2506 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + 7 \times 6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2507 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2508 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(7))/6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2509 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q((Q(7) + (6 - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2510 &:= ((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7 + 6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2511 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 \times Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2512 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7 + 6)) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2513 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + 6 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2514 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3 - Q((4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2515 &:= (((-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) / 4)) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2516 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2 \times 3))) - (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2517 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) - (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2518 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2519 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) \times (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2520 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2521 &:= (Q((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) / Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2522 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2523 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times Q((4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2524 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2525 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2526 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2527 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2528 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2529 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2 + 3) \times (4 \times Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2530 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2531 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2532 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3^4) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2533 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2534 &:= (-1 + ((Q(Q(2 + 3)) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2535 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3 + 4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2536 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2537 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2538 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3 + 4) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2539 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2540 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + Q(3)) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2541 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2542 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2543 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2544 &:= ((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2545 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2546 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2547 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3 + 4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2548 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2549 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2550 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) + Q(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2551 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2552 &:= (-1 + (((2 + Q(Q(3))) \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2553 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times Q((4 + Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2514 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2515 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2516 &:= (-9 - (((Q(8) - Q(7 + 6)) \times Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2517 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2518 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2519 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (6 - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2520 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2521 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (7 - Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2522 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2523 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2524 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q((Q(7) + 6))) - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2525 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2526 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 - 6) - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2527 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (6 + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2528 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + (Q(6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2529 &:= (-9 \times (8 - Q(((Q(7) + Q(6 + 5)) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2530 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + ((7 + 6) \times Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2531 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2532 &:= ((-9 + ((Q(8) + 7) \times Q(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2533 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2534 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2535 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2536 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2537 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8) \times (7 + 6))) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2538 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + 6 - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2539 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(((7 \times 6) - Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2540 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2541 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) - 7 - 6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2542 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - (7 + 6 - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2543 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q((Q(7) - (6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2544 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 \times Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2545 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2546 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2547 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2548 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q((7 \times 6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2549 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2550 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2551 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(7) - Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2552 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) - Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2553 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2554 &:= (-1 + ((Q(Q(2+3)) \times 4) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2555 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3+4))) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2556 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2557 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2558 &:= (-1 + (((2 - Q(Q(3))) \times (4 - Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2559 &:= ((Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2560 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2561 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2562 &:= ((-1 - Q(2 + Q(3))) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2563 &:= (-1 + (Q(2^3) + Q(((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2564 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) - Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2565 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(3 + 4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2566 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) + Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2567 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2568 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3 + 4) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2569 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2570 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2571 &:= ((Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) \times (4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2572 &:= (-1 - ((2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2573 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - Q(Q(3))) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2574 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2575 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + 3) - Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2576 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) - Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2577 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((Q(3) \times 4) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2578 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (Q(4) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2579 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2580 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times 3) + Q(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2581 &:= (Q((Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4))) - 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2582 &:= (-1 - (2 \times Q(3) - Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2583 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2584 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q(3 + 4)) \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2585 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(3 + 4)) \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2586 &:= ((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))))/4) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2587 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2588 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2589 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) - Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2590 &:= (((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2591 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2592 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2593 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2554 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2555 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + Q((Q(7) + (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2556 &:= (-9 \times (Q((8 + 7 + 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2557 &:= ((-9 \times ((Q(8) \times (7 + 6)) - 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2558 &:= (((-9 - (Q(8) + Q(7))) \times (Q(6) + Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2559 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2560 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2561 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2562 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) + 7) \times Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2563 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2564 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2565 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2566 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2567 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2568 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (Q(7) \times 6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2569 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2570 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 + 6) \times (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2571 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + (Q(7 + 6) + Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2572 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + (Q(6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2573 &:= (((-9 - 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2574 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2575 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times (6 - Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2576 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) + Q(((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2577 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2578 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2579 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2580 &:= (((Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) - 6)/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2581 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times (7 + 6)) \times Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2582 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + (6 \times (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2583 &:= (-9 + (8 \times Q((7 + 6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2584 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2585 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2586 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((Q(7) \times (6 + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2587 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 \times 7))) - (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2588 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times (7 - Q(6))) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2589 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2590 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2591 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2592 &:= (-9 + Q((Q((8 - 7) \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2593 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2594 &:= (Q((-1+2+(Q(3)\times 4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2595 &:= ((-1-(2+3)) + Q((Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2596 &:= ((-1\times(2+3)) + Q((Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2597 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) + (Q((Q(4)+Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2598 &:= (-1-2+Q(((Q(Q(Q(3))))/Q(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2599 &:= ((-1+2-3) + Q((Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2600 &:= (-1-((2-3)\times Q((Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2601 &:= Q((Q((-1-(2-(3+4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2602 &:= (((-1+2)^3) + Q((Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2603 &:= (-1+(2\times(Q(Q(3)) - (4-Q(5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2604 &:= (((-1+2)\times 3) + Q((Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2605 &:= ((-1+2+3) + Q((Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2606 &:= ((-1+2\times 3) + Q((Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2607 &:= (-1-2+(Q(3)+Q((Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2608 &:= (-1\times 2+(Q(3)+Q((Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2609 &:= (-1+(((2\times 3)+Q(4+5))\times(6+7+8+9))) \\
2610 &:= (Q(((-1+2)\times 3)) + Q((Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2611 &:= (-1+2+(Q(3)+Q((Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2612 &:= (-1+2-(Q(3)-(4\times(Q(Q(5))+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2613 &:= (((-1+2)\times 3)\times(Q(4+Q(5))+6+7+8+9)) \\
2614 &:= ((-1+Q(Q(2^3))) - (Q(Q(4))+Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2615 &:= ((-1\times(2+3)) + (4\times(Q(Q(5))+6+7+8+9))) \\
2616 &:= (-1-2+(Q(3)\times(Q(Q(4))+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2617 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) + Q((Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2618 &:= (-1+(2\times Q(3)+Q((Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2619 &:= (Q(((-1+2)\times 3))\times(Q(Q(4))+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2620 &:= (-1+2+(Q(3)\times(Q(Q(4))+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2621 &:= (((-1+2)^3) + (4\times(Q(Q(5))+6+7+8+9))) \\
2622 &:= (Q(Q(-1\times 2+Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2623 &:= (((-1+2)\times 3) + (4\times(Q(Q(5))+6+7+8+9))) \\
2624 &:= (-1-((2-(Q(Q(3))-4))\times(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2625 &:= (-1+(Q(2+3)+Q((Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2626 &:= (Q((-1+2\times 3)) + Q((Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2627 &:= (-1-(2\times(Q(3)\times(4-(5\times(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2628 &:= ((-1-2)\times(Q(3+4)-(Q(5)+Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2629 &:= (Q(((-1+2)\times 3)) + (4\times(Q(Q(5))+6+7+8+9))) \\
2630 &:= (-1+2+(Q(3)+(4\times(Q(Q(5))+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2631 &:= ((Q((-1+(2\times Q(3))))\times(4+5))+6+7+8+9) \\
2632 &:= (Q(Q(-1\times 2+Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5-(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2633 &:= (((((-1+2)^3) + Q(4))\times Q((5+6))) + Q((7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2594 &:= (((-9+8)\times 7) + Q((Q(6)+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2595 &:= ((-9+8\times(7+6)) + Q(5\times(4+3+2+1))) \\
2596 &:= (-9-(Q(8)-(Q(7+6)+Q(5\times(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2597 &:= ((-9+Q((Q(8)-7-6))) - (5-(4+3+2+1))) \\
2598 &:= ((-9-8+Q(Q(7))) - (Q(6)-(Q(5)\times(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2599 &:= (-9+8+(Q((Q(7)+(6-5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
2600 &:= (Q(((-9\times(8-7-6)) + 5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
2601 &:= Q((((-9+8+7)\times 6) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2602 &:= (-9+Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(7+6)\times(5+4)) - Q((3+2+1)))) \\
2603 &:= ((-9-8+Q(Q(7))) - (6-Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2604 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) + (6\times(5\times(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2605 &:= (((-9+Q(8))\times Q(7)) - (6\times(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2606 &:= (((-9+Q(8))\times Q(7)) + (6+5-Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
2607 &:= (-9+(Q((Q(8)-7-6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2608 &:= (-9-8+(7\times((6\times Q(Q(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2609 &:= (-9-8+(Q(Q(7))+Q(((6\times Q(5))/(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2610 &:= ((-9+((Q(8+7)\times 6)/5))\times(4+3+2+1)) \\
2611 &:= (Q((-9+(Q(8)+(7-6-5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2612 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (7\times(Q(6)+(5-Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2613 &:= (((-9\times 8)\times(7-Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5))-Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
2614 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) + ((6+Q(5))\times(4+3+2+1))) \\
2615 &:= (-9-8+(Q(Q(7)) + (6+Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2616 &:= (-9+((8+7+6)\times(Q(5)+Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2617 &:= (-9+(Q(Q((8-7+6))) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2618 &:= (((-9-8)\times(7-(Q(6)+(Q(5)+Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2619 &:= ((-9+8+Q(Q(7))) - (6-Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2620 &:= (((-9+(8\times Q(7))) - Q(6+5))\times(4+3+2+1)) \\
2621 &:= (-9+8+(Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6+5)+Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2622 &:= (-9-(Q(Q(8)) - (7\times(Q((Q(6)+(5-(4+3+2+1))))))) \\
2623 &:= (-9-8-(Q(Q(7))-Q((Q(Q(6))-Q((Q(5)+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2624 &:= (-9+8+(7\times((6\times Q(Q(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2625 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + ((7-6-5)\times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
2626 &:= (-9-(((Q(8)-Q(7+6))\times Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2627 &:= (-9+(Q((Q(8)-7-6)) + (Q(5)+4+3+2+1))) \\
2628 &:= ((-9-Q(8))\times(Q((7+6-5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
2629 &:= (((-9+Q(8)\times 7)\times 6) + (5-(4+3+2+1))) \\
2630 &:= ((((-9+8+Q(7))\times 6) - Q(5))\times(4+3+2+1)) \\
2631 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) - (Q(7+6)+Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2632 &:= (9-8)\times(Q(Q(7))+6+Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2633 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q(7)-Q(6+5+4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2634 &:= (-1 - 2 - (3 \times (Q(4) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2635 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(3 + 4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2636 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) + Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2637 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2638 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (Q(4) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2639 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (Q(3) + Q(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2640 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + Q(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2641 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times ((4 \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2642 &:= (-1 - (((2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (4 - Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2643 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2644 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2645 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 \times 3)) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2646 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) + (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2647 &:= (((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))/4) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2648 &:= ((-1 + Q((Q(2 \times 3) + Q(4)))) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2649 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2650 &:= (Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) + Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2651 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2652 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q((3 - (4 - 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2653 &:= (((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) \times (Q(4) - 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2654 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2655 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(3 + 4))) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2656 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2657 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2658 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + Q(4)) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2659 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2660 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2661 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2662 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2663 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2664 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2665 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3 + Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2666 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2667 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((Q(3) \times 4) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2668 &:= ((-1 + Q((Q(2 \times 3) + Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2669 &:= (Q((Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + Q(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2670 &:= (-1 - 2 - (3 \times (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2671 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2672 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - ((4 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2673 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((Q(Q(3)))/(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2634 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2635 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (((7 - Q(6)) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2636 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2637 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2638 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2639 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (Q(7 + 6) - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2640 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7) - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2641 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2642 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) - 7 - 6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2643 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - Q((Q(7) - (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2644 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2645 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2646 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2647 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(7 + 6) - Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2648 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2649 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2650 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2651 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8 + 7) + (Q(6) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2652 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7 + 6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2653 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q((Q(7) - (6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2654 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - (Q(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2655 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + 7) - ((6 + Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2656 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2657 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6 + Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2658 &:= (-9 + (((8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2659 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) - (6 \times (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2660 &:= (Q((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2661 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2662 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times Q(7)) - ((6 - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2663 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2664 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) \times (7 \times 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2665 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q((Q(7) + (6 + 5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2666 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + 6))) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2667 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) - 7 - 6))) - (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2668 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 \times (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2669 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2670 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + 7 \times 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2671 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 + 6) \times Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2672 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) \times (6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2673 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q(((7 \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2674 &:= (-1+2-(3 \times (4+5-Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2675 &:= ((-1+2+Q((Q(Q(3))-4+Q(5))))-(6+7+8+9)) \\
2676 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2) \times (3+4)))-(Q(Q(5))-Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2677 &:= ((-1+2+Q(Q(3+4)))-(Q(Q(5))-Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2678 &:= (-1+(Q((Q(2 \times 3)+Q(4)))+(5-(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2679 &:= (-1-2+(Q(Q(3))+Q((Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2680 &:= (-1 \times 2+(Q(Q(3))+Q((Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2681 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(3)))+(Q((Q(4)+Q(5)))+Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2682 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))+Q((Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2683 &:= (-1+2+(Q(Q(3))+Q((Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2684 &:= ((-1+2+3) \times (Q(4)+(Q(Q(5))+6+7+8+9))) \\
2685 &:= (((-1+2)^3)-4) \times (5-Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
2686 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3))+(Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2687 &:= (((-1 \times 2+Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4)))-(5-Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2688 &:= ((-1-2) \times ((3-(4-5))-Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2689 &:= (-1+2-(Q(Q(3))+(Q(Q(4))-Q(Q(5)+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2690 &:= (((-1-2+Q(3+Q(4))) \times 5)+Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
2691 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3+((4-5) \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2692 &:= (-1-2+((Q(Q(3))-4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2693 &:= (-1 \times 2+((Q(Q(3))-4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2694 &:= ((-1-2) \times (((3+4)-5)-Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2695 &:= ((Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))-4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2696 &:= (-1+2+((Q(Q(3))-4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2697 &:= ((-1-2) \times ((Q(Q(Q(3)))/Q(Q(4+5)))-Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2698 &:= (-1 \times 2+((Q(3)+Q(4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2699 &:= (-1-(((2 \times 3)-4-5) \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2700 &:= ((-1-((2+3)-4-5)) \times Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
2701 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(3)))+(Q((Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2702 &:= (-1+2-((Q(Q(3)) \times 4)-Q(Q(5)+6+7+8+9))) \\
2703 &:= (-1+Q((2+(Q(Q(3)))+(4-(5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2704 &:= Q((((-1+2)^3)+(Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2705 &:= ((Q((-1+((2+3) \times 4))) \times 5)+Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
2706 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2 \times 3)))+(Q(Q(4))+Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2707 &:= ((-1+(2 \times Q(((3 \times 4)+Q(5)))))-(6+7+8+9)) \\
2708 &:= (((-1-(2 \times 3)) \times Q(Q(4)))+(5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2709 &:= ((-1-2) \times ((3 \times (4-5))-Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2710 &:= (((-1+2+Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4)))+(5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2711 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(3+4)))+(Q(Q(5))-(6+7+8+9))) \\
2712 &:= ((-1+2-Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4))-(Q(Q(5))-(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2713 &:= (-1-(2 \times (3-(Q((4 \times (5+6)))-Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
2674 &:= (((-9+Q(8)) \times Q(7))-(6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2675 &:= (-9+(Q(8)+(Q(Q(7))-(6-Q(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2676 &:= ((-9-(8+7))-(Q(6) \times (Q(5)-Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2677 &:= (-9+(Q(8)+(Q(Q(7))+(Q(6+5)+Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2678 &:= (-9 \times 8+((Q(7)+6) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2679 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7)))+(6 \times Q(Q(5))/(4+3+2+1))) \\
2680 &:= ((-9+Q(8+7))-(Q(6)-Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2681 &:= ((-9+((8+7) \times (Q(6) \times 5)))-(4+3+2+1)) \\
2682 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8)))-(7^{6 \times 5/(4+3+2+1)})) \\
2683 &:= (-9+((8 \times Q(7+6+5))+Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
2684 &:= (Q((Q((-9+8+7))+Q(6)))-Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2685 &:= ((-9-(Q(8)-(7 \times Q(6)))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2686 &:= ((-9+Q((8 \times 7)))-Q(6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2687 &:= (-9+(Q(8)+(Q(Q(7))+(6+Q(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2688 &:= (-9+Q(Q(8))-(Q(7)+(6 \times Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2689 &:= ((-9 \times ((8+7)-Q(6)))+Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2690 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8)))-(((7+6) \times Q(5))+4+3+2+1)) \\
2691 &:= (Q((-9+8+(Q(7)+6)))-Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2692 &:= (-9+8-7-(Q(6) \times (Q(5)-Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2693 &:= (-9+Q(Q(8))-(Q(7+6)+Q((Q(5)+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2694 &:= (-9+((Q(8) \times (7 \times 6))+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2695 &:= (-9+Q(((8-7)+(Q(6)+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2696 &:= (((-9+Q(8)) \times Q(7))+(6+5-(4+3+2+1))) \\
2697 &:= (-9+(Q((Q(8)-7-6))+(5+Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2698 &:= (((-9+Q(8)) \times Q(7))+((6 \times 5)/(4+3+2+1))) \\
2699 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8))-(((Q(7)+Q(Q(6))) \times 5)-Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2700 &:= ((-9+(8+7+6)) \times Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2701 &:= (Q((-9+(Q(8)+(7-6-5))))+Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
2702 &:= (((-9-Q(8)) \times Q(7))-(Q((Q(6)+Q(5)))-Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2703 &:= (-9+8+Q((Q(7)+((6 \times 5)/(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2704 &:= (((-9+Q(8)) \times Q(7))-(6-(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2705 &:= (-9+(Q(8)+(Q(7)+Q((Q(6)+5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2706 &:= ((-9+8+7)-(Q(6) \times (Q(5)-Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2707 &:= (-9-(Q(8)+((Q((Q(7)+Q(6)))-5)-Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2708 &:= (-9-8+(Q(Q(7))+Q(((Q(6) \times 5)/(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2709 &:= (-9 \times (8-((Q(7) \times 6)+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2710 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8))+(7 \times Q(6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
2711 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))-(Q(7+6+5)-(4+3+2+1))) \\
2712 &:= (-9+(Q(8)+(Q(Q(7))+(6+(Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2713 &:= (((-9+Q(8)) \times Q(7))+((Q(6) \times 5)/(4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2714 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (3 - 4)) \times (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2715 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((3 - 4) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2716 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2717 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2718 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - 4 - 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2719 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) + (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2720 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2721 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + Q(3)) + Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2722 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2723 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + (Q(4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2724 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2725 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2726 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2727 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2728 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2729 &:= (Q((Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + Q(4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2730 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2731 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((Q(3) - (4 \times Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2732 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2733 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (Q(4) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2734 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + (Q(3 + 4) + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2735 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - (4 + Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2736 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - (Q(4) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2737 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((3 \times 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2738 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2 \times 3) + Q(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2739 &:= (Q((Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + Q(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2740 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2741 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2742 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2743 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + 3) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2744 &:= (Q(((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2745 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2746 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) + Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2747 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(((3 \times Q(4)) - 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2748 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2749 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) \times ((Q(4) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2750 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3 + 4)) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2751 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - (4 \times 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2752 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - (Q((4 + (5 + 6))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2753 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2714 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + ((Q(6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2715 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) + (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2716 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2717 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2718 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2719 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((Q(7) \times 6) + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2720 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - ((7 + 6) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2721 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((Q(7) \times 6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2722 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 + 6) \times (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2723 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - Q(6))) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2724 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7 + 6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2725 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2726 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + (Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2727 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q((Q(7) + 6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2728 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q((Q(7) + 6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2729 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (7 \times 6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2730 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2731 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2732 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) - (Q(6) \times (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2733 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((Q(7) + 6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2734 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2735 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) - (7 - Q(6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2736 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - Q(((Q(7) + Q(6 + 5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2737 &:= ((-9 \times ((Q(8) \times (7 + 6)) - Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2738 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (7 + Q(6))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2739 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - (6 - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2740 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) + 6) \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2741 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times (Q(6) + Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2742 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))/5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2743 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q((Q(7) - (6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2744 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2745 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2746 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2747 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2748 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) - (Q(6) \times (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2749 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) + (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2750 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7) + (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2751 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7 + 6) + (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2752 &:= (-9 + (Q(8 + 7) + (Q(6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2753 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 + 6) \times Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2754 &:= ((-1-2) \times ((3+4) - (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2755 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2^3) \times (4 + Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2756 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + Q(((4 \times 5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2757 &:= (-1-2 + (3 \times ((4 \times 5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2758 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times ((4 \times 5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2759 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (Q(3) + Q(4+5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2760 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) \times Q(Q(4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2761 &:= (((-1-2 + Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2762 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + Q((Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2763 &:= ((-1 - (2+3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2764 &:= (-1 + (((2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2765 &:= ((-1 + ((2+3) \times Q(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2766 &:= (((-1-2) \times Q(Q(3))) - (Q(4) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2767 &:= (-1+2-3 - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2768 &:= (-1 + ((2-3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2769 &:= (Q(Q(Q(Q(Q(Q(Q(-1-2+3))))))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2770 &:= (((Q((-1 + Q(2+3))) - Q(4)) \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2771 &:= (Q((-1-2 + Q(3+4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2772 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2773 &:= ((-1+2+3) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2774 &:= (Q((Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) + 4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2775 &:= (Q((-1+2 \times 3)) \times (Q(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2776 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2777 &:= (Q(Q((-1-2 + Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2778 &:= (Q(((-1+2) \times 3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2779 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2780 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2781 &:= ((-1-2) \times ((3 \times (Q(4) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2782 &:= (((-1+2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))))/5) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
2783 &:= (-1 + (((2 - (3+4)) + Q((5+6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2784 &:= (Q((Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) + 4)) + (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2785 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2786 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2787 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((Q(3) + 4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2788 &:= (-1+2 + (3 \times (4 + (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2789 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times Q(3+4)) - 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2790 &:= ((-1+2 + Q(3)) \times (4 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2791 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + (4 \times (Q((5+6)) + Q((7+8+9)))) \\
2792 &:= (-1 + ((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2793 &:= ((-1 + Q(2+3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2754 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (Q(7+6+5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2755 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) + (Q(6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2756 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((Q(7) + Q(Q(6)))/(5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2757 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) - (6 - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2758 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 \times 6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2759 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 \times Q(Q(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2760 &:= ((-9 - ((8+7) \times (6 - Q(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
2761 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7+6) - (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2762 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7+6) + (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2763 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (((7+6) \times Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2764 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times (Q(6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2765 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7-6 + Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2766 &:= (-9 - (Q((8 + (7 \times (6+5)))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2767 &:= (((-9+8 \times 7) \times (Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
2768 &:= (Q((-9+8 + Q(7))) - (Q(6) - (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2769 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + Q(6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2770 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + Q(6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2771 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 - (Q(6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2772 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) + 7) \times Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2773 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2774 &:= ((-9+8 + Q((Q(7) + 6))) - (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2775 &:= (Q((-9+8 \times (7+6))) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2776 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7-6) - (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2777 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((Q(7) \times 6) + Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2778 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 \times Q(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2779 &:= (-9+8 - ((Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) - 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2780 &:= ((-9+8) \times ((Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) - 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2781 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7+6) - (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2782 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (Q(7+6) + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
2783 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) + 6))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2784 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - (6+5 - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
2785 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2786 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) - (6 \times Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2787 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7+6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2788 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q((Q(7) - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2789 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2790 &:= (9+8 + Q(7+6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1) \\
2791 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - Q(Q((7 - (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2792 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2793 &:= (-9+8 + ((Q(7) \times 6) + Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2794 &:= (((-1-2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - 4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2795 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (Q((4 \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2796 &:= ((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2797 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(((3 \times 4) + Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2798 &:= (((-1-2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2799 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2800 &:= ((-1 + Q((2+3+4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2801 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - (Q(4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2802 &:= ((-1 - (2+3)) - ((4 - Q((5+6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2803 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2804 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(3+4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2805 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times Q(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2806 &:= (-1-2+Q((3+((4 \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2807 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2808 &:= (-1 + Q(((2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))/Q(4+5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2809 &:= Q((-1 + ((2 \times (3 + (4+5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2810 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2811 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) - ((4 - Q((5+6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2812 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q((Q(4) + 5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2813 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(3+4))) + (Q((5+6)) + Q((7+8+9)))) \\
2814 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3 - (Q(4) + (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2815 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + Q(3))) \times Q(4)) - (5 - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2816 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2817 &:= (Q(Q((-1-2+Q(3)))) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2818 &:= (-1 - (Q((Q(2+3) + Q(4))) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2819 &:= (-1 \times (Q((Q(2+3) + Q(4))) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2820 &:= (((-1 - (2+3)) + (4 \times Q(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
2821 &:= (Q((Q((-1 + Q(2+3)))/Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2822 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - (4 \times 5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
2823 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times (Q(4) + (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2824 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2 \times 3) + 4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2825 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2+3) + Q(4)))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2826 &:= (((-1 - (2+3)) \times (4 - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
2827 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) \times Q(Q(4))) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2828 &:= (-1 - (Q((2 \times (3+4))) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2829 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 \times (3+4))) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2830 &:= (((Q((-1 + Q(2+3))) - Q(4)) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9) \\
2831 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2832 &:= (1+2) \times (Q(3+4) - 5 + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
2833 &:= (Q(1 \times 2^3) - Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2794 &:= (Q((-9 + ((8 \times 7) + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2795 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) + (7 + 6 - Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2796 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (6 \times (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2797 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 + (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2798 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (6 - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2799 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 + Q(7)))) - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2800 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - Q(((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2801 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 - 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2802 &:= ((-9 + ((Q(8) + 7) \times (Q(6) + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2803 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2804 &:= (Q((-9 + ((8 \times 7) + 6))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2805 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2806 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2807 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) \times (7 - (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2808 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 \times (Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2809 &:= Q((-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2810 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (6 + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2811 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) - (7 \times Q(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2812 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(7) + Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2813 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + 6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2814 &:= (Q((-9 + ((8 \times 7) + 6))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2815 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + 7 + 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2816 &:= (Q((((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (Q(6) + Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2817 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) - 7 - 6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2818 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q((7 + 6 \times 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2819 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 - 7 + (Q(6) + Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2820 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2821 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2822 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2823 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (6 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2824 &:= (Q((-9 + ((8 \times 7) + 6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2825 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2826 &:= (-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2827 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times (Q(6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2828 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2829 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2830 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2831 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + 7) \times ((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2832 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q((7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2833 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) - (Q(6) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2834 &:= (-1 + (Q((2+3+4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2835 &:= Q(1 \times 2+3+4) \times (5+6+7+8+9) \\
2836 &:= 1 + Q(2+3+4) \times (5+6+7+8+9) \\
2837 &:= (-1+2 + (Q((Q(3+4) - 5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2838 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2839 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
2840 &:= (((-1+2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
2841 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2842 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2843 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2844 &:= (Q((Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) + 4)) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
2845 &:= (((-1 + Q((2 \times (3 \times 4)))) \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2846 &:= ((Q(Q(-1+2+3)) \times (Q(4) - 5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\
2847 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + Q(4)) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2848 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + Q(4)) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2849 &:= (-1 - (((2+3) - (4 \times Q(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2850 &:= (-1 + (((2 + Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2851 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + Q(4)) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2852 &:= (-1 + (((2 + Q(Q(3))) \times Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2853 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q((Q(3) + 4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2854 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2855 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2+3)) - Q((4 + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2856 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2+3)) - Q((4 + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2857 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + Q((Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2858 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2859 &:= (((-1 - 2 - Q(Q(Q(3))))/4) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2860 &:= (((-1 + 2 - Q(Q(Q(3))))/4) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2861 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) - (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2862 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2863 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (3^4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2864 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(3+4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2865 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\
2866 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (4 + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2867 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
2868 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 \times 4)) + (Q((5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
2869 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2870 &:= (1 + Q(2+3+4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9) \\
2871 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2+3+4)))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2872 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2873 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (4 + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2834 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7+6+5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2835 &:= (-9 \times (((8+7) - Q(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2836 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(((7 \times 6) - Q(5))) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
2837 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (7 + (Q(6) \times (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2838 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - (Q(6) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2839 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (Q(7+6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2840 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6) + (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2841 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + Q(6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2842 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 \times 6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2843 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) - (6 + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2844 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2845 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7+6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2846 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) + ((6 \times 5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2847 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2848 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 \times (6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
2849 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7+6) + Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
2850 &:= ((-9 - (8+7+6)) \times (5 - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
2851 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7+6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2852 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7+6) \times Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2853 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7+6) \times Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2854 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7+6+5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2855 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + (6 - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2856 &:= ((-9 - (8+7)) \times (6 - (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2857 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times Q(7)) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2858 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 \times 6) + (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2859 &:= (((-9 + Q(8) \times 7) \times 6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2860 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (((7+6) \times 5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
2861 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7+6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2862 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - Q((Q(((7-6) \times 5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2863 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7+6) \times Q(5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2864 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(6) - (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2865 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) + (6+5 + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2866 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 \times 7))) - (Q(6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2867 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2868 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2869 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2870 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 + (Q(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2871 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7+6) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2872 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (Q(7) \times (Q(6) + Q(5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
2873 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(((7 \times 6) - Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2874 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2875 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(3 + 4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2876 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2877 &:= (((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) \times (4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2878 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3 + 4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2879 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2880 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2881 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times Q(4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2882 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q((3 \times 4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2883 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(3 + 4) + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2884 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(3 + 4) + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2885 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times (3 \times (4 + 5)))))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2886 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2887 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(3 + 4) + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2888 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((3^4) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2889 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 \times (4 - Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2890 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) + Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2891 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2892 &:= (Q((-1 - ((2 - (3 + 4)) \times (5 + 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2893 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (3 \times 4)) + (Q((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2894 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (Q(4) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
2895 &:= (((-1 + Q(((2 + 3) \times 4))) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2896 &:= (-1 - ((2^{3+4}) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2897 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{3+4}) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2898 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + Q(Q(4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2899 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times Q((4 \times 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2900 &:= (((-1 + Q((2 + 3 + 4))) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2901 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4))) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2902 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4))) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2903 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2 + 3) - 4) \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2904 &:= (-1 - 2 - (3 \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2905 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2 + 3) + Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2906 &:= ((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))))/4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2907 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 - (4 \times Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2908 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2909 &:= (-1 + ((Q((2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2910 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2911 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 - (4 \times Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2912 &:= (-1 + (((2 - Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2913 &:= (-1 - 2 + Q((3 + (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2874 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (6 \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2875 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 + 6 - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2876 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) + Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2877 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (Q((Q(6) + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2878 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2879 &:= (-9 + (8 \times Q((Q(7) + (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
2880 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2881 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + 6))) - (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2882 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (7 \times (6 - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2883 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2884 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2885 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2886 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2887 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) - (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2888 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) \times (Q(6) + Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2889 &:= (-9 \times (Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2890 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7) + (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2891 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7 + 6) - (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2892 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q((8 - 7 + 6))) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2893 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) - (Q(6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2894 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (6 - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2895 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2896 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 \times 7))) - (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2897 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2898 &:= (-9 + ((8 + Q(7)) \times (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2899 &:= (-9 - 8 + Q((Q((7 + 6 - 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2900 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7)))/6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2901 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2902 &:= (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) - Q((6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2903 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2904 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (7 \times 6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2905 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 + 6 - Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2906 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 \times 7))) - (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2907 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 + 6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2908 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 + 6) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2909 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 - 7 + (Q(6) + Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2910 &:= (((-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) + Q(Q(6)))) \times 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2911 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + (7 - 6)))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2912 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (((7 + Q(6)) \times Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2913 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + 6 - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2914 &:= (-1 \times 2 + Q((3 + (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2915 &:= (-1 + Q(((2 \times (3 + (4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2916 &:= Q((-1 + (((2 + 3) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2917 &:= (-1 + 2 + Q((3 + (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2918 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (Q(4) + (Q((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2919 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2920 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (4 \times (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2921 &:= (((-1 - Q(2 + 3)) \times 4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2922 &:= (((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2923 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((3^4) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2924 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2925 &:= (Q((Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + (4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2926 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q(3 + 4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2927 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3 + 4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2928 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2929 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2930 &:= (((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + Q(4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2931 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q((Q(4) - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2932 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2933 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - ((4 \times (5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2934 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2935 &:= (((-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + Q(Q(4)))) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2936 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2937 &:= (((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) \times (4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2938 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2939 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q((Q(3) - (4 - 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2940 &:= ((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2941 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2942 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2943 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2944 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2945 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times (3 \times (4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2946 &:= ((Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) \times Q(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2947 &:= (((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))/4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2948 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2949 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (4 + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2950 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (3^4)) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2951 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2952 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3 + 4) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2953 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) \times 4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2914 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2915 &:= (-9 + 8 + Q((Q((7 + 6 - 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2916 &:= Q((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2917 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 + 6 - 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2918 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times (Q(6) + Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2919 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q((Q(7) + 6))) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2920 &:= ((-9 - Q(8)) \times ((7 - 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2921 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 - 6 - 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2922 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2923 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + 6))) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2924 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2925 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) - (7 \times 6)) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2926 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2927 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times Q(7)) + ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2928 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2929 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 - 6 - 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2930 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times 6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2931 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + 6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2932 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + 7 + 6)) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2933 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 + 6 - 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2934 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (Q(7 + 6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2935 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) + (Q(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2936 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2937 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q((Q(7) + 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2938 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2939 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + ((Q(6) + Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2940 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2941 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 + (Q(6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2942 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2943 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 + 6 + 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2944 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7 + 6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2945 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) - 7 - 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2946 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) - (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2947 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 - Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2948 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 \times (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2949 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q((Q(7) + 6)) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2950 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (Q(7) - (6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2951 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q((7 + 6 - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2952 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2953 &:= (-9 \times 8 + Q((((7 + 6) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2954 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2+3)) + (4 \times (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2955 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2956 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2957 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4) + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2958 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4) + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2959 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(3+4))) + (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2960 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((3 \times Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2961 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2962 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - ((4 + (5+6)) - Q((7+8+9)))) \\
2963 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3) \times Q(Q(4))) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2964 &:= (((-1 - (2+3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2965 &:= (-1 + (((2 + Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2966 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) + (Q((4 + Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2967 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2968 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 + Q(4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2969 &:= (-1 + ((2 + Q(3)) \times ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2970 &:= (1 + 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) + 4+5 + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
2971 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q((Q(3+4) - 5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
2972 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) + 4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2973 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) + 4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2974 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3+4)) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2975 &:= ((Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) + 4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2976 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) + 4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2977 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3+4) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2978 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 \times Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2979 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2980 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2981 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (4 \times (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2982 &:= (1 + 2) \times (Q(3+4+Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2983 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+3) + (Q(4) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2984 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+3) + (Q(4) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2985 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 \times 3) + (4 - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2986 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) + 4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2987 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) \times (Q(4) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2988 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (Q(4+5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2989 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 \times 4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2990 &:= (((Q((-1 + Q(2+3))) + Q(4)) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9) \\
2991 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3+4))) - (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
2992 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - (4 \times (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2993 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3+4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2954 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (6 \times (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2955 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) + 6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2956 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + (Q(6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2957 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q((Q(7) + 6)) - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2958 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 \times (6+5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2959 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q((Q(7) - (6 \times 5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2960 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7+6) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2961 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - Q(((7+6+5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2962 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2963 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) - (6+5+Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2964 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) - ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2965 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) + ((6+Q(5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
2966 &:= (Q((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7+6)))) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2967 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2968 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 \times 6) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2969 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7+6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2970 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(7+6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2971 &:= ((-9 \times ((Q(8) + 7) \times (6+5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
2972 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q((7 \times 6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
2973 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) - ((6-5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2974 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q((Q(7) + 6))) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2975 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) + (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2976 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - Q((7 \times (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2977 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) - (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2978 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) \times (Q(6) + Q(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2979 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 + Q(7)))) - (Q(6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2980 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7+6) \times Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2981 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 - (Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2982 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((Q(7) \times (Q(6) + Q(5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
2983 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((Q(7) + (6 - Q(5))) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
2984 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) - (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2985 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) + (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2986 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) + Q((Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2987 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (Q((Q(6) + 5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
2988 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7+6 - (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2989 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - Q((7 - (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2990 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (((7+6) \times 5) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
2991 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (Q(7) - (6+5))) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
2992 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + ((6 \times 5) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
2993 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) + 6))) - (5+4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2994 &:= ((-1 + Q((Q(2^3) - 4 - 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2995 &:= (Q((-1 - (Q(2 + 3) - Q(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2996 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2997 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2998 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2999 &:= 1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3000 &:= (Q((Q(Q(-1 + 2) \times 3)) - Q(4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3001 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3002 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3)) + (4 + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3003 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) - (Q(4) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3004 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3005 &:= ((-1 \times ((2 + 3) \times 4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3006 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3007 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - (Q(4) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3008 &:= (-1 + ((2 - 3) \times (Q(4) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3009 &:= (Q((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (4 \times (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3010 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3011 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3 + 4))) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3012 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (Q(4) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3013 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) - (Q(4) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3014 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) \times (Q(4) - Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3015 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3 + 4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3016 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3017 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3018 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (Q(4) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3019 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (3 + 4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3020 &:= ((Q((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + 4))) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3021 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3 + 4))) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3022 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) - (4 - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3023 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3) - Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3024 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) - Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3025 &:= Q((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3026 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{Q(Q(3+4))}) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3027 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (3 - 4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3028 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3029 &:= ((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3030 &:= ((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3031 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3))/4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3032 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2994 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2995 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2996 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
2997 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2998 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2999 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) + (6 - Q(5))) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3000 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7 + 6)) \times (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3001 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + Q((6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3002 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times (6 + 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3003 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + 6 - (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3004 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - (Q(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3005 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 + Q(Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3006 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + ((6 \times 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3007 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 + 6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3008 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((Q(7) + Q(6 + 5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3009 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q((Q(7) + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3010 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3011 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3012 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 - ((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3013 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) + 6))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3014 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (7 \times Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3015 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3016 &:= (-9 + Q(((8 \times 7) - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3017 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 + 6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3018 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 \times (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3019 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3020 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 - 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3021 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + Q(7))) + (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3022 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 - ((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3023 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3024 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 - 6)^{54321})) \\
3025 &:= Q((-9 + 8 - (Q(7 + 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3026 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 - 6)^{54321})) \\
3027 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 + 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3028 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times (Q(6) + Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3029 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q((Q(7) + 6))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3030 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3031 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3032 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3033 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3034 &:= (Q(((-1 - 2) \times (3 - 4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3035 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3036 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3037 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - (4 - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3038 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3039 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (Q(4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3040 &:= (-1 - ((2 - 3) \times (Q(4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3041 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q(((Q(Q(3)))/(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3042 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3043 &:= 1 + 2 \times Q(Q(Q(3))/(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3044 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3045 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + (4 + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3046 &:= (Q(((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3)))/Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3047 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3048 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3049 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - 4)) \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3050 &:= (Q((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3051 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
3052 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3053 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3054 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3055 &:= (Q((-1 - (Q(2 + 3) - Q(4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3056 &:= (Q(Q(((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3057 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3058 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
3059 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) + Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3060 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3061 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3)))/Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3062 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
3063 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + 4) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
3064 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(4) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3065 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + (Q(4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3066 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((3 \times (Q(4) + 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3067 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((3 \times (Q(4) + 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3068 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + ((4 - 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3069 &:= (Q((-1 + Q((2 - (3 - 4 - 5)))))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3070 &:= ((((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) - Q(4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3071 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3 + 4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3072 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3 + 4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3033 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 + 6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3034 &:= (Q((-9 + ((8 \times 7) + 6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3035 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 - (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3036 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3037 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 \times 7))) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3038 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3039 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3040 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3041 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3042 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((Q(7) + Q(6 + 5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3043 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + 6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3044 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 - Q(6)) \times (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3045 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7 + 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3046 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 - (Q(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3047 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 + 6 - (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3048 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 \times (6 + 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3049 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - (Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3050 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8) + 7) - Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3051 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3052 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3053 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3054 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (6 \times (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3055 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3056 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (7 - Q((6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3057 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7 + Q(6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3058 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3059 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q((Q(7) + 6)) + (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3060 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (((7 + 6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3061 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q((7 - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3062 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 + 6 - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3063 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q(7) - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3064 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) - ((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3065 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3066 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3067 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (7 - ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3068 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(6) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3069 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3070 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3071 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3072 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 \times 6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3073 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3074 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2 + Q(3)) \times 4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3075 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3 + 4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3076 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + Q(((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3077 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3078 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3079 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (4 \times (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3080 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q(Q(3))) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3081 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3082 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (4 \times (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3083 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times 4) + ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3084 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(3 + 4))) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3085 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(3) + Q(4)))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3086 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q(3)) \times Q((Q(4) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3087 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3088 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (Q(4) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3089 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3090 &:= (1 \times 2 \times Q(3 + 4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3091 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times 4) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3092 &:= ((-1 - 2 + ((Q(3) - 4) \times Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3093 &:= 1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) - Q(4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3094 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3 + 4)) \times Q(Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3095 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3 + 4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3096 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((Q(3) - 4) \times Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3097 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((Q(Q(3)) \times 4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3098 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + ((4 + Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3099 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) \times ((4^5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3100 &:= (((-1 + Q(((2 + 3) + Q(4)))) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3101 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - ((4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3102 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - (4 - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3103 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (4 - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3104 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(3 + 4))) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3105 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + 3 + 4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3106 &:= (Q((-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) - Q(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3107 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3^4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3108 &:= ((-1 - 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3109 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times (Q(3 + 4) - Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3110 &:= ((-1 - (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - 4)) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3111 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (4 + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3112 &:= (-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3073 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3074 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q((7 \times (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3075 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3076 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 \times 7))) - (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3077 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (Q((Q(6) + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3078 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (((7 \times 6) + 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3079 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((7 + 6 - 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3080 &:= ((-9 - 8 + ((7 + 6) \times Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3081 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7 + 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3082 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3083 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3084 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + ((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3085 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3086 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3087 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) - (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3088 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3089 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q(((7 + 6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3090 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 + 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3091 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q(7) + (6 - 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3092 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times (6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3093 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + ((6 + Q(5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3094 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7) - (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3095 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3096 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) \times (Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3097 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) - Q((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3098 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) \times ((6 \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3099 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((7 + 6 - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3100 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (((7 + 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3101 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) - (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3102 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3103 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) + 6))) - (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3104 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3105 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3106 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 \times 7))) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3107 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 + 6 + 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3108 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3109 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 + Q(7)))) - (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3110 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) \times ((7 - 6) \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3111 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3112 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times (6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$3113 := (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3114 := ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3115 := (((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (4 + Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3116 := ((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3117 := (((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times Q((Q(4) + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3118 := (-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3119 := (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3120 := (((-1 + Q((2 + Q(3 + 4)))) / Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3121 := (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times 4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3122 := (-1 + ((2 \times Q(3 + 4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3123 := (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3124 := ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3125 := (Q(((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q(4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3126 := (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3127 := (((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) \times Q(Q(4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3128 := (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - Q((4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3129 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + (4 + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3130 := ((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3131 := (Q(((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3132 := ((-1 + 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3133 := (-1 - 2 + Q(((3^4) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3134 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(3 + 4))) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3135 := (-1 + Q((Q(2 + 3) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3136 := Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3137 := (-1 + 2 + Q(((3^4) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3138 := ((((-1 + 2 - (3 + 4)) + Q(Q(5))) \times 6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3139 := (-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3140 := ((-1 - 2 - Q((Q(3) + Q(4)))) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3141 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3142 := (((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4)))) \times (5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3143 := (-1 - (((2 - (3 \times 4)) - Q((5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3144 := (-1 - ((Q(Q(2 + 3)) + 4) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3145 := (((-1 + Q(2 + Q(3))) \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3146 := (Q(((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3147 := (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3 + 4) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3148 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3149 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3150 := ((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + Q(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3151 := (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3152 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3113 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + 6 - (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3114 := (-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3115 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + (Q(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$3116 := ((-9 + Q((8 \times 7))) - (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3117 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 + 6 - 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3118 := (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3119 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3120 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (((7 - 6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3121 := (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + (7 - 6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3122 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3123 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 \times (Q(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$3124 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + (6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3125 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3126 := ((-9 + Q((8 \times 7))) - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3127 := (-9 - (8 \times (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3128 := (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3129 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 - 6 - 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3130 := ((-9 + Q((8 + Q(7)))) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3131 := (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$3132 := (-9 \times ((8 + Q(7 + 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3133 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 + 6 - 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3134 := (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$3135 := ((-9 + Q(8)) \times ((7 \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3136 := (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3137 := (-9 + (Q((Q(8) - (7 + 6 - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3138 := (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$3139 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - Q((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$3140 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 \times Q(6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3141 := (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + 6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3142 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 \times Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3143 := (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7 + 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3144 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + 6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3145 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 + 6 - Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3146 := (Q(((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + Q(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$3147 := (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + ((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3148 := (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3149 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3150 := (((-9 + Q(8 + 7)) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3151 := (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + (7 - 6)))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$3152 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 \times Q(6)) - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3153 := (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q((3!))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$3154 := (-1 - (((2 - (3 + 4)) \times Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3155 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3 + 4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3156 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3157 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3158 := ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3159 := (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3160 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3161 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3162 := 1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3163 := 1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) - 4 \times Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3164 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(((3^4) - Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3165 := (-1 + (Q((Q((2 + 3 + 4)) - Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3166 := (Q((-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) - Q(4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3167 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(((3^4) - Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3168 := ((-1 - 2) \times (Q((Q(3) + 4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3169 := ((-1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3170 := (((-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + Q(4))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3171 := (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3 + Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3172 := ((((-1 \times 2) - Q(Q(3))) \times Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3173 := ((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times Q(Q((Q(4) - (5 + 6)))))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3174 := (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times (4 + Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3175 := ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - ((4 \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3176 := ((-1 - 2 + Q((3 \times Q(4)))) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3177 := (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3178 := (-1 \times 2 + (((3^4) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3179 := (-1 + ((Q(2 + 3) + Q(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3180 := ((Q((-1 + 2 \times 3)) + Q(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3181 := (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3)))/4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3182 := ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3183 := ((-1 \times 2) - ((3 + 4) \times (Q((5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3184 := ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (Q(4) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3185 := (((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3186 := ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3187 := (-1 - (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$3188 := (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$3189 := (Q(((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3190 := (((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3)))) \times (4 \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3191 := (Q(Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)))) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3192 := ((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3153 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + Q((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$3154 := ((-9 + Q((8 + Q(7)))) - (Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3155 := (((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7) + 6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3156 := ((-9 + 8 + 7) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3157 := ((-9 + Q((8 \times 7))) - (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3158 := (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$3159 := (-9 \times (((8 - Q(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3160 := ((-9 + ((Q(8) + (7 - 6)) \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3161 := (-9 - ((8 - ((7 + 6) \times Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3162 := ((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3163 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) - (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3164 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3165 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) + (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3166 := (-9 - ((8 - 7 - 6) \times (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3167 := (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7 + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3168 := ((-9 \times 8) \times (7 - (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3169 := (-9 + (((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times 6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3170 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3171 := (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$3172 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3173 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) - ((6 - 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3174 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$3175 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3176 := (-9 - (Q(8) - Q(((7 \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3177 := (-9 \times 8 + Q(((7 \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3178 := (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3179 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3180 := (((-9 + Q(8) \times 7) - Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3181 := ((-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q(7) + (6 - 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3182 := (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$3183 := ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + Q((6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$3184 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3185 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3186 := ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times ((6 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3187 := ((-9 \times (8 - Q((Q(7) - (6 \times 5)))))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$3188 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - ((Q(6) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3189 := ((-9 + Q((8 + Q(7)))) - (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3190 := ((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3191 := (-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q(7) + (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$3192 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 \times 6) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3193 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q((Q(3) + (4 - 5)))))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3194 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3195 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3+4+5})) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3196 &:= (Q((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3)))/(4 + 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3197 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q((Q(3) + (4 - 5)))))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3198 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3199 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q((Q(3) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3200 &:= (-1 + ((2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3201 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)))) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3202 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3203 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3204 &:= ((Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times (4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3205 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3206 &:= ((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))))/4) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3207 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - (4 + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3208 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - (4 + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3209 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times 4) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3210 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (Q(3 + 4) + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3211 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3^4) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3212 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3213 &:= ((-1 + Q(2^3)) \times (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3214 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + 3) - ((Q(Q(4)) - Q((5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3215 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3216 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3217 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3218 &:= ((-1 + Q((Q(2 \times 3) - (4 - Q(5)))))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3219 &:= (Q((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + (Q(4) + Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3220 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3221 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)))) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3222 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - ((5 + 6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3223 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + (4 - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3224 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 \times (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3225 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3226 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 \times 3))) + Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3227 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((3 \times Q(4))) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3228 &:= (((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4) + Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3229 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3+4}) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3230 &:= (((-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + Q(4))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3231 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3232 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3193 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3194 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (Q((6 \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3195 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) + (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3196 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) - ((6 - Q(5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3197 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) - (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3198 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3199 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + 6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3200 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7) + (6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3201 &:= (-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (Q(6) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3202 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times (6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3203 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (((Q(7) + Q(Q(6))) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3204 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 \times (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3205 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3206 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3207 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) - (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3208 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 \times 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3209 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3210 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + Q(7))) + (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3211 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + (7 - 6)))) - (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3212 &:= ((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 - (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3213 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3214 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (Q((6 \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3215 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) \times Q(6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3216 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 \times 7))) - (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3217 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3218 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q((6 \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3219 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 + Q(7)))) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3220 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3221 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 - (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3222 &:= (-9 - (Q((8 + Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3223 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7 + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3224 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((Q(7) - (6 + 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3225 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3226 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 \times 7))) - ((6 - 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3227 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) - (7 + 6 - 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3228 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + ((6 - 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3229 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3230 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7 + 6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3231 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + Q(7))) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3232 &:= (-9 - 8 + Q(((7 \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$3233 := (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) \times ((5+6) - (7+8+9))))$$

$$3234 := (-1 + (((2+3) \times (Q(4) + Q(Q(5)))) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$3235 := (((-1+2 \times 3) \times (Q(4) + Q(Q(5)))) + 6+7+8+9)$$

$$3236 := (-1 + ((2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$3237 := (((-1 \times 2) - Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4) - (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))$$

$$3238 := (-1 - ((2 - Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))$$

$$3239 := (-1 + (2 \times ((Q(3+4) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$3240 := ((-1-2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5+Q(6+7+8+9)))))$$

$$3241 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$3242 := (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + Q((4 - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))$$

$$3243 := ((-1-2) \times (Q((3 \times 4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$3244 := ((-1+2+3) \times (Q((4+Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$3245 := ((-1 \times (2+3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5+Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$3246 := (-1-2+Q(((3 \times (4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)))$$

$$3247 := (-1 \times 2 + Q(((3 \times (4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)))$$

$$3248 := (-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3) + 4+5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$3249 := Q((-1-2 + (Q(3) + (Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$3250 := (Q((-1-2 + (3 \times Q(4)))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$3251 := (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) - ((Q(4) + Q((5+6))) \times (7+8+9))))$$

$$3252 := ((-1-2-Q(3)) \times ((4+Q(Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$3253 := (-1 - ((2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(4)))) - (Q((5+6)) \times (7+8+9))))$$

$$3254 := (-1 - ((2+3) \times (4 - (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9))))$$

$$3255 := ((-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$3256 := (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + (4 \times (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$3257 := (-1 + (2 \times (Q((3 \times (4+5))) + Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$3258 := ((-1 \times 2) \times ((Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$3259 := (-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9))))$$

$$3260 := (((Q((-1+Q(2+3))) + Q(Q(4))) \times 5) - Q(6+7+8+9))$$

$$3261 := (((-1-2) \times Q(3)) + ((Q(4) + Q((5+6))) \times (7+8+9)))$$

$$3262 := (-1 - (2 \times Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))))$$

$$3263 := ((-1 + Q(((2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4)))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$3264 := (Q(((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) - Q(Q(4)))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$3265 := (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) - (Q(4) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))$$

$$3266 := (-1+2 + (Q(3+Q(4)) + (Q((5+6)) \times (7+8+9))))$$

$$3267 := ((-1-2) \times ((Q(3) \times (4 - Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$3268 := (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(3) + (4 \times Q(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$3269 := (((-1+2^{Q(3)}) \times 4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$3270 := ((Q((-1+2+Q(3))) + (4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))$$

$$3271 := (-1+2 + ((Q(3) + (4 \times Q(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$3272 := (-1 + (((2^3) \times Q(Q(4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$3233 := (-9-8 + (Q((Q(7) + 6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$3234 := (((-9 + (Q(8) + Q(7))) \times (6+Q(5))) + 4+3+2+1)$$

$$3235 := (((-9+Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$3236 := (Q(((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + Q(6+5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))$$

$$3237 := (Q((-9+Q(8))) - (7+6 - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$3238 := (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (6+5+Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$3239 := (-9+8 + (Q(7+6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$3240 := (Q((-9+8+7)) \times (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$3241 := (-9 + (Q((8+Q(7))) + (6+5 - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$3242 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7+6) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))$$

$$3243 := (-9 + (Q((8+Q(7))) + ((6 \times 5)/(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$3244 := (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q(7+6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$3245 := ((-9+Q(8)) \times (Q(7) + ((6-5) \times (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$3246 := (Q((-9+Q(8))) - ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))/(5 - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$3247 := (-9+8 - (7 \times (Q(6) - (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))))$$

$$3248 := (-9+8 + Q(((7 \times 6) + 5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$3249 := Q((Q((-9+8+7)) + 6+5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$3250 := (Q((-9+Q(8))) + Q(((7-6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$3251 := (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (7-6+Q(5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$3252 := (-9+Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(7+6) \times 5) - (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$3253 := (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (7 + (Q(6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$3254 := (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q(7) - (Q(6) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))$$

$$3255 := (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) + (Q(6+Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$3256 := (-9-8 - ((7 \times Q(6+Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$3257 := (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + ((6 \times 5) + Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$3258 := (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)))$$

$$3259 := ((-9 \times ((Q(Q(8) + 7) - Q(Q(6)))/5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$3260 := (-9 + (Q((8+Q(7))) + ((6 \times 5) - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$3261 := (-9 + (Q((8+Q(7))) + 6+5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$3262 := (Q((-9+Q(8))) + ((7 \times Q(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$3263 := (Q((-9+Q(8))) + ((7+6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$3264 := (Q((-9 + ((8 \times 7) + (6+5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1))$$

$$3265 := (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) + Q((Q(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))$$

$$3266 := ((-9 \times (Q(8+7) + (Q(6) - Q(Q(5))))) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$3267 := (-9 - (Q((Q(8) + 7+6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$3268 := (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(6) + (5 + Q(4+3+2+1)))))$$

$$3269 := (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q(7+6) - (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$3270 := (((-9+8 - (Q(7) + Q(Q(6)))) \times 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$3271 := (-9 + (Q((8+Q(7))) + (Q(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))$$

$$3272 := (-9+8 - ((7 \times Q(6+Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3273 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3 + 4))) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3273 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times Q(6 + Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3274 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 + 4)) \times (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3274 &:= (-9 + 8 - (((Q(7) + Q(Q(6))) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3275 &:= ((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4))) \times (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3275 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (((Q(7) + Q(Q(6))) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3276 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3276 &:= (-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3277 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3 + 4))) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3277 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q((Q(7) - (6 \times 5)))))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3278 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (4 + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3278 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + Q(7))) + (((6 + 5) \times 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3279 &:= (Q((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + (Q(4) + Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 3279 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3280 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3280 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3281 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 3281 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q((7 - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3282 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3282 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 \times Q(6)) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3283 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3) - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3283 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3284 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3284 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(6))) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3285 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (4 + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3285 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (Q(6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3286 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3286 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q(7) + 6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3287 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3287 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 + 6 - 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3288 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3288 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 + 6) + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3289 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3289 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + 6) - (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3290 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3290 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7) + (6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3291 &:= ((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times (Q(4) + Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3291 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - Q((Q(7) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3292 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3292 &:= (-9 \times 8 + Q((Q(7) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3293 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3 + 4))) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3293 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) - (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3294 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3 + 4))) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3294 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((Q(7) + Q(Q(6)))/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3295 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3295 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7 + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3296 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3296 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + Q(7))) + (6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3297 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3 + 4))) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3297 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(7) + 6 \times 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3298 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(((3 \times 4) - 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3298 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (7 + Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3299 &:= (Q((Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3299 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + 6) + (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3300 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) - Q(4)) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3300 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 - Q(6)) \times (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3301 &:= (Q(Q((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - 4 - 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3301 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) - (Q(6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3302 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(((3 \times 4) - 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3302 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3303 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3303 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - Q((7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3304 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3304 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + Q(((7 \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3305 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3305 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3306 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3306 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3307 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3307 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 \times 7))) - (Q(6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3308 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3308 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) \times (Q(6) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3309 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3309 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) + ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3310 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3310 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3311 &:= (-1 - (((2 - 3) - (Q(4) + Q((5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 3311 &:= (-9 + ((8 + Q(7 + 6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3312 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q((3 \times 4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3312 &:= (-9 \times ((Q((8 \times 7)) - Q(Q(6)))/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3313 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (Q(3) - Q((Q(4) + Q(5)))))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3314 &:= (Q(((((-1 + 2)^3) + Q(4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3315 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3316 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3317 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)))) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3318 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3319 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3320 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - Q(4))) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3321 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(Q(3))) - (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3322 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3323 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3324 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3325 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3326 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3327 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3328 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q((4 \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3329 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (Q(4) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3330 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + Q(3))) - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3331 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q((4 \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3332 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4) + Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3333 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times (Q(3) + (4 \times 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3334 &:= (Q((Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) + (4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3335 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times Q((Q(4) - 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3336 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(Q(3))) - ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3337 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(Q(3))) - (4 \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3338 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) - (4 \times (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3339 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + ((4 - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3340 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(Q(Q(3))) - ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3341 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3 + 4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3342 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(4) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3343 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3) - Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3344 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3345 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3346 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)))) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3347 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3348 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3349 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(((3 + 4) \times 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3350 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(3 + 4))) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3351 &:= ((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times (Q(4) + Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3352 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3313 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times (7 - Q(6))) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3314 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q(((Q(7) + Q(6 + 5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3315 &:= ((-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7) \times 6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3316 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 \times 7))) - (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3317 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3318 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3319 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3320 &:= (9 - 8 - 6 \times Q(7) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3321 &:= (-9 + ((8 + ((7 + 6) \times Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3322 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + ((7 + Q(Q(6))) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3323 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (7 + 6)) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3324 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((Q(7) \times 6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3325 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3326 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3327 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3328 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q((6 \times 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3329 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 + Q(7)))) - (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3330 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + (7 - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3331 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + (Q(Q(7)) + Q(Q(6))))/5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3332 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3333 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 \times (6 - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3334 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((Q(7) \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3335 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3336 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) - (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3337 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3338 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - (6 + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3339 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + ((7 - Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3340 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 \times Q(6 + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3341 &:= (Q(((((-9 + 8) \times 7) + Q(6))) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3342 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(7 + 6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3343 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3344 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3345 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3346 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 \times 7))) - (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3347 &:= (-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3348 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3349 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q((7 + 6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3350 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + Q(7))) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3351 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + Q(7))) + (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3352 &:= (-9 + (Q(8 + 7) + Q((6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3353 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times 4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3354 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3355 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3356 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3357 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((Q(3) - Q((Q(4) - 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3358 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2 \times 3) + Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3359 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3360 &:= ((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3361 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((Q(3) - Q((Q(4) - 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3362 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3363 &:= (-1 + Q(((2 \times (Q(3 + 4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3364 &:= Q((-1 + 2 - (3 \times (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3365 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2^3)) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3366 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
3367 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3368 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3369 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3370 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3371 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times 4) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3372 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) \times (4 - Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3373 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3)) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3374 &:= ((-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) \times 4)) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3375 &:= (Q((-1 + Q((2 + 3 + 4)))) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3376 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 \times Q(3))) - (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
3377 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3378 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + Q(3)) + (4 \times (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
3379 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) + Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3380 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 \times (Q(3) + 4))) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3381 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3382 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q((3 \times Q(4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3383 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3 + Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3384 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3385 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
3386 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times 4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3387 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3 + Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3388 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3389 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3390 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) \times Q(Q(4))) + Q(Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3391 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times 4) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3392 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3353 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) \times 7 - (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3354 &:= (Q((-9 + ((8 \times 7) + (6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3355 &:= (-9 + Q((Q(8) - (7 - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3356 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7 + 6) - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3357 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) \times ((6 \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3358 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - Q(((7 \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3359 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + 6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3360 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + Q(7 + 6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3361 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + (7 - 6)))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3362 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q((7 - 6) \times 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3363 &:= (-9 + 8 + Q((Q(7) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3364 &:= Q((((-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3365 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6 + Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3366 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3367 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) - Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3368 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7^{6 \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)})) \\
3369 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((Q(7) \times 6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3370 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8 + 7) + Q(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3371 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3372 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) - ((7 - 6) \times 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3373 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3374 &:= (Q((-9 + ((8 \times 7) + (6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3375 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3376 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) + (Q(6) - Q(Q(5))))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3377 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times Q(7 + 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3378 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (7 + Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3379 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times Q(7)) - (Q(6) \times (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3380 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(7) \times (Q(6) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3381 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (6 + 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3382 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3383 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7 + 6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3384 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q((6 \times 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3385 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((Q(7) + (6 + 5))) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3386 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q((Q(7) + (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3387 &:= (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) - (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3388 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3389 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - Q(Q(6)))) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3390 &:= (((-9 - 8 + 7) \times (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3391 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 + 6) \times Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3392 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

3393 := $(-1 \times 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3394 := $(Q((Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) + (4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$
3395 := $((-1 + (2 \times Q(3 + 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
3396 := $(-1 + 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3397 := $(-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(3) + (Q(4) + Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3398 := $((-1 + Q((Q(2 \times Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
3399 := $((Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) \times Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
3400 := $(((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))) \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
3401 := $(-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3402 := $((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3403 := $(((-1 + 2) \times 3) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3404 := $((-1 + 2 + 3) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3405 := $(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3 + 4))) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3406 := $(-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3407 := $(-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3408 := $(((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) - Q((4 + (5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$
3409 := $(Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3410 := $(-1 + 2 + (Q(3) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3411 := $((-1 - 2) \times ((3 \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3412 := $(-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (4 \times (Q((5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))))$
3413 := $(-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times ((4 - (5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$
3414 := $(((-1 - 2) \times (3 - Q((4 + Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
3415 := $(-1 - (2 \times (3 - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3416 := $(((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
3417 := $(((-1 - 2) \times Q(3 + Q(4))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3418 := $(((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) - (4 \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3419 := $(-1 + ((2 - (Q(3) - Q((Q(4) - 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3420 := $((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) + (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3421 := $(((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times 4) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3422 := $(Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q((Q(4) - 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3423 := $((-1 - (2 \times Q(Q(3)))) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3424 := $(-1 + (Q(((2 + 3) \times 4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3425 := $(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3 + 4))) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3426 := $((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3427 := $(-1 \times 2 + ((Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3428 := $(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))))$
3429 := $(-1 + (2 \times (Q(3 + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3430 := $((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
3431 := $(Q(((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3432 := $((-1 - 2) \times ((3^4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$

3393 := $(-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$
3394 := $(-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times ((6 - 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$
3395 := $((-9 \times 8 + Q(7 + 6)) \times (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
3396 := $((-9 - (8 + 7)) - (Q(6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3397 := $((-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (Q(6) + Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
3398 := $(Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) - (Q(6) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3399 := $(-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$
3400 := $((-9 - 8) \times (Q(Q(7)) - Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3401 := $(-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q((7 - 6 + Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
3402 := $(Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times Q(6) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3403 := $(Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
3404 := $(Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3405 := $(Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((Q(7) - (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3406 := $(-9 - 8 - (7 \times (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$
3407 := $(-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + ((Q(6) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3408 := $((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3409 := $(-9 \times 8 + Q((Q(7) + ((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$
3410 := $((-9 - 8 + 7) - (Q(6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3411 := $(-9 + Q(Q(8)) - Q((Q((7 - (6 - 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3412 := $(-9 + 8 - 7 - (Q(6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3413 := $(((-9 + 8) \times 7) - (Q(6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3414 := $((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((7 \times 6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3415 := $(((-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - 7)) / 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3416 := $(-9 - (Q(8 + 7) - ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3417 := $(Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3418 := $(-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3419 := $(Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3420 := $((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q((7 + 6 - 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3421 := $(-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q((7 - 6 + Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3422 := $(-9 + 8 - (7 \times (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$
3423 := $(((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3424 := $(Q((-9 + ((8 \times 7) + 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3425 := $(Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 - 6 - 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3426 := $((-9 + 8 + 7) - (Q(6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3427 := $(-9 - (Q(8) - (Q((Q(7) + (6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3428 := $((-9 \times 8 + Q((Q(7) + (6 + 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
3429 := $((-9 + Q((8 + Q(7)))) - (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3430 := $((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) \times ((6 \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3431 := $((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 - (6 \times Q(((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))$
3432 := $((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - Q(((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
3433 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2^3)) - ((Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3434 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(3 + 4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3435 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3436 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3437 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + ((4 \times (5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3438 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3439 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - Q(Q((4 - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3440 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3441 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3442 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) \times 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3443 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3444 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3445 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 \times 3) - Q((4 + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3446 &:= (Q(((-1 + Q(2^3)) - 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3447 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - ((Q(4) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3448 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2 + 3) \times (Q(4) + Q((5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3449 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (Q(3) + Q(4))) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3450 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q((Q(4) - 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3451 &:= (Q((Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4))) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3452 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (4 \times (5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3453 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3454 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3455 &:= ((-1 + Q((Q(2 + 3) + (Q(4) + Q(5)))))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3456 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) - Q((4 + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3457 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3458 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3459 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3460 &:= (((Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3461 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3462 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((Q(Q(3)) \times (4 - Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3463 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) + (4 \times (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3464 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3465 &:= ((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) \times 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3466 &:= (Q(((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - Q(4)))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3467 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((Q(Q(Q(3))) - Q((4 \times Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3468 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q((Q(4) - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3469 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3470 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((Q(Q(Q(3))) - Q((4 \times Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3471 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3)))) \times Q(4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3472 &:= ((-1 - 2 + ((3 + 4) \times Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3433 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
3434 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3435 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q((8 + 7 - 6))) - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3436 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) + Q(Q(6))) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3437 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 + 6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3438 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7 + 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3439 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 + 6)) + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3440 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) - (6 \times 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3441 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) - (Q(7) \times 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3442 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 + Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3443 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3444 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3445 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - Q(7 + 6))) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3446 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) + (6 - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3447 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q((7 + 6 - 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3448 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(7) \times (6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3449 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + 6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3450 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (((7 + 6) \times Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3451 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8 + 7) + Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3452 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q((7 - 6) \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3453 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 - 6) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3454 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7) + ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3455 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3456 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - (7 + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3457 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3458 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (6 - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3459 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3460 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 - Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3461 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3462 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - Q((Q((Q(7) + (6 - 5)))/Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3463 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3464 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - Q((7 \times (6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3465 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3466 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3467 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) - (Q(6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3468 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) - (Q(6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3469 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) + (Q(6) \times (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3470 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(7) + ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3471 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3472 &:= (-9 + Q(((8 + 7 - 6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3473 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4) \times Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3474 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times (Q(4) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3475 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3476 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((3 + 4) \times Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3477 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3478 &:= (-1 - 2 + Q((Q(3) + ((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3479 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) - Q((Q(4) - 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3480 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3481 &:= Q((-1 - (2 \times (Q(3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3482 &:= (-1 + 2 + Q((Q(3) + ((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3483 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3484 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q((4 + Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3485 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + Q((4 + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3486 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) + Q((4 + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3487 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + Q((4 + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3488 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) + (4 \times (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3489 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4)))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3490 &:= (Q((-1 + 2) \times 3) + Q((4 + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3491 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3492 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) + (4 \times (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3493 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) - (4 \times (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3494 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3495 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(3 + 4)))) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3496 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) + (4 \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3497 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + Q((4 + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3498 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - (4 \times (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3499 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) \times (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3500 &:= (Q((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3501 &:= ((Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) \times (4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3502 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(3)) \times (4 + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3503 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (4 \times (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3504 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) - (4 \times (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3505 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(3 + 4))) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3506 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3)) - 4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3507 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3508 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + Q(3)) \times (4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3509 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2 \times 3) + Q(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3510 &:= ((Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + Q(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3511 &:= (Q((Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)) - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3512 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) - (Q(4) - (Q((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3473 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3474 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (Q(7 + 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3475 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (7 + 6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3476 &:= (9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7) - 6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3477 &:= (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) - (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3478 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3479 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (Q(7) + Q((6 + (5 + 4)))) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3480 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 + 6) \times (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3481 &:= Q((Q((-9 + Q((8 + 7) - (6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3482 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + 6))/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3483 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) + (6 + 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3484 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3485 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 + 6 - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3486 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + Q(7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3487 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(7) + (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3488 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(Q(7)) + ((Q(6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3489 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(Q(7)) + ((Q(6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3490 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3491 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3492 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((Q((Q(7) + 6))/5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3493 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(6) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3494 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times (Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3495 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7 \times (6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3496 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q(7) + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3497 &:= (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) - (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3498 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3499 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q((Q(7) + (6 + 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3500 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3501 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3502 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3503 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((Q(7) \times (6 + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3504 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((Q(Q(7)) - 6)/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3505 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(Q(7)) - (6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3506 &:= (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) - ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3507 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) \times (Q(6) + Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3508 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3509 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - Q(7)) \times (6 - (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3510 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q((7 + 6 - 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3511 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3512 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 + 6 - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3513 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2 \times 3))) - (Q(4) - (Q((5+6)) \times (7+8+9)))) & 3513 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) - ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3514 &:= (Q(((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) + (Q((5+6)) - Q((7+8+9)))) & 3514 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) + (Q(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
3515 &:= (-1 - (Q(2^3) + (4 \times (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 3515 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q(7) + Q(6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3516 &:= (Q(((-1 + Q(2^3)) - 4)) + 5+6+7+8+9) & 3516 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) - (Q(7) - (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3517 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(3))) + Q((4+(Q(5)+6+7+8+9)))) & 3517 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q((Q(7)+(6+5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3518 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + Q(Q(5)+6+7+8+9))) & 3518 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q((Q(7)+(6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
3519 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(3 \times 4))) \times Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9) & 3519 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (Q(7) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3520 &:= (Q((-1+(2+3+4))) \times (Q(5)+6+7+8+9)) & 3520 &:= (Q((-9+8 \times 7)) + (Q(Q(6))+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3521 &:= ((-1+(2 \times (Q(Q(3+4)) - Q(Q(5)))))) - (6+7+8+9) & 3521 &:= (((-9+Q(8)) \times 7) + Q((6+(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3522 &:= (((-1+Q(2+3))/4) \times ((5+6)+Q((7+8+9)))) & 3522 &:= (((-9 - (Q(Q(8))+Q(7))) + (6^5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
3523 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) & 3523 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) - (6 - Q((Q(5)+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3524 &:= ((-1+Q(2+3)) - (4 \times (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 3524 &:= (-9+8+(Q((Q(7)+6)) + (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3525 &:= (-1 + (Q((2+Q(3+4))) + (Q(5)+Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 3525 &:= ((-9-8+(7 \times Q(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3526 &:= (-1-2+(Q((3 \times Q(4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 3526 &:= (-9+((Q(8) \times (Q(7)+6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3527 &:= (-1+(2 \times Q((3+4+5+6+7+8+9)))) & 3527 &:= (-9+(Q(8)+(Q(Q(7))+(Q(Q(6))-Q(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3528 &:= ((-1-2) \times (Q(3+4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 3528 &:= (-9 \times (8 + ((7-6-5) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3529 &:= ((Q((-1+Q(2+3))) \times 4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 3529 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) - ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3530 &:= (-1+2+(Q((3 \times Q(4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 3530 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q((7+6-5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
3531 &:= ((-1-2) \times ((3 \times Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 3531 &:= (-9+(Q(Q(8))+(Q(7+6)-(Q(Q(5))+Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3532 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) - (4+Q(Q(5)+6+7+8+9))) & 3532 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3533 &:= ((-1+2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4+Q(Q(5)+6+7+8+9))) & 3533 &:= (-9-8+(Q((Q(7)+6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3534 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3 - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5)+Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 3534 &:= (Q((-9+((8 \times 7)+6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
3535 &:= ((-1+Q(Q(2^3))) - (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) & 3535 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) + (6+Q((Q(5)+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3536 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))) & 3536 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8+7) + (6 - Q(Q(5)))))) - (4+3+2+1) \\
3537 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5)+6+7+8+9))) & 3537 &:= (-9 \times (Q(Q(8)) - Q((7 \times (6+5) - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3538 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 3538 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q((Q(7)+(6+5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
3539 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2^3))) - (Q((4 \times 5)) + 6+7+8+9) & 3539 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3540 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (4 - Q(Q(5)+6+7+8+9))) & 3540 &:= (-9+Q(Q(8)) - (7+(Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3541 &:= (-1+2+(Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 - Q(Q(5)+6+7+8+9)))) & 3541 &:= (-9+8+(7 \times (6+(5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3542 &:= (-1+((2 \times (3+Q(Q(4)))) + Q(Q(5)+6+7+8+9))) & 3542 &:= (((-9 \times 8 - 7) + Q((Q(6)+Q(5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
3543 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5)+Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 3543 &:= (-9+Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(7) \times 6) + (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3544 &:= (-1+2+(3 \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5)+Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 3544 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + ((Q(7) \times 6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3545 &:= ((Q((-1+(2 \times (3 \times 4)))) \times 5) + Q(6+7+8+9)) & 3545 &:= Q((-9+Q((8-7) \times 6)) \times 5 - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
3546 &:= ((-1-(2+3)) \times (4 - (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 3546 &:= (-9 - (Q(8+7) - (Q(6) \times (5+Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3547 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q((Q(4)-5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 3547 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(Q(8)) - Q(((7 \times 6) + Q(5)))))) + 4+3+2+1 \\
3548 &:= (((-1+(2 \times Q(Q(3)))) \times 4) + (Q((5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) & 3548 &:= (-9+Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) \times (6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3549 &:= (-1+((2 - Q((3 \times 4))) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) & 3549 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((7+6) \times 5) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
3550 &:= (-1+2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q((Q(4)-5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 3550 &:= ((((-9+8+7) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
3551 &:= (((-1+2+(Q(Q(3)) \times 4)) \times (5+6)) - (7+8+9)) & 3551 &:= (Q((-9+8+(Q(7)+6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
3552 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (Q(4) - Q(Q(5)+6+7+8+9))) & 3552 &:= ((-9-8+Q(7)) \times (6+5+Q(4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3553 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3554 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3555 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) + (4 \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3556 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3557 &:= (-1 + (((2^3) \times Q((Q(4) + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3558 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3559 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q((4 + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3560 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q((4 + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3561 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (4 \times (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3562 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + Q((4 + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3563 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q((4 + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3564 &:= ((-1 + Q((Q(2^3) - 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3565 &:= (-1 + (((2 + Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3566 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2^3) - (Q((Q(4) - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3567 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((Q(3) \times 4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3568 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) + (4 \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3569 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + (Q(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3570 &:= ((Q((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - 4)) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3571 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((3 \times (4 \times 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3572 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) + (4 \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3573 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) - (4 \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3574 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) - (4 \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3575 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) - (4 \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3576 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3 + 4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3577 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(3 + 4) + (5 + 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3578 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - (4 \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3579 &:= (-1 + (((2 - 3) \times 4) \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3580 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - 4)) \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3581 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) - Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3582 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (4 \times (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3583 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (4 \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3584 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) - (4 \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3585 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) - (Q(4) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3586 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(3)) - (4 \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3587 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) - (4 \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3588 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3589 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - (4 \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3590 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) - (4 \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3591 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3592 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3553 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7 \times 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3554 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3555 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - Q(7)) \times 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3556 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3557 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3558 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3559 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3560 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3561 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 - 6 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3562 &:= (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3563 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (((7 + 6) + Q(Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3564 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 + 6)) - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3565 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (7 + 6) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3566 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (6 \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3567 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 \times 6) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3568 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3569 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) - (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3570 &:= 9 - 8 + (Q(7) - 5 \times Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3571 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3572 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3573 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) + (6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3574 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((Q(7) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3575 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3576 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + Q((Q(6) + Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3577 &:= ((-9 - Q(8)) \times ((7 - 6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3578 &:= (((-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - 7)) + (6^5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3579 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3580 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) - (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3581 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (6 + 5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3582 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 - ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3583 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3584 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7) - ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3585 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3586 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3587 &:= ((((-9 \times Q(8)) - 7) \times (6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3588 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 - 6) - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3589 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q((Q(7) + (6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3590 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3591 &:= (-9 - (Q((8 - (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3592 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + Q((Q(6) + Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3593 &:= (((-1-2) \times Q(3)) + (4 \times (5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3594 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+3) - (4 \times (5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3595 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+3) - (4 \times (5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3596 &:= ((-1+2+3) \times ((4-5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
3597 &:= (-1-2+Q((Q(3) + (Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3598 &:= (-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(3) + (Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3599 &:= (-1 + Q((2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3600 &:= Q(((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3601 &:= (-1+2+Q((Q(3) + (Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3602 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + (4 \times (5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3603 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - (4 \times Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3604 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - (4 \times Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3605 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2+3))) + (4 + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
3606 &:= (Q(((-1+2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) - (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3607 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((Q(Q(3)) - (4 + Q(5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
3608 &:= (-1-2 - (Q(3) - (4 \times (5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3609 &:= (Q((Q((-1-2 + Q(3))) + Q(4))) + (5 + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
3610 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - (Q(4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3611 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3+4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
3612 &:= (-1+2 - (Q(3) - (4 \times (5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3613 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + (4 \times (5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3614 &:= ((-1 - (2+3)) + (4 \times (5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3615 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + (4 \times (5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3616 &:= (Q((-1-2 + Q(3))) - (4 \times (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3617 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2+3))) + (Q(4) + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
3618 &:= ((-1-2) \times ((3 + Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3619 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2+3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3620 &:= ((-1 - (2 - (3+4))) \times (5 + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
3621 &:= (((-1+2)^3) + (4 \times (5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3622 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - (4 - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3623 &:= (-1-2 + (Q(Q(3+4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3624 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3+4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3625 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (3 \times (Q(4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3626 &:= (Q(Q(((-1+2) \times (3+4)))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3627 &:= (-1+2 + (Q(Q(3+4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3628 &:= (-1+2 - (3 \times (Q(4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3629 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + (Q(Q(3))/(4+5)))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3630 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (4 + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3631 &:= (-1+2 + (Q((3 \times (4 \times 5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
3632 &:= (((-1+2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (4 \times (5+6))) + 7+8+9) \\
3593 &:= (-9-8 + (Q((Q(7) + (6+5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
3594 &:= (-9-8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3595 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (6+5) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3596 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) - (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3597 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + Q(6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3598 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 \times 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3599 &:= (-9+8 + Q((Q(7) + (6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3600 &:= Q(((-9 \times (8-7-6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3601 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) + (7-6-5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
3602 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 - (6 \times (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3603 &:= ((-9-8 + Q(Q(7))) - (6 - Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
3604 &:= ((-9-8) \times (7+6 - Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3605 &:= (((-9 \times (8+7)) + (6 \times Q(Q(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
3606 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) - (6 \times (5 + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3607 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(7) - (6-5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
3608 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(Q(7)) - 6)/(5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3609 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times Q(7))) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3610 &:= ((-9 + Q(((8 \times 7) + 6))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3611 &:= (((-9-8+7) + Q((Q(6) + Q(5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
3612 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + 7) \times (Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3613 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - (6 + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3614 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3615 &:= (Q((-9+8 + Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3616 &:= (-9 - ((8-7-6) \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3617 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q((8-7+6))) + Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
3618 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7+6) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
3619 &:= ((-9+8 + Q(Q(7))) - (6 - Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
3620 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q((7+6-5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
3621 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7+6) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
3622 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - ((5+4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
3623 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - (Q(6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
3624 &:= (-9+8 - ((7 - Q(6)) \times (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3625 &:= (Q((-9-8 + Q(7))) + Q((Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3626 &:= (((-9 - (8+7)) + (6 \times Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
3627 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q((Q(7) + (6+5))) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3628 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q((Q(7) + (6+5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
3629 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (Q(7+6) - Q(Q(5)))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
3630 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - Q(7)) \times (6 \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3631 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7+6)) \times (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
3632 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7+6) \times (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$3633 := ((-1 + Q(Q(2+3))) - (Q(4) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3634 := (-1 + (Q((Q(2^3) - 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3635 := ((-1 + 2 \times 3) + (Q((Q(4) - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3636 := ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) + (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3637 := (-1 + ((2 \times Q(((3 \times 4) + Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3638 := (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - Q(4))) - ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3639 := ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 \times 4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3640 := ((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3641 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3 + 4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3642 := (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3643 := ((-1 + Q(2^3)) - (4 \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3644 := ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(4) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3645 := ((-1 + Q(Q(2+3))) - (4 - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3646 := (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + (Q((Q(4) - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3647 := (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(3) + Q(4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3648 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(3) + Q(4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3649 := (-1 - (Q(2 + 3) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3650 := (Q(Q((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3651 := (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(3) + Q(4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3652 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3653 := (-1 + (Q(Q(2+3)) + (4 + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3654 := ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + 4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3655 := (Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) + (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3656 := (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3657 := ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - (Q((4 \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3658 := (-1 - (Q((Q(2 + 3) + 4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3659 := (-1 \times (Q((Q(2 + 3) + 4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3660 := ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3661 := ((-1 \times 2) - (3 \times (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3662 := ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (4 \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3663 := ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - ((Q(4) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3664 := (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3665 := (-1 + (Q(Q(2+3)) + (Q(4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3666 := ((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3667 := ((-1 + (2 \times Q(((3 \times Q(4)) - 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3668 := (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times Q((Q(4) + (5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3669 := (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (Q(4) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3670 := ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times (Q(4) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3671 := (-1 - ((2^3) \times (Q((Q(4) + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3672 := ((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q((Q(4) + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3633 := (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (6 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3634 := (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - (6 \times (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3635 := (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3636 := (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) \times ((6 - 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3637 := ((-9 \times (Q(Q(8)) - Q(((7 \times 6) + Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3638 := ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3639 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3640 := (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3641 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3642 := ((-9 + 8 - 7 + (6 \times Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3643 := ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (6 \times Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3644 := ((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - (6 + Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3645 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q((Q(7) + (6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3646 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3647 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 + 6 - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3648 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 \times (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3649 := (-9 - ((8 \times (Q(7 + 6) - Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3650 := (((Q((-9 + 8 + 7))/6) \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3651 := (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times Q(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3652 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 - Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3653 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3654 := (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3655 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3656 := (((-9 + 8 + 7) + (6 \times Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3657 := (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3658 := (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + ((6 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3659 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((7 + 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3660 := ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times ((Q(6) + Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3661 := ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3662 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (((7 + 6) \times Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3663 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3664 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((Q(7) \times (6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3665 := (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3666 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3667 := (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3668 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3669 := (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3670 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 + Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3671 := (-9 + (((Q((8 \times 7)) - Q(Q(6)))/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3672 := ((-9 \times 8) \times (Q(7) - Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3673 &:= (((-1-2) \times Q(3)) + (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 3673 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + ((7+6) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
3674 &:= (-1 + ((2-(3-4)) \times Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 3674 &:= (-9-8-(Q(7)-((6 \times Q(Q(5)))) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
3675 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3-4)) \times Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 3675 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + ((7+6) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3676 &:= (Q(Q((-1-2+Q(3)))) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 3676 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) - (Q(7+Q(6)) - Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3677 &:= ((Q((-1+((2+3) \times 4))) \times 5) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q((7+8+9)))) & 3677 &:= (((-9-8) \times 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3678 &:= ((-1-2) \times ((3-4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 3678 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3679 &:= (-1 + (((2+Q((3 \times 4))) \times Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)) & 3679 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3680 &:= ((-1+2+3) \times ((4 \times 5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 3680 &:= (((-9 \times (8-Q(7))) - (6-5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
3681 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3 - ((Q(4) + Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 3681 &:= (-9 + (Q((8+Q(7))) + Q(6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3682 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 3682 &:= ((-9+Q(Q(8)+7)) - (6 \times Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3683 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + Q(Q(5)+6+7+8+9))) & 3683 &:= (-9-8+(Q((Q(7)+(6+5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
3684 &:= (-1-2+(3 \times (4+Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 3684 &:= (Q((-9+(Q(8)+7))) - ((6 \times Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
3685 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (4+Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 3685 &:= ((-9+Q(8)) \times (7 \times (6+5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
3686 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - ((4^5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 3686 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times (6+Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
3687 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times (4+Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 3687 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7-6-5) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3688 &:= (-1+2+(3 \times (4+Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 3688 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((7 \times 6)) + Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3689 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times Q(3+4)) + Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3689 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) - (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
3690 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times ((Q(4) + Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3690 &:= ((Q((-9+8+7))/6) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
3691 &:= (Q(((Q((-1+Q(2+3)))/Q(4)) + Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 3691 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8)+(7-6-5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
3692 &:= ((-1+2+Q((Q(Q(3)) - (4 \times 5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 3692 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (((Q(7) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3693 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 3693 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7+6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3694 &:= ((-1 - (2+3)) + (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 3694 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q(7+6) + (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3695 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 3695 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) - Q(6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3696 &:= ((-1-2) \times (Q(3) - (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 3696 &:= ((-9+8+7) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3697 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q((Q(4)+5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 3697 &:= (((-9+8 \times 7) + (6 \times Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
3698 &:= ((-1+2-3) + (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 3698 &:= (-9+8+(Q(7) + ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3699 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((Q(3) + Q(4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 3699 &:= (-9+8+(Q((Q(7)+(6+5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
3700 &:= ((-1 - (2 - (3+4))) \times (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 3700 &:= (((-9+Q(8)) - (7+6+5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
3701 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) + (4 \times (5+Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 3701 &:= (-9+8+(Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3702 &:= (-1+2+(Q(Q(3)) + (4 \times (5+Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 3702 &:= ((-9+Q((Q((8-7) \times 6) + Q(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
3703 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 3703 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q(7) - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3704 &:= ((-1+2+3) + (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 3704 &:= ((((-9+8) \times 7) + Q((Q(6) + Q(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
3705 &:= (((-1-2) \times (Q(3) + Q(Q(4)))) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) & 3705 &:= (((-9-Q(8+7))/6) \times (5 - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
3706 &:= (-1-2+(Q(3) + (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 3706 &:= ((-9-8) \times (7 - Q(((6 \times Q(5))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3707 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{Q(3)}) \times (4+5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) & 3707 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (7 \times (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3708 &:= (-1-2+(Q(Q(3)) + (Q((Q(4)-5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 3708 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3709 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4+5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9)) & 3709 &:= (Q((-9+8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3710 &:= (-1+2+(Q(3) + (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 3710 &:= (-9+8-(Q(7) - ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
3711 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) + (Q((Q(4)-5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3711 &:= (-9+8+(Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3712 &:= (-1+2+(Q(Q(3)) + (Q((Q(4)-5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 3712 &:= ((-9+8-7) \times (Q(6) - (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$3713 := (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$3714 := ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3715 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3716 := ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3717 := (-1 - 2 + ((3 + Q((Q(4) - 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3718 := (-1 - 2 + Q(((Q(3) \times 4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$3719 := (-1 \times 2 + Q(((Q(3) \times 4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$3720 := (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3721 := Q((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3722 := (-1 + 2 + Q(((Q(3) \times 4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$3723 := (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3724 := (-1 + ((Q(Q(2 + 3)) \times 4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3725 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3 + 4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3726 := (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) + (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3727 := (-1 + ((2 \times Q(((3 \times Q(4)) - 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3728 := (-1 + (Q((Q((2 \times Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3729 := (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$3730 := ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times (4 - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3731 := (-1 - (2^{Q(3)} + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$3732 := (-1 \times (2^{Q(3)} + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$3733 := (-1 + 2 - ((3 \times Q(Q(4))) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3734 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(3 + 4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3735 := (((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3736 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3737 := (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + Q((4 + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3738 := (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3739 := (-1 + ((Q((2 \times Q(3))) - Q(Q(4))) \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3740 := (-1 + (Q(2 + Q(3)) + (4 \times (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$3741 := ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3742 := (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3743 := ((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (4 + Q(Q(5)))))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$3744 := (((-1 - 2 + Q(3)) \times (4 + Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3745 := (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$3746 := (-1 + ((2 \times Q(3 + Q(4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3747 := (-1 - 2 + ((Q(3) + Q(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3748 := (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3749 := (-1 - ((2 - (3 + 4)) \times (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3750 := (-1 - (Q(2 + Q(3)) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3751 := (-1 \times (Q(2 + Q(3)) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3752 := (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - (4 \times 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3713 := (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3714 := (-9 - 8 - (Q(7) - (Q(6) \times (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$3715 := ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3716 := (((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (6 \times Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3717 := (-9 \times (Q(8) - (7 \times Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3718 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 \times ((6 - 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3719 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3720 := (((-9 + (8 \times Q(7))) - (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3721 := ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3722 := (-9 + (Q((Q((8 - 7) \times 6) + Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3723 := (-9 + 8 - 7 + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3724 := (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3725 := (((-9 \times Q(8)) - Q(7 + 6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3726 := ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times ((6 + Q(Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3727 := (-9 - (Q(8) - ((Q(7) - (6 + 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3728 := (-9 \times 8 + ((Q(7) - (6 + 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3729 := (((-9 + (Q(8) + Q(7))) \times Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3730 := (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3731 := ((-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q(7) + (6 + 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3732 := ((-9 + 8 - 7 + (6 \times Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3733 := (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3734 := (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3735 := ((-9 + Q((Q(8) - 7 + 6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3736 := (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (Q(7) + 6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3737 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$3738 := (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$3739 := (-9 - ((8 \times (Q(7 + 6) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3740 := ((((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) - (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3741 := ((((-9 \times Q(8)) + 7) \times (6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3742 := (-9 - 8 - (Q((Q(7) + 6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3743 := (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - ((6 - 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3744 := (-9 \times (8 - (Q(7 + 6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3745 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((Q(7) - Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3746 := (((-9 + 8 + 7) + (6 \times Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3747 := (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3748 := (-9 - 8 + (((Q(7) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3749 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((7 + 6) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3750 := (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3751 := ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3752 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (((7 + 6) \times Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3753 := (-1 + (Q((2 + (Q(3) + Q(4)))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3754 := (Q((-1 - ((2 - Q(3)) \times 4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3755 := (-1 - (((2 \times 3) \times (4 - Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3756 := (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) - (4 \times (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3757 := ((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3758 := ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - (Q((4 \times (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3759 := ((Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) \times (4 + (5 + 6))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3760 := (((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) - 4) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3761 := (Q(((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3762 := (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (Q(4 + 5) + Q((Q(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3763 := (-1 + (Q(2^3) + (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$3764 := ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(4) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3765 := (((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - Q(Q(4))) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3766 := (((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - Q(Q(4)))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3767 := (-1 + ((2^3) \times (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3768 := (Q((-1 + Q(2^3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3769 := (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4 + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$3770 := ((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (4 + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3771 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3772 := (Q(Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)))) - (Q((5 \times 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3773 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - (4 \times (Q((5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$3774 := (-1 - (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$3775 := (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$3776 := (-1 \times (Q(2^3) \times (Q((4 + Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3777 := (-1 - ((2 \times Q(3 + Q(4))) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3778 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$3779 := (-1 + (((2 + 3) + Q((Q(4) - 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3780 := ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times ((4 - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3781 := (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3782 := ((-1 - Q(2 + Q(3))) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3783 := (((-1 - 2) \times ((Q(Q(Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))/(Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3784 := (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - Q(Q(4)))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3785 := (((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3786 := ((-1 \times 2) \times ((3 \times (4 - Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3787 := (-1 + ((2 \times Q((Q(3) + (4 + Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3788 := (((Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3789 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3790 := (-1 - 2 + ((3 \times Q(Q(4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3791 := (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times Q(Q(4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3792 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3753 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3754 := (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3755 := (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3756 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6) - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$3757 := ((-9 - 8) \times ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3758 := (-9 + 8 - (Q((Q(7) + 6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3759 := (((-9 + (Q(8) + Q(7))) \times Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$3760 := (((-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q(7)))/(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3761 := ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) - (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3762 := (-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7) - ((6 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$3763 := (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3764 := (-9 + 8 + (((Q(7) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3765 := ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times Q(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3766 := (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3767 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3768 := (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (6 + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3769 := (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (Q(Q(6)) \times ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3770 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((Q(7 + 6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3771 := (-9 \times (Q((8 + 7 - 6)) - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3772 := (((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6 + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3773 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3774 := (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + ((6 \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3775 := (-9 - (8 \times ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(6))/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$3776 := (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3777 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3778 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(7) \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3779 := (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3780 := ((-9 + (Q(8 + 7) + Q(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3781 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$3782 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + (6 \times (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$3783 := (-9 - 8 + ((Q(7) - (6 + 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3784 := (-9 - 8 - (Q(7) - ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3785 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7) \times (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3786 := ((-9 + 8 + 7) + (Q(6) \times (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3787 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8 - 7) \times 6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3788 := (-9 + 8 - 7 + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3789 := (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 + 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3790 := ((-9 + (Q(8) + Q(7 + 6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3791 := (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$3792 := (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3793 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times Q(Q(4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3793 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3794 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times Q(Q(4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3794 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3795 &:= (((-1 - 2 + (3 \times Q(Q(4)))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3795 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) \times ((Q(7) \times 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3796 &:= ((-1 - Q(2 + 3)) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3796 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3797 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) \times (4 + Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3797 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3798 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + Q(Q(4))) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3798 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - Q(((Q(7) + Q(6 + 5)) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3799 &:= (-1 + (((Q((2 \times Q(3))) + Q(Q(4))) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3799 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) - (6 + 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3800 &:= (((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + 4) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3800 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) + (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3801 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3)))) \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3801 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times Q(7)) - (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3802 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (((Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3802 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3803 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (Q(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3803 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3804 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3804 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (6 \times (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3805 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (3 \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3805 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3806 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3806 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3807 &:= (((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) \times (4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3807 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3808 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3808 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 - 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3809 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3809 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q((7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3810 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3810 &:= (((-9 - 8 + Q(7 + 6)) \times Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3811 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3811 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3812 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q((5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3812 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3813 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(3 + 4) + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3813 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) + (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3814 &:= (Q((-1 - (2 \times Q(3) - Q(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3814 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3815 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times (3 \times (4 + 5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3815 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((Q(7) + 6 \times 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3816 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3816 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) - 7 - 6) \times (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3817 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(3 + 4) + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3817 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3818 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (Q((Q(4) - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3818 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) + Q(Q(6))) / (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3819 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3819 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3820 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3820 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 \times 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3821 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3821 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q(7) + (6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3822 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(Q((Q(4) - (5 + 6)))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3822 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3823 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3823 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3824 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 \times (Q(3) + 4))) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3824 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 + 6) + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3825 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(3 + 4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3825 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3826 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) + Q(4)))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3826 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3827 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((3 \times Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3827 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3828 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2^3) - Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3828 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(6) \times (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3829 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3829 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3830 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((3 \times Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3830 &:= ((-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7 + 6) - Q(Q(5))))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3831 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 + (Q(Q(4)) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3831 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - Q((7 - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3832 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)))) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 3832 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (Q(6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

3833 := $(-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3834 := $((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3835 := $((-1 + 2 - (3 \times Q(Q(4)))) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3836 := $(Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) - (4 \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3837 := $(-1 - 2 - (3 \times (Q(Q(4)) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3838 := $((-1 \times 2) - (3 \times (Q(Q(4)) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3839 := $(-1 + (2 \times (Q((Q(3) + (4 - 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3840 := $(((-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + Q(4)))/5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
3841 := $(-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3842 := $(-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3843 := $(-1 + Q((2 + (Q(3) + (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3844 := $Q(((-1 + (2 \times Q(3 + 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3845 := $(-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3846 := $((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (Q((4 + (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))$
3847 := $(-1 + (2 \times (Q(((3 + 4) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3848 := $(((-1 - (2 \times Q(Q(3)))) \times 4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3849 := $(-1 - ((2 \times (3 + 4)) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3850 := $((-1 \times (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3851 := $((-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) - Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
3852 := $(((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
3853 := $(-1 + (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3854 := $(-1 + (Q((2 + 3 + 4) + ((Q(Q(5)) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3855 := $((-1 - 2 - (3 \times Q(Q(4)))) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3856 := $(-1 + ((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q((Q(4) - (5 + 6))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$
3857 := $(Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3858 := $(Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
3859 := $(-1 \times (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3860 := $((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + Q(4)) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
3861 := $(Q((-1 - 2 - (Q(3) - Q(4 + 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
3862 := $(Q((-1 - (2 \times Q(3) - Q(4 + 5)))) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))$
3863 := $(Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3864 := $((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3865 := $(-1 + (Q((Q(2 + 3) + 4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3866 := $(Q((Q((-1 + 2 \times 3) + 4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3867 := $(-1 - 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3868 := $(-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
3869 := $(Q(((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3870 := $((-1 + (Q(2 + Q(3)) + (4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
3871 := $(-1 + (2 \times Q((Q(3 + 4) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
3872 := $(-1 - 2 - (Q((Q(3) + Q(4))) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$

3833 := $(-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3834 := $(-9 \times ((8 + 7) - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3835 := $(-9 + Q((Q(8) + (7 + 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3836 := $(-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - 6 + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3837 := $(-9 + (Q(8 + 7) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3838 := $(-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 - 6) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3839 := $(((-9 + (Q(8) + Q(7))) \times Q(6)) - (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3840 := $((-9 \times 8 - (Q(7 + 6) - Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
3841 := $(-9 + ((Q(8) \times (Q(7) + (6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
3842 := $(-9 + 8 - 7 + ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3843 := $(-9 \times (8 + ((7 - Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3844 := $Q((-9 + 8 - (7 \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3845 := $(Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3846 := $((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3847 := $(-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(Q(7)) - (6 - 5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3848 := $(-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(Q(7)) - (6 + 5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3849 := $(-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 + 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3850 := $((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
3851 := $((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((7 \times (6 + Q(Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
3852 := $(-9 \times (Q(Q(8)) - (Q((Q(7) - (6 - Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3853 := $(Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3854 := $(Q((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((7 + 6) + Q(Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$
3855 := $(-9 + (Q(8) + ((Q(7) - (6 + 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3856 := $((-9 + 8 + 7) + ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3857 := $(Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3858 := $(-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3859 := $(-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 + (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3860 := $(Q((-9 + Q(8)) + ((Q(7 + 6) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3861 := $(-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - 6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3862 := $(-9 + Q(Q(8)) - Q(((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3863 := $(-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 - 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3864 := $(Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + ((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
3865 := $(Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$
3866 := $(((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
3867 := $(-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
3868 := $(-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3869 := $(Q((-9 + 8 + Q((7 + 6 - 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
3870 := $(Q((-9 + Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
3871 := $(Q((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7)))/Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
3872 := $((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) \times Q((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$

$$\begin{aligned}
3873 &:= ((-1-2) \times (Q(3) - (Q((4 \times 5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3874 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3875 &:= (-1 \times (((2+3)^4) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3876 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3+4)))) - (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
3877 &:= (Q(Q((-1-2+Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
3878 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2+3)) - (4 + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3879 &:= (Q(((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
3880 &:= ((-1 + (Q(2+3) + Q(4))) \times (Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9))) \\
3881 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (Q(Q((4+5-6))) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
3882 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3883 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((3 \times (4+5 - Q(Q(6)))) - (7+8+9))) \\
3884 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times (5+6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
3885 &:= ((-1 - ((2 - Q(3)) \times Q(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3886 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + (Q((Q(4) - 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3887 &:= (-1 - (2^{Q(3)} + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3888 &:= (-1 \times (2^{Q(3)} + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3889 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + (Q(4) \times (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
3890 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2+3)) - (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3891 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3+4)) - 5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
3892 &:= (((Q((-1+2+Q(3))) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6)) - (7+8+9)) \\
3893 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3894 &:= ((-1 - (2+3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3895 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) \times (Q((Q(4) - 5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
3896 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + Q((Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3897 &:= (Q(Q((-1-2+Q(3)))) + Q((Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3898 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (Q((4 \times 5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3899 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2+Q(3)) + (4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3900 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(3))) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3901 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q((Q(3+4) - 5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
3902 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) - (Q((4 \times (5+6))) + 7+8+9))) \\
3903 &:= ((-1-2) \times (Q(3) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
3904 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3905 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2+3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
3906 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3+4))) + (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3907 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((Q(3+4) - 5)) - (6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
3908 &:= (((-1 - Q(2 \times 3)) \times Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
3909 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) + (4 \times (5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3910 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - (Q(4) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3911 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3+4)) + 5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
3912 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2+3)) + ((Q(4) + Q((5+6))) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
3873 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - (Q(6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3874 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - (6 \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3875 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7+6 - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3876 &:= (-9 + (((8-7) + Q(6)) \times (5 + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3877 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3878 &:= ((-9+8) \times (Q(Q(7)) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3879 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((Q(7) \times (6+5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
3880 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((Q(7+6) \times 5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
3881 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + ((7+6) \times Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
3882 &:= (((-9-8+Q(7)) \times Q(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\
3883 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7+6) + (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
3884 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3885 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) + (Q((Q(6) + 5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
3886 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times (6 + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
3887 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - Q((Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3888 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) \times ((6 \times 5)/(4+3+2+1))) \\
3889 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) - ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3890 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - ((7+6) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3891 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (Q(6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3892 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7+6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3893 &:= ((-9 \times ((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times 6)) - (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3894 &:= ((-9-8-Q(7)) \times (Q(6) + (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3895 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + (Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3896 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - Q(((7+6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3897 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) + Q((Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3898 &:= (-9+8 + (Q(7) + ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
3899 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7+6))) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
3900 &:= (((-9-8+Q(7+6)) \times Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
3901 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8+7) + Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
3902 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times (6+5) - (Q(Q(4)) + 3+2+1))) \\
3903 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7+6) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3904 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 \times 6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3905 &:= (-9-8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3906 &:= (-9 + ((8+7) \times (Q(6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3907 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7+6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
3908 &:= (-9+8 - (Q(Q(7)) - ((6 + Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
3909 &:= ((-9+8) \times (Q(Q(7)) - ((6 + Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3910 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
3911 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7) + Q(6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3912 &:= ((-9+8-7) \times (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$3913 := (Q(((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (4 + (5 + 6)))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3914 := (Q(((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3915 := (-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3916 := (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3917 := (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + (4 \times ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3918 := (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3919 := (-1 - ((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3920 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3921 := ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3922 := (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3923 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3924 := ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3925 := (Q((-1 - (Q(2 + 3) - Q(4 + 5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3926 := (Q(Q(((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3927 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3928 := (-1 + (Q((Q(2 \times 3) + Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3929 := (Q((Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3930 := (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3931 := (-1 + (2 \times (Q((Q(3 + 4) - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3932 := (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3 + 4)) - ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$3933 := ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3 + 4)) - ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$3934 := (Q(((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3935 := (-1 \times (Q(Q(((2 + Q(3)) - 4))) - ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$3936 := ((-1 - 2 + Q((3 \times (Q(4) + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3937 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q((3 \times (Q(4) + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3938 := (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3939 := (Q((-1 + Q((2 - (3 - 4 - 5)))))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3940 := (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) - Q(4)) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3941 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3942 := ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3943 := (((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) \times Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3944 := (-1 - (((2 + 3) \times (Q(4) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3945 := (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times (Q(4) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3946 := (Q(Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3947 := (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3948 := (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3949 := (-1 - (((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3950 := (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$3951 := ((-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$3952 := ((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$3913 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q((7 \times (6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3914 := ((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5)))))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3915 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) - (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$3916 := ((-9 \times Q((8 + 7 + 6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3917 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$3918 := (-9 \times 8 - ((7 \times 6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3919 := (-9 - (8 \times (Q(7) - (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$3920 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (((7 + 6) \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3921 := (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3922 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (((7 + 6) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3923 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3924 := ((-9 \times 8 + Q(Q((7 + 6 - 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3925 := ((-9 + Q((Q(8) - 7 + 6))) - (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3926 := (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3927 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3928 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3929 := (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + Q(((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3930 := ((Q((-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(6))) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$3931 := (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (Q(7) + (6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3932 := ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3933 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3934 := (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3935 := (-9 + (Q(((8 - 7) + (Q(6) + Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3936 := (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) \times ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$3937 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) - Q((Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$3938 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$3939 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - ((6 - 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3940 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3941 := (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3942 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3943 := (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - ((6 - 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3944 := (Q(((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((7 + 6) + Q(Q(5)))))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3945 := ((-9 + Q((Q(8) - 7 + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$3946 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) - Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$3947 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$3948 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3949 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$3950 := (((-9 + 8 - Q(7)) \times Q(6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3951 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q((7 - (6 - 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$3952 := (-9 - 8 + Q(((7 + 6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3953 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3954 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(3)) \times (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3955 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3956 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3957 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3958 &:= ((-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) \times 4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3959 &:= ((Q(Q(-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) \times 4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3960 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3961 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3962 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)))) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3963 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (4^5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3964 &:= (Q(((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3965 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - ((4 \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3966 &:= (-1 - 2 + Q((3 \times (Q(4) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3967 &:= (-1 \times 2 + Q((3 \times (Q(4) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3968 &:= (-1 + Q(((2 \times Q(3 + 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3969 &:= Q((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3970 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times Q((4 \times 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3971 &:= (-1 - (2^{Q(3)} + (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3972 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (4^5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3973 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times (4^5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3974 &:= (Q(((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3975 &:= (((-1 + Q((2 \times (3 + 4)))) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3976 &:= 1 + Q(Q(2^3)) - Q(Q(4) + Q(5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
3977 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3978 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3979 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - ((4 \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3980 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3981 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3982 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (3 + Q(Q(4)))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3983 &:= (-1 - (2^{Q(3)} + (4 - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3984 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3985 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times Q(Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3986 &:= ((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3987 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times Q((Q(4) + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3988 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3989 &:= (1 + 2 \times Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4)) + Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3990 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3991 &:= (-1 - ((2^{Q(3)} - (4 + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3953 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) - (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3954 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3955 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3956 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3957 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + Q(Q(((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3958 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (((7 \times Q(Q(6))) - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3959 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) \times (Q(7) - (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3960 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3961 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3962 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(((7 - 6) \times 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3963 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3964 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 - (6 \times 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3965 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + ((Q(6) + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3966 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3967 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + 6 - Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3968 &:= (-9 + 8 + Q(((7 + 6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3969 &:= Q(((-9 \times (Q(8) - Q(7 + 6))) / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3970 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3971 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) / Q(6))) - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3972 &:= (((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3973 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - Q(((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))))) \\
3974 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + ((6 \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3975 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) - 7 + 6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3976 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3977 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3978 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(Q(7)) - ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3979 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q((7 + 6 - 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3980 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 + Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3981 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q((Q(6) + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3982 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (((7 - 6) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3983 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 - 6 - 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3984 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3985 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + Q((Q(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3986 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3987 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3988 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - Q(((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
3989 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7 + 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3990 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3991 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) + (7 - 6)))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3992 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{Q(3)}) - (4 + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3993 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q((Q(3) + 4))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3994 &:= (Q(((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3995 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) \times (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3996 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) \times (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3997 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(3) - (Q(4) - 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3998 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + (4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3999 &:= (Q((-1 + Q((2 - (3 - 4 - 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4000 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4001 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(3) - (Q(4) - 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4002 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (4 - (Q((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4003 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2^3)) - ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4004 &:= (Q(((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4005 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times (4 - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4006 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + 3) + ((4 - (5 + 6)) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4007 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) + ((4 - (5 + 6)) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4008 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4009 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + ((4^5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4010 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + (Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4011 &:= ((-1 + 2^{Q(3)}) - (4 \times (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4012 &:= (((-1 - Q(2 + Q(3))) \times 4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4013 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4014 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4015 &:= (-1 - (Q(((2 \times 3) + Q(4))) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4016 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4017 &:= ((-1 - (Q((2 \times Q(3)) - Q(4))) \times ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4018 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(Q((Q(4) - (5 + 6)))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4019 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + ((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4020 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4021 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times 4) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4022 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((Q(3) - 4) \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4023 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4024 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3 + 4)) \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4025 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3 + 4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4026 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((Q(3) - 4) \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4027 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) - ((4 - (5 + 6)) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4028 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4029 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3992 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (((7 - 6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3993 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3994 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3995 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q((7 + 6 - 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3996 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) \times (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3997 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (Q(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3998 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7 \times (6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3999 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7 \times (6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4000 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4001 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7)))/Q(6))) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4002 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (7 + Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4003 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + (Q(6 + Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4004 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4005 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + 6 + 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4006 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4007 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 + 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4008 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4009 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7 + 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4010 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (((7 + 6) \times Q(Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4011 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 - 6) - (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4012 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (((7 + 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4013 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q((7 + 6 - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4014 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q(Q((7 + 6 - 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4015 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8) \times (7 + 6))) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4016 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4017 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4018 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(7) \times 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4019 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) + ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4020 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4021 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times Q(7) + (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4022 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4023 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) \times (7 \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4024 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4025 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) - (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4026 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4027 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4028 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + ((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4029 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4030 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times Q((4 \times 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4031 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((Q(3 + 4) + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4032 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4033 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(((3^4) - Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4034 &:= (Q((Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) + 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4035 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q((2 + 3 + 4)) - Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4036 &:= (Q((-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) - Q(4 + 5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4037 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(((3^4) - Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4038 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(3)) - ((4 - (5 + 6)) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4039 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + ((4 \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4040 &:= (-1 + (((2 + Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4041 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)))) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4042 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) - ((4 - (5 + 6)) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4043 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (4 \times ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4044 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4045 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - ((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4046 &:= ((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4047 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times ((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4048 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times ((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4049 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times Q(Q(4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4050 &:= ((Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) - Q((Q(4) - 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4051 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3 + 4)))) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4052 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4053 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (Q(4) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4054 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (Q((4 + Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4055 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (Q((4 + Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4056 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4057 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + Q((4 + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4058 &:= (-1 - (Q(((2 + 3) + Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4059 &:= (-1 \times (Q(((2 + 3) + Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4060 &:= ((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4061 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4062 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - Q(((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4063 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q((Q(3) + (4 - 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4064 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4065 &:= Q(Q(1 \times 2^3)) + 4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4066 &:= (Q((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) / (4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4067 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q((Q(3) + (4 - 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4068 &:= (((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times (4 - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4069 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4030 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4031 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4032 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times (Q(7 + 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4033 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4034 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q((7 + 6 - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4035 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + Q((Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4036 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4037 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4038 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - Q((7 \times (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4039 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4040 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6)) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4041 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - ((7 + 6) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4042 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + Q(7 + 6)) - Q(Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4043 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4044 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4045 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4046 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4047 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4048 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - ((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4049 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - Q(7)) \times (6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4050 &:= ((Q((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6))) / 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4051 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - Q((7 - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4052 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (((7 + 6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4053 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q((7 + 6) \times 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4054 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4055 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q((8 + 7 - 6))) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4056 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + Q(((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4057 &:= (-9 - (Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4058 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - ((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4059 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4060 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4061 &:= (Q((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6))) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4062 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4063 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4064 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times (6 + 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4065 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4066 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4067 &:= (-9 - ((Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6)) - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4068 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7)) + Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4069 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - Q(7)) \times (6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4070 &:= ((Q((-1+2+Q(3))) \times (Q(4)+Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
4071 &:= (Q(Q((-1+(2+3+4)))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
4072 &:= ((-1-2+Q((Q(Q(3))-Q(4)))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
4073 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3))-Q(4)))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
4074 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (4+5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4075 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
4076 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4077 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4078 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(3+4) + Q((5+6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
4079 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2 \times 3) + (4 \times Q(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
4080 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2^3))) + (Q(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
4081 &:= (Q(((-1+2+Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4082 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
4083 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2+3+4)))) + ((5+6) - (7+8+9))) \\
4084 &:= ((-1+2+3) \times (Q((Q(4)-5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4085 &:= (((-1+2+Q(3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4086 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (Q(4) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
4087 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
4088 &:= ((-1-2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
4089 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
4090 &:= (((-1+2-Q(Q(Q(3))))/Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4091 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2+3+4)))) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
4092 &:= ((-1+2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
4093 &:= (-1-2+Q(Q(((Q(Q(Q(3))+4) - Q(5))/Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
4094 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2+Q(3)) - 4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4095 &:= (-1 + Q((Q(2+3) + 4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4096 &:= Q((Q((-1+2 \times 3)) + 4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4097 &:= (-1+2+Q(Q(((Q(Q(Q(3))+4) - Q(5))/Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
4098 &:= (((-1-2+Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4)+Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
4099 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3+4}) \times Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4100 &:= (((-1 + (2+3+4)) \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
4101 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2+3+4)))) - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
4102 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+Q(3)) - (Q(4) \times ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))))) \\
4103 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2^3))) - (Q(4) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4104 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) \times (Q(4)+Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4105 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2+3)) + Q((4 + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))))) \\
4106 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2 \times 3))) + Q((4 + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
4107 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3+4) \times ((5+6) + Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
4108 &:= (1+2) \times Q(3+Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9) \\
4109 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2^3))) + (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4070 &:= (-9+8 - (Q(7 \times (6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4071 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4072 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7-6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4073 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - (6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4074 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4075 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + (6 + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4076 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4077 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 \times (7+6-5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
4078 &:= (-9+8 - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4079 &:= (-9-8 + Q(Q(((7+6+5) - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4080 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4081 &:= (Q(((Q((-9+8+Q(7)))/Q(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4082 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7-6) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4083 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - (6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4084 &:= (-9+8 - ((7+Q(6)) \times (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4085 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7+6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4086 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7-6)^{54321})) \\
4087 &:= (-9 + Q((8 - (Q(7+6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4088 &:= ((-9 - Q(8)) \times (Q(7+6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4089 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7+6 - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4090 &:= (((Q((-9+8+Q(7)))/6) + Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
4091 &:= (Q(((Q((-9+8+Q(7)))/Q(6))) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4092 &:= (-9+8-7 + ((Q(6)+5) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
4093 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4094 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4095 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - ((Q(7) \times 6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4096 &:= Q(((-9 \times ((8+7) - (6+5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
4097 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times (7+6-5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
4098 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(7)+6)/(5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4099 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7+6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
4100 &:= ((-9 - (Q(8) + (7 - Q(6+5)))) \times Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
4101 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4102 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7-6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4103 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4104 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) + Q(6+5))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4105 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + (Q(6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4106 &:= (Q(Q(((-9 \times Q(8)) / (Q(7) - Q(6+5)))))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
4107 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(Q(7)) - ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4108 &:= ((-9-8 + Q((7+6) \times 5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
4109 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7+6 - (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4110 &:= ((Q(-1+2+3) + Q((Q(4) - 5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
4111 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) - ((4 - (5+6)) \times Q((7+8+9)))) \\
4112 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
4113 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(Q(3))) - (4 + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
4114 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4115 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (4 - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4116 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (4+5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
4117 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) + (4 \times Q(Q(5)))))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
4118 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times 4)) \times (5+6)) + Q((7+8+9))) \\
4119 &:= (Q(((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4120 &:= (1 \times 2 \times Q(Q(3)) + 4) \times Q(5) - (6+7+8+9) \\
4121 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2+3+4)))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
4122 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4123 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - Q((Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4124 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2+3))) - (4 \times (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4125 &:= (1 + 2^{3+4}) \times Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9) \\
4126 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4127 &:= (-1+2 + (Q(Q((Q(3) + (4-5)))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
4128 &:= (-1-2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4129 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4130 &:= 1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
4131 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2+3+4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
4132 &:= (-1+2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4133 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) + (4 + (Q((5+6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
4134 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + 4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4135 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + (Q(4) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4136 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (Q(4) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4137 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (4 - (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4138 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4) + Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4139 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(Q(3)) \times (4 \times 5))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4140 &:= (-1+2 - (Q(3+Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4141 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2^3) \times (4+5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
4142 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q((4+Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4143 &:= ((((-1+2) \times 3) \times Q((Q(4) + Q(5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
4144 &:= ((-1+2 + (3 \times Q((Q(4) + Q(5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
4145 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + ((4 \times 5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
4146 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4147 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (4 \times ((5+6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
4148 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2 \times 3) - (4 - Q(5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4149 &:= (Q((Q(-1+2+3) + (Q(4) + Q(5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4110 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (6+5) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
4111 &:= (Q((Q((-9+8+Q(7)))/Q(6))) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
4112 &:= (-9+8 - ((7 \times (Q(6) - Q(Q(5)))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
4113 &:= ((-9 - (Q(8) \times 7)) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4114 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 \times 6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4115 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7+6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4116 &:= (-9 - (((8 - Q(7+6)) \times Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
4117 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q((Q(7)+6)) - Q(5))/Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4118 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) - (7 - ((6+5) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4119 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - Q(Q(((6 \times 5)/(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4120 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (((7+6) \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4121 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (Q(6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4122 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (((7+6) \times 5) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
4123 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q((7 - (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4124 &:= ((-9+8 + Q((7+6) \times 5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
4125 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) \times (((7+6) \times 5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
4126 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - (Q(7 \times (6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4127 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4128 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4129 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4130 &:= (-9 + (Q((8+Q(7))) + (Q((6 \times 5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4131 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4132 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (7 + ((6+5) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4133 &:= ((((-9+8) \times 7) \times (Q(6) - Q(Q(5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
4134 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 \times 6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4135 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) - (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4136 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q((7 \times (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4137 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4138 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - Q(((6-5) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4139 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - ((6-5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4140 &:= (-9 \times (((8+7) - (Q(6) + Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4141 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((7+6-5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4142 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (((7+6) \times 5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4143 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7+6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4144 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 \times 6) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4145 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4146 &:= (Q((Q((-9+8+Q(7)))/Q(6))) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4147 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4148 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4149 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (6+5 + Q(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4150 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) - 4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4151 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)))) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4152 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - Q(4))) - (Q((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4153 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4154 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (Q((4 + Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4155 &:= (((-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + 4)) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4156 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) - (4 \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4157 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4158 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4159 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4160 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4161 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q(4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4162 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + 4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4163 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4164 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4165 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4166 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + 4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4167 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q((3 \times 4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4168 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q((3 \times 4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4169 &:= (-1 + (((Q(2 \times 3) \times 4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4170 &:= ((Q(Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - 4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4171 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q((3 \times 4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4172 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + (4 - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4173 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((Q(Q(3)) \times 4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4174 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times Q((4 + Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4175 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + 4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4176 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4177 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((Q(Q(3)) \times 4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4178 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4179 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4180 &:= (((-1 + 2 - Q(Q(3))) \times 4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4181 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4182 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4183 &:= (-1 + (((2 - Q(Q(3))) \times 4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4184 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2^3)) - Q((Q(Q(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4185 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2^3)) - Q((Q(Q(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4186 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4187 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4188 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4189 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + (4 \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4150 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4151 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + Q(Q(((7 + 6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4152 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 + 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4153 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7 + 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4154 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times (6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4155 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (Q(7) \times 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4156 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) \times 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4157 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4158 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - ((7 - 6 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4159 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - Q(7)) \times (6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4160 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(Q(((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4161 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((7 + 6 - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4162 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (((7 + 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4163 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q((7 + 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4164 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4165 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 - Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4166 &:= (-9 - (((Q(8) + Q(7 + 6)) \times Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4167 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4168 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4169 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 + 6 + 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4170 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4171 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) + 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4172 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(Q(7)) - (6 + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4173 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4174 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times (6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4175 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(7) \times (6 + 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4176 &:= (-9 \times (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7 + 6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4177 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (Q(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4178 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(Q(7)) - ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4179 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q((7 + 6 - 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4180 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q((7 + 6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4181 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4182 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (((7 - 6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4183 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 - 6 - 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4184 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4185 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) - 7 + 6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4186 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) - (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4187 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4188 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) + (((7 - 6)^5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4189 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8 + 7)) - (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4190 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) - Q(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4191 &:= ((-1+2+Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4192 &:= ((-1-2+Q((Q(3)+4)) \times Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
4193 &:= ((-1 \times 2+Q(3)) \times ((4+Q(Q(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
4194 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
4195 &:= (Q(((-1 + (2 \times (3+4))) \times 5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
4196 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2+3))) + (4 \times (5+Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4197 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(3+4)) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4198 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3+4)) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4199 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q(3)) \times (4 \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4200 &:= ((-1-2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4201 &:= (-1+2+(Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4202 &:= (((-1+(2 \times Q(3))) \times Q(Q(4))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
4203 &:= (((-1+Q(2^3)) \times Q(4+5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
4204 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times Q((4 - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
4205 &:= (-1 \times (Q((Q(2+3)+4)) \times (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4206 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (Q(4+5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
4207 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4208 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 \times 3) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4209 &:= (((-1-2) \times (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4210 &:= ((-1 - Q((Q(2+3)+4))) \times (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
4211 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q((3 \times 4))) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4212 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q((3 \times 4))) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4213 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2+Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4214 &:= (Q(((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) - Q(Q(4)))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4215 &:= (((-1+Q((Q(2 \times 3) - 4))) \times 5) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
4216 &:= 1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3+4)) - 5 - 6 - Q(7+8+9)) \\
4217 &:= (((-1-2) \times Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4218 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+3) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4219 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+3) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4220 &:= ((Q(Q(-1+2+3)) \times (4 \times 5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
4221 &:= ((Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) \times (Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
4222 &:= (-1-2+Q(((3+4) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
4223 &:= (-1 \times 2 + Q(((3+4) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
4224 &:= (-1 + Q((Q(Q(2+3)) - (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4225 &:= Q((Q(((-1 - (2+3)) + Q(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4226 &:= (-1+2+Q(((3+4) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
4227 &:= ((-1-2+Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)))) - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
4228 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2 \times 3) + Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4229 &:= (Q((Q((-1-2+Q(3))) + Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4190 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4191 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7-6-5) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
4192 &:= ((-9-8+Q(7)) \times (Q(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
4193 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) \times (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
4194 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 + Q(((6-5) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4195 &:= (-9+8+(Q(Q((7+6-5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
4196 &:= (Q(Q(((-9 \times Q(8)) / (Q(7) - Q(6+5)))) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
4197 &:= (-9-8+(Q(7) \times (Q(6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4198 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4199 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7+6 - (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4200 &:= (((-9 \times 8 - 7) + Q(6+5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
4201 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) + (7-6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4202 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (((7+Q(6)) \times 5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4203 &:= ((((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q(7)) \times (6+5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
4204 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 + ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4205 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7+6+5+Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4206 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7+6) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4207 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7+6 - Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4208 &:= (-9+8 - (Q(Q(7)) - ((Q(6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4209 &:= ((-9+8) \times (Q(Q(7)) - ((Q(6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4210 &:= (((-9+8+Q(7+6)) \times Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\
4211 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (Q(6+5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
4212 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(((7-6) \times 5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4213 &:= (-9+8+(Q(7) \times (Q(6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4214 &:= ((-9+8+Q((7+6) \times 5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
4215 &:= (((-9+Q(Q(8)) - Q(Q(7))) / 6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4216 &:= (-9 + Q(((8 \times 7) - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4217 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + Q(Q(((6 \times 5) / (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4218 &:= (-9-8+(Q((7+6) \times 5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
4219 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8+7)) - (6 - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4220 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (6 \times Q(5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4221 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 \times Q(6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4222 &:= (-9+8 - ((7 \times (Q(6) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
4223 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((Q(7) \times (6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4224 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((Q(7) - (6-5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
4225 &:= Q(((-9 - (8+7+6+5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
4226 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4227 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (Q(6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4228 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8)) - (7 - (Q(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4229 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q(Q(7))) - ((6 - Q(5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4230 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((3 + (4 + 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4231 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q(((3^4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4232 &:= (-1 + ((2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4233 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (Q(4) - Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4234 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times Q((4 + Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4235 &:= (Q((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4236 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4237 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4238 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4239 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4240 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4241 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(Q(3))) - (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4242 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4243 &:= (-1 + ((2 - 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4244 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (4 \times (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4245 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4246 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4247 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4248 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4249 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(((3 + 4) \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4250 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - Q(4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4251 &:= (Q(((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)) - 4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4252 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q((Q(3) + 4)) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4253 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4254 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4255 &:= (Q(((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4256 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q((Q(3) + 4)) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4257 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4258 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4259 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q((3 + (4 + 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4260 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - Q(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4261 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4262 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4263 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times (Q(3) + (4 \times 5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4264 &:= (Q((Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) + (4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4265 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times Q((Q(4) - 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4266 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) + (Q(4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4267 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 + Q((Q(4) + Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4268 &:= ((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4269 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - 4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4230 &:= (9 \times Q(8) - 6 \times Q(7)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4231 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) + (7 - 6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4232 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 \times (6 - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4233 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (6 - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4234 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4235 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4236 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4237 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 + 6 - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4238 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) \times Q(7)) + (6^5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4239 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - Q(7)) \times 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4240 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) + Q(6)) \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4241 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4242 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4243 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q(7) - (6 - Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4244 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + Q(((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4245 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (7 \times (6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4246 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4247 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4248 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((Q(7) - (6 - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4249 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) + Q(6)) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4250 &:= ((((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7)))/6) + Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4251 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4252 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (((7 + 6) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4253 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q((7 + 6) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4254 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8 + 7)) - (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4255 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4256 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4257 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4258 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times Q(7)) + ((6^5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4259 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4260 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 + 6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4261 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4262 &:= (-9 + 8 - (7 \times (6 - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4263 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 + 6) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4264 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times (6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4265 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(7) \times (6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4266 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - (((7 + 6) + Q(Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4267 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4268 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) \times (6 + Q(5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4269 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4270 &:= (((-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(4)))) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4271 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 \times Q(Q(4))) - (Q((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4272 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((3 \times Q(Q(4))) - (Q((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4273 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4274 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4275 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4276 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4277 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4278 &:= ((-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) \times 4)) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4279 &:= ((Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) \times 4) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4280 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - Q(4))) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4281 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4 - 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4282 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4 - 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4283 &:= ((-1 + (Q(2^3) \times Q(4 + 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4284 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times (4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4285 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4 - 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4286 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - Q((4 \times (5 + 6)))))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4287 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) - Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4288 &:= (-1 + ((Q(Q(2 \times 3)) \times 4) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4289 &:= ((Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) \times 4) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4290 &:= ((-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) / (4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4291 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((3 \times Q(Q(4))) - Q(Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4292 &:= (-1 + (((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4293 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (Q(4) - Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4294 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4295 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times (Q(4) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4296 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) + (4 \times (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4297 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) \times Q(Q(4))) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4298 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times ((5 + 6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4299 &:= ((-1 + ((Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - Q(Q(4))) \times 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4300 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q((4 \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4301 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4)) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4302 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) \times (4 - Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4303 &:= (-1 - (Q((2 \times (3 + 4))) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4304 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 \times (3 + 4))) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4305 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4306 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4307 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((3 \times Q(4))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4308 &:= (((-1 - 2 - Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4309 &:= ((Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) \times 4) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4270 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 \times 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4271 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4272 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) \times ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4273 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) + (Q(Q(6)) \times ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4274 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - (Q(6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4275 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(7) \times (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4276 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8 + 7) \times (6 - Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4277 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4278 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4279 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) \times (7 \times (6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4280 &:= (((-9 + Q(8) \times 7) - (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4281 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (Q(7) \times 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4282 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4283 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4284 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4285 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4286 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) \times 6) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4287 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4288 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) \times (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4289 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) \times (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4290 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q((7 + 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4291 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4292 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(Q(7)) - ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4293 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (Q(7) \times (6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4294 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7 - 6) + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4295 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 + 6) + Q(Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4296 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + ((6 \times 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4297 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4298 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4299 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 + 6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4300 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((Q(7) + Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4301 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4302 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 + Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4303 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7) \times (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4304 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times (Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4305 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 + Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4306 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4307 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4308 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q((7 + 6) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4309 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(Q(7)) - ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$4310 := (-1 + (((2 + Q(Q(3))) \times ((4 + 5) + Q(6))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$4311 := ((Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) \times (4 + (5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$4312 := ((-1 - 2 + ((3 + 4) \times Q(Q(5)))) - (Q(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$4313 := (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q((4 \times (5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$4314 := ((-1 + 2 - (3 + 4)) + (5 \times (Q(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$4315 := (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (4 \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$4316 := (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$4317 := (((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) \times Q(Q(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$4318 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q((3 + (4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$4319 := (-1 + ((Q(Q(2 \times 3)) / (4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$4320 := ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$4321 := (Q(((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$4322 := (-1 + 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$4323 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$4324 := (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$4325 := ((-1 + Q((Q(2 + 3) + (Q(4) + Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$4326 := ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$4327 := (((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) \times Q(Q(4))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$4328 := (-1 - 2 - (Q((Q(3) + 4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$4329 := ((-1 \times 2) - (Q((Q(3) + 4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$4330 := (((-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(4)))) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4331 := (Q(((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$4332 := (-1 + 2 - (Q((Q(3) + 4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$4333 := ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$4334 := (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) - (4 - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$4335 := ((-1 - 2) \times (Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4)) / (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$4336 := (Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$4337 := (((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$4338 := ((-1 + Q(((2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4)))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$4339 := (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$4340 := ((-1 + (Q(2 + Q(3)) + 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$4341 := (-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - (4 + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$4342 := ((-1 - 2 + ((3 + 4) \times Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$4343 := ((-1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4) \times Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$4344 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$4345 := ((((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) \times Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$4346 := ((-1 + 2 + ((3 + 4) \times Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$4347 := (((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$4348 := (-1 + (Q((Q(2 \times 3)) - Q(Q(4)))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$4349 := (-1 + ((Q(2^3) + Q(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$4310 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6) + ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$4311 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 - 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$4312 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q(((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$4313 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - 6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$4314 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 \times (6 + Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$4315 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 + (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$4316 := ((-9 + ((8 + Q(7 + 6)) \times Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$4317 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 - (6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$4318 := ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$4319 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$4320 := ((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$4321 := (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) / Q(6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$4322 := (-9 + 8 - ((7 \times (6 - Q(Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$4323 := ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (6 - Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$4324 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q((Q(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$4325 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$4326 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$4327 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(Q(7)) - (6 - 5)) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$4328 := (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$4329 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$4330 := (-9 - 8 + (7 \times ((6 + Q(Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$4331 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6) - (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$4332 := (-9 - 8 + (Q(7 + Q(6)) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$4333 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 + Q(Q(6))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$4334 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$4335 := (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (7 \times (6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$4336 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 - 6) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$4337 := (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7) \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$4338 := (-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$4339 := (-9 - 8 + Q((7 - (Q(6) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$4340 := (-9 + (Q((8 + Q(7))) + ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$4341 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$4342 := (-9 + 8 - 7 + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$4343 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q((7 - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$4344 := (-9 - 8 - (Q(7) \times (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$4345 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$4346 := (Q((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$4347 := (-9 + Q((Q(8) - (7 + 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$4348 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 \times (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$4349 := (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4350 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((3 + (4 + 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4351 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4352 &:= (((-1 - Q(2 \times 3)) \times 4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4353 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3 + 4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4354 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times ((4 + Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4355 &:= (-1 + Q(((2 \times (Q(3) + (4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4356 &:= Q(((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4357 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q((3 \times 4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4358 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4359 &:= ((Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) \times (4 + (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4360 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)))) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4361 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4362 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + Q(3)) + (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4363 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4364 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4365 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4366 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - ((4 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4367 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + (Q((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4368 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4369 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (Q(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4370 &:= (((-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + Q(Q(4)))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4371 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4372 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{3+4}) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4373 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4374 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2 + Q(3)) + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4375 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4376 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4377 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) \times Q(Q(4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4378 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4379 &:= (-1 + ((2 + Q((3 + (4 + 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4380 &:= ((Q(((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(4))) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4381 &:= (Q(((Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4))) - 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4382 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4383 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + Q(3)) - (4 + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4384 &:= ((-1 + ((Q(2 + 3) + Q(4)) \times Q((5 + 6)))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4385 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2 + 3) + (Q(4) + Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4386 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4387 &:= (-1 - ((2^{Q(3)}) - (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4388 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{Q(3)}) - (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4389 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4350 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + 6) + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4351 &:= (-9 + ((Q((8 + 7 + 6)) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4352 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4353 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (Q(7) - (6 - Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4354 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 \times 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4355 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) - (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4356 &:= Q((-9 - ((8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4357 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + Q(7)) \times (6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4358 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (6 + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4359 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - Q(((7 \times 6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4360 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(7) \times (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4361 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) \times (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4362 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(7) + 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4363 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - (6 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4364 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4365 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4366 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4367 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4368 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4369 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((Q(7) - (6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4370 &:= ((-9 + (Q((8 + 7 + 6)) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4371 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4372 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(((7 \times 6) + Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4373 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) \times ((6 - 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4374 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7 + 6))) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4375 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(7) \times (6 + 5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4376 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q(((Q(7) + Q(6 + 5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4377 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7) \times 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4378 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4379 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 \times (6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4380 &:= ((-9 + Q(((8 \times 7) + (6 + 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4381 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4382 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4383 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((Q(7) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4384 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4385 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4386 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4387 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(6) \times (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4388 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(((7 \times 6) + Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4389 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8)) - (7 + 6 - Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4390 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) + (Q(4+5) \times (Q(Q(6))/(7+8+9)))) \\
4391 &:= (Q(((-1+2+Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
4392 &:= (-1+2 - (Q(3) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4393 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) - (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4394 &:= ((-1 - (2+3)) - (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4395 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) \times (Q(4) + (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4396 &:= (((-1 - Q(2+3)) \times 4) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4397 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) \times Q((Q(4) + (5+6)))) + 7+8+9)) \\
4398 &:= (-1+2-3 - (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4399 &:= (-1 - ((2+3) \times ((4 \times 5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4400 &:= (Q(((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4401 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q(3+4)) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4402 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((3+4) \times Q(Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
4403 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((3+4) \times Q(Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
4404 &:= ((-1+2+3) - (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4405 &:= ((((-1+2) \times (3+4)) \times Q(Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
4406 &:= (-1+2 + (((3+4) \times Q(Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
4407 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) - (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4408 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2+Q(3)) \times (4+Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4409 &:= (Q(((-1+2) \times 3)) - (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4410 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (Q(3+4) + Q(5)))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
4411 &:= (Q(((-1+2+Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
4412 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) + (4 - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4413 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) + (4 - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4414 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (((3 - Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6)) + Q((7+8+9)))) \\
4415 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2+3)) - Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
4416 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4417 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q(((3 \times 4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4418 &:= (-1 - (Q((2+3+4)) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4419 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2+3+4)) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4420 &:= (((-1 \times (2+3)) \times Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4421 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) - (4 + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4422 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((Q(Q(3)) \times (4+5 - Q(6))) - (7+8+9))) \\
4423 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + Q((Q(4) + Q(5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4424 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
4425 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
4426 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(((3 \times Q(4)) + Q(5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
4427 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(((3 \times Q(4)) + Q(5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
4428 &:= ((-1 + Q((Q(2^3) + (4+5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
4429 &:= (Q((-1+2 - (Q(3) - Q(4+5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
4390 &:= ((-9 - 8 - (Q(7+6) - Q(Q(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
4391 &:= (-9 + ((8 + Q((7 - (6 - 5)))) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
4392 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times (Q(7) - ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4393 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) \times (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4394 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q((7 - (6 \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4395 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) \times 6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4396 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) \times 6) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4397 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (Q(6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4398 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4399 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7+6))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4400 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) \times ((7+6-5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4401 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7+6+5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4402 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (((7+6) \times Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4403 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (Q(7) \times (6+5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
4404 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7+Q(6)) + Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4405 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4406 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + Q(7+6)) \times Q(5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
4407 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) \times ((Q(7) \times 6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4408 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4409 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) \times (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4410 &:= (Q(((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) - (6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
4411 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q((7+6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4412 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4413 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q((7 \times 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4414 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q((7 \times 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4415 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (6 + (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
4416 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - Q((7 \times (6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4417 &:= (-9 \times 8 + Q((7 \times (6+5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
4418 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7+6) - (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4419 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7+6) + Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
4420 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - Q(7)) \times (6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
4421 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7+6+5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
4422 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (((7+6) \times Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
4423 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 + Q(Q(6))) - (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4424 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + (6 \times Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4425 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + 7+6) \times (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
4426 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + Q((Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4427 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(((7 \times 6) + Q(5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
4428 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7+6) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4429 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 + Q(7)))) - (Q(6) - Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4430 &:= (((-1 + (Q(Q(2+3)) + Q(Q(4)))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4431 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 \times Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4432 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4433 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
4434 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4435 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4436 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4437 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4438 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(3) + (Q(4) \times (5+6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
4439 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((Q(3+4) + Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4440 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4441 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4442 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - Q((4 \times (5+6)))))) + Q((7+8+9))) \\
4443 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4444 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4445 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3 \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4446 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4447 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4448 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3+4) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4449 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3+4) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4450 &:= (((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
4451 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(Q(3+4)) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4452 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3+4) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4453 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4454 &:= (Q(((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) - Q(Q(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4455 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) \times (4+5 - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4456 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3^4) \times (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
4457 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3)) - (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4458 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
4459 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+3) + (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4460 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 \times 3) + (4 - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4461 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) + 4)) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4462 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (3 + Q(4))) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4463 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4464 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4465 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((Q(3) \times 4) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4466 &:= ((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
4467 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q((3 \times 4)) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
4468 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) \times Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4469 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3)) - (4 - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4430 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) + (7^{6 \times 5 / (4+3+2+1)})) \\
4431 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) \times 6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4432 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) + Q((6 + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4433 &:= ((((-9+8) \times 7) \times (6 - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
4434 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7) - (Q(6) \times (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4435 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (Q(6) \times (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4436 &:= (((-9 - Q(8+7)) \times (6 - Q(5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
4437 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - 7 + 6) - (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4438 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4439 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (Q(7+6) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4440 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times Q(7) + (Q(6) + Q(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
4441 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) + (7 - 6))) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4442 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 + Q(6)) \times (5 + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4443 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7+6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4444 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + 7 \times (Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4445 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8+7)) + ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
4446 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4447 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + (6+5)) / (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4448 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q((Q(7) + (6 \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4449 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times Q(7))) \times (6 + (5+4))) - Q(Q((3+2+1)))) \\
4450 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7) + Q(6))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4451 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) - (6+5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4452 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q((Q(7) - (6 - Q(5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
4453 &:= ((-9 - Q(8)) \times (Q(7) - ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4454 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4455 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8+7)) - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4456 &:= (Q(((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6+5))) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
4457 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7+6 \times 5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4458 &:= (-9 - 8 - (((Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4459 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((Q(7) - (6+5))) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
4460 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) - 7+6)) + (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4461 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times 7 - (6-5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4462 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(((7 \times 6) + Q(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
4463 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (7 \times ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) / (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4464 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times (Q(7) - (6+5 + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4465 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) \times (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4466 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7 + 6) \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
4467 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) - (6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4468 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((Q(7) \times (6 - (5+4))) - Q(Q((3+2+1)))) \\
4469 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q((Q(7) - (6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4470 &:= ((Q((Q(-1+2+3)-4))+5) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
4471 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+3) + (4 - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4472 &:= (-1-2 - ((Q(3)-4) \times (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4473 &:= ((-1+Q((Q(2 \times Q(3)) - Q(Q(4)))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
4474 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (3+4)) \times (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4475 &:= (((-1+2 - Q(Q(3)))/Q(4)) \times (5 - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4476 &:= ((Q(Q(-1+2+3)) \times (Q(4)+5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
4477 &:= (((-1-2) \times Q(3)) + (4 + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4478 &:= ((-1 - (2+3)) - (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4479 &:= (1+2) \times (Q(3) - Q(4)) + 5 \times Q(6+7+8+9) \\
4480 &:= ((-1 \times ((2+3) \times 4)) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4481 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) - (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4482 &:= (-1+2-3 - (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4483 &:= (-1 + ((2-3) \times (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4484 &:= (Q(Q(Q(Q(Q(-1-2+3)))))) - (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4485 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3+4))) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4486 &:= ((-1 \times (2 \times (3+4))) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4487 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) - (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4488 &:= (-1 + Q((Q(2 \times 3) - (4 - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4489 &:= Q((Q(-1+2+3) + (Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4490 &:= ((-1 - (2+3+4)) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4491 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3+4)) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4492 &:= (((-1+2-3) \times 4) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4493 &:= (Q(((-1+2) \times 3)) - (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4494 &:= ((-1+2 - (3+4)) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4495 &:= (((-1+2 - Q(Q(3)))/Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4496 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4497 &:= (((-1+2)^3) - (4 - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4498 &:= ((-1 - ((2+3) - 4)) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4499 &:= (-1 - (((2+3) \times (4-5)) \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4500 &:= (((-1+2)^{Q(Q(3+4))}) \times (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4501 &:= (((-1+2)^{Q(Q(3+4))}) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4502 &:= ((-1+2 - (3-4)) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4503 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3-4)) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4504 &:= ((-1 - (2 - (3+4))) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4505 &:= ((-1 \times (2 - (3+4))) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4506 &:= (((-1+Q(2+3))/4) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4507 &:= (((-1+2) \times (3+4)) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4508 &:= ((-1 + (2+3+4)) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4509 &:= (Q(((-1-2) \times (3-4))) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4470 &:= ((-9 + Q(((8 \times 7) + (6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
4471 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q(7) + 6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4472 &:= (-9 - 8 + Q((7 \times (6+5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4473 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4474 &:= (-9 + 8 - (((Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4475 &:= ((((-9-8) \times (7+6)) \times Q(5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
4476 &:= ((-9 - (8+7)) + (Q(6) \times (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4477 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (6 \times Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4478 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(((7 \times 6) + Q(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
4479 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - Q(6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4480 &:= (-9 + Q(((8 \times 7) + (6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4481 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7+6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4482 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(((7 \times 6) + Q(5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
4483 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (Q((Q(7) + 6)/5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
4484 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (7 \times (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4485 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q((7 \times 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4486 &:= ((-9+8) \times (Q((7 \times 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4487 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7-6-5) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
4488 &:= (-9 + 8 + Q((7 \times (6+5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4489 &:= Q((-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4490 &:= (-9 + (Q(((8 \times 7) + (6+5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
4491 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) - Q(6)) \times Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4492 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4493 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + (Q(6) \times (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4494 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((7+6 \times 5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
4495 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8)) - (Q(7) \times (6 \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4496 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (Q(6) + (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4497 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4498 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(((7 \times 6) + Q(5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
4499 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (Q(7) - Q(6+5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
4500 &:= (-9 \times ((Q(8) + (7 - Q(6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4501 &:= (-9 - ((8 - Q(7)) \times ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4502 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (Q(6) - (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4503 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4504 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 \times (Q(6) + Q(5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4505 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((Q(7) \times (6 \times 5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
4506 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7+6) + (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4507 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) - (6 - Q(5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
4508 &:= (((-9 - Q((8 + Q(7)))) + (6^5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
4509 &:= (-9 \times (Q(Q(8)) - ((7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4510 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) + (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4511 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4512 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - (4 - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4513 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4514 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4515 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4516 &:= (Q((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4517 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4518 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4519 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times 4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4520 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + (4 + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4521 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - Q(4))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4522 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q(3) - 4) \times (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4523 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4524 &:= (Q(((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) - Q(Q(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4525 &:= ((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4))) \times (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4526 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3 + 4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4527 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(3)) \times 4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4528 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + (4 + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4529 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4530 &:= ((((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3)))/4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4531 &:= ((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) - (4 - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4532 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4533 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q(3) \times 4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4534 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(3) \times 4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4535 &:= (-1 - ((Q(2 \times 3) - Q((4 + (5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4536 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4537 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((3 \times Q(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4538 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + ((4 - (5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4539 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3)))/Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4540 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4541 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 \times 3)) + (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4542 &:= (-1 + ((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4543 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4544 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4545 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4546 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3 + 4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4547 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3 + 4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4548 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4549 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4510 &:= ((Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) - 6)) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4511 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4512 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (((7 + 6) \times Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4513 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (6 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4514 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + Q(6)) \times (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4515 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) - 7 + 6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4516 &:= (-9 + (((8 + Q(7 + 6)) \times Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4517 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(((7 \times 6) + Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4518 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4519 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7 + 6))) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4520 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (((Q(7) + 6) \times Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4521 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4522 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 - Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4523 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4524 &:= (Q(((-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4525 &:= (Q((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6))) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4526 &:= ((-9 - Q(8)) \times (Q(7) - (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4527 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times Q(Q(((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4528 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4529 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7 + 6))) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4530 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - (((Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4531 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4532 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(6) \times (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4533 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4534 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(((7 \times 6) + Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4535 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4536 &:= ((-9 + Q(8 + 7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4537 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + Q((Q(Q(6)) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4538 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (6 - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4539 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4540 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (Q(6) - Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4541 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4542 &:= (-9 - ((8 - Q(7)) \times (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4543 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((Q(7 + 6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4544 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + Q((7 \times (6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4545 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6) - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4546 &:= (((-9 - Q(8 + 7)) \times (6 - Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4547 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + (Q(6) \times (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4548 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(6) \times (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4549 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7 + 6))) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4550 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3 + 4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4551 &:= (Q(((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4552 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4553 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3) \times (Q(4) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4554 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4555 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4556 &:= (-1 + ((2 - Q(3)) \times (4 - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4557 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((3 \times Q(4))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4558 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q(3 + 4)) \times (Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4559 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4560 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4561 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4562 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4563 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4564 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4565 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4566 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4567 &:= (-1 + (Q(2^3) + (4 + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4568 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) \times 4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4569 &:= (((-1 + 2^{Q(3)}) \times (4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4570 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) \times ((4 \times Q((5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4571 &:= (Q(((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4)) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4572 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q((3 \times Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4573 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(3 + 4) + Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4574 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(3 + 4) + Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4575 &:= (-1 - (Q((2 \times Q(3))) - (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4576 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 \times Q(3))) - (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4577 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{Q(3)}) \times (4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4578 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (4 - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4579 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4580 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + 3 + 4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4581 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4582 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + 4) \times (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4583 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4) \times (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4584 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4585 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) \times (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4586 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + 4) \times (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4587 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4588 &:= ((-1 + Q((Q((2 \times Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4589 &:= ((Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) \times Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4550 &:= ((-9 + 8 - (Q(7 + 6) - Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4551 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4552 &:= (-9 \times 8 + Q(((Q(7) + (6 + Q(Q(5)))) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4553 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4554 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - (6 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4555 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8 + 7)) + ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4556 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + Q(6)))) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4557 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4558 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 \times (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4559 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((Q(7 + 6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4560 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((Q(7 + 6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4561 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q((Q(7) - (6 - Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4562 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times Q(7)) - Q((6 \times 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4563 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - (6 - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4564 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((7 \times 6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4565 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times Q(7))) - Q(Q(6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4566 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4567 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) - (6 - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4568 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(6) - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4569 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((Q(7) - (6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4570 &:= ((-9 + (Q((8 + 7 + 6)) + Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4571 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + ((7 \times 6) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4572 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times Q(7)) + Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4573 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7) \times (6 + 5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4574 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7 + 6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4575 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) - 7 + 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4576 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) - Q(((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4577 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4578 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4579 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q((Q(7) - (6 - Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4580 &:= (-9 + (Q(((8 \times 7) + (6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4581 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) \times 7) + (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4582 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times Q(7)) - Q((6 \times 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4583 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times Q((7 - 6 + Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4584 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4585 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8 + 7)) + ((Q(6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4586 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 - 6) - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4587 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) + (6 - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4588 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(((7 \times 6) + Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4589 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4590 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4591 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) \times ((Q(4 + 5) \times 6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4592 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) - ((4 \times (5 - Q(Q(6)))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4593 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4594 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4595 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (Q((4 \times 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4596 &:= ((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4597 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(3 + 4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4598 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4599 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((4 \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4600 &:= (Q((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4601 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4602 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (4 + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4603 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4604 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4605 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times (4 - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4606 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3 + 4))) - Q((Q(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4607 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q((Q(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4608 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{Q(3)}) \times (Q(4) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4609 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((3 + Q(4)) - (5 + 6)) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4610 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2 \times Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) + ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4611 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(3)) \times Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4612 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4613 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4614 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4615 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + Q(((4 \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4616 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4617 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4618 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - (4 \times 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4619 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4620 &:= ((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - Q(4)) \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4621 &:= (Q((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4622 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - (4 \times 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4623 &:= (-1 + Q((2 \times (3 - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4624 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4625 &:= ((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4))) \times (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4626 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times (4 - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4627 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3+4}) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4628 &:= ((-1 + Q((Q(2 \times Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4629 &:= (((-1 + 2^{Q(3)}) \times (4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4590 &:= (9 + 8) \times (Q(7) + Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4591 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4592 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q((Q(7) + 6))/5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4593 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q((Q(6) - ((5 + 4) - Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4594 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + (6 \times (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4595 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4596 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7)))/Q(6))) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4597 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) - (6 - Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4598 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 + Q((Q(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4599 &:= ((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4600 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + 6) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4601 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4602 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) \times (7 - (6 + (5 + 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4603 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7 + Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5 + 4)) - Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4604 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (Q(6) \times (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4605 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + (7 \times Q(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4606 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) \times 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4607 &:= (-9 - 8 + Q(((Q(7) + (6 + Q(Q(5))))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4608 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times (Q((7 - (6 - 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4609 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7 + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4610 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4611 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 - 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4612 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7) \times (Q(6) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4613 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q((Q(7) - (6 - Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4614 &:= (Q((-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4615 &:= (-9 + Q(((8 \times (7 - 6 - 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4616 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) \times (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4617 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + Q(7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4618 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - Q(((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4619 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7 + 6))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4620 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4621 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7)))/Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4622 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - ((Q(6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4623 &:= (-9 + 8 + Q(((Q(7) + (6 + Q(Q(5))))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4624 &:= (Q((-9 + ((8 \times 7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4625 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q((Q(7) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4626 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4627 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4628 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4629 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7 + 6))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4630 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + Q(((4 \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4631 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4632 &:= ((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4633 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4634 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4^5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4635 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4^5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4636 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + Q(3)) + (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4637 &:= (-1 + (((2^{Q(3)}) \times (4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4638 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4^5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4639 &:= (Q((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) - Q(Q(4)))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4640 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times 4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4641 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((3 \times 4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4642 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q((3 \times Q(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4643 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2 \times 3) \times 4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4644 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4645 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((3 \times 4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4646 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((4 \times (5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4647 &:= (((-1 - (2^{Q(3)})) \times (Q(4) - Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4648 &:= ((-1 + Q((Q((2 \times Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4649 &:= ((Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) \times Q(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4650 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 - Q(4 + 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4651 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3 + 4)))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4652 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - (Q(6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4653 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - 4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4654 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 - (Q(3) - (Q(4) \times 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4655 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4656 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4657 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4658 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q((2 \times Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4659 &:= ((Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) \times Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4660 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4661 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (4 + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4662 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) \times (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4663 &:= (-1 - ((2^3) \times ((4 - (5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4664 &:= ((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times ((4 - (5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4665 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + (4 + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4666 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(3) + 4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4667 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(3) + 4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4668 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - ((4 + 5 - 6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4669 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4630 &:= (((-9 - 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4631 &:= (-9 + ((8 - (Q(7 + 6) - Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4632 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4633 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q((Q(7) - (6 - Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4634 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 + (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4635 &:= (-9 \times (((Q(8) - Q(7 + 6)) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4636 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4637 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4638 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) + Q(((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4639 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7 + 6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4640 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) \times (Q(6) - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4641 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 + Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4642 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4643 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4644 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + 7 - 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4645 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4646 &:= (-9 - (Q((8 - 7 + 6)) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4647 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4648 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4649 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4650 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 + 6) \times (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4651 &:= (-9 + ((Q((8 + 7 + 6)) + Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4652 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) + ((7 - 6) \times 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4653 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (Q(Q(((7 - 6) \times 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4654 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times Q(Q(((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4655 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times ((7 \times 6) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4656 &:= ((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(Q(7)))) \times (6 / ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4657 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + Q(7 + 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4658 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (((Q(Q(7)) - Q(6))/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4659 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7 + 6))) + (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4660 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7) + Q(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4661 &:= (Q(((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7)))/Q(6)) + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4662 &:= (-9 - (Q((8 + (7 + 6) \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4663 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q(((Q(Q(7)) - (6 - 5))/Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4664 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((7 \times 6)) - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4665 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((Q(7 + 6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4666 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (((Q(Q(7)) - 6)/5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4667 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4668 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (6 \times (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4669 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q((Q(7) - (6 - Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4670 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(3) + 4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4671 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q((2 - (Q(3) - (4 + (5 + 6)))))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4672 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4673 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) \times (4 + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4674 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times (Q((Q(4) - 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4675 &:= ((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + 4) \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4676 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4677 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((3 \times Q(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4678 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q((2 \times Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4679 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 - Q(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4680 &:= ((-1 + Q(2 + Q(3))) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4681 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4682 &:= (-1 + ((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4683 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4684 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(Q(4 + 5))) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4685 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4686 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((Q(3) \times (4 - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4687 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((Q(3) \times (4 - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4688 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4689 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (4 - Q(Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4690 &:= ((-1 - (Q(2 + Q(3)) - Q(Q(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4691 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4692 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2^3) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4693 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4694 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + ((4 + Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4695 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times (3 + 4))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4696 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2 - 3) + Q(4))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4697 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4698 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4699 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3)))) \times (4 + Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4700 &:= (((-1 + Q(((2 - 3) + Q(4)))) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4701 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4702 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4703 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (Q(4) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4704 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - 4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4705 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4706 &:= (Q(((-1 + Q(2^3)) - 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4707 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3+4+5}) + (Q(6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4708 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4709 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2 \times 3) + Q((Q(4) - 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4670 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) \times (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4671 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - 7) \times 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4672 &:= ((-9 - Q(8)) \times (Q((7 - (6 - 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4673 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) - (Q(6) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4674 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7 + 6))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4675 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((Q(7) + 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4676 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4677 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7)) - ((Q(Q(6)) - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4678 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7 + 6))) + ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4679 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) \times (6 + 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4680 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - (Q(7) + (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4681 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times 6)) + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4682 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4683 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4684 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + Q(6))) - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4685 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8 + 7)) + ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4686 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4687 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) + (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4688 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - Q(((Q(7) \times 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4689 &:= (-9 \times 8 + Q(((Q(7) \times 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4690 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7) + Q(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4691 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) - ((7 \times 6) - Q(5))) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4692 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q((Q(7) + 6)) / (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4693 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4694 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((7 \times 6)) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4695 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6))) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4696 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4697 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 \times 7) + Q(6)) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4698 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - (7 - (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4699 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4700 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + (6 + 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4701 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 - 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4702 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7) \times (Q(6) - Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4703 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7) + (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4704 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 + ((Q(6) + Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4705 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - ((Q((7 \times 6)) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4706 &:= ((-9 + ((Q(8 + 7) - Q(6)) \times Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4707 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q((Q(7) - (6 - Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4708 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4709 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 + 6 - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4710 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4711 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - (Q(Q(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4712 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4713 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) \times 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4714 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4715 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2 \times 3) \times Q(4)))) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4716 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times (4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4717 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(((3 \times Q(4)) + 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4718 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + Q(3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4719 &:= (Q(((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4720 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4721 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) - Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4722 &:= (-1 + (((2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q((5 + 6)))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4723 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) - (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4724 &:= (-1 - ((Q(2 + Q(3)) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4725 &:= (-1 \times ((Q(2 + Q(3)) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4726 &:= (Q(((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4)) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4727 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(Q(3)) \times (4 + Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4728 &:= ((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times (4 - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4729 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4730 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + 3) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4731 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4732 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4733 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)))) + (Q(5) + (Q(6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4734 &:= (((-1 - Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times (Q(4) - Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4735 &:= (((-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + Q(Q(4)))) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4736 &:= ((-1 + Q((Q(2 + 3) + (4 \times (5 + 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4737 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4738 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4739 &:= (Q(((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4740 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) - (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4741 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times (Q(Q(4)) \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4742 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4743 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4744 &:= (Q((-1 - (2 \times Q(3) - Q(4 + 5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4745 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (3 \times Q(Q(4)))) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4746 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3 + 4)))) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4747 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4748 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4749 &:= (Q(((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4710 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4711 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7)))/Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4712 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7) \times (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4713 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + Q((Q(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4714 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4715 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) - 7 + 6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4716 &:= (-9 + (Q(8 + 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4717 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4718 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (((Q(Q(7)) - 6)/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4719 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7 + 6))) - (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4720 &:= (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) + (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4721 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 - 6) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4722 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7) \times (Q(6) - Q(Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4723 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q((Q(7) - (6 - Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4724 &:= (Q(((-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4725 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4726 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) \times (6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4727 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q((7 + 6 - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4728 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((Q(7) - (6 - 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4729 &:= (((-9 + Q(8) \times 7) \times (6 + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4730 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4731 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + (7 \times Q(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4732 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4733 &:= (-9 + (8 \times Q(7) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4734 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + (Q((6 \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4735 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4736 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (Q(7) + 6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4737 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + 6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4738 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + Q(6)) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4739 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((7 \times 6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4740 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((7 \times 6) \times Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4741 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) - (Q(7) \times (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4742 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4743 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q(7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4744 &:= (-9 - 8 + Q(((Q(7) \times 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4745 &:= ((-9 - Q(8)) \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4746 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (Q(6) + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4747 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times ((6 - 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4748 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7 + Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5 + 4)) + Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4749 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7 + 6))) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4750 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4751 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4752 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) - (4 - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4753 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4754 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4755 &:= (-1 - ((2 - 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4756 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4757 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4758 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (Q(3) \times (4 + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4759 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4760 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4761 &:= Q((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4762 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (Q(3) \times (4 + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4763 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4764 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4765 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4766 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3 + 4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4767 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (Q(4) - (Q((5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4768 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q((2 \times Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) + (Q((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4769 &:= (Q(((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4770 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4771 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q((Q(3 + 4) - 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4772 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4773 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4774 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4775 &:= ((Q(((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) - 4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4776 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3 + 4))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4777 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4778 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + Q(3)) - (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4779 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + Q(3)) - (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4780 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4781 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) - Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4782 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) - (Q(4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4783 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4784 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((4 \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4785 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) - (4 - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4786 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) \times ((4 \times (5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4787 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q((3 \times 4))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4788 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4789 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2)^3) + Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4750 &:= 9 + Q(Q(8)) + (7 + Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4751 &:= (Q(((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7)))/Q(6)) + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4752 &:= (-9 + Q((8 - (Q(7) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4753 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((7 - 6 + Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4754 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + (Q((6 \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4755 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + Q((Q(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4756 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4757 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (((7 \times 6) + Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4758 &:= ((-9 - (Q(8) + Q(7))) \times (Q(6) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4759 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 - (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4760 &:= (-9 + 8 + Q(((Q(7) \times 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4761 &:= Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4762 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) + ((7 - 6) \times 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4763 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q((Q((7 - (6 - 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4764 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4765 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((Q(7 + 6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4766 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4767 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) - (6 - Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4768 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(6) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4769 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) \times (6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4770 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4771 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4772 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4773 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((7 - 6 + Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4774 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((7 \times 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4775 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times ((6 \times Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4776 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4777 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (6 + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4778 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) \times ((6 - 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4779 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 + 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4780 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((Q(Q(7)) - 6)/5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4781 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4782 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - ((6 \times Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4783 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((Q(7) - (6 - 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4784 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((7 \times 6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4785 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) \times (7 \times (6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4786 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) \times 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4787 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 + 6 - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4788 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (6 \times (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4789 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) \times (6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4790 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2 + Q(3)) \times 4) + Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4791 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 - (Q(3) - Q(4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4792 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4793 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (Q(4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4794 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2 + Q(3)) + Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4795 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2 \times 3))) - (4 \times (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4796 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3 + 4))) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4797 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4798 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4799 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4800 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4801 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4802 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + Q((Q(Q(Q(4) - (5 + 6)))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4803 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4804 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4805 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (Q(4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4806 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3 + 4)))) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4807 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4808 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - (4 \times Q(Q(5))))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4809 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4810 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + Q((4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4811 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4812 &:= (((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times 4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4813 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4814 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3 + 4)))) - ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4815 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4816 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4817 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) - (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4818 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((4 + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4819 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) - (4 - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4820 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4821 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4822 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times 4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4823 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) \times (Q(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4824 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2^3) - 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4825 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times 4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4826 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3 + 4)))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4827 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q(Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4828 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times 4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4829 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + (4 - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4790 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4791 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((Q(7) + (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4792 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7) \times (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4793 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(6) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4794 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((7 \times 6)) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4795 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4796 &:= ((-9 \times (Q((8 + 7 - 6)) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4797 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((7 \times (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4798 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (6 - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4799 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 + 6 - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4800 &:= (Q(((9 - 8 - 7 - 6) + Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4801 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4802 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 - Q(6)) \times Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4803 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q((7 \times 6)) - (Q(Q(5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4804 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((7 \times 6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4805 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6) - Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4806 &:= (-9 \times (Q((8 + 7 - 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4807 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(7) - Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4808 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + Q((Q(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4809 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4810 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4811 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4812 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7) \times (Q(6) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4813 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4814 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4815 &:= (-9 \times (((Q(8) - Q(7 + 6)) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4816 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q(((7 \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4817 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times (6 + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4818 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - (Q(6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4819 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) \times (7 \times (6 + 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4820 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4821 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) / Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4822 &:= (-9 + 8 - (7 \times (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4823 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4824 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - ((Q(7) + (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4825 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 + 6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4826 &:= ((-9 + 8 - (Q(Q(7)) + (6 + 5))) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4827 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - Q((Q(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4828 &:= (-9 \times 8 + Q((Q(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4829 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4830 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(Q(3)))/Q(4+5)))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
4831 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
4832 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + (Q(4+5) + (6 \times Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
4833 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) - ((4+5-6) \times Q((7+8+9)))) \\
4834 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4835 &:= (-1 - (Q(2^3) - (4 \times Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4836 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3+4))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4837 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4838 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4839 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4840 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - ((4 + Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
4841 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3) - (Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4842 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) - (Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4843 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4844 &:= (-1 - ((2+3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4845 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4846 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2+3+4)))) + (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
4847 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
4848 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
4849 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4850 &:= (((-1 - (Q(2+3) - Q(Q(4)))) \times Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
4851 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3+4)) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4852 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2+3) \times (4+5)))) + Q((Q(Q(6)))/(7+8+9))) \\
4853 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4854 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - (Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4855 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4856 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3+4))) + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
4857 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
4858 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
4859 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4860 &:= ((Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) + Q(4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
4861 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
4862 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3 + Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4863 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4864 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 \times 3) - (4 \times Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4865 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) \times 4) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4866 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(4) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
4867 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4) - 5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
4868 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2+3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4869 &:= (Q((-1 + Q((2 - (3 - 4 - 5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
4830 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (6 \times (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4831 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (Q((Q(7) + 6))/(5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4832 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + (7+6 - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
4833 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4834 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 \times Q(6+5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
4835 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4836 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) - 7 - 6) \times (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4837 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q((6+5-4))) + Q((3+2+1)))) \\
4838 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4839 &:= (((-9 + Q(8) \times 7) \times (6+5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\
4840 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) \times (7+6 - (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4841 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4842 &:= (-9 - (Q((8 + Q(7))) - Q((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4843 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4844 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + (Q((6 \times 5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
4845 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
4846 &:= (((-9 - Q(8+7)) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4847 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4848 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times ((6-5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
4849 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7+6))) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4850 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q(7+6)) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4851 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 - (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4852 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times (Q(6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4853 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4854 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 \times 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4855 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((Q(7) - (6-5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
4856 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4857 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4858 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) \times (6 + (5+4))) + Q((3+2+1)))) \\
4859 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + Q(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4860 &:= ((Q((-9 + (8+7+6))) - (5+4)) \times Q((3+2+1))) \\
4861 &:= (Q(((Q((-9+8+Q(7)))/Q(6)) + 5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
4862 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4863 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) \times (6+5+Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4864 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times (6+5+Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4865 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4866 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) + (7-6)) \times (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4867 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (6 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4868 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - Q(((5+4) \times (3+2+1)))))) \\
4869 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((Q(7) \times (6+5)) + 4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4870 &:= (Q(((−1 \times 2) - (Q(3) - Q(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4871 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4872 &:= (((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times 4) - Q((5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4873 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3)) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4874 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + 3) - (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4875 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) - (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4876 &:= (Q(((−1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(4 + 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4877 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) + (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4878 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4879 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4880 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4881 &:= (-1 - (2 \times Q(3) - (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4882 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4883 &:= (-1 + ((Q((2 \times Q(3))) \times (4 + (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4884 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4885 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 \times 3)) - ((4 + 5) \times (Q(6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4886 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2 \times 3))) - (4 + 5 - Q((Q(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4887 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4888 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) - (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4889 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) - (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4890 &:= ((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - Q(Q(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4891 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4892 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4893 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4894 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4895 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4896 &:= (-1 - ((2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (Q((4 + Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4897 &:= (-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3) - (4 - 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4898 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4899 &:= (-1 - (((2 - 3) \times 4) \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4900 &:= ((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))) \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4901 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4902 &:= (((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4903 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4904 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4905 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4906 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4907 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4908 &:= (-1 + ((Q(Q(2 \times 3)) \times 4) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4909 &:= (Q(((−1 + 2) \times 3)) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4870 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8)) - Q((Q(7) + (6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4871 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q((7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4872 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4873 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7))) - ((Q(6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4874 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7 + 6))) + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4875 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4876 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7) \times ((6 - 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4877 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 + 6 - Q(Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4878 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (6 - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4879 &:= ((-9 \times ((Q(8) \times 7) + Q(6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4880 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4881 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) + (7 - (6 - 5)))))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4882 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5 + 4) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4883 &:= (-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4884 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + Q((6 \times Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4885 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (Q(6 + Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4886 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4887 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + 6 - 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4888 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4889 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4890 &:= (Q(((−9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) + Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4891 &:= (-9 + Q((Q(8) + (7 - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4892 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q((8 - 7 + 6))) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4893 &:= (-9 + ((8 + Q(7)) \times (Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4894 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (6 - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4895 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7) + ((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4896 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 + (5 + 4)))) \times Q((3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4897 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 + 6 - Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4898 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + ((Q(7) \times (6 - Q(5 + 4))) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4899 &:= (-9 + 8 + Q((Q(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4900 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4901 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4902 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - ((6 \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4903 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 - 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4904 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4905 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4906 &:= ((-9 \times (Q((8 + 7 - 6)) - Q(Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4907 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4908 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q((Q(6) + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4909 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) \times (7 \times (6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4910 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4911 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4912 &:= (Q(((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(4 + 5))) - (Q(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4913 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4914 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4915 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + (4 \times (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4916 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4917 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q(3) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4918 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q((Q(3) + 4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4919 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4920 &:= ((Q((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4921 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q((Q(3) + 4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4922 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4923 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4924 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4925 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 \times 3)) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4926 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4927 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4) - 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4928 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4) - 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4929 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times ((3 + 4) \times 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4930 &:= (Q(((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) - Q(4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4931 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q((Q(3 + 4) + 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4932 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - (4 + (5 + 6)))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4933 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4934 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4935 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(3 \times 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4936 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4937 &:= (-1 - (((2^3) \times (4 - Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4938 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4939 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((Q(3) + (Q(4) + Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4940 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2 + 3) + Q(4))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4941 &:= (Q((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - Q(4))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4942 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) \times (Q(4) + ((5 + 6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4943 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4944 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4945 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + Q(3))) \times Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4946 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4947 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) \times (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4948 &:= (((-1 + 2^{Q(3)}) \times 4) + (Q((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4949 &:= (Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4910 &:= (Q(((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) + Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4911 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - Q((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4912 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4913 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (6 - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4914 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4915 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4916 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
4917 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4918 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 + ((6 - Q(5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4919 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) \times (7 \times (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4920 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(7))/6) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4921 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4922 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4923 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(Q(7)) - Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4924 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 \times Q(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4925 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((Q(7) - (6 \times 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4926 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (Q(7) + 6)) \times (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4927 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((Q(7) + (6 - 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4928 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((Q(7) + (6 - 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4929 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4930 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4931 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - ((6 - 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4932 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4933 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + ((6 - 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4934 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + Q(6))) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4935 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (Q(7) + 6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4936 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4937 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4938 &:= (-9 - (((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times 6) - Q((Q(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4939 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (6 + 5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4940 &:= (((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4941 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) - (7 \times 6)) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4942 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4943 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4944 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4945 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8 - 7) \times 6) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4946 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4947 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4948 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) \times ((6 - 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4949 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4950 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4951 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3 + 4))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4952 &:= ((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4953 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4954 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4955 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) \times 4) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4956 &:= ((-1 - 2 - Q(Q(3))) \times (Q((4 + Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4957 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4958 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4959 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4960 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4961 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4962 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4963 &:= (-1 + (Q(2^3) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4964 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4965 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + ((4 + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4966 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - ((4 + Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4967 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q(3) - Q((4 + (5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4968 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + Q((4 + (5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4969 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q((3 \times 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4970 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((3 \times 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4971 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)))) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4972 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4973 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4974 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (Q(4) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4975 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - Q(4))) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4976 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4977 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2^3) - Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4978 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4979 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4980 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (Q((3 \times 4)) + Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4981 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4982 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4983 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((4 + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4984 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + Q(4)))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4985 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times Q((4 + Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4986 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4987 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times Q((4 + Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4988 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{Q(3)}) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4989 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - Q((4 \times (5 + 6)))))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4950 &:= ((-9 + 8 - Q(7)) \times ((6 - 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4951 &:= (-9 + ((Q(Q(8)) - Q((Q(7) + (6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4952 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4953 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - Q((Q(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4954 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4955 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + Q((Q(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4956 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + Q((6 \times Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4957 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4958 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - (7 - 6 + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4959 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + Q(6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4960 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4961 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8) + 7) - (6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4962 &:= (-9 - (((8 - Q(7)) \times Q(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4963 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times (6 - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4964 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(7) \times (6 - Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4965 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((Q(7 + 6) + Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4966 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (7 - Q(6))) + Q(Q(Q(((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4967 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4968 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - ((7 - 6 + Q(Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4969 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q((7 \times 6)) \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4970 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (Q((6 \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4971 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((Q(7) \times (6 - Q(5 + 4))) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4972 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4973 &:= (((-9 - (Q(8) \times 7)) \times (6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4974 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) - ((6 - Q(5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4975 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4976 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4977 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7) \times 6)) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4978 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(Q(7)) - Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4979 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + Q(6)) + (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4980 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times (7 - Q(6))) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4981 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4982 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4983 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((Q(7) + (6 - 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4984 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + Q((6 \times 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4985 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4986 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4987 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 + 6 - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4988 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (6 - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4989 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 - 6 + Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$4990 := ((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$4991 := (Q(Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)))) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$4992 := (((-1 - 2 - Q(Q(3))) \times Q(4)) + ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$4993 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3) + (4 - 5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$4994 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3) + (4 - 5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$4995 := (-1 + ((2^{3+4+5}) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$4996 := (Q(Q(Q(-1 + Q(2 + 3)) / (4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$4997 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3) + (4 - 5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$4998 := (((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times (4 - Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$4999 := (-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(Q(3) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$5000 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5001 := (Q(Q(Q(-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)))) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5002 := (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5003 := (-1 - (Q(Q(2^3)) - (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5004 := (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5005 := ((-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) \times 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5006 := (Q((-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) \times 4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5007 := ((-1 + 2^{Q(3)}) - (4 - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5008 := ((-1 - Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times (Q(Q(4)) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5009 := (-1 - ((2 - (Q(3 \times 4) + Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5010 := ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + Q(4 + 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5011 := (Q((-1 + ((2^3) \times (4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5012 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5013 := ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times Q((Q(4) + Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5014 := ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times Q(Q(4) + Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5015 := ((-1 + Q(((2 + Q(Q(3)) - 4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5016 := (Q((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times Q(4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5017 := ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5018 := (((-1 + Q(2 \times Q(3))) \times Q(4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5019 := ((-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + Q((5 + 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5020 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5021 := (-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5022 := ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5023 := (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5024 := ((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) - (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5025 := ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3) - 4))) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5026 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3 + 4))) + (5 \times (6 + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5027 := (-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5028 := ((-1 + Q(Q(Q(2 \times 3) + (Q(4) + Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$4990 := (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$4991 := (-9 - ((Q(8) + (7 - Q(6 + 5))) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$4992 := ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) - Q((Q(Q(6)) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$4993 := (-9 - ((8 \times ((7 - 6) - Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$4994 := (-9 + 8 - (Q(Q(7)) - Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$4995 := (((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) - Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$4996 := ((-9 \times (Q((8 + 7 - 6)) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$4997 := (((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7) \times 6)) - (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$4998 := (((-9 - (Q(8) + Q(7))) \times (Q(6) + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$4999 := (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) + (6 - 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5000 := (((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5001 := (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5002 := ((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5003 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (6 - (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5004 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5005 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5006 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5007 := (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5008 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(7) \times (6 - Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5009 := (-9 + ((8 \times (7 - 6 + Q(Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5010 := ((((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) / 6) \times Q(Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5011 := ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5012 := ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - ((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5013 := ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5014 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((7 \times 6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5015 := (-9 + (8 \times (((7 + 6) + Q(Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5016 := (-9 - 8 - (7 \times (6 - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5017 := ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + Q((Q(Q(6)) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5018 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5019 := (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (7 \times (6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5020 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (((7 \times Q(Q(6))) - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5021 := ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5022 := (-9 \times (Q(8) + (7 + 6 - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5023 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5024 := (-9 - 8 + Q(((Q(7) + (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5025 := ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + Q(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5026 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) - Q(((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5027 := (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5028 := (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) \times (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5029 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5030 &:= (((-1 + (2+3+4)) \times Q(Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
5031 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4)) + (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5032 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
5033 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5034 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) - 4)) + (5 - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
5035 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2+3)) - (Q(Q(4+5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5036 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2+3)) - (Q(Q(4+5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5037 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
5038 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
5039 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) \times (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
5040 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) - Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
5041 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
5042 &:= (-1 + 2 + Q(((Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
5043 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5044 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5045 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
5046 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(3)) \times Q((4 - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5047 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5048 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5049 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5050 &:= (Q(((Q(-1+2) \times 3)) + Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5051 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) + Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5052 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) + (Q(4) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5053 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times Q(Q(3)))) \times (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
5054 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) - 4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
5055 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5056 &:= (((Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6)) - Q((7+8+9))) \\
5057 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) + Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
5058 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q(3) + Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5059 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((Q(3) + (Q(4) + Q(5)))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
5060 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2+3)) - (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5061 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
5062 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q((3 \times Q(4)))) - (Q((5+6)) - Q((7+8+9)))) \\
5063 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) - 5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
5064 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
5065 &:= (-1 + (Q(2+3) + Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5066 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) \times 4)))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
5067 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q((3 \times 4)) + Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
5068 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q((3 \times 4)) + Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
5029 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - ((6 \times 5)/(4+3+2+1))) \\
5030 &:= (-9 + (((8 - Q(7)) \times Q(6+5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5031 &:= 9 \times (7 \times Q(8) + 6+5 + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
5032 &:= (-9 + Q((8 - (7 \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5033 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5034 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 \times Q(6+5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5035 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + ((6 \times 5)/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5036 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) + ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
5037 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q(7)) \times (6 - Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5038 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (Q((6 \times 5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5039 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - Q(Q(((7-6) \times 5)))))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
5040 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times Q(7) + Q(6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
5041 &:= Q((-9 + (Q(8) + (7 - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5042 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + ((6-5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5043 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5044 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5045 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (6 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5046 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (Q(6) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5047 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + Q((Q(Q(6)) - Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5048 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 \times Q(6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5049 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q(((7+6) \times 5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
5050 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7+6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5051 &:= (Q((-9+8 - (Q(7) - Q(6+5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
5052 &:= (-9 - (((8 - Q(7)) \times Q(6+5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
5053 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + 6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
5054 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + (Q(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
5055 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 + Q((Q(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5056 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) + ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
5057 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + Q((Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5058 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8)) - Q(Q(7))) \times ((6 \times 5)/(4+3+2+1))) \\
5059 &:= (Q((Q((-9+8+7)) + Q(6))) - (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
5060 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) + Q(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1) \\
5061 &:= (-9 - (Q((8 + Q(7))) + (Q((Q(6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5062 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7+6) \times (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5063 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7 \times (6+5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5064 &:= (-9 - ((8 + Q(7)) \times (6+5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5065 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + Q(Q(7))) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5) - Q(4+3+2+1) \\
5066 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - ((7+6) + Q(Q(5)))))) - Q(4+3+2+1) \\
5067 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) \times ((6 \times 5) - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5068 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - (7 - 6 + Q(Q(5)))))) + 4+3+2+1
\end{aligned}$$

$$5069 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5070 := (Q((-1 + (2 + (3 + (4 + 5)))))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5071 := (Q((-1 + ((2^3) \times (4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5072 := (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) - (4 - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5073 := (((-1 + Q(2^3)) \times Q(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5074 := (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times Q((Q(4) + Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5075 := ((-1 + 2 + Q((3 \times 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5076 := (Q((-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) \times 4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5077 := ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5078 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5079 := (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$5080 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5081 := ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5082 := (((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) \times ((Q(5) \times 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5083 := (-1 + (Q(((2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5084 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5085 := (((-1 + Q((Q(2 \times 3) - 4))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5086 := ((-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) \times 4)) - (Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5087 := (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5088 := ((Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) - (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5089 := 1 + 2 \times Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$5090 := ((Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times (4 \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5091 := (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (Q((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5092 := (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5093 := (-1 - ((2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - Q(((4 + 5) \times 6)))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5094 := (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - Q(((4 + 5) \times 6)))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5095 := (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + ((4 \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5096 := (Q((-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) \times 4)))) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5097 := ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)))) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5098 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)))) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5099 := (-1 + ((2 \times Q(3) + Q(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5100 := (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5101 := (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5102 := (((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5103 := ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) \times (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5104 := (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times Q((4 + Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5105 := (((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times Q((4 + Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5106 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4)) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5107 := ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5108 := ((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) - (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5069 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times (Q((Q(Q(6)) / Q(5 + 4))) + Q((3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5070 := (-9 - (((Q(Q(8)) - Q(Q(7))) \times (6 - (5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5071 := (-9 - ((Q(Q(8) + 7) - Q(6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5072 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5073 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$5074 := ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) \times 6))) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5075 := ((-9 + Q((8 + Q((7 + 6 - 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5076 := (-9 \times (Q(8) - (((7 + 6) + Q(Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5077 := ((-9 \times (8 + (Q(7) \times (6 + 5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5078 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (Q((Q(Q(6)) / Q(5 + 4))) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5079 := (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + Q(6))) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5080 := (((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) / 6) \times (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5081 := (-9 + ((Q((Q(8) - (7 \times 6))) + Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5082 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (6 \times Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5083 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5084 := (Q((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5085 := ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) + Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5086 := (-9 - 8 + (7 \times Q((Q(6) - Q(((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5087 := (((-9 - 8) \times Q(((7 \times 6) - Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5088 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$5089 := (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + Q(6))) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5090 := (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5091 := (-9 - (Q((Q(8) + (7 - (6 - 5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5092 := (-9 + (Q((Q(8) - 7 - 6)) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5093 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) - (6 - Q(((5 + 4) + Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))))$$

$$5094 := (-9 \times (Q(8) - (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5095 := (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + 6 - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5096 := (-9 - (((Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5097 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + Q((Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))))$$

$$5098 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(7) \times 6) - ((5 + 4) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5099 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5100 := ((-9 + (Q(8) + (7 - 6 - 5))) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5101 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5102 := ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - ((6 \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5103 := (-9 + (8 \times ((Q(7) \times (6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5104 := (((-9 \times 8) \times (Q(7) - (6 - Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5105 := (-9 + ((8 \times ((7 + 6) + Q(Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5106 := (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5107 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (Q(6 + Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5108 := (-9 + 8 + ((7 \times Q((Q(6) - (5 + 4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5109 &:= (-1 + ((2 + Q((3 \times 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5110 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5111 &:= (-1 - ((2^3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5112 &:= ((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5113 &:= (((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) \times Q(4)) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5114 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + (6 + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5115 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5116 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (Q((Q(4) - 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5117 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)))) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5118 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)))) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5119 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5120 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) - (4 - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5121 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)))) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5122 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5123 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5124 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5125 &:= (Q(Q((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5126 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(3) + Q(4))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5127 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5128 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (4 + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5129 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + (4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5130 &:= ((Q(((-1 + 2 - 3) + Q(4))) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5131 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5132 &:= ((Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times (4 \times 5)) + (Q(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5133 &:= (((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) \times Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5134 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5135 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times Q((Q(4) - 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5136 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) - Q((4 + (5 + 6)))))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5137 &:= (-1 + ((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5138 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (Q(4) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5139 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (Q(4) - ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5140 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5141 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3 + 4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5142 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) - ((Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5143 &:= (((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) \times Q(4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5144 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5145 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 \times 3))) \times 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5146 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - ((4 + 5) \times (6 - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5147 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5148 &:= ((-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) \times 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5109 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5110 &:= (9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5111 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - Q(((7 - 6 - 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5112 &:= (-9 \times (8 - Q(((Q(Q(7)) - (6 - 5)) / Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5113 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + Q(Q(((6 \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5114 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (((6 + 5) \times Q(Q(4))) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5115 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times Q(6)) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5116 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5117 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5118 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5119 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5120 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5121 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + 7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5122 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5123 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5124 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7 + 6))) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5125 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5126 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5127 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (((7 \times 6) \times Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5128 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5129 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5 + 4) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))))) \\
5130 &:= (-9 + 8 + Q(7) + 6) \times (-5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5131 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - ((6 - 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5132 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5133 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + ((6 - 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5134 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + Q(6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5135 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times Q(6)) - (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5136 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times (Q(6) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5137 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + (Q(Q(6)) - ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5138 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5139 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5140 &:= (((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5141 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 - (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5142 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5143 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5144 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5145 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times Q(6)) + 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5146 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5147 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (Q(7) + 6 \times 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5148 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - (7 - 6 + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5149 &:= ((Q(Q((-1-2+Q(3)))) \times 4) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
5150 &:= ((Q(Q(-1+2+3)) \times (4 \times 5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\
5151 &:= ((-1-2+Q((Q(Q(3))-4-5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
5152 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3))-4-5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
5153 &:= ((-1 + (Q(2^3) \times Q(4+5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
5154 &:= ((Q((-1+Q(2+3))) \times (4+5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
5155 &:= ((-1+2+Q((Q(Q(3))-4-5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
5156 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + (4 \times Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
5157 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((3 \times Q(4))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5158 &:= (-1 + ((Q(Q(2 \times 3)) \times 4) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5159 &:= (Q(((-1+2+Q(Q(3))) - 4) - (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5160 &:= ((-1-2 + ((3+4) \times Q(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
5161 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + Q(((4 \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5162 &:= (-1 + (((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
5163 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5164 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times 5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
5165 &:= ((((-1+Q(Q(2 \times 3))) - Q(Q(4))) \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
5166 &:= ((-1 + (2^{Q(3)} \times Q(4))) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
5167 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5168 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4+5)) - (Q(Q(6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
5169 &:= ((-1 + ((Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - Q(Q(4))) \times 5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
5170 &:= ((-1-2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) \times (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
5171 &:= ((Q(Q((-1-2+Q(3)))) \times 4) + ((5+6) - (7+8+9))) \\
5172 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) \times (Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
5173 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5174 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2+3) \times Q(4)))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
5175 &:= (Q((-1+Q((2+3+4)))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
5176 &:= (Q((-1+2+(Q(3)+Q(4)))) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
5177 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3))-4))) - (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
5178 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2^3))) - (Q(4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
5179 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) - 4) - (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5180 &:= ((-1+2+Q((Q(Q(3))-4))) - (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
5181 &:= (-1-2+Q((Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5182 &:= (-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5183 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3) - Q((Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5184 &:= (Q((-1 \times (2 \times (3 - (4+5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5185 &:= (-1+2+Q((Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5186 &:= (Q(((-1+Q((2 \times Q(3))) - Q(Q(4))) + (Q((5+6)) + Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
5187 &:= ((-1-2) \times ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
5188 &:= ((-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) \times 4) - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5149 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7 + 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
5150 &:= ((((-9 + Q(8+7)) - 6) \times Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
5151 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5152 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) \times (Q(6) + (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5153 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + Q((6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5154 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + Q(6)) - Q(((5+4) \times (3+2+1)))))) \\
5155 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
5156 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) \times (Q(6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5157 &:= (-9 \times (((8 \times 7) + 6) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
5158 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - (7 - 6 + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
5159 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - (Q(6) - Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5160 &:= ((-9 + ((8+7+6) \times Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
5161 &:= (-9+8 - (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - Q((Q(5+4) + 3+2+1)))))) \\
5162 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + ((6 \times 5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5163 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(6+5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
5164 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times Q(7+6)) - (Q(Q(5+4)) - Q((3+2+1)))))) \\
5165 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5166 &:= ((-9+8+7) \times (Q(6+Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
5167 &:= (-9-8 + Q(((Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) - Q(5))/Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5168 &:= ((-9+8) \times (Q(Q(7)) - Q((6+Q(Q((5+4) - (3+2+1))))))) \\
5169 &:= (Q((Q((-9+8+7)) + Q(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
5170 &:= (9 - Q(8)) \times (7 - 6 + 5 - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
5171 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5172 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 \times (6 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5173 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(6) + (5 + Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5174 &:= (Q(((-9+8) \times (Q(7) - Q(6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
5175 &:= (-9 + Q((8 + Q(((7+6+5) - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5176 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - ((7+6) + Q(Q(5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
5177 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5178 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 \times 6) \times (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5179 &:= (Q((Q((-9+8+7)) + Q(6))) + (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
5180 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - ((6+5) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5181 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) \times (6 - (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5182 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5183 &:= (-9+8 + Q(((Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) - Q(5))/Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5184 &:= (Q(((-9+8-7) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5185 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + Q((7+6-5)))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
5186 &:= (-9 - (((Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) \times 5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
5187 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5188 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(6) + Q(((5+4) + Q((3+2+1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5189 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5190 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5191 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) \times 4)))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5192 &:= ((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5193 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5194 &:= (Q(((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5195 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5196 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5197 &:= ((Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) \times 4) - ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5198 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5199 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + (3^4))) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5200 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q((4 \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5201 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q(((Q(Q(Q(3)))/Q(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5202 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((Q(Q(3)) \times (4 - Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5203 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5204 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5205 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 \times 3))) \times 4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5206 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((3 \times Q(4))) + (Q((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5207 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5208 &:= ((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times (4 - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5209 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5210 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5211 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4 - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5212 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4 - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5213 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2^3) \times Q(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5214 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times (4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5215 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 \times 3))) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5216 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5217 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5218 &:= (-1 + ((Q(Q(2 \times 3)) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5219 &:= ((Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5220 &:= ((Q((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5221 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5222 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 + Q(4)) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5223 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5224 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (Q((4 + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5225 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5226 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times ((4 + Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5227 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) \times Q(Q(4))) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5228 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + (Q(3) + Q(4)))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5189 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + Q(6))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5190 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5191 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (Q(7) + (6 + 5))) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5192 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5193 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + (Q(6) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5194 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5195 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5196 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5197 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5198 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + Q(6)) + ((5 + 4) \times Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5199 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + Q(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5200 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q(((7 - 6) - (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5201 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times (7 + 6)) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5202 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - 7) + Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5203 &:= (((-9 \times 8 - Q(Q(7))) + (6^5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5204 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(Q(7)) - (Q((6 + Q(5 + 4))) + Q((3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5205 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times Q(7))) - Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5206 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q(7) + Q(6)))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5207 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5208 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((Q(7) + 6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5209 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) + ((6 \times 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5210 &:= (((-9 - (Q(8 + 7) - Q(Q(6)))) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5211 &:= (-9 \times (Q((8 - 7) \times 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5212 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (Q(6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5213 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (Q(6) + Q(Q(5))))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5214 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times (Q(6) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5215 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + ((6 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5216 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((7 \times 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5217 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5218 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + 6) \times (Q(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5219 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + Q(6))) + (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5220 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (Q(7) \times (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5221 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5222 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - ((6 - Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5223 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (Q(6) - Q(Q(5))))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5224 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((Q(7) + 6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5225 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((Q(7) + 6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5226 &:= (((-9 - Q(8 + 7))/6) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5227 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 - Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5228 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (((7 \times 6) + Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5229 &:= (-1 + (((Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - Q(Q(4))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5230 &:= (((Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) - Q(Q(4))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5231 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5232 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + Q((4 + (5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5233 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5234 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5235 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5236 &:= (Q(((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(4 + 5))) + (Q(6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5237 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5238 &:= (-1 + ((Q(Q(2 \times 3)) \times 4) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5239 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5240 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)) \times (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5241 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - Q(Q(4)))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5242 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5243 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5244 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5245 &:= (((Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) + 4) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5246 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5247 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + 4) \times (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5248 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4) \times (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5249 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5250 &:= ((Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) - Q(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5251 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + 4) \times (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5252 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5253 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3 + Q(4))) + ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5254 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - ((Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5255 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2 + 3) + (Q(4) + Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5256 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 - ((3 - Q(4)) \times 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5257 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5258 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((4 \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5259 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - Q(Q(4)))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5260 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5261 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q((4 \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5262 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((4 \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5263 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - ((5 + 6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5264 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((Q(4) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5265 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5266 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times Q(Q(4))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5267 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5268 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times Q(Q(4))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5229 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - ((7 + Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5230 &:= (-9 - (Q((Q(8) + ((7 - 6) \times 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5231 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + (Q(6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5232 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + ((Q(6)/(5 + 4)) \times Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5233 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 \times 6) \times (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5234 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + Q(6))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5235 &:= ((((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) - Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5236 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5237 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5238 &:= 9 + Q(8 + 5 \times (7 + 6)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5239 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) \times ((7 + 6 + 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5240 &:= ((((-9 + Q(8 + 7)) - 6) \times Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5241 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7 + 6) \times (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5242 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5243 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (7 + Q(6))) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5244 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(((7 \times 6) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5245 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5246 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5247 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) - 7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5248 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5249 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 \times 6) \times (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5250 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) - 7 - 6) \times (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5251 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5252 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) + Q(Q(5 + 4))) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5253 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7 \times (6 + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5254 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (((7 \times 6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5255 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 + 6) \times 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5256 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5257 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (((7 + 6) + Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5258 &:= (((-9 - 8 - Q(Q(7))) + (6^5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5259 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7 + 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5260 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times 6)) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5261 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5262 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7))) - (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5263 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5264 &:= (((-9/(8 + 7 - 6)) + Q(Q(5 + 4))) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5265 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times (Q(6) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5266 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5267 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times Q(7)) + ((Q(6) + Q(5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5268 &:= ((-9 + Q(8) \times 7) \times (Q(6)/(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$5269 := (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5270 := (1 \times 2 + 3) \times (Q(\sqrt{4} \sqrt{Q(5)} + \sqrt{Q(\sqrt{Q(\sqrt{Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))})})$$

$$5271 := ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5272 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5273 := (-1 \times 2 + (((3 + 4) \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5274 := ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times (Q(4) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5275 := (((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) \times Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5276 := (-1 + 2 + (((3 + 4) \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5277 := (((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5278 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$5279 := (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times ((4 \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5280 := ((-1 + 2 + ((3 + 4) \times Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5281 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5282 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$5283 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((4 + (5 + 6))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5284 := (Q((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + 4))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5285 := ((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times (Q((Q(4) - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5286 := ((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4 + 5))) - (Q(Q(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5287 := ((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5288 := ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5289 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$5290 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$5291 := ((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 + 5) \times (6 - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$5292 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5293 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$5294 := (-1 - (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5295 := (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5296 := ((-1 - 2 + Q(((3 \times Q(4)) + Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5297 := (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5298 := ((-1 + Q((Q(2^3) + (4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5299 := (Q((-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - Q(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5300 := (((-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + Q(Q(4)))) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5301 := (Q((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) \times 4))) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5302 := (-1 - (((2 - Q(3)) \times (4 + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5303 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5304 := ((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5305 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4) - 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5306 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (Q((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5307 := (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) + Q(Q(6)))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5269 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 - 6 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$5270 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(((7 - 6) \times 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$5271 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - ((7 - 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$5272 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) - (Q(5 + 4) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$5273 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 \times Q(6)) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5274 := (-9 \times ((8 \times (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5275 := (((-9 \times (8 + 7 + 6)) \times Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5276 := (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times Q(Q(6))) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5277 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times ((Q(6) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$5278 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$5279 := (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + Q(6))) - (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5280 := ((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5281 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$5282 := ((-9 \times (((8 - 7) + Q(6)) - Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5283 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (7 + 6 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$5284 := (Q((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5285 := ((-9 + Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5286 := (-9 - 8 - ((7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5287 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 + 6 - Q(5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5288 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (6 + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$5289 := (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + Q(6))) + (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5290 := (Q((-9 - (8 \times (7 - 6 - 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5291 := ((-9 \times (Q((8 - 7) \times 6)) - Q(Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5292 := (((-9 - (Q(8) + Q(Q(7)))) + (6^5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5293 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5294 := (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$5295 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5296 := (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5297 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$5298 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$5299 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 + 6 - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5300 := (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times Q((6 \times 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5301 := (-9 - ((8 - (Q(7) \times (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5302 := (-9 + 8 - ((7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5303 := (-9 - (Q(8) \times (7 - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$5304 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - Q((7 + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$5305 := ((-9 + Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5306 := ((-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5307 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7)) - (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5308 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5309 &:= (-1 + ((2 + ((3 + 4) \times Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5310 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5311 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5312 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5313 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{3 \times 4}) - Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5314 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5315 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5316 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q(2^3))) - (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5317 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5318 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5319 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (4 - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5320 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5321 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5322 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(4 + 5) - (Q(Q(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5323 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5324 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5325 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(4))) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5326 &:= (-1 - 2 + Q(((3 \times Q(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5327 &:= (-1 \times 2 + Q(((3 \times Q(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5328 &:= (-1 + Q(((2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5329 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5330 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5331 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - ((Q(4) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5332 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5333 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5334 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (Q(3)^4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5335 &:= ((-1 + Q(Q((2 + 3 + 4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5336 &:= ((Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))^4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5337 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (Q(3)^4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5338 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5339 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (Q(3) \times (4 \times 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5340 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5341 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5342 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 - 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5343 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5344 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5345 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5346 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5347 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5308 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q((8 - 7 + 6))) + Q(((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5309 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + Q(6))) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5310 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 + (7 + 6) \times 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5311 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 - 6) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5312 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q((Q(((7 - 6) \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5313 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - 6 + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5314 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5315 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5316 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5317 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7) \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5318 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5319 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5320 &:= (-9 + Q((8 - ((7 + 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5321 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) / Q(6))) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5322 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 + 6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5323 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5324 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - Q(7)) \times (6 - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5325 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + 6) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5326 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5327 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q((8 + 7 - 6)))) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5328 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5329 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q((Q(7) - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5330 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + (7 + 6) \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5331 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times Q(7)) - Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5332 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5333 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (((7 + 6) + Q(Q(5 + 4))) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5334 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(((7 \times 6) + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5335 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) \times (7 + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5336 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5337 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5338 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (Q((Q(6) - (5 + 4))) + Q((3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5339 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7 + 6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5340 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q((6 \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5341 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times 6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5342 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q((Q(6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5343 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7 \times (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5344 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + (6 \times (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5345 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - ((7 \times 6) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5346 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5347 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (Q(6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5348 &:= ((Q((-1-2+(Q(3)+Q(4)))) \times (5+6)) + 7+8+9) \\
5349 &:= (-1-2+(Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4)-Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
5350 &:= (-1 \times 2+(Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4)-Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
5351 &:= (-1+(2 \times (Q(Q(3+4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5352 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (Q(4)-Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
5353 &:= (-1+2+(Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4)-Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
5354 &:= (-1+((2+3+4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
5355 &:= ((-1+(2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - 4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
5356 &:= (-1-2+(Q(((3 \times Q(4)) + Q(5)))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
5357 &:= (-1 \times 2+(Q(((3 \times Q(4)) + Q(5)))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
5358 &:= (-1+(Q((Q(2^3) + (4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
5359 &:= (Q((-1+2-(Q(3)-Q(4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
5360 &:= (-1+2+(Q(((3 \times Q(4)) + Q(5)))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
5361 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2+Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 \times 5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
5362 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5363 &:= (-1+(2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + Q((Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
5364 &:= ((-1+2+3) \times (Q((Q(4)+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
5365 &:= (-1+(Q(((2+Q(Q(3)) - 4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5366 &:= (Q((-1+((2+3) \times Q(4)))) + (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
5367 &:= ((-1+Q((2+Q(Q(3)))) - Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
5368 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{Q(3)}) - ((Q(Q(4)) - (5+6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
5369 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
5370 &:= ((-1+(2 \times (Q(3)+Q(4+5)))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
5371 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2+Q(Q(3)))) - ((4+Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
5372 &:= ((-1 \times 2+Q(Q(3))) \times ((4 \times (5+6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
5373 &:= (-1+(Q((Q((2 \times Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) + (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5374 &:= (-1 - (((2+3) - Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
5375 &:= (((-1 \times (2+3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9) \\
5376 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) \times (Q(4) - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5377 &:= ((-1-2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5378 &:= ((-1 \times 2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5379 &:= (-1+(Q((2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5380 &:= (-1+(Q(Q(2+3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5381 &:= ((-1+2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5382 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5383 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4)+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
5384 &:= (Q((-1+Q((2 \times Q(3)))) - Q(Q(4))) - (5 - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
5385 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (((Q(3) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
5386 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
5387 &:= (((-1 \times 2+Q(3)) \times (Q(4) + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
5348 &:= (((-9-8-Q(Q(7))) + (6^5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
5349 &:= (-9+Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5350 &:= (((-9-8-Q(7+6)) \times Q(5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
5351 &:= (-9+(Q(Q(8)) + (Q((7 \times 6)) - (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5352 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (((Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5353 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q((7 \times (6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5354 &:= (-9+(Q(Q(8)) + ((7 \times 6) + Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
5355 &:= (-9 \times ((8+7) - ((Q(6) + Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
5356 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) \times (6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5357 &:= (((-9-8) \times Q(7)) - ((6 - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
5358 &:= (-9-8+((7+Q(6)) \times (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5359 &:= (-9-8 - (Q((Q(7) - (6 - Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5360 &:= ((((-9 \times (8+7)) + Q(Q(6))) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
5361 &:= (-9+Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (Q(Q(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5362 &:= (-9+(Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) + Q(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5363 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7 \times (6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
5364 &:= (((-9+8-Q(Q(7))) + (6^5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
5365 &:= (Q((-9+(Q(8)+7))) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5366 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7) \times (6+5+Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5367 &:= (-9 - (Q((Q(8) - 7+6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5368 &:= ((-9-8-Q(Q(7))) + ((6^5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
5369 &:= (-9+Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
5370 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6+(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5371 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8+7)) + Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5372 &:= (-9+8 - ((7 \times (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5373 &:= (-9-8+(Q(7) \times ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
5374 &:= (-9+8+((7+Q(6)) \times (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5375 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5376 &:= ((-9+8) \times (Q((Q(7) - (6 - Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5377 &:= ((-9 \times (8+Q(7))) - ((Q(6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
5378 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - ((5+4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
5379 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7)) + (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5380 &:= ((-9+8+(Q(7) \times (6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
5381 &:= (-9+Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5382 &:= (-9 \times (((8-7) + Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
5383 &:= (-9+(Q(Q(8)) + Q(Q((7 - (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5384 &:= ((-9+8-Q(Q(7))) + ((6^5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
5385 &:= (((-9+8) \times Q(Q(7))) + ((6^5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
5386 &:= (((-9 - (8+7)) \times Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
5387 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5388 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) \times ((4 + Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5389 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((Q(Q(3)) - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5390 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times (4 + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5391 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times ((4 + Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5392 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) \times ((4 + Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5393 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times ((4 - 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5394 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5395 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (Q((4 \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5396 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3 + 4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5397 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 - 4 - 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5398 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((3 - 4 - 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5399 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((Q(3) + Q(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5400 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) / (4 + 5))) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5401 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 - 4 - 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5402 &:= ((-1 - Q(2 \times 3)) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5403 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (Q((4 + (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5404 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + (Q((4 + (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5405 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times ((4 - 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5406 &:= ((Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times (Q(4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5407 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5408 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5409 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((Q(3 + Q(4)) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5410 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5411 &:= (-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5412 &:= ((-1 - 2 - Q(3)) \times ((4 + Q((5 + 6))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5413 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5414 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5415 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5416 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5417 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5418 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5419 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4) \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5420 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5421 &:= (Q(((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4)) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5422 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5423 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5424 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5425 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5426 &:= (Q(Q(((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5427 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5388 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5389 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5390 &:= ((-9 - (Q(8) + (7 + 6 - Q(Q(5)))))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5391 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5392 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times Q((7 + 6 - 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5393 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q((7 - (6 - 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5394 &:= (((-9 + Q(((8 + 7) \times 6))) / (5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5395 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5396 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + ((Q(6) + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5397 &:= (-9 - (Q((Q(8) - 7 + 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5398 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + (Q((Q(6) - (5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5399 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 - (Q(6) + Q(5))) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5400 &:= (((-9 \times 8 - 7 - 6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5401 &:= ((-9 \times (Q((8 - 7) \times 6) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5402 &:= ((-9 - Q(8)) \times ((7 - 6 + Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5403 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - Q((Q((7 + 6 - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5404 &:= (-9 \times 8 + Q((Q((7 + 6 - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5405 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5406 &:= ((-9 \times Q((8 + 7 + 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5407 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5408 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - Q((7 - 6 + Q(5)))))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5409 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + Q(6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5410 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5411 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times Q(7)) - (6 - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5412 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5413 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - (7 - Q(6)))) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5414 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) / ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5415 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5416 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5417 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5418 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q((7 - 6 + Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5419 &:= ((Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) \times 6) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5420 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + (7 + 6) \times 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5421 &:= (-9 - (Q((8 + Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5422 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) \times (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5423 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times Q(7)) + (6 + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5424 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((Q(7) + (6 + 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5425 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5426 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q(Q((7 \times (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5427 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5428 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5429 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5430 &:= ((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + Q(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5431 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5432 &:= (((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) \times Q(4)) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5433 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5434 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5435 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5436 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times (Q(4) - 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5437 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q((Q(Q(3)) - (4 + Q(5)))))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5438 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - (Q((Q(4 + 5) - 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5439 &:= (Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5440 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((4 + (5 + 6))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5441 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5442 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5443 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(3 + 4) + Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5444 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(3 + 4) + Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5445 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 - (Q(3) - Q(4 + 5)))))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5446 &:= (Q((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + Q(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5447 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5448 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5449 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((Q(3) \times (Q(4) - Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5450 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5451 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5452 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((Q(3) \times (Q(4) - Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5453 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5454 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(3)) \times ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5455 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5456 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3 + 4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5457 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q((3 \times Q(4))) - Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5458 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5459 &:= ((Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) \times 4) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5460 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3)))/4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5461 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5462 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5463 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5464 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 \times 3) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5465 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5466 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5467 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5428 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - ((7 \times (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5429 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7 + 6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5430 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5431 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) - (6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5432 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + Q(((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5433 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times 7) + ((Q(6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5434 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + Q(6))) + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5435 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5436 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5437 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5438 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) \times (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5439 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5440 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7 - 6)) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5441 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times Q(6)) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5442 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5443 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5444 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5445 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5446 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (Q(7) + Q(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5447 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5448 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + ((Q(Q(6))/Q(5 + 4)) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5449 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - (Q(Q(5 + 4)) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5450 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8 + 7) + 6)) \times Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5451 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (Q(6) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5452 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + 6) \times (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5453 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7 \times (6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5454 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + 7 - 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5455 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5456 &:= ((-9 + ((Q(8 + 7) - 6) \times Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5457 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5458 &:= ((-9 - 8 - Q(Q(7))) + ((6^5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5459 &:= (-9 - 8 + Q((Q((7 + 6 - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5460 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q((6 \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5461 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (Q(7) \times (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5462 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7 + 6) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5463 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5464 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + Q((6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5465 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + Q((6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5466 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5467 &:= (-9 + Q(((8 \times (7 + 6 - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5468 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2 + Q(3)) \times ((4 + 5) + Q(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5469 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5470 &:= (-1 \times (((Q(2 \times 3) - Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5471 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5472 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + Q((4 + (5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5473 &:= (-1 - 2 + Q((Q(3 + 4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5474 &:= (-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(3 + 4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5475 &:= (Q((-1 + Q((2 + 3 + 4)))) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5476 &:= Q((-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5477 &:= (-1 + 2 + Q((Q(3 + 4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5478 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (Q(4) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5479 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q((4 + (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5480 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4) - (Q((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5481 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5482 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5483 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5484 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5485 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 + Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5486 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - (Q((Q(4 + 5) - 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5487 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5488 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5489 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5490 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5491 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times Q(4)))) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5492 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5493 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5494 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5495 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5496 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (4 + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5497 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + (4 - 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5498 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5499 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + (3^4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5500 &:= (Q((-1 - ((2 - 3) \times Q(4 + 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5501 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + (4 - 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5502 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q((3 \times Q(4)))) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5503 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5504 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(3 + 4) + Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5505 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 - (Q(3) - Q(4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5506 &:= (Q((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + Q(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5507 &:= (-1 + (((2^{Q(3)}) \times (4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5468 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 \times (Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5469 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) \times (7 + 6)) + Q(5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5470 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5471 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) + (7 + 6 - Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5472 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - 7 + 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5473 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5474 &:= ((-9 + 8 - Q(Q(7))) + ((6^5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5475 &:= (-9 + 8 + Q((Q((7 + 6 - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5476 &:= Q((-9 - (Q(8) - (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5477 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5478 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5479 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q((7 - 6 + Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5480 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (((Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5481 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5482 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5483 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q((7 - (6 - 5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5484 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 + Q(5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5485 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5486 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5487 &:= (-9 + (Q(8 + 7) + ((6 + Q(Q(5 + 4))) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5488 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q((6 \times 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5489 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5490 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + (7 - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5491 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) - (6 - 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5492 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5493 &:= (((-9 + Q((8 \times 7))) - Q(Q(6))) \times ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5494 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) \times (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5495 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5496 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 - (Q(6) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5497 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5498 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - Q((7 - 6 + Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5499 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times Q((7 - 6 + Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5500 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5501 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5502 &:= (-9 - (Q(((8 \times 7) + (6 + 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5503 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) + (7 - (6 - (5 + 4)))) + Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5504 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q((Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) / Q(5 + 4)))) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5505 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5506 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) \times (6 + Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5507 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + Q(Q(((6 \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

5508 := $((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
5509 := $(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
5510 := $(((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(4) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
5511 := $(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$
5512 := $(-1 + 2 - ((Q(3) \times (Q(4) - Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
5513 := $(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))))$
5514 := $(((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
5515 := $(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
5516 := $(Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
5517 := $(((-1 - (2^{Q(3)})) \times (Q(4) - Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
5518 := $((-1 + Q((Q(2 \times Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
5519 := $(-1 - ((Q(((2 + 3) + Q(4))) - Q(Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
5520 := $(-1 \times ((Q(((2 + 3) + Q(4))) - Q(Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
5521 := $(((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times 4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
5522 := $((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3 + 4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) + (6 \times Q((7 + 8 + 9))))))$
5523 := $(-1 + (Q((Q(2 \times 3) - 4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
5524 := $(-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
5525 := $(Q(Q((-1 + 2 \times 3))) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
5526 := $((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times (4 - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
5527 := $(Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))))$
5528 := $(-1 + (Q((Q(2 \times Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
5529 := $(-1 + (((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
5530 := $(-1 \times (((Q(2 \times 3) - Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
5531 := $(Q((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - Q(4))) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
5532 := $((-1 \times 2) \times ((3 + Q(Q(4))) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
5533 := $(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4) - (5 + 6))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$
5534 := $(-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - (Q(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))))$
5535 := $(-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
5536 := $(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
5537 := $((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) - 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
5538 := $((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
5539 := $(-1 - (Q(2 + Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
5540 := $(-1 \times (Q(2 + Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
5541 := $((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) - 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
5542 := $(((-1 - 2 + Q(3 + 4)) \times Q((5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))$
5543 := $(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
5544 := $((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
5545 := $((-1 + (2 \times Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)))) - (Q((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$
5546 := $((-1 + ((2 + 3 + 4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))$
5547 := $((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$

5508 := $(-9 - 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5509 := $((Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) \times 6) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
5510 := $(-9 + 8 - (Q(((7 \times 6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5511 := $((-9 + 8) \times (Q(((7 \times 6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5512 := $(Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 + 6 - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5513 := $(Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 + Q(Q((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))))$
5514 := $((-9 + 8 + ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
5515 := $(Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5516 := $(Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5517 := $(-9 \times (Q(8) - ((7 \times 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5518 := $((-9 \times (Q(8) - Q((7 - 6 + Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$
5519 := $((-9 - 8) \times (7 + Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
5520 := $((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(Q((7 - 6) \times 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
5521 := $(-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) - (6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5522 := $(-9 - (Q(((8 \times 7) + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
5523 := $(((-9 - Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5524 := $(Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) \times (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
5525 := $(Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q((Q(7) + (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
5526 := $(-9 \times ((8 + 7 + 6) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
5527 := $(-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7 + 6) - Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5528 := $(-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5529 := $((Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) \times 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
5530 := $((-9 + 8 - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
5531 := $(-9 + (Q(8) + Q((Q(7 + 6 - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
5532 := $(-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q((Q(7) + Q(6)) / (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5533 := $(-9 + (((Q(8 + 7) + Q(6 + 5)) \times Q(4)) + 3 + 2 + 1))$
5534 := $((-9 \times ((8 + 7 - 6) - Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
5535 := $(-9 \times (8 + (7 \times (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5536 := $(Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5537 := $(Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5538 := $(Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 + 6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5539 := $(-9 - ((Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(6) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5540 := $(((-9 + (Q(8 + 7) + 6)) \times Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
5541 := $(-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) - (6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
5542 := $((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7) - ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5543 := $(-9 + (8 \times (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
5544 := $((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((7 + 6 - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
5545 := $((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
5546 := $((-9 + (((8 + Q(Q(7))) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
5547 := $(Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + Q((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$

$$\begin{aligned}
5548 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q((2 \times Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5549 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5550 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3))/4) \times (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5551 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3 + 4))) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5552 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5553 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5554 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + (6 - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5555 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5556 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5557 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((Q(3) \times (4 - Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5558 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5559 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (4 - Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5560 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((Q(3) \times (4 - Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5561 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - ((4 \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5562 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5563 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5564 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5565 &:= (((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4))) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5566 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((3 \times Q(Q(4))) - ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5567 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - ((4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5568 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5569 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5570 &:= (((-1 + Q((2 - 3) + Q(4))) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5571 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5572 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5573 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5574 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5575 &:= (((((-1 + 2) \times 3) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5576 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5577 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) \times Q(Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5578 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5579 &:= ((-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3))) \times (4 \times 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5580 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5581 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5582 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5583 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) + (5 + 6))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5584 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((4 \times 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5585 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4))) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5586 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times (4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5587 &:= (-1 - ((2^{Q(3)}) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5548 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (Q(7) + Q(6))) + (Q(5 + 4) + Q((3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5549 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (Q(6) + (Q(5 + 4) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
5550 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5551 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (6 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5552 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - Q(((7 + 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5553 &:= (-9 \times 8 + Q(((7 + 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5554 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7 - 6) - Q(Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5555 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) \times (((7 - 6)^5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5556 &:= (-9 - (((8 + Q(Q(7))) - Q(Q(6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5557 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5558 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) \times (6 + Q(5 + 4))) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5559 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5560 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5561 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7) \times 6) - Q(Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5562 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (6 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5563 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(Q((7 - 6) \times 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5564 &:= (-9 - (Q((8 \times 7)) + ((Q(Q(6)) - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5565 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + 6 \times 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5566 &:= (-9 - (((8 + Q(7 + 6)) \times Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5567 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q((8 - 7 + 6)) + Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5568 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) - (6 - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5569 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8) + 7) + (6 - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5570 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - ((7 + Q(6)) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5571 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5572 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5573 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) + ((Q(6) + Q(5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5574 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + Q((6 \times Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5575 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - ((7 + Q(6 + Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5576 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (6 \times 5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5577 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) - Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5578 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q((6 \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5579 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) - (Q(6) - Q((Q(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5580 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5581 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - 7) \times 6) - Q(Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5582 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 \times (6 + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5583 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (6 + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5584 &:= (-9 - (Q((8 \times 7)) + ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5585 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (Q(6) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5586 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 \times Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5587 &:= (((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times Q(6 + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5588 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) - (Q((4 \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5589 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5590 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5591 &:= (((-1 + 2^{Q(3)}) \times (Q(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5592 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5593 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5594 &:= ((-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) \times (4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5595 &:= (Q((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5596 &:= (-1 - (Q(2^3) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5597 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2^3) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5598 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((3 \times Q((Q(4) - (5 + 6)))))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5599 &:= ((-1 + ((Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + 4) \times 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5600 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5601 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3)))) \times Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5602 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5603 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(4)) \times Q(Q(5))) - (Q(Q(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5604 &:= (((-1 - Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times (Q(4) - Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5605 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q((5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5606 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q((4 + (5 + 6))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5607 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(Q(3))) - ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5608 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5609 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5610 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) \times (4 - Q(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5611 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5612 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4) + ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5613 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5614 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(3) + Q((4 + (5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5615 &:= (-1 - (((2 + Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5616 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5617 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5618 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5619 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (4 - Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5620 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q(4) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5621 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5622 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5623 &:= (((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) \times Q(4)) - (Q((5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5624 &:= (-1 + Q((Q(2 \times 3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5625 &:= (Q((Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5626 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5627 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2 + 3) + (Q(4) + Q(5)))) + (Q(Q(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5588 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) + Q(6)) \times Q(5 + 4))) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5589 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times Q(7))) \times (6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5590 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8) + Q(7 + 6))) \times Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5591 &:= (-9 - ((8 - Q((7 + 6 - 5))) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5592 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + Q((6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5593 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5594 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 \times (6 - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5595 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 \times (6 - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5596 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + ((Q(6) + Q(5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5597 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (7 \times ((6 \times Q(5 + 4)) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5598 &:= 9 + Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5599 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5600 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + Q(6 + 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5601 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5602 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (6 \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5603 &:= (((-9 - (Q(8) + Q(7))) \times Q(6)) - (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5604 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + (7 + Q(6)))) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5605 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + 7 + 6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5606 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7 - 6) \times Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5607 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7 - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5608 &:= (-9 - 8 + Q(((7 + 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5609 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7 + 6)) + Q((Q(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5610 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8) + Q(7 + 6))) \times Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5611 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) - (7 - 6 + Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5612 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q(7)) \times (6 - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5613 &:= ((((-9 - (Q(8) + Q(7))) \times Q(6)) + 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5614 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times Q(7))) \times (Q(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5615 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5616 &:= (-9 + Q(((8 + 7) \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5617 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((Q(7) \times 6) - Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5618 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times Q(6) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5619 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5620 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5621 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 \times 7))) - (6 - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5622 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5623 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) \times (7 + 6 - (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5624 &:= (-9 + 8 + Q(((7 + 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5625 &:= Q((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5626 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) - Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5627 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(Q(7)) - Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5628 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (Q(3) \times (4 + Q(Q(5)))))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5629 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5630 &:= (((-1 + Q(((2 - 3) + Q(4)))) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5631 &:= ((Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times (4 + Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5632 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (4 + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5633 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5634 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5635 &:= 1 - 2 + (Q(3)^4 - Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5636 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5637 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (Q(3)^4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5638 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5639 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5640 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q(4) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5641 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - ((4 \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5642 &:= (-1 - (2 \times Q(3) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5643 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5644 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (Q((Q(4 + 5) - 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5645 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (Q(4) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5646 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times (4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5647 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) - (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5648 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5649 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5650 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5651 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) - Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5652 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5653 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5654 &:= (-1 + ((Q(Q(2 + 3)) \times (4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5655 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q(Q(4 + 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5656 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(Q(4 + 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5657 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (Q(3)^4)) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5658 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4 + 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5659 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) - (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5660 &:= (Q(((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)) - 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5661 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - (2 - (3 + (4 + 5)))))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5662 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5663 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + (3^4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5664 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5665 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) + Q(Q(4 + 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5666 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times 3) + Q(Q(4 + 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5667 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5628 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((Q(7) + (6 - Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5629 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) - (Q(6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5630 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((7 \times 6) - Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5631 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) - (6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5632 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((7 \times 6) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5633 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5634 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5635 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5)))))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5636 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + (7 - 6)))) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5637 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((Q(7) \times 6) - Q(Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5638 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - Q(((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5639 &:= ((-9 \times Q((Q(8) - (7 \times 6)))) - (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5640 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5641 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times Q(6)) + Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5642 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + ((Q(6) + Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5643 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (Q(Q(((7 - 6) \times 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5644 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7 - 6) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5645 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5646 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5647 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5648 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5649 &:= (((-9 \times Q((Q(8) - (7 \times 6)))) + 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5650 &:= ((-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 + 6) + Q(Q(5)))))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5651 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8 + 7)) + (6^5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5652 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - 7 + 6) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5653 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(Q(((7 - 6) \times 5)))))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5654 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 \times (Q((6 \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5655 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times Q(7))) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5656 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (Q(7) + Q(6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5657 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5658 &:= ((Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) \times 6) - (Q(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5659 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((Q(7) - Q(Q(6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5660 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6) - Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5661 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (7 + 6 - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5662 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7 + 6) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5663 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5664 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (((7 - 6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5665 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q((Q(7) - (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5666 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times Q(6 + Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5667 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) - (7 + 6 - Q(5)))))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5668 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5669 &:= 1 + Q(2 + Q(Q(3))) + 4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5670 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5671 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5672 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(4) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5673 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5674 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (Q(3) + Q(Q(4)))) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5675 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + Q(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5676 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3 + 4)))) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5677 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5678 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q(3) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5679 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5680 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5681 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5682 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5683 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5684 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5685 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5686 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 \times 3) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5687 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(3)^4) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5688 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5689 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5690 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + ((4 + Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5691 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) - 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5692 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5693 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - Q((4 + 5) \times 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5694 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 + 3) + (Q(4) - ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5695 &:= (((((-1 - 2) \times Q(3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5696 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5697 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5698 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5699 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5700 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 \times (3 + 4)))) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5701 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5702 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(4) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5703 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5704 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5705 &:= ((Q(((1 + Q(2 \times 3)) - 4) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5706 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3 + 4))) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5707 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5668 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (((7 \times Q(6)) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5669 &:= (((-9 \times Q((Q(8) - (7 \times 6)))) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5670 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5671 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - 7) \times 6) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5672 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q((6 + (Q(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5673 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((7 - 6) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5674 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(((7 - 6) \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5675 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5676 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5677 &:= (((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times Q(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5678 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5679 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (Q(7) \times (6 + 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5680 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times (Q(7) + (6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5681 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) \times 7) + Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5682 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(Q(7)) - Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5683 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - 7 + 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5684 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + Q(6))) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5685 &:= ((((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5686 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - ((6 - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5687 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q((Q(7) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5688 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (Q((7 + 6 - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5689 &:= ((-9 \times (Q((Q(8) - (7 \times 6))) - 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5690 &:= ((-9 + 8 - (Q(7) + (6 - Q(Q(5))))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5691 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 + 6) \times 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5692 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5693 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5694 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + 6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5695 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5696 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (6 \times Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5697 &:= (((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times Q(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5698 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(Q(7)) - Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5699 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(Q(7)) - Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5700 &:= ((-9 - (Q(8) - 7 - 6)) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5701 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5702 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q((7 + 6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5703 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q((7 + 6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5704 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5705 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + Q(Q(6))) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5706 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(6 + Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5707 &:= (((-9 - Q((8 + Q(7)))) / 6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$5708 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5709 := (Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) - (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5710 := (Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5711 := (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5712 := ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q((Q(3) + 4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5713 := (-1 + (Q(((2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5714 := (Q(((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) - Q(Q(4)))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5715 := (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - (4 + ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$5716 := (((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) - 4) \times (5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5717 := ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - Q((4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$5718 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5719 := ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$5720 := (((-1 - (Q(2 + 3) - Q(Q(4)))) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5721 := ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - Q((4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$5722 := ((-1 - 2 + ((Q(3) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5723 := ((-1 \times 2 + ((Q(3) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5724 := (-1 + (Q(2^3) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5725 := (((Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5726 := (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3 + 4))) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5727 := ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5728 := (-1 + (Q((Q(2 \times 3) + Q(4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5729 := (-1 + ((Q((2 \times (3 + 4))) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5730 := ((Q((-1 + 2 - 3) + Q(4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5731 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5732 := (-1 + ((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5733 := ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5734 := (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (Q((4 \times (5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5735 := (((-1 + ((2 + Q(Q(3))) \times Q(4))) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5736 := ((-1 - 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(4) + Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5737 := ((-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(4) + Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5738 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((Q(4) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5739 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5740 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5741 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + ((Q(4) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5742 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5743 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5744 := ((-1 + Q(((2 + 3) \times Q(4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5745 := (Q((-1 + Q((2 + 3 + 4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5746 := (Q(((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5747 := ((-1 + 2 + Q(((3^4) - 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5708 := (((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6 + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5709 := (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5710 := (((-9 \times (8 - 7) \times 6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5711 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5712 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + 6) \times (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5713 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5714 := ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5715 := (-9 \times (((8 + 7) \times 6) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5716 := ((-9 + ((Q(8) + Q(7 + 6)) \times Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5717 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5718 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 + (Q(6) \times (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5719 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - Q((Q(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5720 := (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7 + 6)) - Q(Q(Q((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5721 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5722 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5723 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) - ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5724 := (-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - (Q(6 + Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5725 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5726 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5727 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7 + 6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5728 := (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5729 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q((Q(7) + ((6 \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5730 := (-9 + ((Q(8) + Q(7 + Q(6))) \times ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5731 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7 + 6) - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5732 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + ((Q(Q(6)) - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5733 := (-9 \times (8 - ((7 + Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5734 := ((-9 + Q((8 + Q(7)))) - (6 - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5735 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((Q(7) - (6 - (5 + 4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5736 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + Q(((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5737 := ((-9 \times (8 + Q(7))) - ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5738 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + (6 \times Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5739 := (((-9 - Q(8)) \times 7) - ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5740 := (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5741 := (((-9 \times Q(8 + 7)) + (6^5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5742 := (-9 + ((Q(8) + 7) \times Q(Q(((6 \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5743 := ((-9 \times (8 + Q(7))) + (6 + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5744 := (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - ((6 - Q(5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5745 := ((-9 + (8 \times Q(7))) \times ((6 \times Q(5)) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5746 := (-9 + (Q((8 + Q(7))) + (6 + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5747 := (((-9 - 8) \times Q(7)) + ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5748 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5749 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5750 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5751 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5752 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5753 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4) - (5 + 6)))))) - (7 + 8 + 9) \\
5754 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5755 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5756 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5757 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5758 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((4 \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5759 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((4 \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5760 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(3) + 4)) + Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5761 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5762 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((4 \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5763 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - ((4^5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5764 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5765 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + ((Q(4) - (5 + 6)) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5766 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times (4 + 5)) + (6 + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5767 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 \times 3))) \times 4) + ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5768 &:= (-1 + ((Q(Q(2 + 3)) \times (4 + 5)) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5769 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times ((4^5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5770 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times ((4^5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5771 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((Q(3 + 4) + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5772 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times ((4^5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5773 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times ((4^5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5774 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5775 &:= (-1 + Q((Q(2 + 3) + (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5776 &:= Q((-1 \times (Q(2^3) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5777 &:= (-1 + 2 + Q(((3^4) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5778 &:= (-1 + ((Q(Q(2 \times 3)) \times 4) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5779 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times Q(Q(4))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5780 &:= (((-1 - (Q(2 + 3) - Q(Q(4)))) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5781 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5782 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q((Q(4) - 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5783 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5784 &:= ((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + Q((4 + (5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5785 &:= ((-1 - Q((2 \times Q(3) + Q(4)))) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5786 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times Q(4))) + (Q((5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5787 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2 - 3) + Q(4 + 5)))) - (Q(6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5748 &:= (-9 + ((8 + Q(7)) \times ((6 - 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5749 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5750 &:= (((-9 + 8 - Q(7 + 6)) \times Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5751 &:= (-9 \times ((Q(8) + 7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5752 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5753 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) + (Q(6) - (5 + 4)))))) - (3 + 2 + 1) \\
5754 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5755 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - ((Q(6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5756 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7 \times (6 + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5757 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q(7 \times (6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5758 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q((7 + 6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5759 &:= (-9 - 8 + Q(((7 - 6) - (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5760 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7)))/6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5761 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8 + 7)) + ((6^5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5762 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - ((7 \times (6 - Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5763 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (6 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5764 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - ((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5765 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times Q(6)) + Q(Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5766 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5767 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + Q(6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5768 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times 7) - (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5769 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) \times (6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5770 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7 - 6) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5771 &:= (-9 - ((Q((Q(8) + (7 - 6))) - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5772 &:= (-9 - ((8 - Q(7)) \times (Q(6) + (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5773 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5774 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q((7 + 6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5775 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q((7 + 6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5776 &:= Q(((((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5777 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) - (7 + 6 - Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5778 &:= 9 \times (8 - 7 + 6 + Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5779 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 - (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5780 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 - (Q(6) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5781 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times Q(7)) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5782 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5783 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 - 6) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5784 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + Q(Q(6)))))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5785 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5786 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5787 &:= (((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times Q(6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$5788 := (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$5789 := (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5790 := (((-1 - 2) \times Q((3 \times 4))) + Q(Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5791 := ((-1 + Q(Q(2 \times 3))) - (4 - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5792 := (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) - (4 - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5793 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5794 := (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5795 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q(4) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5796 := (Q((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3)))/Q(4))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5797 := (-1 + 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5798 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4) - 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5799 := (-1 + (Q((2 \times ((3 + 4) \times 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5800 := (Q(((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) - Q(4 + 5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5801 := ((-1 + (2 \times Q((Q(3 + 4) + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5802 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (Q((5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$5803 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5804 := (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$5805 := (Q((-1 + Q((2 + 3 + 4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5806 := (Q(((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5807 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (4 + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5808 := ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5809 := (-1 + (((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5810 := ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(3) + 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5811 := ((Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3))^4) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5812 := (((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5813 := (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5814 := ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5815 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5816 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$5817 := (-1 - 2 + ((Q((Q(3) + 4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5818 := (-1 \times 2 + ((Q((Q(3) + 4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5819 := (Q((-1 + 2 + (3^4))) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5820 := ((Q((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5821 := (-1 + 2 + ((Q((Q(3) + 4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5822 := (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5823 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 - 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5824 := (Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))/Q(4 + 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5825 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 - 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5826 := (((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4 + 5) - 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5827 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(4) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5788 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7)) - ((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5789 := (-9 - (8 \times Q(7) + ((6 - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5790 := (((-9 - 8 + 7) \times (Q(6) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5791 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) - 7 - 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5792 := (((-9 - Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - ((6 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5793 := ((-9 \times (8 \times Q(7) + 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5794 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) \times ((6 \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5795 := (((-9 - (Q(8) \times (7 + 6))) \times 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5796 := (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) \times (Q(6) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5797 := ((-9 - 8) \times ((Q(7) \times 6) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5798 := (((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5799 := (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5800 := ((-9 + ((8 \times 7) + (6 + 5))) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5801 := (((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times Q(6)) - 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5802 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - Q(((6 + 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5803 := (-9 - 8 - ((Q(7) - (6 + Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5804 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (((7 + 6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5805 := (((((-9 - 8) \times Q(7)) - 6) \times 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5806 := ((-9 \times (Q((8 + 7 + 6)) + Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5807 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5808 := ((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times Q((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5809 := ((-9 \times Q((8 - 7 + 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5810 := ((-9 + 8 - 7 - (Q(6) - Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5811 := ((-9 \times 8 - 7) - ((Q(6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5812 := ((-9 - 8 + Q(7 \times (6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5813 := (-9 - 8 - (((7 \times 6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5814 := (-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5815 := ((-9 + Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6))) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5816 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + ((6 \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5817 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + Q((Q(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5818 := (((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$5819 := (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5820 := (((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(Q(7))))/6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5821 := ((-9 + (8 + 7 + 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + (4 \times Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5822 := (-9 - ((Q(8) \times 7) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5823 := (-9 + (8 \times Q(((7 \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5824 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q((Q(7) + (6 + 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5825 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((Q(7) + 6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5826 := (-9 + (((Q(8) + Q(7 + 6)) \times Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5827 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7 + 6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5828 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5829 := (Q((-1 + 2 + (3^4))) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5830 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5831 := (Q((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - Q(4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5832 := (-1 + ((2 \times Q((3 \times Q(4)))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5833 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5834 := (Q((Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) + 4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5835 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5836 := (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (Q((4 + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5837 := (-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - (4 \times (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$5838 := (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5839 := ((Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) \times 4) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5840 := (-1 + ((2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5841 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5842 := (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5843 := ((Q((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4)))) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5844 := (-1 - ((2 - Q((Q(3) + 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5845 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(3) + 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5846 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (Q((5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5847 := ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q((5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5848 := (-1 + (Q((Q((2 \times Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5849 := ((Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5850 := ((-1 + Q((2 + (3 + (4 + 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5851 := ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q((5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5852 := (((-1 \times 2) - Q(3)) \times ((4 \times (5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5853 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 + Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5854 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5855 := (-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5856 := (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) \times (4 - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5857 := (((-1 - 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5858 := (-1 \times ((2^{Q(3)}) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5859 := (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (4 - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5860 := (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) \times (4 - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5861 := (-1 + ((2 \times Q((Q(3 + 4) + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5862 := ((-1 \times 2 + (Q(3^4)) - (Q((5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5863 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5864 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5865 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5866 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 - (Q((5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5867 := (-1 - (((2^3) \times (4 - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5828 := ((-9 + 8 + Q(7 \times (6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5829 := (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + (Q(6) + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5830 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (((7 + 6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5831 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((7 + 6 - 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5832 := (-9 \times 8 - (Q(Q((7 + 6 - 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5833 := ((-9 + Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6))) - (Q(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5834 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5835 := ((-9 + (8 \times Q(7) + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5836 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((7 \times 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5837 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times ((6 \times Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5838 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (Q(6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5839 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (((7 + Q(Q(6))) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5840 := (-9 + 8 - (Q(7) + ((Q(6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5841 := (-9 + (Q((8 + Q(7))) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5842 := (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7 + 6) \times (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5843 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) \times (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5844 := (-9 - 8 - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times (Q(5 + 4) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5845 := (-9 + (Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6)) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5846 := (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7 \times (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5847 := ((-9 \times 8 + Q(7 \times (6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5848 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (((7 \times 6) + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5849 := (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7 + 6))) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5850 := (((-9 - 8 + 7) + Q(6)) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5851 := ((-9 \times Q(8 + 7)) + ((6^5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5852 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) - (Q(Q(5 + 4)) + Q((3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5853 := (((-9 \times 8) \times Q(7)) + (6 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5854 := (((-9 - 8 - Q(7)) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5855 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5856 := ((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times (6 - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5857 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) - (6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5858 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + 6 \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5859 := (-9 \times ((Q((8 + Q(7))) + 6) / (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5860 := ((((-9 - Q(8 + 7)) / 6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5861 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (Q(6) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5862 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) + 7 + 6)) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5863 := (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - (6 - Q(((5 + 4) + Q((3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5864 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5 + 4)) - Q((3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5865 := ((-9 + Q(((8 \times 7) - Q(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5866 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((7 \times 6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5867 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5868 &:= (((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times (4 - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5869 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5870 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q(4)) \times ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5871 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5872 &:= ((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5873 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5874 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - 4)) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5875 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4))) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5876 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5877 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(((3 + Q(4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5878 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(((3 + Q(4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5879 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + (3 + (4 + 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5880 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2 \times 3) + (4 + 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5881 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5882 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) - (4 \times Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5883 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - Q((4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5884 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5885 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5886 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5887 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times Q((4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5888 &:= (-1 \times (2^{Q(3)} + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5889 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5890 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5891 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5892 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5893 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5894 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5895 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5896 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - (4 + Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5897 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q(3) + ((Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5898 &:= ((-1 + Q((Q(2 \times 3) + (Q(4) + Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5899 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2 + (3^4)) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5900 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)) \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5901 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5902 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5903 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5904 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5905 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5906 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5907 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5868 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7 - ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5869 &:= ((-9 \times ((Q(8) \times 7) + (6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5870 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5871 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - ((7 - 6) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5872 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - ((7 - (6 \times 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5873 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) + Q(((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5874 &:= ((-9 - 8 - Q(7)) \times (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5875 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + Q(Q(6))) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5876 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5877 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + 6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5878 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (((7 \times 6) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5879 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) \times ((7 + 6 - 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5880 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7 + 6)) \times (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5881 &:= (-9 - ((Q((8 - 7) \times 6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5882 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - ((Q(6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5883 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (7 + 6 - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5884 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7 \times (6 + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5885 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6))) - (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5886 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + Q(6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5887 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + 6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5888 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - Q(Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5889 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 - (6 - 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5890 &:= ((-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5891 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - ((7 - 6 - 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5892 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) - Q((6 \times Q(((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5893 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(6 + Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5894 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5895 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - Q((Q(7) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5896 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) - ((Q(6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5897 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (7 + (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5898 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7 + 6) \times (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5899 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) + (7 - 6 - 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5900 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (6 + 5))) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5901 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (6 - 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5902 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(7 \times (6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5903 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(Q((7 + 6 - 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5904 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times ((7 + 6 + 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5905 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5906 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + (Q(7) - Q(Q(6)))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5907 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) + (7 + 6 - Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5908 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (4 - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5909 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5910 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (4 - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5911 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (4 - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5912 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(3) + 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5913 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(3) + 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5914 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((Q(4) + (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5915 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5916 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(3) + 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5917 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5918 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5919 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5920 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q((4 \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5921 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4)) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5922 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5923 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5924 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5925 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4)) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5926 &:= (((-1 + 2 - Q(Q(Q(3)))) / Q(4)) + ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5927 &:= (-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(3) + ((4 \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5928 &:= (-1 + Q((Q(2 \times 3) + (Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5929 &:= Q(((((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5930 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5931 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + ((4 - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5932 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5933 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5934 &:= (Q(((((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5935 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - Q(Q(4 - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5936 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - Q(Q(4 - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5937 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5938 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5939 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5940 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 \times Q((Q(4) + Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5941 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2^3) \times (4 + 5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5942 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5943 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times Q((Q(4) + Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5944 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5945 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4) - 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5946 &:= (((-1 - 2 + Q(3)) \times Q((4 + Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5947 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5908 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5909 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5910 &:= (((-9 + Q((Q(8) + (7 - Q(6)))))) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5911 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5912 &:= (-9 - 8 + Q((7 \times (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5913 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (7 + 6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5914 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5915 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5916 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) + Q(7 + 6)) \times Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5917 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q((8 + 7 - 6)))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5918 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7 \times (6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5919 &:= ((Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) \times 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5920 &:= (-9 + Q(((8 \times 7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5921 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5922 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7 \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5923 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times Q(7) + (Q(6) + Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5924 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (((7 + 6) \times 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5925 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5926 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) - ((Q(6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5927 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((Q(7) + (6 + 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5928 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((Q(7) + (6 + 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5929 &:= Q((-9 - 8 + (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5930 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5931 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + Q(6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5932 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (7 + 6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5933 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - Q(7)) + (6 + 5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5934 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - Q((6 \times Q(((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5935 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5936 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (Q(6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5937 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q((8 + 7 - 6)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5938 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7 \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5939 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + (Q(6) + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5940 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) \times (6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5941 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q((Q((7 + 6 - 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5942 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q((6 \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5943 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) \times (7 - Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5944 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - Q(7)) - Q(Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5945 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (6 - 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5946 &:= (Q((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5947 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6))) - ((5 + 4) - Q((3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$5948 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5949 := (-1 + (2 \times ((Q(Q(3)) + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5950 := ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(3) + 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5951 := (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3 + 4) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5952 := ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3 + 4) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5953 := (-1 - (2 \times ((3 \times Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5954 := (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - 4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5955 := ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5956 := (-1 - ((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5957 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5958 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5959 := (Q(((-1 + 2 + (3^4)) - 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5960 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5961 := (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5962 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5963 := ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 + Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5964 := (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$5965 := (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5966 := (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5967 := ((-1 + 2 + (Q(3^4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5968 := ((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times (4 - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5969 := (-1 + (((2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5970 := (((Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) - Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5971 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5972 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((Q(4) \times (5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5973 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5974 := (-1 - (((2 + 3) - Q(4)) \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5975 := ((((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(4)) \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5976 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) \times (Q(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5977 := ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5978 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5979 := ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5980 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5981 := (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4)) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5982 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(4) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5983 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5984 := (-1 + ((2 + Q((Q(3) + 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5985 := (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4)) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$5986 := ((-1 - 2 + Q((3 + (Q(4) \times 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$5987 := (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 - 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$5948 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5949 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((7 - Q(6)) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5950 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 + 6) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5951 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5952 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5953 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5954 := (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5955 := (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (6 + 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5956 := (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7 \times (6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5957 := (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7 \times (6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5958 := (-9 \times (Q(8) - (7 - 6 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5959 := ((-9 + Q(8)) - (Q(Q((7 + 6 - 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5960 := (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (7 + 6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5961 := (-9 + ((8 \times Q(7) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5962 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (((7 + 6) \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5963 := (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (6 - Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5964 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((7 - (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5965 := ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + ((Q(6) + Q(5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5966 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5967 := (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5968 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7)) + Q(Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5969 := (((-9 - Q(8)) \times 7) - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5970 := (-9 + (Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5971 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + Q(6)) + (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5972 := (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (6 + 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5973 := ((-9 + Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q((Q(6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5974 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7 \times (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5975 := ((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - Q((6 \times 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5976 := 9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7) + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5977 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7 - (6 - 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5978 := (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5979 := (((-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7)) + (6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5980 := (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) + (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5981 := (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + ((Q(6) + Q(5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5982 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$5983 := (-9 - 8 + ((Q(7) + (6 + 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5984 := (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + 6 \times 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$5985 := (-9 \times (Q(8) - Q(((7 \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5986 := ((-9 - Q(8)) \times ((7 + 6 + 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$5987 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) - (6 \times 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$5988 := ((-1 + Q((2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))/Q(4+5)))))) - Q(6+7+8+9))$$

$$5989 := (Q(((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (4 - 5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))$$

$$5990 := ((-1 + 2 + Q((3 + (Q(4) \times 5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9))$$

$$5991 := (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3+4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))))))$$

$$5992 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((4 + (5+6))) + 7+8+9))$$

$$5993 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$5994 := (((-1 + Q(2+3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$5995 := (-1 + (Q(Q((2+3+4)) + ((5+6) - Q((7+8+9))))))$$

$$5996 := ((Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3))^4) + ((5+6) - Q((7+8+9))))$$

$$5997 := ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$5998 := ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$5999 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$6000 := (Q((Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) + 4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$6001 := (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) - (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$6002 := ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$6003 := (((-1 + Q(2^3)) \times Q(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))$$

$$6004 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) \times (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$6005 := (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (4 \times (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9))))))$$

$$6006 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (((4+5) \times 6) + 7+8+9))$$

$$6007 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q((Q(4) - (5+6))) - Q((7+8+9))))))$$

$$6008 := (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 \times 5) - Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$6009 := (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (5 - Q(6+7+8+9))))))$$

$$6010 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$6011 := (-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$6012 := ((-1 \times 2) \times ((3 + Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))$$

$$6013 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))$$

$$6014 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$6015 := (((-1 + Q((Q(2 \times 3) - 4))) \times 5) + Q(6+7+8+9))$$

$$6016 := (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))))))$$

$$6017 := ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))))))$$

$$6018 := (-1 - ((2^{Q(3)}) - (Q(Q(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$6019 := (-1 \times ((2^{Q(3)}) - (Q(Q(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$6020 := ((-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$6021 := ((-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3+4)) + Q(Q(5)))) - (6+7+8+9))$$

$$6022 := (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9))))))$$

$$6023 := (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3) + (4 - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))))))$$

$$6024 := ((-1 + Q(2+3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$6025 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((4 + Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$6026 := (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3+4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$5988 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) - 7 + 6)) + (Q(Q(5+4)) - (3+2+1)))$$

$$5989 := (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) + (Q(6) \times (5 + Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$5990 := (((-9 - 8 + 7) \times (Q(6) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4+3+2+1))$$

$$5991 := (-9 + (Q(((8 \times 7) - Q(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$5992 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 + Q(Q(Q(((6 \times 5)/(4+3+2+1)))))))$$

$$5993 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + Q((Q(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$5994 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7 \times (6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)))$$

$$5995 := ((-9 + Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6))) - (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$5996 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) - Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$5997 := (-9 + 8 - ((7 \times Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$5998 := ((((-9+8) \times 7) \times Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$5999 := (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) + (6+5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$6000 := (((-9+8+Q(Q(7)))/6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$6001 := (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$6002 := ((-9 \times (8 - Q((7 - 6 + Q(5)))) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$6003 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(6 + Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))$$

$$6004 := ((-9 \times ((8+7) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4+3+2+1))$$

$$6005 := (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6006 := ((-9 \times Q((8+7+6))) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6007 := (-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q(7+6) + (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6008 := (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7+6) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6009 := (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) + (7 - Q(6+5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6010 := (-9 - (Q(8+7) + (6 - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6011 := (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (Q(7+6)) + Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6012 := (-9 - 8 + (Q(7 \times (6+5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$6013 := (-9 - (Q(8) \times 7 - ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6014 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((7 \times 6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6015 := ((-9 + Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6))) - (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$6016 := (-9 - (Q(8+7) + ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6017 := (-9 - (Q((Q(8) - 7 + 6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6018 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - ((6 \times 5) \times Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6019 := ((Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) \times 6) - (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$6020 := ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5)))) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$6021 := (-9 + ((Q(8) + (Q(7) \times (6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$6022 := (-9 - (Q(8+7) - (6 + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6023 := (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (7 + Q(6+5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6024 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) - (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$6025 := (-9 + (Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6)) + (5 + Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6026 := ((-9 \times Q((8+7+6))) - (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6027 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6027 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7 + 6) + Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6028 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6028 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7 \times (6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6029 &:= (-1 + ((Q((2 \times (3 + 4))) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6029 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6030 &:= ((-1 + (Q(2 + Q(3)) + Q(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6030 &:= ((-9 - (Q(8) - Q((7 - 6 + Q(5)))))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6031 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6031 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7 + 6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6032 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 \times ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6032 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + ((6 \times 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6033 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6033 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((Q((Q(7) + 6))/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6034 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6034 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6035 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 + 4) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6035 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((Q(7) + 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6036 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((3 + 4) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6036 &:= (((-9 \times Q((8 + 7 + 6))) + 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6037 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6037 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6)) + (Q(5 + 4) + Q((3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6038 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6038 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) + (7 - (6 \times Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6039 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6039 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - Q(7 + 6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6040 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6040 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6041 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - (Q(Q(4)) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6041 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) - (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6042 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6042 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((7 \times Q(Q(6)))/(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6043 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6043 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times ((7 + 6) + Q(5 + 4))) + Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6044 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6044 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6045 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6045 &:= (((-9 + Q(8) \times 7) - Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6046 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 \times Q(3))) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6046 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (Q(7) + Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6047 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - Q((4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) & 6047 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6048 &:= (-1 - ((2^{Q(3)}) - Q(Q((4 - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))) & 6048 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((7 + 6 - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6049 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6049 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((Q((Q(7) + 6))/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6050 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3)) - Q(4)) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6050 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q(((7 + 6) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6051 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 - 4) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6051 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) - ((Q(6) + Q(5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6052 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((3 - 4) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6052 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7 + 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6053 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6053 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) + ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6054 &:= (-1 - (((2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6054 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8 + 7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6055 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6055 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((Q(7) + (6 + 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6056 &:= ((Q((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q((5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) & 6056 &:= (((-9 \times Q((8 + 7 + 6))) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6057 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) + Q((Q(4) - 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6057 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + Q(Q(Q(((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6058 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q((4 \times 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6058 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + (6 + Q(Q(5))))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6059 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2 + Q(3)) + Q(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6059 &:= ((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6060 &:= ((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + Q((Q(4) - 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6060 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (Q(6) + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6061 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (Q((4 \times 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6061 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 + 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6062 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q((4 \times 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6062 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6 + Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6063 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6063 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (((Q(7) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6064 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6064 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7 + 6) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6065 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6065 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((Q(7) + 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6066 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (Q(Q((4 + 5 - 6))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6066 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - ((7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6067 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6068 &:= (-1+2+(Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6069 &:= (-1+(Q((2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4+5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
6070 &:= (((-1-2-(Q(3)-Q(Q(4)))) \times Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
6071 &:= (Q(((-1-2+Q(Q(3))) - 4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6072 &:= (-1+2-(Q(3)+(Q(Q(4)) - ((5+6) \times Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
6073 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + (4 - (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
6074 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+3) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
6075 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+3) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
6076 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2+3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
6077 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4)) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6078 &:= (-1 - ((2^{Q(3)}) - (Q(Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
6079 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{Q(3)}) - (Q(Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
6080 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) \times ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
6081 &:= (-1-2+(Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4 - 5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
6082 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4 - 5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
6083 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2^3) \times Q(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
6084 &:= ((-1+2+3) \times Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
6085 &:= (-1+2+(Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4 - 5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
6086 &:= (((-1-2+Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - ((5+6) \times Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
6087 &:= (((-1-2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4)+5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
6088 &:= (-1-2-(Q(3) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
6089 &:= (((-1+Q(2+3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
6090 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) - (Q((Q(4)+5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
6091 &:= (Q((-1+((2+3) \times Q(4)))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
6092 &:= (-1+2-(Q(3) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
6093 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6094 &:= (((-1 - (2+3)) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
6095 &:= (((-1 \times (2+3)) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
6096 &:= (-1 + ((2 - Q(3)) \times ((4+Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6097 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times ((4+Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6098 &:= (((-1+2-3) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
6099 &:= (-1 - (((2-3) \times 4) \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6100 &:= (((-1 - (2 - (3+4))) \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6101 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6102 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (Q((Q(4)+5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
6103 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6104 &:= (-1 - ((2+3) \times (4 - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
6105 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) \times (4 - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6106 &:= (-1-2+(Q(3) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6067 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7 - (6+5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6068 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q((Q(7)+6 \times 5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6069 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7+6)+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6070 &:= 9 + Q(Q(8+7-6)) - 5 \times Q(4+3+2+1) \\
6071 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) \times (((7-6) \times 5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6072 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8+7) \times (Q(6) - (5+4))) + 3+2+1)) \\
6073 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + (Q(6) \times (5+4))) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
6074 &:= (Q((-9+8+(Q(7)+6 \times 5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
6075 &:= (-9 + Q((Q(8) - (7 - (6+5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6076 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((7 \times 6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6077 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) + ((Q(6) + Q(5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6078 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)+7) + (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6079 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) - (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6080 &:= (-9+8 - (Q(7+6) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6081 &:= ((-9+8) \times (Q(7+6) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6082 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times Q(7)) + (Q(6+Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6083 &:= (-9+8 + Q((Q(7) - (6 - (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6084 &:= Q((((-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
6085 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8+7) - Q((6 \times 5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
6086 &:= (-9 - (((Q(8) - (7 + Q(Q(6)))) \times 5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6087 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
6088 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - Q(((6 \times 5) - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6089 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7)) + Q(6+5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6090 &:= (-9+8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6091 &:= (-9 + ((Q((8-7) \times 6) + Q(5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6092 &:= (-9+8-7 + ((Q(6) + Q(5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6093 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + ((Q(6) + Q(5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6094 &:= (Q((-9+8+(Q(7)+6 \times 5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
6095 &:= (((-9-8) \times 7) - (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6096 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) \times (Q(6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6097 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8)+7) \times (Q(6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6098 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times 7) + (6 - Q(Q(Q(((5+4) - (3+2+1)))))))) \\
6099 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q(7+Q(6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
6100 &:= ((((-9+8+7) \times 6) + Q(5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
6101 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((7 \times 6)) + (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6102 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (Q((7-6+Q(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
6103 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)+7) + (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6104 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) \times 7 - Q(Q(Q(((6 \times 5)/(4+3+2+1))))))) \\
6105 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6106 &:= ((-9+8+7) + ((Q(6) + Q(5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$6107 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6108 := (-1 + ((Q(Q(2 \times 3)) \times 4) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6109 := (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6110 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$6111 := (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6112 := (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) - Q(4)) \times (5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6113 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6114 := (Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))/Q(4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$6115 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6116 := ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6117 := ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - Q((Q(4) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$6118 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - Q((Q(4) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$6119 := (Q(((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)) - 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6120 := ((-1 + Q(2 + Q(3))) \times (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6121 := ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - Q((Q(4) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$6122 := (-1 - 2 + ((Q(3) - 4) \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6123 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$6124 := (-1 - ((2 - (3 + 4)) \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6125 := ((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4))) \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6126 := (-1 + 2 + ((Q(3) - 4) \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6127 := (((-1 - 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6128 := ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((4 \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6129 := (Q((-1 + 2 + (3^4))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6130 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6131 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q((4 \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6132 := ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((4 \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6133 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6134 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6135 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6136 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6137 := (((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6138 := ((-1 + Q((2 + (3^4)))) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6139 := (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6140 := (-1 \times (Q((2 \times (3 + 4))) - ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$6141 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6142 := (-1 - 2 - (((Q(3) - Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6143 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((4 + Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6144 := (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6145 := ((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6146 := (-1 + 2 - (((Q(3) - Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6107 := (((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7) + (Q(6) \times 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6108 := (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) \times (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6109 := (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6110 := (((-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6111 := (-9 \times ((8 \times Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6112 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6113 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - ((6 \times Q(Q(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6114 := (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6115 := ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6116 := (-9 - ((8 - 7 - 6) \times Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6117 := (-9 - (Q((8 + 7 + 6)) - (Q(Q(5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6118 := (-9 - 8 - (((Q(7) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6119 := (-9 + 8 - ((7 + 6 - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6120 := (((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) + Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6121 := (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6122 := (-9 - (Q(((8 \times 7) + 6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6123 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6124 := ((-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) + 6 \times 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6125 := (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6126 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) - (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6127 := (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + ((6 \times 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6128 := ((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times Q((6 \times 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6129 := ((Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6130 := ((Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) + (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6131 := (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6132 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6133 := (((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7) - (6 \times Q(5 + 4)))) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6134 := (-9 + 8 - (((Q(7) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6135 := (-9 + (Q(8) \times ((7 - 6 - 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6136 := ((-9 + Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6137 := ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6138 := (-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + (6 + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6139 := ((Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) \times 6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6140 := ((-9 + 8 + Q((Q(7) + 6 \times 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6141 := (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((Q(6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6142 := (-9 - (Q(((8 \times 7) + 6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6143 := ((-9 \times (8 \times Q(7) + Q(6))) - (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6144 := ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6145 := (-9 + (Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6146 := (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) - ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6147 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3+4) + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
6148 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) + 5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6149 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2+3) + Q(4)) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6150 &:= ((-1 - (Q(2+3) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
6151 &:= (Q((Q((-1+2+Q(3))) - Q(4))) - (5+Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
6152 &:= ((-1-2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6153 &:= ((-1-2+Q((3+Q(4+5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
6154 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((3+Q(4+5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
6155 &:= (-1 - (Q((2 \times Q(3))) \times (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
6156 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 \times Q(3))) \times (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
6157 &:= ((-1+2+Q((3+Q(4+5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
6158 &:= (-1-2+(Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6159 &:= (-1 + ((2+Q(3)) \times (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
6160 &:= ((-1+2 - (Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
6161 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (Q(4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6162 &:= (-1+2+(Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6163 &:= (-1+2+(Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
6164 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6165 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - (Q(Q(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6166 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) + 4)) + ((5+6) \times Q((7+8+9)))) \\
6167 &:= (-1 + ((Q((2 \times (3+4))) + (Q(5) + Q(6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6168 &:= ((-1+2+Q((Q(3) - (4 - (5+6)))) \times (7+8+9)) \\
6169 &:= (((-1+Q(2+3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6170 &:= (-1 + (Q(2+Q(3)) \times (Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6171 &:= (Q((-1+2+(Q(Q(3)) + 4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
6172 &:= (-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + (Q(Q(4+5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6173 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(3) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6174 &:= (((-1-2+Q(3)) \times (4^5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\
6175 &:= ((-1 - Q((2 \times Q(3)))) \times (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6176 &:= (-1+2+((Q(3) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6177 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - (Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
6178 &:= (-1-2+(Q(Q(3)) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6179 &:= (((-1+Q(2+3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
6180 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2+3) + Q(4))) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6181 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6182 &:= (-1+2+(Q(Q(3)) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6183 &:= ((-1+Q((2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) + (5+6))) - (7+8+9))) \\
6184 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6185 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
6186 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2+3) \times Q(4))) - (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6147 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - ((7 \times Q(6+5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6148 &:= (-9+8+(Q(7) + ((Q(6) + Q(5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6149 &:= ((Q((-9-8+Q(7))) \times 6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
6150 &:= ((-9 - (((8-7)^6) - Q(Q(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
6151 &:= (9+Q(8)) \times (Q(7) + Q(6)) - (5+4) \times (3+2+1) \\
6152 &:= (-9 - ((Q(((8 \times 7) + 6)) - 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6153 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (((Q(7) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
6154 &:= (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) + ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6155 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q((Q(7) + 6)) + (5+Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6156 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (Q(7) + Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6157 &:= ((-9+8 \times 7) \times (Q(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
6158 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (Q((6 \times 5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6159 &:= ((Q((-9-8+Q(7))) \times 6) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
6160 &:= (-9 - (Q((8+7-6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6161 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7+Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6162 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((Q(7) - Q(Q(6))) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6163 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((Q(7) - Q(Q(6))) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6164 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (7+6 - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6165 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7 - 6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6166 &:= ((-9 - (8+7)) - ((6 - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6167 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (((7-6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6168 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - Q((Q(7) - (6 \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6169 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7-6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6170 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) + 7+6)) + (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6171 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times 7 - Q(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
6172 &:= (-9 - ((Q(((8 \times 7) + 6)) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6173 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (((Q(7) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
6174 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (Q(7+6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6175 &:= ((-9+Q(8)) - ((7+6 - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6176 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + ((7-6) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6177 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(((7-6) \times 5))) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6178 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(((7-6) \times 5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6179 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7-6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6180 &:= ((-9 + ((8+Q(7)) \times (6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
6181 &:= (-9 - (((8-7) \times 6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6182 &:= (-9+8-7 - ((6 - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6183 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) - ((6 - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6184 &:= (Q((-9+8+(Q(7) + 6 \times 5))) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
6185 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6186 &:= (-9 + ((8+Q(7+6)) \times (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$6187 := (((-1 - 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6188 := ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((4 \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6189 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((4 \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6190 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6191 := ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6192 := ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((4 \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6193 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6194 := (-1 + ((2 - (Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6195 := (-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6196 := (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6197 := (((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$6198 := ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 + (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6199 := (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6200 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6201 := ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6202 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6203 := ((-1 \times 2) - (((Q(3) - Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6204 := (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6205 := ((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6206 := (Q((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6207 := (-1 \times (Q((2 \times Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6208 := ((Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + 4^5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6209 := (-1 - (((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6210 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6211 := (Q(((-1 + 2 - 3) + Q(4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6212 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6213 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (Q((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6214 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6215 := (-1 + (Q(((2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6216 := (Q((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times Q(4)))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6217 := ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6218 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6219 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6220 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6221 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6222 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6223 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6224 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6225 := (((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6226 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(((3 \times Q(4)) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6187 := ((-9 \times (8 - 7 + 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6188 := (-9 \times 8 + ((7 - 6 + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6189 := (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) - ((6 + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6190 := (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6191 := (-9 + (((8 - 7 - 6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6192 := (-9 - (Q((8 - 7 + 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6193 := ((-9 \times (8 \times Q(7) + (6 + Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6194 := (-9 + 8 - (Q(7) + (6 - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6195 := ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) + (6 - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6196 := ((-9 + 8 + 7) - ((6 - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6197 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6198 := ((Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) \times 6) + ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6199 := (-9 + (Q(8) \times (7 + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6200 := (((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((7 + 6) + Q(Q(5)))) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6201 := ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) + ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6202 := (((-9 + 8 - 7) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6203 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q((Q((7 - (6 - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6204 := ((-9 - 8 + 7) - (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6205 := (-9 - (Q((8 - 7) \times 6) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6206 := (-9 + 8 - 7 - (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6207 := (-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6208 := (((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6209 := (-9 - ((8 \times Q(7)) - ((Q(6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6210 := (9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7) + Q(6)) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$6211 := (((-9 - Q(8 + 7))/6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6212 := (-9 - (Q(8) + (7 - (Q(6 + 5) \times (Q(4) + Q((3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$6213 := (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (Q((6 \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6214 := ((-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) + 6 \times 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6215 := (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6216 := (-9 + ((Q((Q(8) + (7 - Q(6)))) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6217 := (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 \times Q((6 \times 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6218 := (-9 - 8 + ((Q(7) - Q(Q(6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6219 := (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - Q(7 + 6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6220 := ((-9 - (8 + 7 + 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6221 := (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6222 := ((-9 + Q(((8 \times (7 + 6)) - Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6223 := (-9 - 8 - (((7 - 6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6224 := (-9 + 8 - (((Q(7) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6225 := ((-9 + 8) \times (((Q(7) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6226 := (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) - ((6 - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6227 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(((3 \times Q(4)) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6228 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2^3) + (4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6229 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6230 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(((3 \times Q(4)) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6231 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - ((Q(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6232 &:= ((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q((Q(4) - 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6233 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - ((Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6234 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6235 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4) - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6236 &:= (-1 + ((2 - Q(3)) \times (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6237 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6238 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6239 &:= (-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(((3 \times 4) - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6240 &:= (-1 + Q((((2 + Q(3)) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6241 &:= Q((-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6242 &:= (-1 + 2 + Q((Q(((3 \times 4) - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6243 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6244 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) - Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6245 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6246 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times Q(4)))) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6247 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6248 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6249 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2 + 3) \times Q(4)))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6250 &:= (Q((-1 + Q((2 + 3 + 4)))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6251 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6252 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6253 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6254 &:= (-1 + (((2 - (Q(3) - Q(Q(4)))) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6255 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6256 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times Q(4)) + ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6257 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) - (4 + ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6258 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6259 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2 - 3) + Q(4 + 5))) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6260 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6261 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6262 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6263 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((3 + 4) \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6264 &:= ((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6265 &:= ((Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - Q(4)) \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6266 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) \times 4)))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6227 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6228 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 \times Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6229 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (Q((6 \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6230 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7 + 6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6231 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (6 + Q(5))))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6232 &:= (-9 + Q((Q(8) + ((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6233 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(((7 - 6) \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6234 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) - Q(Q(6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6235 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6236 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6237 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6238 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) - ((6 - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6239 &:= (-9 + 8 - (((7 - 6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6240 &:= (((-9 / (8 + 7 - 6)) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6241 &:= Q(((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) / Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6242 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6243 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (Q(7 + 6) + Q(Q(5))))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6244 &:= (-9 + 8 - (((Q(7) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6245 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) \times 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6246 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7 - 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6247 &:= ((-9 + (8 - 7) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6248 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6249 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((7 + 6) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6250 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) - (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6251 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) / 6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6252 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6253 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6254 &:= (Q(((-9 + 8 \times 7) + Q(6))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6255 &:= ((-9 + ((Q(8) + 7) \times 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6256 &:= ((-9 \times (Q((8 + 7 + 6)) - Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6257 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6258 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) / 6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6259 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 - 6 + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6260 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) / 6) + Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6261 &:= (-9 + ((8 + Q(7)) \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6262 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7 + 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6263 &:= (-9 + (8 \times Q((7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6264 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((Q(7) - Q((6 + (5 + 4)))) \times Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6265 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6266 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (Q(7) - Q(Q(6)))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6267 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6268 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6269 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6270 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6271 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6272 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6273 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - Q((4 - ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6274 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6275 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6276 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times Q(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6277 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6278 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6279 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3)))) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6280 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6281 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6282 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (4 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6283 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6284 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(3)^4) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6285 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6286 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6287 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(3)^4) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6288 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6289 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6290 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + ((4 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6291 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6292 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6293 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times ((4 - 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6294 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6295 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6296 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times Q(4)))) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6297 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6298 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((3 \times 4) - 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6299 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (Q(Q(3)) / (4 + 5))) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6300 &:= ((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - 4 - 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6301 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6302 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6303 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6304 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - ((Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6305 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6306 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times (Q(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6267 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6268 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q((Q(7) + 6 \times 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6269 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6270 &:= (-9 - (Q((Q((8 - 7) \times 6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6271 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6272 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) - (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6273 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times Q((6 \times 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6274 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q(((7 \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6275 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((Q(7) + 6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6276 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6277 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6278 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6279 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6280 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) - (6 - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6281 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + Q(((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6282 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) - ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6283 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) + (6 + Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6284 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) \times (6 \times Q(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6285 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times Q(7) + Q(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6286 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6287 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) + ((6 + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6288 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6289 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times Q((6 \times 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6290 &:= (((Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) - Q(6)) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6291 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 - (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6292 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - (7 + 6 - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6293 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 \times Q((6 \times 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6294 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8 + 7)) - (Q((Q(6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6295 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6296 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6297 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6298 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6299 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6300 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(6)) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6301 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7) \times 6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6302 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6303 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + ((6 + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6304 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (6 + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6305 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(((7 - 6) \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6306 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 - 6 + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6307 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times ((4 - 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6308 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6309 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6310 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6311 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6312 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6313 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6314 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) - (Q(4) - ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6315 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6316 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6317 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6318 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6319 &:= ((-1 + (Q((2 \times (3 + Q(4)))) \times 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6320 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6321 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6322 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6323 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6324 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2 + 3) + (Q(4) \times 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6325 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2 + 3) + Q(4 + 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6326 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3 + 4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6327 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6328 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6329 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - (Q(4) - ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6330 &:= (((Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) - 4) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6331 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6332 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6333 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6334 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 \times 3) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6335 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) \times (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6336 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6337 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6338 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6339 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6340 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6341 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6342 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6343 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6344 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6345 &:= (Q((-1 + Q((2 + 3 + 4)))) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6346 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6307 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (((7 + 6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6308 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (((7 + 6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6309 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 \times Q((6 \times 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6310 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) + 7) \times (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6311 &:= (Q((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6))) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6312 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 - ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6313 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6314 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7)))/Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6315 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) + Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6316 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + ((6 + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6317 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7 - Q(6))) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6318 &:= (-9 + ((8 + Q(7)) \times (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6319 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times (6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6320 &:= (((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6321 &:= (-9 + ((8 + Q(Q((7 - 6) \times 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6322 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6323 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6324 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q((Q(7) + 6 \times 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6325 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) \times (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6326 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) - (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6327 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q((8 + 7 - 6)))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6328 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q((Q(7) + (6 + 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6329 &:= ((-9 + Q(8) \times 7) - ((Q(6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6330 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(7) - ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6331 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7 - 6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6332 &:= (-9 + (Q(((8 \times (7 + 6)) - Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6333 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (Q(7 + 6) + Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6334 &:= (-9 + 8 - (((Q(7) - Q(Q(6))) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6335 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6336 &:= (Q((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6337 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + Q((Q(Q(6)) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6338 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) - (6 - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6339 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7 + 6) - (Q(Q(5 + 4)) - Q((3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6340 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(Q(6))) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6341 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (6 + Q(5))))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6342 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + ((6 + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6343 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6344 &:= (-9 + 8 - (((7 - Q(Q(6))) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6345 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - (Q(7) + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6346 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7) \times (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6347 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6348 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6349 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2 + Q(3)) \times 4))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6350 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + 4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6351 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6352 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6353 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (((3 - Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6354 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6355 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6356 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6357 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - (4 \times Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6358 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6359 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)) - 4) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6360 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6361 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6362 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q(3)) \times ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6363 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6364 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2 + 3) \times Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6365 &:= (Q((-1 + Q((2 + 3 + 4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6366 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times (Q(4) - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6367 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + (4 - 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6368 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6369 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2 - 3) + Q(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6370 &:= (Q((-1 - ((2 - 3) \times Q(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6371 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + (4 - 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6372 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3)))/Q(4)) + ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6373 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(3 + 4) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6374 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(3 + 4) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6375 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6376 &:= (Q(((-1 - (2 \times 3) + Q(4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6377 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(3 + 4) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6378 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((Q(3) \times (Q(4) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6379 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6380 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6381 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6382 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((Q(3) \times (Q(4) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6383 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3 + 4) + ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6384 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3 + 4)))) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6385 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6386 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6347 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) \times (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6348 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times Q(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6349 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q((Q(7) + 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6350 &:= ((Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6351 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times Q(7)) - (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6352 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6353 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (Q(7 + 6) + Q(Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6354 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6355 &:= ((-9 \times (Q((8 + 7 - 6)) \times 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6356 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) \times 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6357 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6358 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + ((6 + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6359 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6360 &:= ((Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q((7 \times 6) + Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6361 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6362 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - (Q(6) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6363 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((7 + 6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6364 &:= (Q(((-9 + 8 \times 7) + Q(6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6365 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 \times Q((6 \times 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6366 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) - 7 - 6) \times (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6367 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - Q((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6368 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(6))/5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6369 &:= ((Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) \times 6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6370 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7 + 6)) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6371 &:= ((-9 + (Q(Q(8 - 7) \times 6) \times 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6372 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times Q(7)) - ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6373 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times Q(7) + (6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6374 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((Q(7) + Q(6)) \times (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6375 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7 - 6) \times (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6376 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + Q(((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6377 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6378 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6379 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((7 + 6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6380 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6381 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + 7) \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6382 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6383 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q((Q(7) + (6 + 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6384 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + Q(Q(6)))) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6385 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6386 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) + (Q(Q(6)) \times 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6387 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6388 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6389 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6390 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((Q(3) - (Q(4) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6391 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times Q(4)))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6392 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6393 &:= (((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6394 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6395 &:= (Q((-1 + Q((2 + 3 + 4)))) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6396 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6397 &:= (-1 - 2 + Q((Q(3) + (Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6398 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6399 &:= (-1 + Q((2 \times (Q(3) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6400 &:= Q((Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6401 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6402 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) + (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6403 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6404 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6405 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 \times 3))) \times 4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6406 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6407 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (4 + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6408 &:= (-1 + ((Q(Q(2 \times 3)) \times 4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6409 &:= ((Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) \times 4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6410 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6411 &:= ((Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3))^4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6412 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (Q(3)^4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6413 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6414 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6415 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6416 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6417 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6418 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6419 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6420 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) + (4 \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6421 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6422 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6423 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6424 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2 + 3) \times Q(4)))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6425 &:= (Q((-1 + Q((2 + 3 + 4)))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6426 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (4 + 5 - (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6387 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + Q((Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6388 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6389 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q((Q(7) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6390 &:= (Q(((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7)))/(6 \times 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6391 &:= (-9 + Q((Q(8) + (7 - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6392 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6393 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + Q(((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6394 &:= (Q((-9 + (8 + 7 + 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6395 &:= ((-9 \times Q(((8 \times 7) - Q(6)))) - (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6396 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - Q(Q(7)) - Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6397 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6 + Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6398 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6399 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q((Q(7) + (6 + 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6400 &:= Q(((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6401 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 - (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6402 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) \times (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6403 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6404 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + ((Q(6) + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6405 &:= (((Q((-9 + Q(8))) - Q((7 \times 6))) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6406 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + Q(((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6407 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
6408 &:= (-9 \times (8 + ((Q(7) - Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6409 &:= (Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7) + Q(6))) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6410 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) + Q(Q(6))) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6411 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times Q(7) + Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6412 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - (6 + 5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6413 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times Q(7) + 6)) - (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6414 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((7 + Q(Q(6))) \times 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6415 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6416 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7) + ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6417 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - (7 \times (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6418 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) \times (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6419 &:= (Q(((-9 + Q(8)) - (7 \times 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6420 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6)) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6421 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6422 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - ((6 - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6423 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6424 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6425 &:= (((-9 + Q(Q(8 - 7) \times 6)) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6426 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$6427 := (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (Q(4) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$6428 := (-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)))$$

$$6429 := (-1 + (Q(((2-3) + Q(4+5))) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$6430 := (Q((-1 - ((2-3) \times Q(4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9)$$

$$6431 := (-1+2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + (4-5)))) + 6+7+8+9)$$

$$6432 := ((-1+2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$6433 := (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$6434 := (-1 + (Q(((2+3) \times Q(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$6435 := (Q((-1+Q((2+3+4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$6436 := (Q((-1-2+Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$6437 := (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) - (4^5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$6438 := ((-1+2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4^5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$6439 := (Q((-1+2) \times 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$6440 := (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) - Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))))))$$

$$6441 := ((-1+2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))))))$$

$$6442 := ((-1-2 + ((3+Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9))$$

$$6443 := (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$6444 := (((-1+Q(2+3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9))$$

$$6445 := (((((-1+2) \times 3) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))$$

$$6446 := (Q(-1+2+3) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$6447 := ((-1-2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4+5) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$6448 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4+5) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$6449 := (Q((-1+2+(3^4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$6450 := (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) - (Q(4+5) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$6451 := ((-1+2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4+5) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$6452 := (-1+2 + (Q(Q(3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$6453 := (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + ((4+Q(Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$6454 := (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$6455 := (Q((-1+Q((2+3+4)))) + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$6456 := ((-1+2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$6457 := (-1 + (2 \times (Q((3 \times Q(4))) + (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$6458 := (-1-2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$6459 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$6460 := (-1 \times ((Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - 4) \times (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$6461 := (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (4 \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$6462 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$6463 := (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$6464 := (Q((-1-2+Q(Q(3)))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$6465 := (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$6466 := (-1 - (Q(2^3) - (Q(Q(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$6427 := (-9 - (Q(8) - (((7+6) \times 5) \times Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6428 := (-9 \times 8 + (((7+6) \times 5) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$6429 := (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + ((Q(6)+5) \times Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6430 := ((-9+Q(8+7)) - (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6431 := ((-9+8) \times (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6432 := (-9-8 + (Q(7) + Q(((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6433 := ((-9 \times 8 + ((7+Q(Q(6))) \times 5)) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$6434 := (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) \times (6+5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6435 := ((-9+Q(8)) \times (7 + ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6436 := (Q((-9+8+7)) + Q(((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6437 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6438 := (-9-8 - (((7-Q(Q(6))) \times 5) - (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$6439 := ((-9 \times ((8+7) - Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$6440 := (((Q(Q((-9+8+7))) - 6) \times 5) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$6441 := (Q((-9+8 + (Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$6442 := (-9 - (Q(8) + ((7+Q(Q(6))) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6443 := (-9 + ((8 \times (Q(7+6) + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$6444 := (-9 \times ((8+7-6) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6445 := (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6446 := (((-9 - (8+7)) + (Q(Q(6)) \times 5)) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$6447 := ((-9+Q(Q((8+7-6)))) - (5+Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$6448 := (-9+8 + (Q(7) + Q(((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6449 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$6450 := ((-9 - (Q(8) + 7 + 6)) \times (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$6451 := (-9 + (((8+7+6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$6452 := (-9 - (Q(8) + ((7-Q(6)) \times Q(5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6453 := (-9 \times 8 - ((7-Q(6)) \times Q(5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$6454 := (-9+8 - (((7-Q(Q(6))) \times 5) - (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$6455 := ((-9+Q(8)) - (Q((Q(7) + (6+5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6456 := ((-9 - (8+7)) - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6457 := (-9 + (Q(Q((8+7-6))) + (5 - Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6458 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times (5 - (4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$6459 := (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) - ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) + Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$6460 := (((Q(Q((-9+8+7))) - 6) \times 5) + 4+3+2+1)$$

$$6461 := (Q(Q(Q((-9+8-7+6+5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1))$$

$$6462 := ((-9+8-7 + (Q(Q(6)) \times 5)) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$6463 := ((((-9+8) \times 7) + (Q(Q(6)) \times 5)) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$6464 := ((((-9-Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + (Q(6) + 5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$6465 := ((-9 + (8 \times (Q(7) + 6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$6466 := (((-9+8+7) \times (Q(6) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6467 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2^3) - (Q(Q(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6468 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6469 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
6470 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
6471 &:= (Q((-1+2+(Q(Q(3))+4))) - (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
6472 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3+4) \times (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6473 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3+4) \times (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6474 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+3) \times (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6475 &:= (((-1+2) \times (3+4)) \times (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
6476 &:= (-1+2+((3+4) \times (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6477 &:= (-1-2-(Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q((4 - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))))))) \\
6478 &:= ((-1-2+Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6479 &:= (-1 - ((Q(Q(2+3)) - Q((4+Q(5)))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
6480 &:= ((-1+Q(2+3)) \times ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
6481 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6482 &:= ((-1+2+Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6483 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
6484 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6485 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times 3)^4)) \times (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6486 &:= (-1-2-((Q(3) \times (4 - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
6487 &:= ((-1-2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
6488 &:= (-1 + (Q((2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6489 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) \times (4 - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9) \\
6490 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) - (Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
6491 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) - ((4 \times Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6492 &:= ((-1+2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6493 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6494 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) - (Q(Q(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6495 &:= ((-1+Q(((2+3) + Q(4+5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9) \\
6496 &:= (Q((-1+2 \times 3) + Q(4+5)) - Q(6+7+8+9) \\
6497 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q(((3 \times (4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
6498 &:= (-1 + (((2+Q(Q(3))) - Q(4)) \times (Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
6499 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times (Q((4 \times 5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6500 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6501 &:= (Q((-1+2+(Q(Q(3))+4))) + (5 - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
6502 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) + (Q((4+Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
6503 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6504 &:= (((-1-2) \times Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6505 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+3) - (Q(Q(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6506 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+3) - (Q(Q(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6467 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6468 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - ((6 \times 5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6469 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) + ((Q(6) + Q(5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6470 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(7+6) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
6471 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q(8-7) \times 6) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6472 &:= (-9 + (Q(8+7) + (6 + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6473 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6474 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) \times (Q(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
6475 &:= (((-9 \times (8+7)) - 6) \times Q(5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
6476 &:= (((-9+8+7) + (Q(Q(6)) \times 5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
6477 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q((8+7-6))) + (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6478 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - ((6-5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6479 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6480 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - Q((7+6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6481 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times Q(7)) - (6-5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6482 &:= (-9+8-7+((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
6483 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times Q(7)) + (6+5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
6484 &:= (-9-8+(Q(Q(7)) + ((Q(6) + 5) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6485 &:= (-9-8+(7 \times Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6486 &:= ((-9+8+7) - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6487 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6488 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q(Q((7 \times (6+5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6489 &:= (-9 \times (8 - Q(((7 \times 6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6490 &:= ((-9+Q(8)) \times (7+6+5+Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6491 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) - Q(6+5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6492 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6)/Q(((5+4) - (3+2+1)))))) \\
6493 &:= (Q((-9 \times 8 + Q(7+6))) - Q(((5+4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
6494 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q(7) - (Q(6) \times (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6495 &:= (((-9+Q(8) \times 7) - 6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
6496 &:= ((-9+8+7) + ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
6497 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6498 &:= (-9-8-((7+Q(Q(6))) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6499 &:= (-9+8+(((7+6) \times 5) \times Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
6500 &:= (((-9+8+7) + Q(Q(6))) \times 5) - (4+3+2+1) \\
6501 &:= (-9+8+(7 \times Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6502 &:= (((-9-8) \times Q(7+6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6503 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times Q(7)) + Q(6)) - (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6504 &:= ((-9+8+((7+Q(Q(6))) \times 5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
6505 &:= (((-9+Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
6506 &:= (Q((-9+8+7) + ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) - (4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

6507 := $((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
6508 := $((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
6509 := $((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
6510 := $(Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
6511 := $((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
6512 := $(-1 - (2 \times Q(3) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
6513 := $((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
6514 := $(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
6515 := $((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$
6516 := $((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times (4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$
6517 := $((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
6518 := $((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
6519 := $((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
6520 := $((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
6521 := $((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
6522 := $(Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
6523 := $((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
6524 := $((-1 \times 2 + (Q(3)^4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
6525 := $((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3 + 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
6526 := $((Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3))^4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
6527 := $((-1 + 2 + (Q(3)^4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
6528 := $(-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
6529 := $((-1 + 2 - 3) + Q(Q(4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$
6530 := $(Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
6531 := $(-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
6532 := $(Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
6533 := $((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
6534 := $((((-1 + 2) \times 3) + Q(Q(4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
6535 := $((-1 + 2 + 3) + Q(Q(4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$
6536 := $((-1 + 2 \times 3) + Q(Q(4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$
6537 := $(-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
6538 := $(-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
6539 := $(-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
6540 := $(-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
6541 := $(-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
6542 := $(Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
6543 := $(-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
6544 := $(-1 - (((2 + 3) - Q(4)) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
6545 := $((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(4)) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
6546 := $(-1 \times 2 + ((Q(3)^4) + ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))))$

6507 := $(-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) + (7 + 6 - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
6508 := $(-9 - 8 - ((7 - Q(6)) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
6509 := $(-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
6510 := $(-9 - (Q((Q(8) - ((7 - 6) \times 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
6511 := $(Q((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
6512 := $((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) - Q(Q(Q(((6 \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))))$
6513 := $((((-9 \times 8) \times Q(7)) + (Q(6) + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
6514 := $(-9 + 8 - ((7 + Q(Q(6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
6515 := $((((-9 + 8) \times 7) - Q(Q(6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
6516 := $(Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
6517 := $((-9 + Q(Q((8 + 7 - 6)))) - (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
6518 := $(-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
6519 := $(-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
6520 := $((((-9 + 8 + 7) + Q(Q(6))) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$
6521 := $(-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (7 - 6 + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
6522 := $(-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
6523 := $(-9 - 8 - ((7 - (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
6524 := $(-9 + 8 - ((7 - Q(6)) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
6525 := $((((-9 + 8) \times 7) + Q(6)) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
6526 := $(Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
6527 := $((-9 + 8 \times 7) - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
6528 := $((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
6529 := $(-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
6530 := $((-9 + 8 - 7 + (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
6531 := $(Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
6532 := $(-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
6533 := $(-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - ((7 + 6) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
6534 := $(-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - (Q(6 + Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
6535 := $((-9 \times ((Q(8) + 7 + 6) \times 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
6536 := $((-9 + (((8 + 7) + Q(Q(6))) \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
6537 := $((-9 + Q(Q((8 + 7 - 6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
6538 := $(((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
6539 := $(-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
6540 := $(((-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(Q(6))) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
6541 := $(-9 + (((8 \times (Q(7) + Q(6))) - Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
6542 := $(-9 + (Q(8) + (7 - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
6543 := $(-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
6544 := $((((-9 - Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + Q(6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
6545 := $((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7 + 6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
6546 := $(Q((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$

$$\begin{aligned}
6547 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) + (Q(Q(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6548 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q(3) + (Q(Q(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6549 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2+3) \times Q(4))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6550 &:= (Q((-1+Q((2+3+4)))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
6551 &:= (-1 - ((2^3) \times (Q(4+5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6552 &:= ((-1+2-Q(3)) \times (Q(4+5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
6553 &:= (-1+2+(Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6554 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) - (Q(Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
6555 &:= (-1 + (Q(2+3) + (Q(Q(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6556 &:= (Q((-1+2 \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6557 &:= (-1+2+((Q(3)^4) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6558 &:= (-1-2+Q(Q(Q(Q(Q(3)+Q(4+5)))/Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6559 &:= (-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(Q(Q(3)+Q(4+5)))/Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6560 &:= (-1+Q(Q(Q(Q((2 \times (3+Q(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
6561 &:= Q(Q(Q(Q((-1 \times (Q(2 \times 3) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
6562 &:= (-1+2+Q(Q(Q(Q(Q(3)+Q(4+5)))/Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6563 &:= ((-1+2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4+Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6564 &:= (((-1-2) \times Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
6565 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+3) - (Q(Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
6566 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+3) - (Q(Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
6567 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6568 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6569 &:= (-1-2+(Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6570 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2^3))) + Q((Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6571 &:= ((-1+2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6572 &:= (-1 - (2 \times Q(3) - (Q(Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
6573 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
6574 &:= (Q((-1+2+(3^4))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
6575 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times 3)) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6576 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) \times (Q((Q(4)+5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6577 &:= ((-1-2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6578 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6579 &:= ((-1-2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4+5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6580 &:= (Q(Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) - (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6581 &:= ((-1+2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6582 &:= (Q(Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) - (4+5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6583 &:= ((-1+2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4+5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6584 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6585 &:= ((-1 - (2+3)) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
6586 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6547 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q((8+7-6))) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6548 &:= (-9 - (((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6549 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) + (7 - (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6550 &:= (((Q(Q((-9+8+7))) - 6) \times 5) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
6551 &:= (Q(Q(Q(Q((-9+8-7+6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
6552 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(Q((8+((7-6)^{54321})))))) \\
6553 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6554 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + Q(Q(Q(((6 \times 5)/(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6555 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (((7+6) \times 5) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6556 &:= (Q((-9 + ((8+7) \times 6))) + (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
6557 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q((8+7-6)))) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
6558 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - (Q(6) - Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6559 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times Q(6)) + Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6560 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(7+6) + Q(Q(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
6561 &:= Q(Q(Q(Q((-9 \times (8-7-6))/(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6562 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(Q(Q(8 - ((7-6) \times 5)))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
6563 &:= (((-9-8) \times Q(7)) + Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6564 &:= (Q((-9 + ((8+7) \times 6))) + ((5+4) - (3+2+1))) \\
6565 &:= ((-9 \times (8-7-Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6566 &:= (Q((-9 + ((8+7) \times 6))) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
6567 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q((8+7-6))) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
6568 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((7 - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6569 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + Q(Q(((6 \times 5)/(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6570 &:= (-9 \times ((8-7-6) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6571 &:= (Q(Q(Q(Q((-9+8-7+6+5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
6572 &:= (-9+8-7+((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6573 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6574 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7+6 - Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6575 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) + ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6576 &:= (Q((-9 + ((8+7) \times 6))) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
6577 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6+5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6578 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6579 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) \times (6 + (5+4)))) + Q((3+2+1))) \\
6580 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - ((7 - Q(6)) \times Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
6581 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6582 &:= (-9-8 - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q((6 \times 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6583 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) \times (7 - ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6584 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6585 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (Q(6+Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
6586 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) \times (Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6587 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (Q(3)^4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6588 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6589 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6590 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6591 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - (2 - (3 + (4 + 5)))))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6592 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6593 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6594 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(3)^4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6595 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3 + 4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6596 &:= ((Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))^4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6597 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6598 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6599 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
6600 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6601 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6602 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6603 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
6604 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6605 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + Q(Q(4)))) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6606 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (Q(4) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6607 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6608 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q(3) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6609 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6610 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6611 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
6612 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6613 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6614 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((Q(4) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6615 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6616 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 \times 3) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6617 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(3)^4) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6618 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6619 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6620 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q((4 + Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6621 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((4 + Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6622 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((Q(3) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6623 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((Q(3) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6624 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6625 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6626 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6587 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q((Q(7) + (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6588 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6589 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6590 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q((7 - 6 + Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6591 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((Q(7) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6592 &:= (-9 - (Q((8 + Q(7))) + (6 \times Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6593 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times Q(7)) + Q(6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6594 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) - ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6595 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6596 &:= (Q((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6))) + (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6597 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + Q(Q(Q(((6 \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6598 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6599 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6600 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6601 &:= (-9 + ((Q((8 - 7) \times 6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6602 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q((8 + 7 - 6))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6603 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + ((Q(6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6604 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) - ((5 + 4) + Q((3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6605 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8 + 7) \times 6)) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6606 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6607 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6608 &:= ((-9 - 8 + ((Q(7) + Q(Q(6))) \times 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6609 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + Q(Q(Q(((6 \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6610 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6611 &:= (Q((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6612 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6613 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q((Q(6) + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6614 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - Q(6 + Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6615 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6616 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6617 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7) + (6 \times Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6618 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6619 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6620 &:= (((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + Q(Q(6)))) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6621 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times 7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6622 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6623 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((7 - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6624 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((Q(7) - Q(6 + 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6625 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) + (6 \times Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6626 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times Q(6 + Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6627 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
6628 &:= (-1-2+(Q(Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 \times Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6629 &:= (-1 + ((Q((2 \times (3+4))) + Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
6630 &:= ((Q((-1+2-3) + Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
6631 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6632 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
6633 &:= (-1+2+(Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
6634 &:= (-1+2+(Q(Q(Q(3)))) + ((4+5-6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6635 &:= ((-1-2+Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - ((5+6) + Q((7+8+9)))) \\
6636 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - ((5+6) + Q((7+8+9)))) \\
6637 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6638 &:= ((-1-2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) \times (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6639 &:= (-1-2+(Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q((4 - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
6640 &:= (Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
6641 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) - (Q(4) \times (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6642 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) + Q(Q((4 - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
6643 &:= (-1+2+(Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q((4 - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
6644 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6645 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6646 &:= (Q((-1+2+(Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
6647 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6648 &:= (((-1+Q(Q(2+3)))/4 + Q((5+6))) \times (7+8+9)) \\
6649 &:= (-1-2+(Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q((Q(4)-5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6650 &:= (((-1 - (Q(2+3) - Q(Q(4)))) \times Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
6651 &:= (-1 + (Q(2+Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6652 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (Q((Q(4)-5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6653 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
6654 &:= (-1 + (Q(2^3) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
6655 &:= (Q((-1 \times (2+3)) + Q(4)) \times (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
6656 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6657 &:= ((-1+Q((2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6658 &:= ((-1-2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6659 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6660 &:= ((((-1-2) \times 3) + Q(Q(4))) - Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
6661 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) - (4 \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6662 &:= ((-1+2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6663 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6664 &:= (-1-2+(Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6665 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((4+Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
6666 &:= ((-1-2+Q((3 \times (4+Q(5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6627 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q((8+7-6)))) - (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6628 &:= (-9+8+(Q(7) + ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6629 &:= (-9+(Q(Q(8)) + ((7 \times 6) + Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6630 &:= (((-9+8-7+Q(Q(6))) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
6631 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7) + ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6632 &:= (-9+(Q(Q(8)+7) + Q(((6 \times 5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
6633 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((Q(7+6) \times 5) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6634 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
6635 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q((Q(7) + (6+5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
6636 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6637 &:= (-9+8 - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6+Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6638 &:= ((-9+8) \times (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6+Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6639 &:= (-9+Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - Q((Q(6)+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6640 &:= ((((-9+8) \times 7) + Q(Q(6))) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
6641 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8+7) \times (6 \times 5))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
6642 &:= (-9-8+(Q(7) + ((Q(6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6643 &:= ((-9 \times ((Q(Q(8)) + 7)/(6+5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6644 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6645 &:= (-9+(Q((Q(8)+7+6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6646 &:= (Q((-9+8+7)) + ((Q(6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6647 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) \times ((7-6-5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6648 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) - (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6649 &:= (-9+(Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6650 &:= ((Q(Q((-9+8+7))) - (6+Q(Q(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
6651 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((7 \times Q(6+5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6652 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + ((Q(7) + Q(Q(6))) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6653 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((Q(7) + Q(Q(6))) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6654 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8+7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6655 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times Q((Q(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6656 &:= (((-9 \times Q((8+7+6))) + Q(Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6657 &:= (-9+(Q(Q((8+7-6))) + (5+Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6658 &:= (-9+8+(Q(7) + ((Q(6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6659 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7))) + (6^5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
6660 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(7+6) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
6661 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-9+8-7+6+5)))) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
6662 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times Q(7))) - (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6663 &:= (-9-8+((Q(7) - (6 - Q(Q(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6664 &:= ((-9-8) \times (Q(7) - Q(6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
6665 &:= (-9+(Q(8) + (Q(7) + Q(Q(Q(((6 \times 5)/(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6666 &:= (Q((-9 + ((8+7) \times 6))) + (5 + Q(4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$6667 := ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6668 := ((-1 + Q(((2 \times 3) + Q(4 + 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6669 := (Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + Q(4 + 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6670 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6671 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + ((Q(4) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6672 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6673 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6674 := ((-1 + Q(((2 + 3) \times Q(4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6675 := (Q((-1 + Q((2 + 3 + 4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6676 := (Q(((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6677 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(((3^4) - 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6678 := ((-1 + Q(2^3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6679 := (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - 4)) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6680 := (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4)) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6681 := (-1 + (Q(2 + Q(3)) + Q(Q((4 - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))))$$

$$6682 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$6683 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6684 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6685 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6686 := (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6687 := (((-1 - 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6688 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((4 \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6689 := (Q((-1 + 2 + (3^4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6690 := ((-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6691 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6692 := (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6693 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6694 := (Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)) / Q(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6695 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6696 := (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6697 := (-1 + (2 \times ((Q(Q(3)) \times 4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6698 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6699 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6700 := ((-1 - 2 - (Q(3) + Q(Q(4)))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6701 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6702 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6703 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6704 := (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6705 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6706 := ((Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3))^4) + (Q((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6667 := ((-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times Q(6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6668 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$6669 := (-9 + 8 + (((7 \times 6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6670 := ((-9 + Q((8 + 7 + 6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6671 := (-9 + (8 \times ((Q(7 + 6) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6672 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (Q(6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$6673 := ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6674 := ((-9 \times Q(8 + 7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$6675 := ((-9 + ((Q(8) \times 7) + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6676 := (-9 + ((8 - (Q(7) + Q(Q(6)))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6677 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$6678 := (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7 \times 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$6679 := (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) - (6 - Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6680 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (((Q(7) + Q(Q(6))) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6681 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6682 := (-9 + (Q((8 + 7 + 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6683 := (-9 - 8 + (((7 \times 6) + Q(5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6684 := ((-9 \times Q(8 + 7)) - ((Q(Q(6)) - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6685 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((Q(7) + 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6686 := ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6687 := (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times Q(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6688 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q((7 - 6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$6689 := (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6690 := (((-9 + (Q(8) + (7 + Q(Q(6)))) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6691 := (-9 + (((8 \times 7) + (6 + 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6692 := ((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) + Q((3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6693 := ((-9 + Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6 + Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$6694 := (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) + Q((3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6695 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$6696 := ((-9 + Q(8 + 7)) \times (Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6697 := ((-9 \times (((8 + Q(7)) \times 6) + Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6698 := (-9 + 8 - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$6699 := ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(Q(7)) + (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$6700 := (((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6701 := -9 + (Q(Q((8 - 7) \times 6)) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$6702 := (((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7 + 6) + Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6703 := (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6704 := ((-9 \times Q(8 + 7)) - ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6705 := ((-9 + Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6706 := (((-9 + Q(8 + 7)) \times (6 + Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6707 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) - (4 - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6708 &:= ((-1+2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6709 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(3+4))) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
6710 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q((2+3+4))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6711 &:= (-1 + (Q(2+Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
6712 &:= (-1+2 + ((Q(3)^4) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6713 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6714 &:= (((-1+Q(2+3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
6715 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6716 &:= (-1+2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))))) \\
6717 &:= (-1-2 + (3 \times ((Q(Q(4)) \times (5+6)) - Q((7+8+9)))) \\
6718 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (((3 - Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6)) - Q((7+8+9)))) \\
6719 &:= (-1 - ((Q(2^3) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6720 &:= (-1 \times ((Q(2^3) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6721 &:= (-1-2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - ((4+Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6722 &:= ((-1+Q((2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6723 &:= (-1 + Q((Q(2+Q(3)) - (4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6724 &:= Q((-1 \times 2 + (Q(3+4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6725 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - ((4+Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6726 &:= ((-1-2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 - (5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6727 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (Q(4) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6728 &:= (-1+2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))))) \\
6729 &:= (Q((-1+2+(3^4))) - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6730 &:= ((-1+2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 - (5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
6731 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q((Q(3+4) + 5))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
6732 &:= ((-1-2-Q(3)) \times ((4 + (5+6)) - Q((7+8+9)))) \\
6733 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6734 &:= ((-1-Q(2+3)) \times (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6735 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6736 &:= (Q(((-1+2+3) + Q(4))) + ((5+6) \times Q((7+8+9)))) \\
6737 &:= ((-1+Q((2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4)-5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
6738 &:= ((-1+Q((2+(3^4)))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
6739 &:= (((-1+Q(2+3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6740 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4+5)) - (6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
6741 &:= (Q((-1+2+(Q(Q(3))+4))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
6742 &:= (-1 + (Q((2+Q(Q(3)))) + (4 - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))))) \\
6743 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6744 &:= ((-1+Q(2+3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6745 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - (4+5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6746 &:= (-1 + (((2+Q(3+4)) \times Q((5+6))) + Q((7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6707 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - Q(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
6708 &:= (-9-8 - ((Q(7) + Q(Q(6))) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6709 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1))))) \\
6710 &:= ((Q(((-9+8+7) \times 6)) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
6711 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) \times (((7-6) \times 5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6712 &:= (-9 - (Q((8+Q(7))) + ((6 \times 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))) \\
6713 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + Q((Q(6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
6714 &:= (-9 \times ((8+7) - (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))))) \\
6715 &:= (-9 + Q((Q(8) + (7+6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
6716 &:= ((-9 - Q(8)) \times ((7+6-5) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6717 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
6718 &:= (-9-8 + (((Q(7) + Q(Q(6))) \times 5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
6719 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 + Q(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
6720 &:= ((Q((-9+8+Q(7)))/Q(6)) \times (5 + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6721 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times 6) - 5) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
6722 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (7 + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
6723 &:= (-9 - (Q((8+Q(7))) - (6 - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))) \\
6724 &:= Q(((-9 \times 8 + Q(7+6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
6725 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) + 7+6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
6726 &:= (-9+8 + (7 \times Q((Q(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
6727 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
6728 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((Q(7) - (6 - Q(5))) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6729 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) - (7 - (Q((Q(6) + Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6730 &:= ((-9+8 - (Q(7) + Q(Q(6)))) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
6731 &:= (-9 - (Q((8+Q(7))) + (6+5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))) \\
6732 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (Q(6+Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6733 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + ((Q(7) \times 6) + 5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6734 &:= (-9 - (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(6+5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))) \\
6735 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((Q(7) - (6 - Q(Q(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6736 &:= (-9+8 + ((7 \times Q(6+Q(5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
6737 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + Q((Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
6738 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (Q(6) \times (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1))))) \\
6739 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) \times (6 \times (5+4))) + 3+2+1)) \\
6740 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7+6) \times 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6741 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (Q(7+6) \times 5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
6742 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times Q(6+5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6743 &:= (-9 - ((Q((8+Q(7))) - (6-5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6744 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) - (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6745 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7-6)) \times (5 - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6746 &:= (Q((-9+8+7)) + ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6747 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 + Q(Q(4)))))) \times ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6748 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6749 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6750 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) - 4 - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6751 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - (4 - 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6752 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6753 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6754 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))/Q(4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6755 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6756 &:= (((-1 - 2 + Q(((3 + 4) \times 5))) \times 6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6757 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q((3 \times Q(4))) + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6758 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) - ((4 \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6759 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + (3^4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6760 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6761 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + ((Q(4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6762 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6763 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6764 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) - ((4^5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6765 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6766 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) \times ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6767 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) - Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6768 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6769 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q(4) \times ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6770 &:= (((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6771 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 \times Q(Q(4))) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6772 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6773 &:= (-1 - ((Q((2 \times Q(3))) \times (4 - Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6774 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + 3) \times ((4 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6775 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6776 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) \times 4))) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6777 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) - (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6778 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6779 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6780 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6781 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (4 \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6782 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6783 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6784 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) \times (4 + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6785 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6786 &:= (Q((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (4 + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6747 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (7 \times (6 + (5 + 4)))) + Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6748 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6749 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6750 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) - 6) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6751 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + 7 + 6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6752 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 + 6) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6753 &:= (-9 - ((Q((8 + Q(7))) - (6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6754 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6755 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (((7 \times 6) + Q(5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6756 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6757 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times Q(6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6758 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6759 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q((7 - 6 + Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6760 &:= (Q(((((-9 + 8 + 7)/6) + Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6761 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (Q(7 + 6) \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6762 &:= (((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (Q(Q(6))/(5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6763 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((7 + Q(Q(6))) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6764 &:= (((Q((-9 + Q(8))) - Q(Q(7))) \times (6 + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6765 &:= (-9 - (Q((Q(8) - 7 - 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6766 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) - (7 - Q(Q(6)))) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6767 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times Q((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6768 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times (Q(6) + (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6769 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) + Q(((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6770 &:= ((Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (6 - Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6771 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7) - Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6772 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6773 &:= (-9 - ((Q((8 + Q(7))) - Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6774 &:= (-9 - ((8 + Q(7)) \times (6 - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6775 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + 6) \times Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6776 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6777 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q((8 + 7 - 6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6778 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6779 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((7 + Q(Q(6))) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6780 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - ((Q(7) + Q(Q(6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6781 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6782 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 \times Q((Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6783 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((Q(7) - (6 - Q(5))) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6784 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q((Q(7) + 6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6785 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) + Q(((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6786 &:= (Q((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6787 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + (Q(Q(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6788 &:= (-1 + (Q((2+Q(Q(3)))) + (4 \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6789 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6790 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6791 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + (3^4)))) - (Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9))) \\
6792 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6793 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6794 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 \times Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6795 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (Q(5)+6+7+8+9))) \\
6796 &:= (Q(Q((-1-2+Q(3)))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
6797 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6798 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((Q(4+5) \times 6) - Q((7+8+9)))) \\
6799 &:= (((-1 + Q(2+3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
6800 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - Q((4 + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
6801 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6802 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((3 \times Q(4))) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6803 &:= (-1 - (Q((2 \times Q(3))) \times (4+5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6804 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 \times Q(3))) \times (4+5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6805 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((3 \times Q(4))) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6806 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2+3) \times Q(4)))) - ((5+6) - Q((7+8+9)))) \\
6807 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - Q((4 - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6808 &:= (-1 - ((2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6809 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6810 &:= ((Q(Q(-1+2+3)) - (4 + Q(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
6811 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q((4 + (5+6))) + 7+8+9))) \\
6812 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6813 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6814 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q(3+4)) \times (Q((5+6)) + 7+8+9))) \\
6815 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6816 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2^3) + (4 + (5+6)))) + Q((7+8+9)))) \\
6817 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + Q(Q((4 - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6818 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6819 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6820 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
6821 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6822 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6823 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6824 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6825 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times (3+4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
6826 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(3^4) + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6787 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7) \times (6 \times Q(5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6788 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6+5))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
6789 &:= ((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 - Q(((6-5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6790 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (6 + Q(Q(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
6791 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) - 7 + 6 + 5) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6792 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 \times Q(6 + Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6793 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times Q(6 + 5)) + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6794 &:= (Q(((-9 + 8 \times 7) + Q(6))) + (5 - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6795 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7+6)) - Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6796 &:= (((-9 + Q(8+7)) \times (6 + Q(5))) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
6797 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6798 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - (Q(6) \times (5 + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6799 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) - (6 - Q(5))) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6800 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 - 5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
6801 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) \times 7) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6802 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q((8+7-6))) + (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6803 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((Q(7) + 6) \times (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6804 &:= (-9 \times ((8+7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6805 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6806 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6807 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) - Q(6 + Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6808 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7+6) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6809 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (Q(7) - Q((6 \times 5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
6810 &:= ((-9 - 8 - (Q(7) + Q(Q(6)))) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
6811 &:= (Q((-9 + ((8+7) \times 6))) + (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6812 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) \times (7+6 - Q(5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
6813 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (7 - Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6814 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6815 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6 + 5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6816 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + (7 - 6)) \times (5 + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6817 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7) + (6 \times (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6818 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5+4)) - Q((3+2+1)))) \\
6819 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times 7) + ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6820 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6821 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + (Q(6) \times 5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6822 &:= (-9 \times ((Q(8) \times (7+6 - Q(5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
6823 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(((7 \times 6) - Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6824 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7+6) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6825 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((Q(7) - (6+5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
6826 &:= (-9 + (Q(8+7) + ((Q(6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$6827 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$6828 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6829 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6830 := (((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$6831 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6832 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6833 := ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6834 := (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times (Q(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6835 := (-1 - (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6836 := (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6837 := ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) - (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$6838 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6839 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$6840 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (4 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6841 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$6842 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6843 := ((-1 + Q((2 \times (Q(3 + 4) - 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6844 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + Q(4 + 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6845 := (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(4)) \times Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$6846 := (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - ((Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6847 := (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6848 := ((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + 4^5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6849 := ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6850 := (Q(((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6851 := (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4)) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6852 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6853 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6854 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6855 := (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4)) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6856 := ((-1 - 2 + Q((3 + (Q(4) \times 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6857 := (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6858 := ((-1 + Q((2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)) / Q(4 + 5)))))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6859 := (-1 + (Q((2 \times (3 + 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6860 := (Q(((-1 + 2 - 3) + Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6861 := ((((-1 \times 2) - Q(3)) \times (4 - Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$6862 := (((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(3) + Q(4)))) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6863 := (-1 + (Q((2 + (3^4))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6864 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6865 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6866 := (-1 - ((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6827 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 + Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$6828 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6829 := (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) \times (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6830 := (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4)))) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6831 := (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + Q(6)))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6832 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6833 := (((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q(7)) \times 6) - (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6834 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6835 := (((-9 \times (Q(8) + 7)) + 6) \times 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6836 := (-9 - (Q(((8 - 7) + Q(6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6837 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) + 6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6838 := (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6839 := (-9 + (Q(8) \times (7 + Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6840 := (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) \times ((Q(6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6841 := (-9 + ((Q(8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6842 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 - Q(6)) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6843 := (((-9 - 8) \times Q(7)) + (6^5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$6844 := (-9 - (Q((8 \times 7)) + (6 + 5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6845 := (((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7) + 6)) \times 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6846 := (-9 + (Q(((8 - 7) + Q(6))) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6847 := (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times Q(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6848 := (-9 + 8 + (7 \times Q(6) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) + Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6849 := (-9 \times (Q(8) - ((Q(7) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6850 := ((Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) + Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6851 := (-9 + ((8 \times (Q(7 + 6) \times 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6852 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 \times (Q(6 + Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6853 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6854 := (((Q((-9 + Q(8))) - Q(Q(7))) \times (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6855 := (-9 - (Q((Q(8) - (7 + 6 - 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6856 := (-9 - ((Q((8 \times 7)) - (6 - 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6857 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6858 := 9 \times (8 - 7 + Q(6) + Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6859 := (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) \times (6 \times Q(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6860 := (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6861 := (-9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6862 := ((-9 - Q(8)) \times ((7 - (6 - 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6863 := (-9 - ((Q((8 + Q(7))) - Q(6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6864 := ((Q((-9 + Q(8))) - Q(Q(7))) \times (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6865 := (((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6866 := (-9 - ((Q((8 \times 7)) - (6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6867 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6868 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6869 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6870 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + Q(Q(4))) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6871 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6872 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6873 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6874 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) \times (Q(4) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6875 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4) - 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6876 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3))/4)^5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6877 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6878 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6879 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6880 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6881 &:= (-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6882 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (Q(3 + 4) - Q(Q(5)))) \times 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6883 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + (3^4))) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6884 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6885 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) - (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6886 &:= (-1 - 2 + Q(((3 \times Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6887 &:= (-1 \times 2 + Q(((3 \times Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6888 &:= (-1 + Q((Q(2^3) - (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6889 &:= Q((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6890 &:= (-1 + 2 + Q(((3 \times Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6891 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6892 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6893 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) - ((Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6894 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6895 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(4) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6896 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6897 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6898 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6899 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6900 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(3 + 4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6901 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6902 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6903 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6904 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) - Q(4)) \times Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6905 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(4)) \times Q(Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6906 &:= (Q((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - Q(4))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6867 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) \times Q(6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6868 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7)) + Q((6 \times 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6869 &:= ((Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6870 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6871 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) - ((7 - 6) - Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6872 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q((Q(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6873 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6874 &:= (Q(((-9 + 8 \times 7) + Q(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6875 &:= (((-9 \times 8 - 7) - Q(Q(6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6876 &:= (-9 - ((8 - 7 - 6) \times (Q(5 + 4) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6877 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q((Q(7) + 6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6878 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6879 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (Q(7) - (Q((6 \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6880 &:= (-9 + Q((8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6881 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + Q(Q((7 - 6) \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6882 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6883 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + Q(7))) + Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6884 &:= (Q(((-9 + 8 \times 7) + Q(6))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6885 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times 7) + Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6886 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) + Q(6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6887 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + 6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6888 &:= (-9 + ((8 + Q(7)) \times Q((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6889 &:= Q((-9 + (Q(8) + (7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6890 &:= (((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7)))/Q(6)) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6891 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6 + 5))) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6892 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) \times (Q(6) + (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6893 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) \times 7 - (6 \times Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6894 &:= (Q(((-9 + 8 \times 7) + Q(6))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6895 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6896 &:= (-9 - ((Q((8 \times 7)) - (Q(6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6897 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q((Q(7) + 6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6898 &:= (-9 + (((8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6899 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (Q(7) - Q((6 \times 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6900 &:= ((((-9 + Q(8)) \times (7 + 6)) - Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6901 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6 + 5) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6902 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6903 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) \times ((7 + 6 - 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6904 &:= (Q(((-9 + 8 \times 7) + Q(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6905 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) + Q(6 + Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6906 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times (Q(Q(6))/(5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6907 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) - (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6908 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(Q(3))) - Q((4 \times Q(5)))))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
6909 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) - (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6910 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6911 &:= ((-1 + 2^{Q(3)}) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6912 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6913 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + (3^4)))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6914 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6915 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6916 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((3 + (Q(4) \times 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6917 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
6918 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))/Q(4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6919 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6920 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((3 + (Q(4) \times 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6921 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6922 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - ((Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6923 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + (3^4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6924 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6925 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6926 &:= ((((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4)) \times Q((5 + 6))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6927 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6928 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6929 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
6930 &:= ((Q(Q((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))))) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6931 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q((4 \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6932 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q((4 \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6933 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6934 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6935 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6936 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + ((Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6937 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + ((Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6938 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6939 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6940 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) + ((Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6941 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6942 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6943 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6944 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6945 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6946 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6907 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(6) \times (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6908 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) \times (Q(6) + (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6909 &:= (Q((-9 \times 8 + Q(7 + 6))) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6910 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) - (7 \times 6)) \times 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6911 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(Q(7)) + ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6912 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) \times ((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6913 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + (Q(Q(6)) + Q((Q(5 + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6914 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) - ((Q(6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6915 &:= (((-9 - 8 + (Q(7) \times 6)) \times Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6916 &:= (-9 - ((Q((8 \times 7)) - (Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6917 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + Q(7)) \times 6)) - (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6918 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times (Q(Q(6))/(5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6919 &:= ((-9 + Q(8) \times 7) - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6920 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((Q(7) + Q(6)) \times Q(5 + 4)) + Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6921 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6922 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) \times (7 + 6 - Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6923 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6924 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q((Q(7) + (6 - 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6925 &:= ((((-9 + Q(Q(8)) - Q(Q(7)))/6) \times Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6926 &:= (-9 + (Q(8 + 7) + ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6927 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6928 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6929 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6930 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 + 6) + Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6931 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6932 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - ((6 - Q(5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6933 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q((Q(7) + 6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6934 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) - ((6 + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6935 &:= ((-9 - Q(8)) \times (((7 - 6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6936 &:= (-9 + ((Q(((8 - 7) + Q(6))) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6937 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6938 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6939 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - ((Q(7 + 6) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6940 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (7 + Q(6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6941 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6))/(5 + 4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
6942 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) + 7) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) - Q((3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6943 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
6944 &:= (-9 + (8 \times Q(7) + Q(Q(Q(((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
6945 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times Q(7)) + Q(Q(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6946 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) + Q(Q(Q(((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$6947 := (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6948 := (-1 - ((2^{Q(3)}) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6949 := (-1 \times ((2^{Q(3)}) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6950 := (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + 4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6951 := (((-1 + 2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6952 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q((5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$6953 := ((Q((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) \times (5 + Q(6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$6954 := (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6955 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6956 := (-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6957 := (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6958 := ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6959 := (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6960 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6961 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6962 := ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6963 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6964 := ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q((4 + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6965 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$6966 := ((-1 + ((2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6967 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6968 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$6969 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q((Q(4) + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6970 := (((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + Q(Q(4)))) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6971 := (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (4 + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6972 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q((Q(4) + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6973 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q((Q(4) + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6974 := (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) \times (4 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$6975 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6976 := (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6977 := (Q(Q((-1 + 2 \times 3))) + (Q(4) + ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$6978 := (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) - (Q(4) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6979 := (Q(((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6980 := (((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3)))) \times 4) + ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6981 := (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3) + (4 \times (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$6982 := ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) + (4 \times (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$6983 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6984 := ((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6985 := ((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6986 := (-1 + (Q(((2 + 3) \times Q(4))) + ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$6947 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6948 := (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6949 := (-9 + 8 - (Q((Q(7) + 6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6950 := ((-9 + 8) \times (Q((Q(7) + 6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6951 := (-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (Q(6) - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6952 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6953 := (-9 - 8 - (Q((Q(7) + 6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6954 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - Q((6 \times Q(((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))))$$

$$6955 := (((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7)))/6) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6956 := ((-9 + (Q(8 + 7) \times (6 + Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6957 := (-9 \times (Q(8) - ((7 \times Q(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6958 := ((-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6959 := (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 \times 6)) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6960 := (((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6961 := (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + Q(6)))) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6962 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6963 := (-9 - 8 - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6964 := (((Q((-9 + Q(8))) - Q(Q(7))) \times (6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6965 := (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6966 := (-9 + (Q(8 + 7) \times (Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6967 := (-9 + 8 - (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6968 := ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6969 := (-9 + 8 - (Q((Q(7) + 6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6970 := ((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6971 := (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6972 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6973 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + ((5 + 4) \times Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6974 := (((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7 + 6) + Q(Q(5)))))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6975 := (-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - (Q((6 \times 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6976 := (-9 - ((Q((8 \times 7)) - Q(6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6977 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(((7 \times 6) - Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6978 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) \times (Q(6) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6979 := (-9 + 8 - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6980 := ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6981 := (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + Q(6)))) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6982 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6983 := ((-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6984 := (-9 \times (8 - Q((7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$6985 := (((-9 + 8 \times 7) - Q(6)) \times (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6986 := (((-9 \times Q(8)) - (7 - Q((6 + Q(Q(((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$6987 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6988 := ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) - (4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6989 := (Q(((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4)) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6990 := ((((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$6991 := (Q((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times Q(4)))) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6992 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q((4 \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6993 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6994 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6995 := (Q((-1 + Q((2 + 3 + 4)))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6996 := (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times 4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$6997 := (-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + (4 \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$6998 := ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) + (4 \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6999 := (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7000 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3 + 4))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7001 := (Q((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - Q(4))) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7002 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + Q((Q(4) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$7003 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7004 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7005 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7006 := (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7007 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7008 := (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) \times (Q((Q(4) - 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7009 := (Q(((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4)) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7010 := (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + (Q(4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7011 := (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7012 := (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) \times (Q((Q(4) - 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7013 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7014 := ((-1 \times 2 + (Q(3)^4)) - (Q((5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7015 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7016 := (((-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + Q(4))) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7017 := ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7018 := ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(3) + (Q(4) \times 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7019 := (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7020 := ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - Q(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7021 := (Q((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - Q(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7022 := ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(3) + (Q(4) \times 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7023 := ((-1 - 2 + Q((3 + Q(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7024 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q((3 + Q(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7025 := (-1 \times ((Q(2 + 3) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$6987 := ((-9 \times 8 + Q(Q(7))) \times ((6 \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6988 := (-9 + (((8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6989 := (-9 - (Q(8) - ((Q(7) \times (Q(Q(6))) / (5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6990 := (((-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) + Q(Q(6)))))) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6991 := (-9 + ((Q(8) + (7 - (6 - 5))) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6992 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 + Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$6993 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q((7 \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6994 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q(((7 + 6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$6995 := (-9 - ((8 \times Q(7)) - Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$6996 := ((-9 + 8) \times ((Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6997 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7 - Q(Q(6)))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$6998 := (-9 + ((8 \times (Q(7) + 6)) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$6999 := ((-9 + 8 + Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7000 := (((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) + Q(5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7001 := (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7002 := (-9 \times ((Q(8) \times (7 + 6 - Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7003 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q((Q((7 + 6 - 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7004 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7005 := (-9 - ((Q((8 \times 7)) - (6 \times Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7006 := (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7007 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + 6)) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7008 := ((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) \times (Q((6 + (5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7009 := (-9 + 8 - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7010 := ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7011 := (-9 + ((Q(8) + ((7 + 6) + Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7012 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + 6) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7013 := (-9 \times 8 + (((7 + 6) \times Q(Q(5))) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7014 := ((-9 \times Q(8 + 7)) - (Q(6 + Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7015 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 \times 6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7016 := (-9 - (((Q(8) + (Q(7) + 6)) \times Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7017 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + 6)) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7018 := (((-9 - 8) \times Q(7)) - (6 - (Q(Q(5 + 4)) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7019 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(7 + 6) \times 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7020 := ((-9 - Q(8 + 7)) \times (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7021 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q((7 + 6 - 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7022 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7023 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7024 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((Q(Q(7)) - (6 - 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7025 := (((-9 - 8 + (Q(7) \times 6)) \times Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7026 &:= (Q(((((-1+2) \times 3) + Q(4+5))) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
7027 &:= ((-1+2+Q((3+Q(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
7028 &:= (-1+(Q((2+Q(Q(3)))) + (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
7029 &:= ((Q(((((-1+2) \times 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7030 &:= (((-1+(Q(2+3) + Q(Q(4)))) \times Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\
7031 &:= (Q((Q((-1+2+Q(3))) - Q(4))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
7032 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
7033 &:= (-1+2+(Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
7034 &:= ((-1+Q((2+Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7035 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
7036 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((3+Q(4+5))) + (6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
7037 &:= ((-1+(2 \times Q((3 \times (Q(4) + 5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
7038 &:= (-1+(Q((2+(3^4))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7039 &:= (-1+((2^{3+4}) \times (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
7040 &:= ((-1+2-Q(3)) \times ((4 \times 5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7041 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7042 &:= (-1+(2^{Q(3)} + (Q(Q(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7043 &:= (-1+(((2 \times 3) \times (4^5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7044 &:= (((-1-2+Q(3)) \times (4^5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
7045 &:= (((Q((-1+Q(2 \times 3))) + 4) \times 5) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
7046 &:= ((-1-Q(2+3)) \times ((4+Q(Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7047 &:= ((-1-2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7048 &:= (Q(((((-1 \times (2+3)) + Q(4+5))) + (Q(Q(6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
7049 &:= (-1 - ((2-Q(3+4)) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7050 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(3+4)) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7051 &:= (Q((Q((-1+2+Q(3))) - Q(4))) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
7052 &:= ((-1-2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7053 &:= (-1-2+Q((Q(3+4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7054 &:= (-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(3+4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7055 &:= (-1+Q((2 \times (3+4+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
7056 &:= Q((Q(((((-1+2) \times (3+4))) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7057 &:= (-1+2+Q((Q(3+4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7058 &:= (((-1-2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((4 \times 5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7059 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((4 \times 5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7060 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4+5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7061 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) - (Q((4 \times 5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7062 &:= ((-1+2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((4 \times 5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7063 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7064 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(Q(3)))) + ((Q(4) \times 5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7065 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4+5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7026 &:= ((-9+8+7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7027 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) - (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7028 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7029 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7+6) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7030 &:= (((-9+Q(8)) \times (7+Q(6+5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7031 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7032 &:= ((((-9+Q(8)) - Q(Q(7))) \times (6 - (5+4))) - (3+2+1)) \\
7033 &:= ((-9 \times (8+Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7034 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((Q(Q(7)) - (6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7035 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - Q((6 \times 5)))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7036 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) + (Q(7) + Q(Q(6)))) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7037 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - (7 \times Q(6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7038 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - ((6 \times 5) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7039 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(7+6) \times 5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
7040 &:= ((-9+Q(8)) \times (7+Q((6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7041 &:= (Q((-9+8+(Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
7042 &:= (((-9-8) \times (Q(7+6) + 5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7043 &:= (((-9-8) \times Q(7)) + ((6^5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7044 &:= (((-9-8+Q(Q(7))) - Q(6)) \times ((5+4) - (3+2+1))) \\
7045 &:= (((-9+Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7046 &:= (Q((-9-8 - (Q(7) - (6 \times Q(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7047 &:= (-9 + Q(((Q(8)/(7-6-5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7048 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (5 + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7049 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7050 &:= (((-9+Q(8)) \times (7+Q(6+5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
7051 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times Q(Q(6))) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7052 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q((8+7-6))) + (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7053 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7054 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7055 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7056 &:= Q(((Q(Q((-9+8+7))) - Q(6))/(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7057 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7 - Q(6+5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7058 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7059 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7060 &:= (((-9 + ((8+7) \times 6)) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7061 &:= (Q((-9 + ((8+7) \times 6))) + (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7062 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + 6)) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7063 &:= (-9 + (Q(((8-7-6) + Q(5+4))) + Q(Q((3+2+1)))))) \\
7064 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7+6) + Q(Q(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7065 &:= (-9 \times ((8+7) - (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$7066 := (-1 - (((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7067 := (((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7068 := (Q(((((-1 + 2) \times 3) + Q(4 + 5))) + (Q(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7069 := (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7070 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((4 \times Q((5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7071 := (-1 + (2 \times ((Q(3)^4) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7072 := ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7073 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7074 := (-1 + (((Q(Q(2 + 3)) + Q(4)) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7075 := (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + 4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7076 := ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7077 := (-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - (4 \times (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$7078 := ((Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + 4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7079 := (-1 + (((2 + 3) + Q(Q(4))) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7080 := ((Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) - (4 \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7081 := (Q((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - Q(4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7082 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + Q((4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$7083 := (-1 - 2 + (Q((3 + Q(4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$7084 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q((3 + Q(4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$7085 := (-1 + (Q(((2 + Q(Q(3))) - (4 - 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7086 := (Q(((((-1 + 2) \times 3) + Q(4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7087 := (-1 + 2 + (Q((3 + Q(4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$7088 := (((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + Q(4)) \times (5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7089 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$7090 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7091 := (Q((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - Q(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$7092 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7093 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$7094 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((4 \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7095 := (((-1 + Q((Q(2 \times 3) + 4))) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7096 := (Q(Q((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q(4))) - (Q((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7097 := (-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - (Q((Q(4) - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$7098 := ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7099 := ((-1 + (Q((Q(2 \times 3) + 4)) \times 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7100 := (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(3 + 4))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7101 := (Q((-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) + Q(4)))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7102 := (-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7103 := (-1 + (Q(2^3) \times (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7104 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7105 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4) - 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7066 := (-9 + ((Q(8 + 7) \times (6 + Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7067 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7068 := ((-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - Q((6 \times (5 + 4)))))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7069 := (Q((-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + 6))) + Q((Q(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7070 := ((Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (Q(6) - Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7071 := (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + Q(6)))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7072 := ((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) \times (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7073 := (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7074 := (-9 \times (8 - ((Q(7) \times 6) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7075 := ((-9 \times Q(8 + 7)) - (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7076 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((7 \times 6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7077 := (-9 + (Q(Q((8 + 7 - 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7078 := (-9 \times 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7079 := ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) + ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7080 := ((-9 - 8 - ((7 - Q(6)) \times Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7081 := ((-9 - Q(8)) \times ((Q(7 + 6) + Q(5)) / (4 - (3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7082 := (((Q((-9 + Q(8)) - 7 - 6)) + 5) \times 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7083 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7))) + Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7084 := ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7 + 6) + Q(Q(5)))))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7085 := ((-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) + Q(Q(6)))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7086 := (Q((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7087 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) + (6 - Q(5))) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7088 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (Q(6) + Q(((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7089 := (-9 - (Q(8) \times 7 - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7090 := ((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7091 := (Q(((((-9 + 8) \times 7) + Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7092 := (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7093 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7) - Q((6 \times 5)))))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7094 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 + ((6 \times 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7095 := (((-9 - (Q(8) + 7)) \times Q(6)) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7096 := (((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times Q(6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7097 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7098 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + ((Q(6) + Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7099 := ((-9 + 8 + Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7100 := ((-9 + 8 - (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5))) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7101 := (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + Q(6)))) + ((5 + 4) + Q((3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7102 := (((-9 - 8) \times Q(7 + 6)) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7103 := ((-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7104 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7105 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((Q(7) - Q((Q(6) - (5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7106 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3 + 4) \times (Q((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7107 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7108 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7109 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7110 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7111 &:= (Q((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - Q(4))) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7112 &:= ((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7113 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
7114 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((3 + Q(4 + 5))) + (Q(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7115 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4))) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7116 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times Q(4)))) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7117 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) \times (Q((5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7118 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7119 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7120 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7121 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7122 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7123 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7124 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7125 &:= (((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times 4)) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7126 &:= ((Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4 - ((5 + 6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7127 &:= (-1 - ((2^3) \times (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7128 &:= ((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7129 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - Q(4))) + (Q((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7130 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7131 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
7132 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7133 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7134 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7135 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4) + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7136 &:= (-1 - (Q((2 \times Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7137 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 \times Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7138 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7139 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((3 \times (4 \times 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7140 &:= ((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - 4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7141 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2 - 3) + Q(4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7142 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 - 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7143 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) - ((5 + 6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7144 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - ((4 - (5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7145 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times Q(3 \times 4))) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7106 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + Q(6)))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7107 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + Q((Q(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7108 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) - ((5 + 4) + Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7109 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 + Q(Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7110 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7) + Q(6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7111 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q((7 + 6 - 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7112 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q(((7 + 6) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7113 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7114 &:= (Q(((-9 + 8 \times 7) + Q(6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7115 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) - 7 + 6) \times 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7116 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 + (7 \times (6 + 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7117 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + 6)) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7118 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7119 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - ((Q(7 + 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7120 &:= ((-9 - (Q(8) + 7)) \times (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7121 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q(Q(((7 + 6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7122 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times Q(7 + 6)) - (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7123 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) \times ((7 \times Q(Q(6)))/Q(5 + 4))) - Q((3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7124 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 \times (6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7125 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) - (7 \times 6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7126 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7127 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + 6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7128 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((Q(7) - Q(6 + 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7129 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(7 + 6) \times 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7130 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) \times ((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7131 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q((7 + 6 - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7132 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times Q(7 + 6)) + 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7133 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7134 &:= (((-9 - 8 + Q(Q(7))) - 6) \times ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7135 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 \times (Q(Q(6)) + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7136 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + ((6 \times 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7137 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7138 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7139 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - Q(Q(6)))) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7140 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (7 + Q(6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7141 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times Q(Q(6))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7142 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5))) - Q((Q(4) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7143 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7144 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7145 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - Q(7 + 6)) \times 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7146 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times Q(4)))) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7147 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q((Q(4) - 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7148 &:= ((Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3))^4) + ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7149 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2 + 3) \times Q(4))) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7150 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7151 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7152 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7153 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7154 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7155 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7156 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7157 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(3)^4) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7158 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7159 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
7160 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) \times 4) \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7161 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7162 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
7163 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + (3^4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7164 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7165 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + Q((Q(4) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7166 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times Q(4)))) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7167 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7168 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7169 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
7170 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + 4)) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7171 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7172 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7173 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
7174 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) - Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7175 &:= ((((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7176 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2 + 3) + 4)) + ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
7177 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7178 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7179 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7180 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7181 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7182 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7183 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7184 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7185 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + Q(Q((4 - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7146 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7147 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - (7 \times Q(6 + 5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7148 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7149 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7150 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((7 + 6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7151 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7152 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times Q(7 + 6)) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7153 &:= (-9 \times 8 + Q((Q((7 + (Q(6) / (5 + 4)))) - Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7154 &:= ((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 \times (Q(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7155 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - Q(7 + 6)) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7156 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 - (Q(7) - (6 \times Q(5))))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7157 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7158 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7159 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) \times (7 + 6 - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7160 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8 + 7) \times 6)) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7161 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times Q(Q(6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7162 &:= (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) - Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7163 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7164 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7165 &:= ((-9 \times ((Q(8) - 7 + 6) \times 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7166 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4))) + Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7167 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7168 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7169 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7170 &:= (-9 - ((8 - Q(Q(7))) \times ((6 \times 5) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7171 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) - (7 - (Q(6) + Q(Q(5))))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7172 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6^5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7173 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7174 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7175 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7176 &:= (Q((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7177 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((Q(7) \times (6 \times Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7178 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) \times (6 \times Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7179 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) + (7 - Q(Q(6)))) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7180 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times Q(7 + 6))) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7181 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + Q(6)))) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7182 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + Q(7)) \times (Q(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7183 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((Q(7) - Q(6 + 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7184 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((Q(Q(7)) - 6) \times ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7185 &:= ((((-9 \times Q(8)) + 7 + 6) \times 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7186 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7187 &:= ((-1-2+Q((Q(Q(3))+4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7188 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3))+4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7189 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4-Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7190 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) + 4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7191 &:= ((-1+2+Q((Q(Q(3))+4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7192 &:= ((-1+2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4-Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7193 &:= (((-1+2-3) \times Q(4)) + Q((Q(Q(5)) + (Q(6) - Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
7194 &:= ((-1+Q(((2+3) + (Q(4) \times 5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
7195 &:= (Q(((-1+2+3) + Q(4+5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
7196 &:= (-1-2 - (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) \times (Q((5+6)) - Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
7197 &:= ((-1-2) \times (Q(Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
7198 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(3) + Q(4+5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
7199 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q((Q(3) + (Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7200 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) + Q(4+5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
7201 &:= ((-1+2+Q((Q(3) + Q(4+5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
7202 &:= ((-1+Q((2 \times Q(3+4)))) - Q(Q((Q(5) + (6 - (7+8+9)))))) \\
7203 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2 \times 3) + Q(4))) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7204 &:= (-1 - (((2+3) - Q(4)) \times (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
7205 &:= (((-1 \times (2+3)) + Q(4)) \times (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
7206 &:= (Q((Q((-1+2+Q(3))) - Q(4))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7207 &:= (-1 - ((2^3) \times ((4-5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7208 &:= ((-1+2-Q(3)) \times ((4-5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7209 &:= ((-1-2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
7210 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7211 &:= ((-1+2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5+Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7212 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) - (4 - (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
7213 &:= ((-1+2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
7214 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(3)^4) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
7215 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2+3)) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
7216 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2 \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
7217 &:= (-1+2 + ((Q(3)^4) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
7218 &:= (((-1-2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7219 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4) \times 5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7220 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) + 4)) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
7221 &:= (-1+2 + (Q((Q(Q(3))+4)) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7222 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4+5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7223 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (((3 - Q(4)) \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7224 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7225 &:= Q((-1+2 + (Q(3+4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7186 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) - ((Q(6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7187 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7 - Q(6+5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7188 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7189 &:= ((-9+8+Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
7190 &:= (((-9+8+Q(7)) \times (6 \times Q(5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7191 &:= (-9 + ((8+Q((7+6-5))) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7192 &:= (-9-8 - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6+Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7193 &:= ((-9-8+Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
7194 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 + ((6+Q(5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7195 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - Q(7+6))) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7196 &:= (Q((-9 + ((8+7) \times 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
7197 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + 7) + (6^5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7198 &:= ((-9 - (Q(8) + Q(7))) \times (Q(6) + (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7199 &:= (-9+8 - ((Q(7) - Q(6+5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7200 &:= ((-9+8) \times ((Q(7) - Q(6+5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7201 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7202 &:= (-9+8 + (Q(Q(7)) \times ((6 \times 5)/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7203 &:= (-9-8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7204 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) - ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7205 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7206 &:= ((-9+Q((8+(7 \times (6+5)))))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7207 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + 6)) - (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7208 &:= (-9+8 - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6+Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7209 &:= ((-9+8+Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
7210 &:= ((-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7+6) + Q(Q(5)))))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7211 &:= ((((-9 \times Q(8)) + 7) \times 6) + Q(Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7212 &:= (((-9-8) \times (Q(7+6) - 5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7213 &:= ((-9-8+Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
7214 &:= (Q((-9-8+Q(7))) - ((6 - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7215 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) + (6 \times Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
7216 &:= (-9 + Q(((8+7) \times 6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7217 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6+5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7218 &:= (-9 + ((8+Q(Q(7))) \times ((6 \times 5)/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7219 &:= (-9+8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7220 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (Q(7+6) + Q(Q(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7221 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q(Q((7+6-5))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7222 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7223 &:= (-9-8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
7224 &:= (-9+8+Q((Q((7+(Q(6)/(5+4)))) - Q((3+2+1)))))) \\
7225 &:= Q((-9+Q(8+7)) - (Q(6+5) + 4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7226 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((3 - Q(4)) \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7227 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7228 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7229 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 \times Q(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7230 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times Q(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7231 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7232 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7233 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7234 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - (4 \times (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7235 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7236 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times (Q(4) - 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7237 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
7238 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7239 &:= (-1 - (((2^3) - Q(4)) \times (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7240 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)) \times (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7241 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7242 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) - (Q((Q(4) - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7243 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (Q((5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
7244 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7245 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7246 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7247 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7248 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7249 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times 4)) \times Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7250 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + 4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7251 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7252 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - (Q((5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
7253 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7254 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7255 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2 + 3) + Q(4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7256 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times (5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7257 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7258 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7259 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((3 \times (4 \times 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7260 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7261 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7262 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4) - 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7263 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7264 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 \times 3) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7265 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7226 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + (7 \times (6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7227 &:= ((-9 - Q(8)) \times (((7 - 6)^5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7228 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7229 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7230 &:= ((Q((-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + 6))) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7231 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (6 \times Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7232 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
7233 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (Q(7) \times (6 \times Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7234 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7 + Q(6))) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7235 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - Q(7 + 6)) \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7236 &:= (-9 \times (Q(Q(8)) - Q((Q(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7237 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + Q((6 \times 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7238 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7239 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7240 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((7 + 6) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7241 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8 + 7) \times 6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7242 &:= (((-9 + 8 - Q(Q(7))) \times (6 - (5 + 4))) + Q((3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7243 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7244 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7245 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (Q(6 + Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7246 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7247 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) - (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7248 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7249 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) \times (6 \times Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7250 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + Q(6)) \times (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7251 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) - (7 \times 6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7252 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) - (7 \times (6 - (5 + 4)))) + Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7253 &:= (((-9 - (Q(8) \times 7)) \times 6) - (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7254 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4))) - Q((3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7255 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - ((Q(7) - Q(6 + 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7256 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8) + 7)) - (6^5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7257 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + Q((6 \times 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7258 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7259 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7260 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7261 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times Q(7 + 6)) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7262 &:= 9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7) + Q(6)) - Q(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7263 &:= (((-9 - (Q(8) \times 7)) \times 6) + 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7264 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times (Q(7) - (6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7265 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7266 &:= ((-1 + (2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7267 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4) + (5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7268 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7269 &:= ((-1 + ((Q(2 \times 3) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7270 &:= (((Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7271 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7272 &:= ((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7273 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7274 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7275 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 \times 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7276 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 \times (Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7277 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4)) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7278 &:= (((-1 - 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7279 &:= (-1 + ((2 - 3) \times (Q(4) \times (Q((5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7280 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + 4)) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7281 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7282 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7283 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (Q(4) \times (Q((5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7284 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7285 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 + (5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7286 &:= ((-1 + (2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4)) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7287 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7288 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7289 &:= (-1 + ((Q((2 \times Q(3))) - Q(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7290 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7291 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7292 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7293 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7294 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7295 &:= (Q((-1 + Q((2 + 3 + 4)))) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7296 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7297 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + (4 - 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7298 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7299 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2 - 3) + Q(4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7300 &:= (Q((-1 - ((2 - 3) \times Q(4 + 5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7301 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7302 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q((Q(4 + 5) + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7303 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7304 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7305 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7266 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + Q((Q(7) - (6 + (5 + 4)))))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7267 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times Q(7)) + Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7268 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) - (6 - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7269 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7270 &:= ((-9 - (Q(8 + 7) - Q(6 + Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7271 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times ((6 \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7272 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + Q((6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
7273 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (Q(7) - (6 \times Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7274 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7275 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7276 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times Q(Q(6))) - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7277 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7 - Q(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7278 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7 + 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7279 &:= (-9 + 8 - (7 \times (Q((Q(Q(6)) / Q(5 + 4)) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7280 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + (6 + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7281 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + Q(6)))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7282 &:= 9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7) + Q(6)) - 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7283 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7284 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7) - (6 \times Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7285 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7286 &:= (Q((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7287 &:= (-9 - (Q((Q(8) + (7 + 6 - Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7288 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7289 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((7 \times 6)) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7290 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(((8 - 7)^6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7291 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (7 + 6) \times 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7292 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8) + Q((Q(7) - (6 + 5)))))) \times 4) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7293 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) - 7) + ((6^5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7294 &:= (((-9 - 8 - Q(7)) \times (Q(6) + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7295 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7296 &:= (Q((-9 + (((8 + 7) \times 6) + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7297 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7 - Q(6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7298 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7 \times 6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7299 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7300 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + 7 + 6 + 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7301 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) - (6 \times Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7302 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7))) - (Q((Q(6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7303 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7304 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8 + 7)) - ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7305 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7306 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7307 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (4 - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7308 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7309 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7310 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q((2 + 3 + 4))) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7311 &:= ((Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3))^4) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7312 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(3)^4) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7313 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7314 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((Q(4) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7315 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (4 + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7316 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7317 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) \times ((4 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7318 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((4 \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7319 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + (3^4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7320 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times Q(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7321 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - (4 \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
7322 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + 4) + (Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7323 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 + Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7324 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2 + 3) \times Q(4))) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7325 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7326 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7327 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(4) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7328 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7329 &:= (-1 + (((Q(2 \times 3) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7330 &:= (((Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7331 &:= (Q((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - Q(4))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7332 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(((3 + 4) \times 5))) \times 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7333 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(((4 \times 5) - 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7334 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7335 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7336 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7337 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) - 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7338 &:= (((-1 - 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7339 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7340 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7341 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) - 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7342 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7343 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7344 &:= ((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + Q((4 + (5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7345 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) + Q((4 + (5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7306 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) + 7 + 6) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7307 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (Q(7) \times 6))) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7308 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - Q(6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7309 &:= (((-9 - (Q(8) \times 7)) + (6^5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7310 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + Q((7 - 6 + Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7311 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + (Q(7) - (6 - Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7312 &:= (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7313 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7314 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8 + 7)) - (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7315 &:= (((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) \times 6)) \times Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7316 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 + (7 \times (6 + 5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7317 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7) + Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7318 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7 - (6 \times Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7319 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) - (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7320 &:= ((Q((-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + 6))) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7321 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7322 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) - (6 \times (Q(5 + 4) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7323 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (Q(7) \times (6 \times Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7324 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((Q(7) + 6 \times 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7325 &:= (Q(((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7326 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7327 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7328 &:= (-9 - (((Q(8) \times (7 \times 6)) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7329 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7330 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7) - Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7331 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + (6 \times Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7332 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + Q(Q(6))) - (5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7333 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7334 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + ((6 + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7335 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - Q(7 + 6)) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7336 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q(((7 \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7337 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + 6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7338 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7339 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - Q((Q(7) - (6 + 5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7340 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) + (6 \times Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7341 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7) \times 6) \times Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7342 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 + (6 \times Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7343 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (6 \times Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7344 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7345 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - Q(7 + 6)) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7346 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 - Q(4)) \times ((5 + 6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7347 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7348 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7349 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3 \times Q(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7350 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3))/4) \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7351 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7352 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7353 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7354 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7355 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 \times 3))) - 4) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7356 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))/Q(4 + 5)))) + (Q(Q(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7357 &:= (((-1 - (2^{Q(3)})) \times 4) + Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7358 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7359 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times ((4 \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7360 &:= (((Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) - 4) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7361 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7362 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7363 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7364 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7365 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2 + 3) + Q(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7366 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2 \times 3) + Q(4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7367 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(((3^4) + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7368 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) \times (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7369 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7370 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4))) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7371 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7372 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) \times (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7373 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7374 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(3)) \times (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7375 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + 4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7376 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7377 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7378 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7379 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) - (Q(Q(4)) - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7380 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7381 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7382 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7383 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7384 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((4 \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7385 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4))) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7346 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(7) - Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7347 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) - Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7348 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 \times (6 - Q(Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7349 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7350 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q((7 + 6) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7351 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8 + 7) - Q(6 + Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7352 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 - (6 \times (Q(5 + 4) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
7353 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((Q(7) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7354 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7355 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (Q(6 + Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7356 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + (6 \times Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7357 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7358 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times Q(6 + 5)) - (4 \times Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7359 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) \times (6 \times Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7360 &:= (((-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + Q(Q(6))))/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7361 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + (7 - Q((6 \times 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7362 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times Q(7)) - (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7363 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (Q(6) \times 5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7364 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((Q(7 + 6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7365 &:= (-9 - (Q((Q(8) - 7 - 6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7366 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) - Q(7 + 6)) \times Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7367 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (Q(7) - (Q(6 + Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7368 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + Q(Q(7)))) \times ((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7369 &:= ((Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) \times 6) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7370 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7 + 6) - (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7371 &:= (-9 \times ((Q(Q(8)) - 7 + 6)/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7372 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7373 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) + Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7374 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + Q(6)) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7375 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) - (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7376 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7377 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7378 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - Q(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7379 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + ((Q(7) - Q((Q(Q(6))/Q(5 + 4)))) \times Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7380 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7 + 6)) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7381 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q((7 - (Q(6) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7382 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + (6 \times Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7383 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (Q(7) - (6 \times Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7384 &:= ((((-9 - Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + Q(6 + Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7385 &:= (-9 - (Q((Q(8) - 7 - 6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$7386 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - ((5 + 6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$7387 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - ((5 + 6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$7388 := ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) - (Q((4 \times 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7389 := (-1 + (((2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4))) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7390 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - ((5 + 6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$7391 := (Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4))) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7392 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7393 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7394 := ((Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times (4 + Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7395 := (-1 + Q((2 + (Q(3 + 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7396 := Q((Q((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7397 := (-1 \times (Q(2^3) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7398 := (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + (Q(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7399 := (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7400 := ((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)) \times (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7401 := (Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7402 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + Q((4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$7403 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + Q((4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$7404 := (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7405 := ((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7406 := (-1 + (((Q(Q(2 + 3)) - 4) \times (5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7407 := (-1 - 2 + (3 \times ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7408 := (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7409 := (-1 + ((2 + (Q(3 + 4) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7410 := ((Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7411 := (-1 + 2 + (3 \times ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7412 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7413 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$7414 := (Q(((-1 + 2 \times 3) + Q(4 + 5))) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7415 := ((-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7416 := ((Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7417 := ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7418 := ((-1 + Q((2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4)))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7419 := (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7420 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q(4) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7421 := (Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7422 := (((-1 - 2 - Q(3)) \times (4 - Q(Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7423 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(((3^4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7424 := (Q((-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7425 := (-1 + (Q(((2 + 3) + Q(4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7386 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) \times (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7387 := (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7 - Q(6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7388 := (-9 + 8 - 7 + Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7389 := (-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7390 := (Q(((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) - (5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7391 := (-9 - (((8 \times (7 + 6)) \times Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7392 := ((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) \times (6 + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7393 := (-9 + (Q((Q(8) + (7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))))) + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7394 := (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) + Q(6)) \times (Q(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7395 := ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 - Q(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7396 := Q(((Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) - 6) / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7397 := (-9 + (Q((Q((8 + 7 - 6)) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7398 := (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (6 \times Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7399 := (-9 - ((8 \times Q(7 + 6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7400 := (((-9 + (8 + 7 + 6)) \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7401 := (-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7402 := (((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times Q(6 + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7403 := (-9 \times 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7404 := ((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7405 := (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7406 := (-9 \times 8 - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7407 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7 - Q(Q(6)))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7408 := (((-9 \times 8) \times Q((7 - (6 - 5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7409 := (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7 \times (6 + 5)) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7410 := (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (Q(6 + Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7411 := ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7412 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 + (6 \times Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7413 := (-9 - ((Q((8 + Q(7))) - Q(Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7414 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(((7 \times 6) + Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7415 := (-9 - ((Q((Q(8) - 7 - 6)) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7416 := 9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - (Q(6) - Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7417 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) - (7 \times Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7418 := (-9 + 8 - (Q(Q(7)) + ((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7419 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((7 + 6) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7420 := (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) + Q((3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7421 := (((-9 \times ((8 \times Q(7)) - Q(6))) + Q(Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7422 := ((-9 + 8 - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7423 := (-9 + (8 \times ((Q(7) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7424 := (-9 - (Q(8) - (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7425 := (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7426 &:= (Q((-1+2 \times 3) + Q(4+5))) + 6+7+8+9 \\
7427 &:= (-1+2 + (Q(((3^4) + 5))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
7428 &:= ((-1-2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7429 &:= ((-1-2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4+Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7430 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4+Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7431 &:= (Q((-1+2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
7432 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) - ((4+Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7433 &:= ((-1+2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4+Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7434 &:= (((-1-2) \times Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7435 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+3) - (Q(Q(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7436 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+3) - (Q(Q(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7437 &:= ((-1+2 + (Q(3^4))) - (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7438 &:= ((-1-2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times 5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7439 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 \times 5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7440 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) - (Q(4) + (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7441 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) - ((4 \times 5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7442 &:= (-1 - (2 \times Q(3) - (Q(Q(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7443 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7444 &:= (Q((-1-2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((4 \times (5+6))) - Q((7+8+9)))) \\
7445 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
7446 &:= ((-1-2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7447 &:= ((-1-2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7448 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
7449 &:= ((-1-2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4+5 - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7450 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7451 &:= ((-1+2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7452 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) - (4+5 - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7453 &:= ((-1+2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4+5 - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7454 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7455 &:= ((-1 - (2+3)) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7456 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7457 &:= ((-1+2 + (Q(3^4))) - (5 - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7458 &:= (-1-2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7459 &:= ((-1+2-3) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7460 &:= (-1 - ((2-3) \times (Q(Q(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7461 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - (2 - (3 + (4+5)))))) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
7462 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7463 &:= ((-1+2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - ((4-5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7464 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7465 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7426 &:= (((-9 - Q(8+7)) \times (6+5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7427 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q((Q(7) + (6-5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7428 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q((Q(7) + (6-5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7429 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (Q(7) \times (6 - Q(5)))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
7430 &:= (-9 - (((Q(8) + 7) \times Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7431 &:= (-9 + ((Q(((8-7) + Q(6))) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7432 &:= (Q((-9+8+7)) + Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7433 &:= (-9-8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7434 &:= (-9 \times (Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
7435 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q(7) \times (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7436 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + 6)) + ((5+4) \times Q((3+2+1)))) \\
7437 &:= ((-9 + (((8 \times 7) + Q(6)) \times Q(5+4))) - (3+2+1)) \\
7438 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((7 \times 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7439 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times ((Q(7) \times 6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7440 &:= (((Q((-9+Q(8))) - Q(7))/6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
7441 &:= (-9+8 + (Q(Q(7)) + Q((Q(Q(6)) - Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
7442 &:= (((-9 - Q(8+7)) + (6^5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
7443 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((Q(7+6) \times 5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
7444 &:= (-9+8 + (Q(7) + Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7445 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - Q(((5+4) + Q((3+2+1)))) \\
7446 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5+4)))) \times (3+2+1)) \\
7447 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7448 &:= (-9+8 - (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7449 &:= (-9+8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7450 &:= ((Q((-9+Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7451 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q((Q(7) - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7452 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + ((7 \times (6 + Q(Q(5)))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
7453 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7+Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7454 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7+Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7455 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (((7 \times Q(Q(6))) - 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7456 &:= ((-9 + Q(((8+7) \times 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
7457 &:= (-9-8 + (Q(7+Q(6)) + Q((Q(5+4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
7458 &:= (-9 + ((8+Q(7)) \times (Q(6+5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7459 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6+Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7460 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8+7) + Q(Q(6)))) \times 5) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
7461 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + 7)) + Q((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7462 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times Q(7)) - (6 + (Q(Q(5+4)) + Q(Q((3+2+1)))) \\
7463 &:= (((((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q(7)) \times 6) + Q(Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7464 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + (5+4))) \times (3+2+1))) \\
7465 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7466 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times Q(4)))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7467 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7468 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7469 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7470 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7471 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7472 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(4) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7473 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7474 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7475 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7476 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((Q(4) \times (5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7477 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7478 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q(3) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7479 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7480 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7481 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + ((4 \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7482 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7483 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7484 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(3)^4) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7485 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7486 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 \times 3) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7487 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(3)^4) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7488 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7489 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + 4)) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7490 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (4 + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7491 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (4 + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7492 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) \times 4))) + ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7493 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) - ((Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7494 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 \times 3) - ((Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7495 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7496 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7497 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7498 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times Q(((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7499 &:= (-1 + ((Q(((2 - 3) + Q(4))) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7500 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(3 + 4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7501 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times Q(((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7502 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(4) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7503 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7504 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times Q((Q(4) + Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7505 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) - ((Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7466 &:= (-9 - (Q((8 + 7 \times 6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7467 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (7 \times Q(Q(6)))) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7468 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) \times (Q(6) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7469 &:= (Q((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6 - Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7470 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7471 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + (7 - Q((6 \times 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7472 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7 - Q(6))) - Q((Q(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7473 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (Q(7) - (6 \times Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7474 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7475 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7) - Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7476 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7477 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7478 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7479 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) \times (7 + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7480 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7481 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7482 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 \times (Q(6 + Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7483 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q((Q(7) + (6 - 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7484 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7 - 6) + Q((Q(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7485 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7486 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) - ((6 - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7487 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q((8 + 7 - 6)) + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7488 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times ((7 - 6 - 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7489 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + ((7 + Q(6)) \times 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7490 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7 + 6)) \times Q(Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7491 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8 + 7) - (6 \times Q(5))) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7492 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times Q(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7493 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7 + 6) + Q(((5 \times Q(4)) + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7494 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7495 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 + Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7496 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7497 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7498 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 - 6)) + Q((Q(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7499 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q((Q(7) + (6 - 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7500 &:= (((-9 - (8 - 7 - 6)) \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7501 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7502 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times Q((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7503 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7) + (Q((6 \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7504 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7505 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$7506 := (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7507 := ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7508 := (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 \times (5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7509 := ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - (Q((4 \times (5 + 6))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7510 := (Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7511 := (-1 - (2 \times Q(3) - ((Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7512 := (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7513 := (-1 + (Q(((2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7514 := (Q(((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) - Q(Q(4)))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7515 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q((5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$7516 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(3) + Q(4 + 5)))) - (6 + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7517 := ((((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(4)) \times (Q(Q(5)) + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7518 := (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) - ((Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7519 := ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) - ((Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7520 := ((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times ((Q(4) \times (5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7521 := (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7522 := (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - ((Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7523 := ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7524 := (-1 + (Q(2^3) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7525 := ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7526 := (-1 + 2 + (((Q(3) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7527 := ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7528 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7529 := (-1 - ((2 - 3) \times ((Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7530 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7531 := ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7532 := (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3 + 4)))) - (5 + (Q(Q(6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7533 := ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7534 := ((-1 + 2 + 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7535 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((4 + Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7536 := (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7537 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q((3 \times (4 + Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7538 := ((-1 + Q(((2 \times 3) + Q(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$7539 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7540 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7541 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + ((Q(4) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7542 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$7543 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7544 := (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (Q(4) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7545 := ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times (Q(4) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$7506 := (-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (Q((6 \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7507 := (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))))$$

$$7508 := (-9 \times 8 - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7509 := (-9 - 8 - (Q(7 + Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7510 := (((-9 + (8 + 7 + 6)) \times Q(Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7511 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q((7 \times 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7512 := (((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times Q(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$7513 := (-9 + 8 - (Q(7) + (6 - Q((Q(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7514 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q((7 \times (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7515 := (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 + 5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7516 := (-9 - ((Q(8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7517 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (7 - Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7518 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (7 - (Q(6) \times (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7519 := ((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7520 := ((-9 + 8 \times 7) \times ((6 \times Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7521 := (-9 - 8 - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7522 := ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7523 := ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7 + 6) \times 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7524 := (-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - (Q(6 + Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7525 := (((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times 6)) \times Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7526 := (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7527 := (-9 \times 8 - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7528 := (-9 \times 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - (6 - 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7529 := ((((-9 \times 8) \times (7 + Q(6))) + Q(Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7530 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7531 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 + Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7532 := (((-9 - Q(8 + 7)) + (6^5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7533 := ((-9 + Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7534 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) + (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7535 := ((-9 + Q(8)) \times ((7 + 6 \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7536 := ((-9 - 8 + 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7537 := (-9 - (Q(8) + ((Q(Q(7)) - (6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7538 := (-9 \times 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - (6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7539 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (((7 + 6) \times Q(Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7540 := (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) - (6 - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7541 := ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times Q(6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$7542 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((7 \times (6 + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$7543 := (-9 + (Q(8) \times (7 + 6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$7544 := (-9 + ((8 \times (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) + ((5 + 4) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$7545 := (((Q((-9 + Q(8))) - 7) / 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7546 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) + ((Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7547 &:= (-1 + (Q((2+Q(Q(3)))) + (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
7548 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + Q((Q(4+5) + 6))) - (7+8+9) \\
7549 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2^3))) - (4 \times (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7550 &:= (((-1+2 + (Q(3) + Q(Q(4)))) \times Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
7551 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
7552 &:= (((-1-2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) + 4^5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
7553 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) + 4^5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
7554 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2+3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7555 &:= ((Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + 4^5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
7556 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7557 &:= (-1-2 - ((Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) + 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7558 &:= (-1-2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((4 \times Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7559 &:= (-1 - (((2-3) - (Q(Q(4)) - 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7560 &:= ((-1-2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - Q((Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
7561 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7562 &:= (-1+2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((4 \times Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7563 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + (Q(3) + Q(4+5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
7564 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3+4))) - 5) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
7565 &:= (Q((-1-2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7566 &:= (-1-2 + Q((3 \times (4 - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7567 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7568 &:= (-1 + Q((Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + (Q(4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
7569 &:= Q((((-1+2 + Q(Q(3))) \times Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7570 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) - (Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7571 &:= ((-1 + ((Q(Q(2+3)) + (Q(4) + Q(Q(5)))) \times 6)) - (7+8+9)) \\
7572 &:= ((-1+2+3) \times (Q(4) + (5 + (Q(Q(6)) + Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
7573 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
7574 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)))) + (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7575 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(Q(2+3)))/Q(4))) \times 5) - (6+7+8+9) \\
7576 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + Q((4 + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
7577 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) + (Q(4) + ((5+6) \times Q((7+8+9)))) \\
7578 &:= ((-1 - (2+3)) \times (4+5 - (Q(Q(6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
7579 &:= (-1-2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q((Q(4) - 5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7580 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q((Q(4) - 5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7581 &:= (-1 + (Q(2+Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7582 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (Q((Q(4) - 5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7583 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) + (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7584 &:= ((-1 + (Q((2 \times (3+4))) + Q((5+6)))) \times (7+8+9)) \\
7585 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times Q(Q(4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7546 &:= (Q((-9+8+7) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7547 &:= (((-9 \times ((8+Q(7)) \times 6) + Q(Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7548 &:= (-9+8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + ((5+4) \times Q((3+2+1)))) \\
7549 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6+Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7550 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8+7) + Q(Q(6)))) \times 5) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7551 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times Q(Q(6))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
7552 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7553 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
7554 &:= (((-9 - (Q(8) + Q(7))) + (6^5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
7555 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - (Q((Q(7) + (6-5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7556 &:= (Q((-9+8 + (Q(7) + Q(6)))) + (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7557 &:= (-9+8 - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7558 &:= ((-9+8) \times (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7559 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7560 &:= (-9 + Q((Q(8) - (7 \times (6+5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7561 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times Q(7)) - Q(6+5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7562 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + Q((6 + Q(Q((5+4) - (3+2+1)))))) \\
7563 &:= (-9-8 - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7564 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (((7+Q(6)) \times Q(5+4)) - (3+2+1))) \\
7565 &:= (-9 - (Q(Q((8-7+6))) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7566 &:= ((-9+8+7) \times (Q(6) + Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
7567 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times Q(6+5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7568 &:= (-9+8 + Q((7 \times (6+5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7569 &:= Q((Q((-9+8+7)) + (Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7570 &:= ((-9 \times ((Q(8+7) \times 6)/5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7571 &:= (-9-8 - (Q(Q(7)) + (6+5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7572 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (((7+Q(Q(6))) \times 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7573 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) + Q((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7574 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q(7) + (Q(6) \times (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7575 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) - (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7576 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + ((Q(6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7577 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - (7 + Q((6 \times 5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7578 &:= (-9-8 + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7579 &:= (Q((-9 - (8 \times (7+6 - Q(5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
7580 &:= ((-9+8) \times (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7581 &:= (-9 + ((8+7) \times (6 + (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7582 &:= ((-9-8) \times (Q(7+6) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7583 &:= (-9-8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - (6-5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7584 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
7585 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8)) - ((Q(7+6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$7586 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4))) + (Q((5+6)) + Q((7+8+9))))$$

$$7587 := (-1 - ((2^{Q(3)}) - ((4+5) \times Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$7588 := (-1 \times ((2^{Q(3)}) - ((4+5) \times Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$7589 := (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + (4 \times (5 + Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$7590 := (((-1+2) \times 3) \times ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$7591 := (-1 + 2 + (3 \times ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9)))$$

$$7592 := (-1 + (Q(((2 \times Q(3+4)) - (5+6))) + 7+8+9))$$

$$7593 := ((-1 + Q((2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4)))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$7594 := (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + ((4+Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$7595 := (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - ((4+Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$7596 := (-1 - 2 + (Q((3 \times (4 + Q(5)))) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$7597 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q((3 \times (4 + Q(5)))) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$7598 := (-1 + (Q(((2 \times 3) + Q(4+5))) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$7599 := (Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + Q(4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9)$$

$$7600 := (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) - (Q(4) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$7601 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((4 \times (5+6))) - Q((7+8+9))))$$

$$7602 := (Q(((-1+2) \times 3)) + (Q((Q(4+5)+6)) + 7+8+9))$$

$$7603 := (-1 + (Q((2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4))) + 5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$7604 := (-1 + ((2+3) \times Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$7605 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$7606 := (-1 + (Q(((2+3) \times Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + (6 + Q((7+8+9))))))$$

$$7607 := (-1 + ((Q((2 \times (3+4))) + Q((5+6))) \times (7+8+9)))$$

$$7608 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$7609 := (Q(((-1+2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$7610 := (-1 + (2 \times Q(3) + (Q((Q(4+5)+6)) + 7+8+9)))$$

$$7611 := (Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$7612 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$7613 := (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (5+Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$7614 := (((-1 - (2+3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$7615 := (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - (4+5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$7616 := (((-1+2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (4^5) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$7617 := (((-1-2) \times (Q(Q(Q(3))) - (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$7618 := (-1 \times 2 + (((3 + Q(Q(4))) - 5) \times (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$7619 := (Q((-1+2+(3^4))) - (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$7620 := ((-1 + ((2 + Q(3+4)) \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))$$

$$7621 := (-1 + 2 + (((3 + Q(Q(4))) - 5) \times (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$7622 := (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$7623 := (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + ((4-5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$7624 := (-1 + (Q(((2+3) \times Q(4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$7625 := (Q((-1 + Q((2+3+4)))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$7586 := ((-9 + ((Q(8+7) + Q(Q(6))) \times 5)) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$7587 := ((-9 \times (8 + Q(7))) + Q((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7588 := ((-9+8) \times (Q(Q(7)) + (6+5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7589 := (((-9 - Q(8)) \times 7) + Q((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7590 := ((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7) - (6+5 - Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7591 := (-9 + ((Q(8) - (7+6 - Q(5))) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$7592 := ((-9 - Q(8)) \times ((7-6-5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$7593 := (-9 - 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - (6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7594 := (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7595 := (-9 - ((Q(Q((8-7+6))) - 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7596 := ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + Q((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7597 := (-9 + 8 - (Q(Q(7)) + ((6-5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7598 := (-9 + 8 - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(((6-5) \times (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7599 := ((-9+8) \times (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(((6-5) \times (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7600 := ((-9+8+(7 \times (6+5))) \times Q(4+3+2+1))$$

$$7601 := (-9 - 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) + (6 - Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7602 := (((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times Q(6+5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))$$

$$7603 := (((-9 - 8) \times 7) - (6 \times ((5+4) - Q(Q((3+2+1))))$$

$$7604 := (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$7605 := (-9 \times (Q((Q(8) + (7-6)) / (5 - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7606 := (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) + ((6 + Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$7607 := (-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q(7+6) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7608 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7609 := (-9 + 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - (6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7610 := ((-9+8) \times ((Q(Q(7)) - (6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7611 := ((-9+8) \times (Q((7 \times 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7612 := (-9 + (Q(8+7) + Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7613 := (-9 - 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7614 := (-9 \times (Q(8+7) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7615 := (-9 - ((Q(Q((8-7+6))) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7616 := (((-9+8+7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5))) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$7617 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7 - Q(Q(6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$7618 := ((-9+8) \times ((Q(Q(7)) + (6 - Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7619 := (((-9 - 8 - Q(7)) \times Q(6)) - (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7620 := ((-9 + (8+7+6)) \times (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1))$$

$$7621 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7622 := (-9 - ((Q(8) \times 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7623 := (-9 \times (8 - ((Q(7+6) \times 5) + 4+3+2+1))$$

$$7624 := (-9 + (Q(8) + Q((7 \times (6+5) + 4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7625 := (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - Q(Q(7))) + ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7626 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(3) - 4) \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7627 &:= (-1 + (((2^3) \times Q((4 + Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7628 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 - Q(4)) \times ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7629 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + (3^4))) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7630 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7631 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((Q(3 + 4) + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7632 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q((3 \times Q(4)))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7633 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7634 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7635 &:= ((Q(((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) / Q(4))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7636 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) + (4 + ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7637 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q((Q(Q(6)) / (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7638 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + (3^4))) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7639 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4))) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7640 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((Q(4) \times (5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7641 &:= (((-1 + 2^{Q(3)}) \times (4 + (5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7642 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7643 &:= (Q((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - Q(4))) + ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7644 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7645 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7646 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) \times Q((5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7647 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + (Q(4) + ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7648 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q((2 \times Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7649 &:= (-1 + ((2 + Q(3 + 4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7650 &:= ((-1 + Q((Q(2 + 3) - 4 - 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7651 &:= (Q((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7652 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (4 \times ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7653 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7654 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7655 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - Q((Q(Q(4)) - 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7656 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - Q((Q(Q(4)) - 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7657 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7658 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7659 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7660 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(4) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7661 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7662 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7663 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7664 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7665 &:= ((-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) - Q(Q(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7626 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) + Q(6))) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7627 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (7 \times (6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7628 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7629 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7630 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7631 &:= 9 - 8 - Q(Q(7)) + Q(6) - 5 + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7632 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7) - Q((Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7633 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7634 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + ((Q(6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7635 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) - ((7 - 6) - Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7636 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7637 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7 - Q(Q(6)))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7638 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - Q((6 + ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7639 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7640 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7641 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7642 &:= ((-9 - Q(8 + 7)) + ((6^5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7643 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) \times 7 - Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7644 &:= (Q(((-9 + 8 \times 7) + (Q(6) + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7645 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7646 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7647 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7 - Q(Q(6)))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7648 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7649 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (((7 + 6) \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7650 &:= ((-9 - (Q(8 + 7) + Q(Q(6)))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7651 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times Q(6 + 5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7652 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7 + 6) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7653 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7654 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7655 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - ((Q(Q(7)) - (6 - 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7656 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) + Q(6))) + 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7657 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q((8 - 7 + 6))) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7658 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7 + 6) - Q(5))) - (Q(Q(4)) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7659 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7660 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8 + 7) + Q(Q(6)))) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7661 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q((8 + 7 - 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q((Q(4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7662 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7663 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7) + (Q((6 \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7664 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (Q((7 \times 6)) + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7665 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - ((Q(Q(7)) - (6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7666 &:= (Q(Q((-1-2+Q(3)))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
7667 &:= ((-1+Q((2+Q(Q(3)))))) - (Q((Q(4)-5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7668 &:= ((-1-2-Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (5-Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7669 &:= (((-1+Q(2+3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7670 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4+5)) + (Q(Q(6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
7671 &:= (Q((-1+2+(Q(Q(3))+4))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7672 &:= (Q((-1 - ((2-3) \times Q(4+5)))) + (Q(Q(6)) - (7+8+9))) \\
7673 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 \times (4+5 - Q(Q(6)))) + 7+8+9))) \\
7674 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) + (Q((Q(4+5)+6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
7675 &:= ((-1+Q(Q(2^3))) - (4 \times (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7676 &:= ((-1+2+3) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + (Q(Q(6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
7677 &:= (-1-2+(Q(Q((3-(4-5)))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7678 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q((3-(4-5)))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7679 &:= (-1 + (Q((Q(2+3)-4-5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7680 &:= (Q(Q((-1 \times ((2+3)-4-5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7681 &:= (-1+2+(Q(Q((3-(4-5)))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7682 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+3) - ((4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(6)))) + 7+8+9))) \\
7683 &:= (((-1+Q((2 \times Q(3)))) \times (Q(4)+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
7684 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7685 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times Q(Q(4)))) \times (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
7686 &:= (((-1-2+Q(3)) \times (Q(4+5) + Q(Q(6)))) - Q((7+8+9))) \\
7687 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q((Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7688 &:= ((-1+Q((2+Q(Q(3)))))) - ((4 \times Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7689 &:= (-1-2+(Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7690 &:= ((-1+Q(((2 \times 3) \times Q(4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7691 &:= ((Q((-1+Q(2+3))) \times Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7692 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7693 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7694 &:= (-1 - (Q((2+3+4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
7695 &:= ((-1+Q(Q(2 \times 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7696 &:= ((-1+2+3) \times ((4^5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7697 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3) \times (4+5 - Q(Q(6)))) + 7+8+9)) \\
7698 &:= (((-1 - (2+3)) \times (4+5 - Q(Q(6)))) - (7+8+9)) \\
7699 &:= (-1 - ((Q(2 \times 3) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7700 &:= (-1 \times ((Q(2 \times 3) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7701 &:= ((-1-2) \times (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q((5+6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
7702 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((3 - ((4+5) \times Q(6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
7703 &:= (-1 - ((Q((2 \times Q(3))) \times (4 - Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7704 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7705 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4+5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7666 &:= (((-9-8+7) + (6^5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
7667 &:= ((-9 + (((8-7) \times 6^5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
7668 &:= ((-9+8-7+(6^5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
7669 &:= (Q((-9 - (8 \times (7+6 - Q(5)))) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
7670 &:= (((-9+Q(((8 \times 7)+6)))/5) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7671 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - Q((7+6 - (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7672 &:= (-9 \times 8 + Q((7+6 - (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7673 &:= ((-9+Q(8)) - ((Q(Q(7)) + (6 - Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7674 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8+7) - Q(6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7675 &:= (((-9+Q(8)) \times 7) - (6 \times (Q(5+4) - Q(Q((3+2+1)))))) \\
7676 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) + ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7677 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - (7 \times (Q(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
7678 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7+6) + Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7679 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((7+6) \times (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7680 &:= ((-9+8+Q(7)) \times ((6 \times Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
7681 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times Q(Q(6))) + (5 - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7682 &:= (((-9+8+7) + (6^5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
7683 &:= (-9-8+(7 \times (6+5) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7684 &:= (Q((Q((-9+8+7)) + Q(6))) + Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7685 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((Q((7 \times 6)) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7686 &:= ((-9+8+7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7687 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q((Q(7) + (6 - (5 - (4+3+2+1))))))) \\
7688 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7689 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7690 &:= ((Q((-9 + (8+7+6))) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7691 &:= (Q((-9+8+(Q(7)+Q(6)))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
7692 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7693 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 + (6 \times (Q(5+4) + Q(Q((3+2+1)))))) \\
7694 &:= (Q((-9-8+(Q(7)+6))) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7695 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7-6)) \times (5 - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7696 &:= ((-9 \times Q(Q(((8+7) - (6+5)))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7697 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + (6+5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7698 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7699 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times Q(7)) - Q((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7700 &:= ((Q((-9+8+7)) + (Q(6)+5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
7701 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times Q(Q(6))) + (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7702 &:= (((-9-8) \times 7) - (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5+4)) + Q(Q((3+2+1)))))) \\
7703 &:= (-9-8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7704 &:= (((-9+Q(8) \times 7) - Q((6+(5+4)))) \times Q((3+2+1))) \\
7705 &:= ((-9 \times ((Q(8) - 7 - 6) \times 5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7706 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q((Q(4+5) + 6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
7707 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) - (Q(4+5) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
7708 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) - ((Q(4) \times 5) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
7709 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7710 &:= ((Q(Q(-1+2+3)) - (4-5)) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
7711 &:= (Q((Q((-1+2+Q(3))) - Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
7712 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7713 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times (Q(3+4) - 5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
7714 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + Q(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
7715 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (4 \times (5 + Q(6+7+8+9))))) \\
7716 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7717 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7718 &:= ((Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + 4^5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
7719 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 + Q(6+7+8+9))))) \\
7720 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 + Q(6+7+8+9))))) \\
7721 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - (4 - (5+6)))))) - (7+8+9) \\
7722 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7723 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 + Q(6+7+8+9))))) \\
7724 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 \times Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7725 &:= ((-1 - (Q((2 \times Q(3))) - Q(4))) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
7726 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
7727 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q((3 + (4 + (5+6)))))) \times (7+8+9)) \\
7728 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) \times (Q(4) + (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7729 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3))) + Q((4 - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7730 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7731 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (Q(4) + (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7732 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) \times (Q(4) + (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7733 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((3 - Q(4)) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7734 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7735 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7736 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 - Q(4)) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7737 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 - (Q(Q(4)) + 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7738 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((3 - (Q(Q(4)) + 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7739 &:= (-1 + ((2 + Q(Q(3 - (4 - 5)))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7740 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7741 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 - (Q(Q(4)) + 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7742 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7743 &:= (-1 + Q((2 \times (Q(3+4) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))))) \\
7744 &:= Q((Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) + 4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7745 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4) - 5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7706 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) + 5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
7707 &:= -Q(-9 + 8 + Q(7)) + 6+5 + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
7708 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7709 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1))))) \\
7710 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (Q(5+4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
7711 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (6 \times ((5+4) + Q(Q(3+2+1))))) \\
7712 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + (6^5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
7713 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + ((Q(7) \times (6 - Q(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7714 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times Q(7)) + Q(Q(6))) - (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7715 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - ((Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7716 &:= (((-9 + 8 - Q(7)) + (6^5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7717 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times Q(7)) + (6^5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7718 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(((7 \times 6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7719 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7720 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7721 &:= 9 - 8 - Q(Q(7)) + Q(6+5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
7722 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (Q(6+Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
7723 &:= (((-9 + 8 \times 7) + (6^5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
7724 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7725 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) - ((7 - 6) - Q(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7726 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times Q(Q(6))) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7727 &:= (-9 - 8 + Q((7+6 - (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7728 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times (Q(6) + (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7729 &:= (Q(((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) / (5+4)))) - Q(Q(3+2+1))) \\
7730 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (Q(7+6) \times 5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7731 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))) \\
7732 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7733 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7734 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7735 &:= (-9 + Q((8 + ((7+6-5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7736 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - 5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7737 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times Q(7)) + ((6^5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
7738 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) + (6^5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
7739 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - Q(7+Q(6))) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))) \\
7740 &:= (-9 + ((8 - Q(7)) \times (Q(6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7741 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times Q(Q(6))) - (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
7742 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7+6) - Q(Q(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7743 &:= (-9 + 8 + Q((7+6 - (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7744 &:= Q((-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) + (6+5+Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7745 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) - ((7 - 6) - Q(5)))) + 4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7746 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 + 3))/4)^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7747 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) - ((Q(Q(4)) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7748 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2 \times Q(3 + 4)) - 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7749 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) - 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7750 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7751 &:= (-1 - ((2^3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7752 &:= ((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7753 &:= (Q((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - Q(4))) + (Q((5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7754 &:= (Q((-1 - ((2 \times Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7755 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((3 \times 4))) \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7756 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7757 &:= (-1 - (((2^{Q(3)}) - Q(4 + 5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7758 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7759 &:= (-1 - ((Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7760 &:= (-1 \times ((Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7761 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (Q(Q(Q((4 + 5 - 6)))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7762 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7763 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + (3^4)))) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7764 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times (Q(4) - 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7765 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7766 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times Q(4)))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7767 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7768 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7769 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (Q(3) \times (4 + Q(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7770 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7771 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7772 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q((5 + Q(6)))))) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
7773 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times (Q(3 + 4) - 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7774 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + Q(4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7775 &:= (-1 - (Q((2 \times Q(3))) - ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7776 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7777 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7778 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7779 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7780 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7781 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) + ((4 + 5) \times (Q(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7782 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7783 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7784 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(3)^4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7785 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3 + 4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7746 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7747 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (7 \times (Q(6) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7748 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7749 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - Q(7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7750 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times Q(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7751 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - (Q((Q(7) - (6 - 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7752 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times Q(7 + 6)) + Q(Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7753 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 + 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 \times Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
7754 &:= (Q(((-9 + 8 \times 7) + (Q(6) + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7755 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 \times (6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7756 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7757 &:= -Q(-9 + 8 + Q(7)) + Q(6) + Q(5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7758 &:= 9 + (8 - Q(7)) \times (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7759 &:= 9 - 6 \times (8 + 7) \times Q(5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7760 &:= (((Q((-9 + (Q(8) + 7))) + Q(6))/5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7761 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times Q(Q(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7762 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7 + 6) - Q(Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7763 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) \times Q(7)) + Q(Q(6))) - (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7764 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7) - (6 \times ((5 + 4) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
7765 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) + Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7766 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7767 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7 - (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7768 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) \times ((6 \times Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7769 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7770 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (Q(7 + 6) + Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7771 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times Q(Q(6))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7772 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7773 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) \times Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7774 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(((7 \times 6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7775 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7776 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7777 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q((8 + 7 - 6))) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7778 &:= 9 \times 8 + Q(Q(7)) + Q(6 + 5) + 4 \times Q(Q(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7779 &:= 9 \times Q(8) + Q(Q(7)) \times 6 \times 5 / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7780 &:= ((-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) - Q((6 \times 5)))))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7781 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times Q(Q(6))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7782 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + Q(7 + 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7783 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + ((7 - 6) - (Q(Q(5 + 4)) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
7784 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7785 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - 7 - Q(6)) \times Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7786 &:= ((Q(((−1+2) \times 3))^4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 7786 &:= (Q((−9+Q(8))) + Q(((Q(7) \times 6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7787 &:= (−1+2 + ((Q(3)^4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 7787 &:= (−9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + (6+5))) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7788 &:= (−1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 7788 &:= (−9 \times 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7789 &:= (Q(((−1+2 + Q(Q(3))) - (4-5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)) & 7789 &:= (−9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7790 &:= (Q(Q(Q((−1+2) \times 3))) + (4 + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 7790 &:= ((Q((−9+8-7+Q(6))) - 5) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7791 &:= (−1+2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 7791 &:= (((−9+8+7) \times Q(Q(6))) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
7792 &:= (−1+2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((Q(4) + Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 7792 &:= 9 \times 8 - Q(Q(7)) + Q(6+5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
7793 &:= (−1 - (Q(2 \times 3) - ((Q(Q(4)) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 7793 &:= (((−9 \times 8) \times Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
7794 &:= ((−1-2) \times (3 - Q((Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) & 7794 &:= (−9 + (Q((Q(8) - 7 - 6)) \times ((5+4) - (3+2+1)))) \\
7795 &:= (Q((−1-2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) & 7795 &:= ((−9 \times Q(8+7)) - ((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7796 &:= (−1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4+5)) - (Q(6) + 7+8+9)))) & 7796 &:= (((−9+8+7) \times (Q(Q(6)) + 5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7797 &:= (−1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4+5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 7797 &:= ((−9 \times 8 - 7) + ((6^5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7798 &:= (−1 \times 2 + ((Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) - 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 7798 &:= (((−9 - 8 + Q(7)) + (6^5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7799 &:= (−1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 7799 &:= (−9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7800 &:= (−1 - 2 + (3 \times Q((Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) & 7800 &:= (Q((−9+8 \times (7+6))) - Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7801 &:= (−1 \times 2 + (3 \times Q((Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) & 7801 &:= (−9 + ((Q(8) + 7) \times ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7802 &:= (Q(Q(Q((−1+2) \times 3))) + (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 7802 &:= ((Q((−9+8+7)) + (6^5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7803 &:= (((−1+2) \times 3) \times Q((Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) & 7803 &:= (−9 \times 8 - (((Q(7) + Q(6)) \times Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7804 &:= (−1+2 + (3 \times Q((Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) & 7804 &:= ((−9 \times (Q(8+7) - (6 - Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7805 &:= (−1 \times (Q(Q(2+3)) - ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 7805 &:= (−9 + (Q(8) + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7806 &:= (((−1 + Q(2+3))/4)^5) + 6+7+8+9 & 7806 &:= ((−9+8+7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7807 &:= (Q(((−1+2+3) + Q(4+5))) + (6 + Q((7+8+9)))) & 7807 &:= (−9 + (8 \times (7 \times Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7808 &:= (−1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 7808 &:= (((−9 - Q(8)) \times 7) - (Q((Q(6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7809 &:= (−1 - ((2 - Q((3 \times 4))) \times (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) & 7809 &:= (−9 - ((Q(Q(8)) + (7 - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7810 &:= ((−1+2 + Q(3)) \times (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) & 7810 &:= (((−9 - 8) \times 7) + Q((6 \times 5))) \times (4+3+2+1) \\
7811 &:= (Q(Q(Q((−1+2) \times 3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) - (6+7+8+9))) & 7811 &:= (((−9+8+7) \times Q(Q(6))) + (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
7812 &:= (−1+2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 7812 &:= (−9 \times ((Q(8) \times (7+6 - Q(5))) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7813 &:= (−1 + (Q((2 + (3^4))) + (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 7813 &:= 9 \times (Q(8) \times (7+6) + Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1) \\
7814 &:= (Q((−1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4))) + (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 7814 &:= (((−9+8+Q(7)) + (6^5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7815 &:= (((−1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + (Q(Q(6)) - (7+8+9)))) & 7815 &:= ((−9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (Q((Q(6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7816 &:= (Q((−1 + Q(2 \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)) & 7816 &:= (((−9+8+7) \times (Q(Q(6)) + 5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\
7817 &:= (−1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 7817 &:= (−9 \times 8 + (Q(7) \times (Q(6) + (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7818 &:= (−1 - 2 - (Q(3) - ((Q(Q(4)) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 7818 &:= ((−9 - 8 + Q(7)) + ((6^5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
7819 &:= ((−1 \times 2) - (Q(3) - ((Q(Q(4)) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 7819 &:= (−9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7820 &:= (Q((Q(Q((−1+2) \times 3)) + 4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))) & 7820 &:= (((−9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7+6) - Q(5))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
7821 &:= (−1+2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 7821 &:= (−9 - ((Q(8) - (7 \times Q(6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7822 &:= (−1+2 - (Q(3) - ((Q(Q(4)) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 7822 &:= (Q((−9+8+7)) + ((6^5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
7823 &:= ((−1 - (2 \times 3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 7823 &:= (−9 - 8 + (Q(7) \times ((6 \times Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7824 &:= ((−1 - (2+3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 7824 &:= (((−9 - 8) \times (7 + Q(6+5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7825 &:= ((−1 \times (2+3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 7825 &:= ((−9 \times Q(8+7)) - (6 \times Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7826 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7827 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7828 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7829 &:= (-1 - ((2 - 3) \times ((Q(Q(4)) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7830 &:= ((Q(Q((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))))) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7831 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7832 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4))) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7833 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7834 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7835 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7836 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) \times ((4 + Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7837 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) \times ((4 + Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7838 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7839 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (Q((4 + Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7840 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2 - 3) + Q(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7841 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7842 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7843 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7844 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - (Q(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7845 &:= (((-1 - ((2 - Q(Q(3))) \times 4)) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7846 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7847 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7848 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7849 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times (3 + 4)) \times Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7850 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + Q(4)) \times Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7851 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7852 &:= (Q(((-1 + (2 \times Q(3 + 4))) - 5)) - (Q(6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7853 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7854 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7855 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7856 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + Q(Q((4 - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7857 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7858 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q((4 \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7859 &:= (-1 - (((2 - 3) - (Q(Q(4)) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7860 &:= ((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - 4) \times (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7861 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q((4 \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7862 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q((4 \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7863 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q((Q(4) + (5 + 6))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7864 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q((Q(4) + (5 + 6))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7865 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7826 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times Q(Q(6))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7827 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times Q(7)) + ((6^5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7828 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((Q(7) + 6 \times 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7829 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - Q(7)) \times 6) - Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7830 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times Q(Q(6)))) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7831 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) - Q((7 - (6 - 5)))))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7832 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times Q(Q(5)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7833 &:= 9 + Q(8) \times (2 - Q(6)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7834 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) + ((6^5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7835 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) - ((7 - 6) - Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7836 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + (6 \times ((5 + 4) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7837 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7838 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7839 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) \times ((6 \times Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7840 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + Q(7 + 6))) \times (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7841 &:= ((-9 + Q(((8 + 7) \times 6))) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7842 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7843 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7844 &:= (Q(((-9 + 8 \times 7) + (Q(6) + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7845 &:= (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7846 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7847 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7848 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7849 &:= (-9 \times 8 + Q((Q(7) + ((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7850 &:= (((-9 - (Q(8) + 7 + 6)) \times Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7851 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (Q(7 + 6) + Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7852 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7 + 6) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7853 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q(7)) + ((6^5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7854 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8 + 7)) - (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7855 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7856 &:= ((-9 / (8 + 7 - 6)) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7857 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7 - Q(Q(6)))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7858 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7 + 6) + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7859 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7860 &:= ((-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + Q((6 \times 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7861 &:= (-9 - (((Q(8) + 7) \times (6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7862 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times 7) + (Q((Q(6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7863 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) \times ((7 - (6 \times 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7864 &:= (-9 - (((Q(8) \times (7 + Q(6))) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7865 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - Q((6 \times 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7866 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4))+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7867 &:= (-1+2+(Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4)+(5+6))) + Q((7+8+9)))) \\
7868 &:= (-1-2+(Q(Q(Q(3)))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
7869 &:= (-1+(Q((2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4+5)+Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7870 &:= (((-1 \times 2+Q(Q(3))) \times (4 \times Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
7871 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
7872 &:= (-1+2+(Q(Q(Q(3)))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
7873 &:= (((-1-(2+3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
7874 &:= (-1+(Q(((2-3)+Q(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7875 &:= (Q((-1-((2-3) \times Q(4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7876 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2+3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7877 &:= (-1-2+(Q((Q(Q(3))+4)) + (Q(Q(5))+6+7+8+9))) \\
7878 &:= (-1 \times 2+(Q((Q(Q(3))+4)) + (Q(Q(5))+6+7+8+9))) \\
7879 &:= (Q(-1 \times 2+Q(3)) + ((Q(Q(4))+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7880 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))+4)) + (Q(Q(5))+6+7+8+9)) \\
7881 &:= (-1+2+(Q((Q(Q(3))+4)) + (Q(Q(5))+6+7+8+9))) \\
7882 &:= ((-1 \times 2+Q((Q(Q(3))+Q(4)))) - (Q(Q(5))+Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7883 &:= (((-1+2+(3 \times Q(Q(4)))) \times (5+6)) - Q((7+8+9))) \\
7884 &:= (Q((-1+(2 \times Q(3+4)))) - (Q(Q(5))+Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7885 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5+Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7886 &:= (-1+(Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
7887 &:= (Q(Q((-1-2+Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
7888 &:= ((-1-2+Q((Q(3)+(Q(4) \times 5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
7889 &:= (-1+(((2 \times Q(3 \times 4))) - Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
7890 &:= ((-1+Q(((2^3)+Q(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
7891 &:= (Q((Q((-1+(2+3+4))) + Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
7892 &:= ((-1+2+Q((Q(3)+(Q(4) \times 5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
7893 &:= (-1+(Q(2^3) + ((Q(Q(4))+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7894 &:= (-1+(Q((2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7895 &:= ((-1+(2 \times (Q((Q(Q(3))-Q(4))) + (5+6)))) - Q((7+8+9))) \\
7896 &:= ((-1-2+(Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4))+Q(Q(5)))))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
7897 &:= ((-1 \times 2+(Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4))+Q(Q(5)))))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
7898 &:= (-1+(2 \times Q(3) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + (Q(Q(6))+7+8+9)))) \\
7899 &:= ((Q(((-1+2) \times 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
7900 &:= (((-1+(Q(2+3)+Q(Q(4)))) \times Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
7901 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2+Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7902 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (Q((Q(4)+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7903 &:= (-1+2+(Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4)+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7904 &:= ((-1+Q(Q(2+3))) - (Q(4) \times (Q((5+6)) - Q((7+8+9)))) \\
7905 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7866 &:= ((-9+8+7) \times (Q(Q(6))+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
7867 &:= (-9+(Q(Q(8)) + (7 \times (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7868 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((Q(7+6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7869 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + ((6^5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7870 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + Q(Q(6))) - 5) \times (4+3+2+1) \\
7871 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times Q(Q(6))) - (5 - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7872 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8)+7) \times (6+5+Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7873 &:= (Q(((-9 - (8+7)) + Q(6+5))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (3+2+1))) \\
7874 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7+6) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7875 &:= (Q(((-9 + Q((8+Q(7)))) / Q(6))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
7876 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8+7) + (6+5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7877 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q((Q(7)+Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7878 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7+6))) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7879 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) - (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7880 &:= (((-9 \times (8+Q(7))) + (Q(Q(6))+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7881 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times Q(Q(6))) + (5+Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7882 &:= ((-9+8+7) + ((6^5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7883 &:= (-9-8+((Q(7)+6 \times 5) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7884 &:= (Q((-9+8+7) \times (Q((6+(5+4))) - (3+2+1))) \\
7885 &:= ((-9 \times ((8-7-Q(6)) \times Q(5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
7886 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) - (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7887 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) - (6+5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7888 &:= (-9+8+(Q(7) \times (Q(6) + (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7889 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5+Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7890 &:= ((Q((-9+8-7+Q(6))) + 5) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7891 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7+6)) - Q(5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7892 &:= (((-9+Q(8+7)) + (6^5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
7893 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + ((Q(7) \times (6-Q(5))) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
7894 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7) + Q(6+5)))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7895 &:= (((-9 - (Q(8) \times 7 - Q(6))) \times 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7896 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8+7)+6)) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7897 &:= (-9 + (Q((8-7+6)) + (Q(Q(5+4)) + Q(Q((3+2+1)))))) \\
7898 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7+6))) - (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7899 &:= (-9+8+((Q(7)+6 \times 5) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7900 &:= ((-9+8+(Q(7) + (6+Q(5)))) \times Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
7901 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times Q(Q(6))) + (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7902 &:= (-9 \times ((Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) \times 6)) / (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7903 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7) \times (6-Q(5)))) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
7904 &:= (-9-8+Q((Q(7) + ((6 \times 5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
7905 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((Q(7) \times (6+Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7906 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2 \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + (Q(Q(6)) - Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
7907 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q((3 \times (Q(4) + 5)))))) - (6+7+8+9) \\
7908 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) \times (Q(4) + (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7909 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) \times (Q(4) + (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7910 &:= (((-1+2+Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
7911 &:= (Q(((-1+2) \times 3)) \times (4 - (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7912 &:= (-1+2 - (Q(3) \times (Q(4) + (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7913 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q((Q(3) + ((4+5) \times 6)))))) - (7+8+9) \\
7914 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (Q(4+5) + (Q(Q(6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
7915 &:= (-1+2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4+5) + (Q(Q(6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
7916 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7917 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) \times ((4 \times 5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7918 &:= (-1 - 2 + Q((Q((3 \times 4)) - (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
7919 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(Q(3))) - Q((Q(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7920 &:= (Q((Q(-1+2+3) - 4) \times (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
7921 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2+Q(3)) + (4 - (5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7922 &:= (-1+2 + Q((Q((3 \times 4)) - (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
7923 &:= (-1+2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4) + (Q((5+6)) + Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
7924 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2+3) \times Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7925 &:= (Q((-1 + Q((2+3+4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7926 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - Q((5+6)))) + Q((7+8+9)))) \\
7927 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4))) - ((5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
7928 &:= ((-1 + (Q(2+Q(3)) \times Q(4+5))) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q((7+8+9)))) \\
7929 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(Q(3))) \times (4 \times Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
7930 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7931 &:= (Q((Q((-1+2+Q(3))) - Q(4))) - (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7932 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - Q((Q(4+5) + (6 - (7+8+9)))))) \\
7933 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7934 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2+3)) + (Q(4) \times ((5+Q(6)) - Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
7935 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) - 5)))))) - Q(6+7+8+9) \\
7936 &:= (Q(((-1 - (2+3)) + (4 \times Q(5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9) \\
7937 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - ((4+5) \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7938 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + ((4+5) \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7939 &:= (Q((Q((-1 + (2+3+4))) + Q(5))) - (6 - (7+8+9))) \\
7940 &:= (((Q((-1 + Q(2+3))) - Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) - (Q(6) + 7+8+9)) \\
7941 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) + (5 - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
7942 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) + ((4^5) + 6+7+8+9) \\
7943 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times 4^5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7944 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2+3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5+6))) \times (7+8+9)) \\
7945 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7906 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times (Q(Q(6)) + 5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
7907 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (Q(7) \times 6))) + Q(Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7908 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7+6))) + 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7909 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7910 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7+6) - Q(5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7911 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
7912 &:= (-9 + Q(((8 \times (7+6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7913 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 - 6 + (Q(Q(5+4)) + Q(Q((3+2+1)))))) \\
7914 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8+7)) - (Q(6) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7915 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) - (7 - Q(6)))) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7916 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7917 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5+4))) \times (3+2+1))) \\
7918 &:= (-9 - (8 \times Q(7) + (Q((Q(6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7919 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((Q(7) \times (Q(6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7920 &:= (-9+8 + Q((Q(7) + ((6 \times 5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
7921 &:= Q((((Q((-9+Q(8))) - Q(Q(7)))/6) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7922 &:= ((-9-8) \times (Q(7+6) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7923 &:= (-9-8 + ((Q(7+6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7924 &:= ((-9+8+Q(7)) + ((6^5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7925 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + Q((Q(7) + 6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7926 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8+7) + 6)) + 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7927 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) \times (7 - (Q(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
7928 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7+6))) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7929 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - ((Q(7+6) \times 5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7930 &:= ((-9+8 + (Q(7+6) + Q(Q(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7931 &:= (Q((-9+8+7 \times 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7932 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 + Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7933 &:= (-9-8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7934 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8+7)) - (Q(6) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7935 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
7936 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
7937 &:= (-9+8 - (Q(7) \times (6 \times ((5+4) - Q((3+2+1)))))) \\
7938 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) + ((6^5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7939 &:= (-9+8 + ((Q(7+6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7940 &:= ((Q((-9+Q(8)) - (7 \times 6))) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7941 &:= (-9 + ((Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + Q((6 \times 5)))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7942 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q((7 \times 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7943 &:= (((-9-8) \times (Q((Q(7) + 6))/Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
7944 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7945 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8+7)) - ((6 \times 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$7946 := (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3+4))) + (Q((Q(5) + Q(6))) - Q((7+8+9))))))$$

$$7947 := (-1 + (((2^3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$7948 := (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(3) + (Q(4) \times 5))) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$7949 := (Q((-1+2+(3^4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$7950 := ((Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + (4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))$$

$$7951 := (Q((Q((-1+(2+3+4))) + Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9)$$

$$7952 := (-1+2+(Q((Q(3) + (Q(4) \times 5))) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$7953 := (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + (4+Q(5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$7954 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q((3+Q(4+5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$7955 := (-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$7956 := (Q((-1-2+Q(3))) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$7957 := (-1+2+(Q((3+Q(4+5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$7958 := (-1+2-3 - ((Q(Q(4)) \times (5-Q(6))) - (7+8+9)))$$

$$7959 := ((Q(((-1+2) \times 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5)))) + 6+7+8+9)$$

$$7960 := (-1+2+((Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5)))) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$7961 := (Q((Q((-1+2+Q(3))) - Q(4))) + (5+Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$7962 := ((((-1+2+Q(Q(3))) - Q(4)) \times Q((5+6))) - (7+8+9))$$

$$7963 := (-1+2+(Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4+5) + (Q(Q(6)) + 7+8+9))))$$

$$7964 := (-1 - (Q((2 \times (3+Q(4)))) - Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9))))))$$

$$7965 := (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$7966 := (Q(((-1+2 \times 3) + Q(4+5))) - (6 - Q((7+8+9))))$$

$$7967 := (-1 + ((2 \times Q((3 \times (Q(4) + 5)))) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$7968 := ((-1 - 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times 4) + (5+6))) \times (7+8+9))$$

$$7969 := ((-1 + (Q((Q(2 \times 3) + 4)) \times 5)) - (6+7+8+9))$$

$$7970 := (((Q((-1+Q(2+3))) - Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))$$

$$7971 := (-1 + (Q(((2+3) + Q(Q((4+5-6)))) + Q((7+8+9))))$$

$$7972 := (-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + (Q(Q(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$7973 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4)) + (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$7974 := (-1 - ((Q(2+3) + 4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$7975 := (-1 \times ((Q(2+3) + 4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$7976 := (-1+2+(Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4)) + (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$7977 := (-1 + (Q(((2+3) + Q(4+5))) + (6+Q((7+8+9))))$$

$$7978 := (-1 - (Q(2+Q(3)) - ((4+5) \times Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$7979 := (-1 \times (Q(2+Q(3)) - ((4+5) \times Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$7980 := (((-1+2 \times 3) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))$$

$$7981 := (Q((Q((-1+2+Q(3))) - Q(4))) + (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$7982 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((4+Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$7983 := (Q((-1+2+(Q(Q(3)) + 4))) + ((5+6) + Q((7+8+9))))$$

$$7984 := (((-1+Q((2+(Q(3)+Q(4)))) \times (5+6)) - (7+8+9))$$

$$7985 := (-1 + (2 \times (Q((Q(3) + ((4+5) \times 6))) + 7+8+9)))$$

$$7946 := (((-9 \times (Q(8+7) + 6)) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$7947 := (-9 \times (Q(8) - ((7 \times Q(6+5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7948 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7+6) - 5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$7949 := (-9+8+(Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7950 := (((-9+8-Q(7)) \times (Q(6)+5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$7951 := (-9-8-((Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5+4))) \times (3+2+1)))$$

$$7952 := (-9 - (Q(8) - (((7+6) \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7953 := ((-9 \times 8 + ((7+6) \times Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1))$$

$$7954 := (((-9-8-Q(7)) \times (6+Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$7955 := ((-9 \times ((8+7) - Q((6 \times 5)))) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$7956 := (Q((-9+8+7)) \times (Q(6+5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$7957 := (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))))$$

$$7958 := (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$7959 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q((6+Q(5+4))) - Q(Q((3+2+1))))))$$

$$7960 := ((-9 - ((8 - Q(7+6)) \times 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))$$

$$7961 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q((5+4) - (3+2+1))))))))$$

$$7962 := (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7963 := (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (Q(7) - (6 - Q(5+4)))) + Q((3+2+1))))$$

$$7964 := ((-9 \times Q(8+7)) - (6+5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7965 := ((-9 \times (8+7)) + Q((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7966 := (-9 - (Q(((8 \times 7) - (6+5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7967 := (-9 - (8 \times (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$7968 := ((-9+8) \times ((Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5+4))) \times (3+2+1)))$$

$$7969 := (((-9+8+Q(Q(7)))/6) + Q((Q(5+4) + 3+2+1)))$$

$$7970 := (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))$$

$$7971 := (((-9 - Q(8+7)) \times 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7972 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$7973 := ((-9 - 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(6) - Q((Q(5+4) - (3+2+1))))))$$

$$7974 := (-9 \times (8 - (Q(7+6) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7975 := ((-9 \times Q(8+7)) + Q(Q(((6-5) \times (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7976 := (((-9 \times Q(8+7)) + (6-5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$7977 := ((((-9+Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - Q(6)) \times ((5+4) - (3+2+1)))$$

$$7978 := (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) - Q((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$7979 := (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) - Q((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7980 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q((Q(7) - (6+5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7981 := (((-9-8) \times 7) + Q((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$7982 := (((-9+Q(8+7)) + (6^5)) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$7983 := (-9 - 8 + ((Q(7) + (6+Q(5))) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$7984 := ((-9 \times (Q(8+7) - (6-5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$7985 := (((-9-8-Q(Q(7)))/6) \times 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7986 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times ((3 + 4) - Q(Q(5)))))) \times 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7987 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + 5 - (Q(Q(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7988 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) - (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7989 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7990 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2 \times 3) \times Q(4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7991 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7992 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3 + Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7993 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7994 &:= (Q((-1 - (2 \times Q(Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7995 &:= (((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times 4)) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7996 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((4 \times (5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7997 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((3 \times (Q(4) + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7998 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) \times (Q(4) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7999 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8000 &:= ((-1 + 2 - Q(Q(3))) \times (4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8001 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (Q(4) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8002 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) \times (Q(4) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8003 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times ((3 + 4) - Q((Q(5) + Q(6)))))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8004 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8005 &:= ((-1 - Q((Q(2 \times 3) + 4))) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8006 &:= ((Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times (4 + Q(5))) + (6 + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8007 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) \times (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8008 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4^5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8009 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2 \times 3) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8010 &:= ((Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (Q(4) - 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8011 &:= (-1 + ((Q((2 \times (Q(3) + 4))) \times (5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8012 &:= ((Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(3) + Q(4)))) \times (5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8013 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((Q(3 + 4) \times 5) - Q((Q(Q(6)) / (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8014 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - ((4 + (5 + 6)) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8015 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8016 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) \times (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8017 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) \times (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8018 &:= (-1 + ((2 + Q(3)) \times Q((4 + 5 - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8019 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8020 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) \times (4 + 5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8021 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times (5 + (Q(6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8022 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8023 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4)))) - (Q((5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8024 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((4 \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7986 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8 + 7)) + (6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7987 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times Q(7)) - ((6 + 5 - Q(Q(4))) \times Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7988 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7989 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(6) - Q((Q(5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7990 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((Q(7) \times (Q(6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7991 &:= (-9 + ((8 - (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5))) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7992 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (Q((7 \times 6)) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7993 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + ((7 + Q(6)) \times 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7994 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7995 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((Q(7 + 6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7996 &:= (-9 + (Q(((8 + 7) \times 6)) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7997 &:= (-9 - (Q(((8 - 7) + Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7998 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7 + 6)) - ((5 - 4) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7999 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) + (6 + Q(5))) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8000 &:= (Q((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6 + 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8001 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times Q(Q(6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8002 &:= ((-9 + Q(8 + 7)) + ((6^5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8003 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((Q(7) + Q(6)) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8004 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - 6)) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8005 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8 + 7)) + 6 \times 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8006 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8007 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) \times ((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8008 &:= ((-9 - 8 + ((7 + 6) \times Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8009 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8010 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + (7 - Q((Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
8011 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (Q(7 + 6) + Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8012 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) + Q(((7 - 6) \times 5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8013 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q((7 \times 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8014 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times Q(7 + 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8015 &:= (-9 - ((Q((Q(8) - 7 - 6)) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8016 &:= (-9 + (Q(((8 + 7) \times 6)) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8017 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(7) - Q((Q(Q(6)) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8018 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q((Q(7) + (Q(6) + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8019 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times 7 - Q((6 + (5 + 4)))) \times Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8020 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (7 - Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8021 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7) + Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8022 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7))) - (Q(6 + Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8023 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4)))) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8024 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8025 &:= ((-1 - (Q(2^3) + Q(Q(4)))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 8025 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((Q(7) + (6 - 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8026 &:= (((-1 + 2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 8026 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8027 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) + Q((Q(4) + 5))) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8027 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8028 &:= ((-1 - 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8028 &:= (-9 \times 8 + Q((Q(7) + (Q(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8029 &:= (-1 + ((2 + Q((3 \times 4))) \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 8029 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + Q(Q(7)))/(6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8030 &:= (((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) - Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 8030 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8031 &:= (((-1 + 2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4)) - (Q((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 8031 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (Q(6) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8032 &:= (((-1 + Q((2 + (Q(3) + Q(4)))) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) & 8032 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + ((6 \times 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8033 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (4 - (Q((5 \times 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 8033 &:= (-9 - ((Q((8 + Q(7))) - Q(Q(6))) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8034 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 8034 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7) - Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8035 &:= (-1 - (Q(2^3) - ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8035 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8036 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2^3) - ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8036 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8 + 7)) + (Q(6) + Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8037 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 8037 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8038 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + Q((Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8038 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8039 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8039 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8040 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8040 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + 7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8041 &:= ((-1 + (2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 8041 &:= (-9 - ((8 - Q(7 + 6)) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8042 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 8042 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (((7 + 6) \times Q(Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8043 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8043 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times Q(7))) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8044 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((4 \times (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 8044 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) - (7 \times 6))) + Q((Q(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8045 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8045 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - Q(6 + Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8046 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 8046 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - ((Q(7) \times (Q(6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8047 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8047 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + (Q((6 \times 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8048 &:= ((Q((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + 4))) \times (5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))) & 8048 &:= (Q((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6 + 5)))) - (Q(4) + Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8049 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (Q(Q(3)) \times 4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8049 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (((Q(7) + 6) \times Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8050 &:= ((-1 - (Q(2 + 3) - Q(Q(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 8050 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(7) - Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8051 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 8051 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) - Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8052 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (Q(3 + 4) + Q(Q(5)))) \times (Q(6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) & 8052 &:= ((Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q((7 \times 6)) - Q(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8053 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 + 5) + (Q(Q(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 8053 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7 + Q(6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8054 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3 + 4) \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8054 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - 6)) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8055 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3 + 4)) \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 8055 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8056 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8056 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q(((7 + 6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8057 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8057 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + Q((Q((6 + 5 - 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8058 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 + ((4 - (5 + 6)) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8058 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((Q(7) + Q(6)) \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8059 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 8059 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times Q(7))) + (6^5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8060 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) \times 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 8060 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times ((6 \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8061 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(Q(3))) - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8061 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) \times (7 + 6)) - Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8062 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 8062 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (((7 + 6) \times Q(Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8063 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) - ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8063 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (((7 + 6) \times Q(Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8064 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 \times 3) - ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8064 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) \times (7 - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$8065 := (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4)+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8066 := (Q((-1+(2 \times (Q(3) \times 4)))) + Q(Q(5)+6+7+8+9))$$

$$8067 := ((-1-2+Q((Q(3)+Q(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9))$$

$$8068 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(3)+Q(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9))$$

$$8069 := ((-1 + ((Q(Q(2 \times 3))/4) \times Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9))$$

$$8070 := (Q((Q((-1+2) \times 3)) + Q(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9))$$

$$8071 := ((-1+2+Q((Q(3)+Q(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9))$$

$$8072 := (-1 - ((Q(Q(2+3)) - 4) \times ((5+6) - (7+8+9))))$$

$$8073 := (((-1-2) \times Q(3)) + ((4+5) \times Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8074 := (-1 - (Q(2+3) - ((4+5) \times Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8075 := (-1 \times (Q(2+3) - ((4+5) \times Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8076 := (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) - (4^5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8077 := ((-1+2+Q((Q(3)+Q((4+5-6)))))) - (7+8+9))$$

$$8078 := ((-1+Q((2 \times Q(3+4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8079 := (-1-2+(Q(Q(Q(3))) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8080 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8081 := (-1 - (2 \times Q(3) - ((4+5) \times Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8082 := (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$8083 := (-1+2+(Q(Q(Q(3))) + Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8084 := (-1 - ((Q(2+3) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8085 := (-1 \times ((Q(2+3) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8086 := (Q(Q((-1+2 \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8087 := (-1+2+((Q(3)^4) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8088 := (-1-2-(Q(3) - ((4+5) \times Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8089 := ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) - ((4+5) \times Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8090 := (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8091 := (((-1-2) \times 3) + ((4+5) \times Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8092 := (-1+2-(Q(3) - ((4+5) \times Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8093 := ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + ((4+5) \times Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8094 := ((-1 - (2+3)) + ((4+5) \times Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8095 := ((-1 \times (2+3)) + ((4+5) \times Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8096 := (-1+2-(((3-Q(4)) \times Q(Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$8097 := ((-1+Q((2+Q(Q(3)))))) - (Q(4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8098 := ((-1+2-3) + ((4+5) \times Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8099 := (-1+Q((Q(2+Q(3)) + (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))))))$$

$$8100 := Q(((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - (4+5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8101 := (((-1+2)^3) + ((4+5) \times Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8102 := (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8103 := (((-1+2) \times 3) + ((4+5) \times Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8104 := ((-1+2+3) + ((4+5) \times Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8065 := ((-9 \times ((8+7) - Q((6 \times 5)))) + Q(4+3+2+1))$$

$$8066 := (-9 - (((Q(8)+7+6) \times Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8067 := ((-9+Q(8+7)) - (6 - (Q(Q(5+4)) + Q(Q((3+2+1))))))$$

$$8068 := (Q((-9 \times (8 - (7+6+5)))) + (4 - Q((3+2+1))))$$

$$8069 := ((-9-8+7) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$8070 := (((-9+Q(8)) \times Q(7+6)) - Q((Q(5)+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8071 := (-9+8-7 - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$8072 := (((-9+8) \times 7) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$8073 := ((-9-8+Q((Q(7)+(Q(6)+5)))) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$8074 := ((-9 \times (Q(8+7) - (6+5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8075 := ((-9 \times 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8076 := ((-9 - (8+7)) + Q((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8077 := (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) + Q((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$8078 := (-9 - (Q(8) - ((Q(7) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5+4)) + Q(Q((3+2+1))))))$$

$$8079 := (-9 + (Q(8+7) + (6 + (Q(Q(5+4)) + Q(Q((3+2+1))))))$$

$$8080 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (((7+6) \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8081 := ((-9+Q((Q(8)+(7-6+Q(5)))))) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$8082 := (-9-8+(Q(7+Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8083 := ((-9+(Q(8) \times (7+Q(6+5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1))$$

$$8084 := (-9 \times 8 - ((Q(7+Q(6)) - 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8085 := ((-9+Q(8)) \times (7 \times (6+5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8086 := (-9 + (Q(((8+7) \times 6)) + (5 - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8087 := (-9 - (8 \times (Q(7) - (Q(6+Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8088 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + Q(((6 \times 5) + 4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8089 := ((-9+8+Q((Q(7)+(Q(6)+5)))) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$8090 := ((-9-8+7) + Q((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8091 := (-9 + ((8+7) \times (Q(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8092 := (-9+8-7+Q((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8093 := (((-9+8) \times 7) + Q((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8094 := (Q(((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + (5 + 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8095 := (Q(((-9 + Q((8 + Q(7)))) / Q(6))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8096 := (((-9 \times Q(8+7)) + Q(6+5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8097 := (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7 - Q(6))) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8098 := ((-9-8+((7+6) \times Q(Q(5)))) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$8099 := (-9+8+Q((Q(7)+(Q(6)-(5-(4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$8100 := (((-9+8+7) \times 6) \times Q(5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$8101 := (-9 + (Q((Q(8) + (7 - 6 + Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8102 := (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 - 6 + Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8103 := (-9 - (Q(8) + ((Q(7+Q(6)) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8104 := (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - Q(((7 \times 6) + 5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8105 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) + ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8106 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8107 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8108 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + (4 - Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8109 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))))) - (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8110 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) + ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8111 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4)) - Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8112 &:= ((-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + (4 + (5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8113 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + (3^4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8114 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8115 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8116 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8117 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8118 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8119 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + Q((Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8120 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + 4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8121 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8122 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (Q(3 + Q(4)) \times Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8123 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (Q(3 + Q(4)) \times Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8124 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8125 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2 + 3) + Q(4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8126 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (Q(3 + Q(4)) \times Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8127 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(3) + Q(4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8128 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(3) + Q(4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8129 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8130 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + Q(4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8131 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(3) + Q(4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8132 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3 + 4)))) - ((5 + Q(Q(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8133 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8134 &:= (Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(4) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8135 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) + ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8136 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8137 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + (Q(Q(6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8138 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8139 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (Q((5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8140 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (Q((Q(4 + 5) + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8141 &:= (((-1 + 2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8142 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(((Q(Q(Q(3)))/Q(4 + 5)) + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8143 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q((3 + Q(4)) - (5 + 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8144 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3 + 4) \times (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8105 &:= (Q(((-9 + Q((8 + Q(7))))/Q(6))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8106 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8107 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 \times Q(5 + 4)))) - Q((3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8108 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times (7 - Q(6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8109 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q((Q(7) + (Q(6) + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8110 &:= (Q((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8111 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8112 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times Q(7 + 6)) + (5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8113 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + Q((6 + 5 - 4)))) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8114 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8115 &:= (Q(((-9 + Q((8 + Q(7))))/Q(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8116 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + (7 - 6)) \times (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8117 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + Q((Q(5 + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8118 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7 - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8119 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - ((7 - Q(6)) \times 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8120 &:= (Q((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6 + 5)))) - (Q(4) - Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8121 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8122 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8123 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8124 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8125 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8 + 7)) + (6 \times Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8126 &:= (-9 + (Q(((8 + 7) \times 6)) + (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8127 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8128 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7 + 6) - Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8129 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7 + Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8130 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7) + (Q(6) + Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8131 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8 + 7) - (Q(6) - Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8132 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8133 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) - ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8134 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((7 + 6) \times Q(Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8135 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) - (7 \times 6)) \times Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8136 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8137 &:= ((-9 \times ((Q(8) \times (7 + 6)) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8138 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q((7 \times 6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8139 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((Q(7 + Q(6)) - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8140 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - Q(6))) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8141 &:= (-9 + (Q(((8 + 7) \times 6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8142 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (7 \times (6 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8143 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((Q(Q(7)) - 6)/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8144 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((Q((7 \times 6)) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8145 &:= (Q((-1-2) \times (3-4)) \times (5+Q(6+7+8+9))) & 8145 &:= (-9 \times ((8-Q(7+6)) \times 5) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
8146 &:= (Q((-1+2+(Q(Q(3))+4))) + (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 8146 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8)+Q(7+6)) \times (Q(5)+4+3+2+1))) \\
8147 &:= (-1-2+(Q((Q(Q(3))+4)) + (Q(5)+Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 8147 &:= ((-9+8 \times 7) + Q((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
8148 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3))+4)) + (Q(5)+Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 8148 &:= (-9+8+(Q(7)+Q((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
8149 &:= (Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) + ((4+5) \times Q(6+7+8+9))) & 8149 &:= (((-9+(8 \times Q(7)))+(6^5))-(4+3+2+1)) \\
8150 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))+4)) + (Q(5)+Q(6+7+8+9))) & 8150 &:= (((-9-(Q(8)+(7-6))) \times Q(5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8151 &:= (-1+2+(Q((Q(Q(3))+4)) + (Q(5)+Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 8151 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
8152 &:= (-1-2-(((3-Q(4)) \times Q(Q(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 8152 &:= (-9-(Q(8)-((7+6) \times Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
8153 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (((3-Q(4)) \times Q(Q(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 8153 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7+6) \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
8154 &:= (-1+(Q(Q(2+3)) + ((Q(Q(4))-5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 8154 &:= (-9 \times (Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + Q((Q(6)+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
8155 &:= (((-1+(2 \times (3+4))) \times Q(Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9) & 8155 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8+7)) + (Q(6) \times 5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8156 &:= ((-1+(2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 8156 &:= ((-9+8) \times ((Q(7+Q(6))-5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8157 &:= (((-1-2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - (4 \times Q(Q(5)))))) + Q(6+7+8+9) & 8157 &:= (-9-(Q(8)+((Q(Q(7)) - (6+Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8158 &:= (-1-2+(Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 8158 &:= (-9+Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7 \times (6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8159 &:= (-1+((Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - (4^5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 8159 &:= (-9-8-((Q(7+Q(6)) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8160 &:= ((((-1-2) \times 3) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) & 8160 &:= ((Q((((-9+8) \times 7) + Q(6))) - Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
8161 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) & 8161 &:= (Q((-9+Q((8-7+6)))) + Q(Q(Q(((5+4)-(3+2+1))))) \\
8162 &:= (-1+2+(Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 8162 &:= (-9+(Q(8)+(7+Q((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
8163 &:= (-1+(Q(2^3) + ((4+5) \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 8163 &:= (-9 \times (Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))))) \\
8164 &:= ((-1-2-Q((Q(3)+Q(4)))) \times ((5+6)-(7+8+9))) & 8164 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((7 \times (Q(6) \times 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8165 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4^5) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 8165 &:= (((-9+(8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
8166 &:= (-1+(((2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4)) + (5-(6+7+8+9)))) & 8166 &:= ((-9+Q(((8+7) \times 6))) - (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8167 &:= (-1+((2^3) \times (Q((Q(4)-5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 8167 &:= (-9-(8 \times (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
8168 &:= ((-1+Q((2+Q(Q(3)))))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))) & 8168 &:= (-9+(Q(Q(8)+7) + Q((6+(5 \times (4+3+2+1))))) \\
8169 &:= ((-1+((Q((2 \times Q(3))+4) \times Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 8169 &:= (-9+(Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + Q((Q(6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
8170 &:= (((-1+2+Q(Q(3))) \times (4 \times Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 8170 &:= ((-9-(Q(8)+7+6)) \times (5 - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8171 &:= (((-1+2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4)) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))) & 8171 &:= (-9-8-((Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8172 &:= ((-1-2-Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - (Q((5+6)) + Q((7+8+9))))) & 8172 &:= (-9+Q(Q(8)) - ((7+Q(6)) \times (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8173 &:= ((-1+2+(3 \times Q((4+5) \times 6))) - Q((7+8+9))) & 8173 &:= ((-9+(Q(8) \times (7+Q(6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
8174 &:= (-1+((2 \times Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 8174 &:= (-9+Q(Q(8)) \times ((7 \times Q(6)) - (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
8175 &:= ((-1-2-(Q(Q(3)) \times 4)) \times (5-(6+7+8+9))) & 8175 &:= (-9-((Q(Q(8)) - Q(Q(7))) + (Q(6+5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8176 &:= (-1-((Q(Q(2+3))+4) \times ((5+6)-(7+8+9)))) & 8176 &:= (-9-(((8+7) \times Q(6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8177 &:= (-1 \times ((Q(Q(2+3))+4) \times ((5+6)-(7+8+9)))) & 8177 &:= (-9+(Q(Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + (6+(5+4)))) - (3+2+1))) \\
8178 &:= (-1-2+(Q(3) \times ((4+5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 8178 &:= (-9+(Q(((8+7) \times 6)) + (Q(5+4)+3+2+1))) \\
8179 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) \times ((4+5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 8179 &:= (-9+(Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q((Q(6)+5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
8180 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) + (4 \times (Q((5+6)) - Q((7+8+9))))) & 8180 &:= (((-9+(Q(8) \times (7+6))) - 5) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
8181 &:= ((-1-2+Q((Q(Q(3))+Q(4)))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 8181 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (Q(6+5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
8182 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3))+Q(4)))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 8182 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (Q(7+6) + Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8183 &:= (-1-((Q(2 \times 3) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q((5+6)))) \times (7+8+9)) & 8183 &:= (-9-(Q(Q(8)) \times (7+6-(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
8184 &:= (Q((-1+(2 \times Q(3+4)))) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 8184 &:= (Q((-9 \times 8 + Q(7+6))) - Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8185 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8186 &:= (-1 + (((2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4)) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8187 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8188 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((4 \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8189 &:= (-1 - (((2^3) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8190 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8191 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)} \\
8192 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times (((4 \times 5) + Q(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8193 &:= (((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) \times Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8194 &:= (Q((-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) + (Q((5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8195 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(4)) \times (Q(5) + (Q(Q(6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
8196 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(4) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
8197 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - Q((Q(Q(4)) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8198 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) - Q((Q(Q(4)) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8199 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times (Q(4) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8200 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8201 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - Q((Q(Q(4)) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8202 &:= (((-1 + 2 - (3 + 4)) \times (Q(5) - Q(Q(6)))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8203 &:= ((-1 + ((Q((2 \times Q(3))) - Q(Q(4))) \times Q((5 + 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8204 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4))) - ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8205 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8206 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - Q(3)) \times (4 - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8207 &:= (-1 + (((2^{Q(3)}) \times (4 + 5)) + Q((Q(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8208 &:= (((-1 - 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8209 &:= ((Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) \times 4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8210 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8211 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3)))) \times (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8212 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8213 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8214 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3 + 4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
8215 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q((3 + Q(4)) - (5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8216 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8217 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2^3) - Q((Q(Q(4)) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8218 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + Q(4)) \times ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8219 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8220 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + Q(3)) + ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8221 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(Q(3) + (4 - 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8222 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - ((Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
8223 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
8224 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
8185 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8186 &:= ((-9 + Q(((8 + 7) \times 6))) - (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8187 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8188 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8189 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((Q((7 \times 6)) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8190 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (((7 + 6) \times Q(Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8191 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + 7 + 6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8192 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) \times (6 + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8193 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (7 + Q(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8194 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - ((Q(6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8195 &:= (((-9 + 8 - Q(7)) \times Q(6)) - (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8196 &:= (-9 + (Q(((8 + 7) \times 6)) + (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8197 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
8198 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times (7 - Q(6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8199 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + ((7 + 6) \times (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8200 &:= (Q((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6 + 5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8201 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) + (6 - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8202 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) - ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
8203 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((7 - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8204 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) + Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
8205 &:= (((-9 + 8 - Q(7)) \times Q(6)) + 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8206 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times Q(7)) - (Q(6 + Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8207 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (Q(7) \times (6 - Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8208 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((7 + 6) \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8209 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q(((Q(Q(7)) + Q(6))) - Q(5)) / Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8210 &:= ((-9 - Q(Q(8))) \times (7 + 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8211 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q((7 \times 6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
8212 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((7 + 6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8213 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - (6 + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8214 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q((7 \times 6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8215 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q((8 - 7 + 6))) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8216 &:= (-9 + (Q(((8 + 7) \times 6)) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8217 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) + (6 - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8218 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times (7 - Q(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8219 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q(Q(7))) - ((Q(6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8220 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((7 \times (Q(6) - Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8221 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8222 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 - Q(6 + 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8223 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8224 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((7 + 6) \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8225 &:= ((-1 - (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + 4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8226 &:= (-1 + (((2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8227 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + Q(3)) \times ((4 \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8228 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (Q(((Q(4) \times 5) + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8229 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8230 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (4 \times Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8231 &:= (((-1 + 2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4)) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8232 &:= ((Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (Q(4 + 5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8233 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8234 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3 + 4)))) - Q((Q(5) + (Q(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8235 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times (Q(Q(4) + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8236 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + ((4 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8237 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (Q(4 + 5) + Q(Q(6)))))) - (7 + 8 + 9) \\
8238 &:= (((-1 - 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(4 + 5) + Q(Q(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8239 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8240 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8241 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8242 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8243 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8244 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) - Q((Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8245 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8246 &:= (-1 + (((2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4)) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8247 &:= (Q((-1 + Q((2 + 3 + 4)))) - (Q(5) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8248 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((4 \times (5 + 6))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8249 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) - Q(4)) \times (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8250 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8251 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(3) + Q(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8252 &:= (-1 - (Q((2 \times Q(3) + Q(4))) - Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8253 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8254 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8255 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + 3) - Q((Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8256 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) - Q((Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8257 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q((2 + 3 + 4)) + (5 + 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8258 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3 + 4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) + (Q(Q(6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8259 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q((4 + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8260 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (4 + (5 + 6)))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8261 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8262 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) \times (Q((Q(4) + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8263 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + Q((Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8264 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8225 &:= ((((-9 + 8 - Q(7)) \times Q(6)) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8226 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8227 &:= (-9 - (Q(((8 - 7) + (Q(6) + 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8228 &:= (((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) \times Q((Q(Q(6))/Q(5 + 4)))) + Q((3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8229 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - (6 + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8230 &:= ((-9 + Q(((8 \times 7) + Q(6)))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8231 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q((7 \times 6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8232 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8233 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 + 6 - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(Q(4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8234 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((Q((7 \times 6)) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8235 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (Q(6 + Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8236 &:= ((-9 \times Q(((8 + 7) - (6 - 5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8237 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (7 + ((6 + 5 - Q(Q(4))) \times Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8238 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 + 6) \times (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8239 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + ((7 + Q((Q(6) + 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8240 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - Q(7 + 6))) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8241 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((Q((7 \times 6)) - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8242 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8243 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8244 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q((7 \times 6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8245 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - (6 \times 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8246 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8247 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(Q(((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
8248 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7 \times 6)) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8249 &:= ((((-9 - 8 - Q(7)) \times Q(6)) + Q(Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8250 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7) + ((6 - 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8251 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (7 \times (Q(6) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8252 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times 7) + ((Q(Q(6)) - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8253 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8254 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8255 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) - (7 \times 6)) \times (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8256 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 + 4))) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8257 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) \times Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8258 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) \times ((Q(6) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8259 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8260 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q((Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8261 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) \times (7 + 6)) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8262 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8263 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((Q(Q(7)) - (6 + 5)) \times 4)) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8264 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$8265 := (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8266 := (-1 - ((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8267 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8268 := ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8269 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8270 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8271 := (Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4))) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8272 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8273 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8274 := ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + Q((Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8275 := ((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q((Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8276 := ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q((Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8277 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) \times ((4 \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8278 := (-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - ((4 \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8279 := (-1 - (((2 + 3) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8280 := (-1 + Q((Q((2 + (Q(Q(3)) / (4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8281 := (Q((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - Q(4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8282 := (-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - ((4 \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8283 := ((-1 + Q((2 \times (Q(3 + 4) - 5)))) - (Q(6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8284 := (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + Q((Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8285 := ((-1 + 2 + 3) + Q((Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8286 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(4) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8287 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + Q((Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8288 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + Q((Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8289 := (Q((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (Q(4) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8290 := (Q((-1 + 2) \times 3) + Q((Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8291 := ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times Q(4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8292 := (((-1 + Q(Q(2 \times 3))) - 4 - 5) \times 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8293 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(((3^4) + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8294 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(((3^4) + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8295 := ((-1 - (2 \times Q(3) - Q(Q(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8296 := (Q((-1 + 2 \times 3) + Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8297 := (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + Q((Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8298 := ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + Q(Q(4))) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8299 := (-1 - ((2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8300 := (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) - Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8301 := (Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4))) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8302 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q((4 + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8303 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((4 + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8304 := (-1 - 2 - (3 \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8265 := (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8266 := (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - Q(Q(7))) + ((6 \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8267 := (((-9 - 8) \times Q(7)) - (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8268 := ((-9 + 8 + 7) + (6 \times (Q(5 + 4) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$8269 := (-9 + 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8270 := ((-9 + 8) \times ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8271 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8272 := (-9 + Q(((8 - 7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8273 := ((-9 + Q(8)) - ((Q(Q(7)) + (6 - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8274 := ((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - Q(6))) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8275 := (Q((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8276 := (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times Q(Q(6))) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8277 := (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - Q(Q(7))) - (6 - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$8278 := (-9 - (8 \times Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$8279 := ((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8280 := ((-9 - 8 + (Q(7 + 6) \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8281 := Q((-9 + Q((8 - (7 + 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$8282 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (7 - (Q((6 + Q(5 + 4))) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$8283 := (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (7 + Q(6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8284 := (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (Q((7 \times 6)) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8285 := (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - Q(Q(7))) + (6 + 5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8286 := (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + Q(6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8287 := (Q((-9 + Q(((8 + 7) \times 6) / (5 + 4)))) + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8288 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$8289 := (-9 \times (8 - ((Q(7) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8290 := ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - ((Q(6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8291 := (Q((-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7 + 6) - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8292 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (7 - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$8293 := (-9 + (((8 + Q(7)) \times Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8294 := ((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - Q(6))) - (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8295 := ((-9 - (8 + 7)) - (Q((Q(6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8296 := (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - Q(Q(7))) - Q(Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$8297 := (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (6 - 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8298 := (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - Q(6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8299 := ((-9 \times (8 - ((Q(7) \times 6) + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8300 := ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times Q(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8301 := (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times Q(Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8302 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((7 + 6) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8303 := (-9 + (8 \times (Q((7 \times 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8304 := (((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - Q(6))) + 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8305 &:= (-1 + (Q(2+3) + Q((Q((Q(4) - 5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
8306 &:= (Q((-1+2 \times 3)) + Q((Q((Q(4) - 5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
8307 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3+4)))) - Q(Q(((5 \times 6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
8308 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8309 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+Q(3)) - ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
8310 &:= ((Q(Q(-1+2+3)) - (4 - Q(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
8311 &:= (Q((-1+2+(Q(3)+Q(4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
8312 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4+5)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
8313 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (Q(3) \times 4^5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
8314 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) \times 4^5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
8315 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
8316 &:= (Q((Q(-1+2+3) + (Q(4) \times 5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
8317 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (Q(3) \times 4^5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
8318 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4))) + (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
8319 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) - Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
8320 &:= (((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4)))) \times Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
8321 &:= ((Q((-1+Q(2+3))) \times Q(4)) + (5 - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
8322 &:= (((-1 + 2 - (3+4)) \times (5 - Q(Q(6)))) + Q((7+8+9))) \\
8323 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times (Q(5) + Q(6))) + Q((7+8+9))) \\
8324 &:= (-1 + ((2+3+4) \times (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
8325 &:= (-1 \times ((Q(2+3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
8326 &:= (((-1 + 2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4)) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
8327 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times (3+4)) - Q((Q(5) - 6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
8328 &:= (((-1 - 2 + Q(3+Q(4))) - (5+6)) \times (7+8+9)) \\
8329 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q(3) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
8330 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
8331 &:= (((-1 + Q((2 \times (3+4)))) \times Q(5)) + (6 \times Q((7+8+9)))) \\
8332 &:= (-1 - ((Q(Q(2+3)) + Q(4)) \times ((5+6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
8333 &:= (-1 \times ((Q(Q(2+3)) + Q(4)) \times ((5+6) - (7+8+9)))) \\
8334 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2+3)) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
8335 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2+3)) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
8336 &:= (-1 + (((2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4)) + (Q((5+6)) + 7+8+9))) \\
8337 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
8338 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((3 - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
8339 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
8340 &:= ((-1 - (Q(2+Q(3)) - Q((4 \times 5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
8341 &:= ((Q((-1+Q(2+3))) \times Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
8342 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
8343 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
8344 &:= (Q(((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4))) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8305 &:= ((Q((-9+8+7 \times 6)) \times 5) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
8306 &:= (-9 - 8 - (7 \times (Q(6) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8307 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (6+5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8308 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times (7 - Q(6+5))) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
8309 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) - (Q((Q(6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8310 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7+6) \times (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
8311 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - (Q((Q(6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8312 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 - Q(6+5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
8313 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) \times ((Q(6) \times 5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
8314 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8315 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8316 &:= (Q((-9+8+7)) \times (6+Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
8317 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (Q(7) \times (6 - Q(5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
8318 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q((7 \times 6)) + (Q(Q(5+4)) - (3+2+1)))) \\
8319 &:= (Q(((-9 + Q(8)) - 7 - 6) + (Q(Q(5+4)) - (3+2+1))) \\
8320 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8321 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6)) + Q(Q((5 - (4 - (3+2+1)))))) \\
8322 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((7+6) \times 5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
8323 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) \times (Q(6) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8324 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8+7) - Q(6))) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8325 &:= (Q(((-9 + Q((8 + Q(7)))) / Q(6))) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
8326 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + 6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8327 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7 - 6 + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8328 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8)) - ((7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8329 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) \times ((Q(6) \times 5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
8330 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times ((6 \times 5) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8331 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) - (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8332 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 - Q(6+5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
8333 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) - (6 - (Q(Q(5+4)) - Q(Q((3+2+1)))))) \\
8334 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
8335 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - 7) + Q(6)) \times 5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8336 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8337 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((Q(7) + Q(6)) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
8338 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times (7 - Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
8339 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(Q(((5+4) - (3+2+1)))))) \\
8340 &:= ((-9 - (Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + Q(6))) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
8341 &:= (-9 + (Q(((8+7) \times 6)) + (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
8342 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5+4)))) - Q(Q((3+2+1))) \\
8343 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8+7) + ((Q(Q(6)) / (5+4)) - Q(Q((3+2+1)))))) \\
8344 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8+7) - (Q(6) + 5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8345 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2 \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8346 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8347 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) - ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8348 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + Q(3)) \times ((4 + 5) + (Q(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8349 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8350 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8351 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((Q(Q(3)) \times 4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8352 &:= (((-1 - 2 - Q(3)) \times (4 - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8353 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8354 &:= ((-1 + (Q(((2 + 3) + Q(4))) \times (Q(5) - 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8355 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (4 \times (Q((5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8356 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8357 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3 + 4))) + Q((Q(5) + (Q(Q(6)) / (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8358 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) \times (4 + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8359 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q((Q(Q(4)) - 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8360 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q((Q(Q(4)) - 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8361 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times (4 + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8362 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + Q((Q(Q(4)) - 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8363 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q((Q(Q(4)) - 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8364 &:= ((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) - 4) \times (Q((5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8365 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8366 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2^3) - ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8367 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - ((Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8368 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8369 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8370 &:= (((-1 + Q((Q(2 + 3) + Q(4)))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8371 &:= (((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) - (Q(Q(6)) / (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8372 &:= ((((-1 + 2 + 3) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8373 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - (4 \times Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8374 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times Q((Q(4) + Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8375 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8376 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times ((Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8377 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times ((Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8378 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3 + 4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8379 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8380 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times Q((4 + Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8381 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + Q((Q(Q(4)) - 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8382 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (Q((5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8383 &:= (-1 + (((2^3) \times Q(Q(4))) + ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8384 &:= (-1 - (Q((Q(2 \times 3) - 4)) - Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8345 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + ((6 + Q(Q(5 + 4))) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8346 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8347 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7) - (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8348 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 + Q(((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8349 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - Q(7)) \times (Q(6) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8350 &:= (((-9 + Q(8 + 7)) - (6 - Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8351 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) - (Q((Q(6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8352 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) \times (Q(6) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8353 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(6))) + Q((Q(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8354 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((7 - Q((6 \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8355 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) - (Q((Q(6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8356 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8357 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8358 &:= (((-9 - 8 + (Q(7) \times (6 + 5))) \times Q(4)) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8359 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5 + 4) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8360 &:= ((Q(((-9 + 8) \times 7) + Q(6))) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8361 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8362 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (Q(7 + 6) + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8363 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((Q(Q(7)) \times (Q(6) / (5 + 4))) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8364 &:= (Q(((-9 \times 8 + Q(7 + 6)) - 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8365 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times Q(Q(6)))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8366 &:= (-9 - (((Q(8) + (7 - 6)) \times Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8367 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) - (Q((Q(6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8368 &:= ((-9 + Q(((8 \times 7) + Q(6)))) - (Q(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8369 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + Q((6 \times 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8370 &:= (-9 \times ((Q(8) - (7 + (6 \times Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8371 &:= (-9 - ((Q(((8 + 7) \times 6)) / 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8372 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7 - Q(6))) - (Q(Q(5 + 4)) - Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8373 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7 + Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) - Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8374 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) + (6 \times Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8375 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) \times (Q(7) + (Q(6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8376 &:= ((Q((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4)) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8377 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7 + 6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8378 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7 + 6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8379 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + (Q((6 \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8380 &:= ((-9 \times (Q((8 - 7) \times 6) \times 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8381 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times Q(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8382 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + Q(7 + 6))) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8383 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7) + (Q((6 \times 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8384 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8385 &:= (Q((-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8386 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(Q(Q((4 + 5 - 6)))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8387 &:= (-1 - ((Q(((2 + 3) + Q(4))) + Q(5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8388 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 - Q(6))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8389 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) + ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8390 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3 + 4)) \times (Q(5) - (Q(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8391 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (4 \times Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8392 &:= ((-1 - 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8393 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) - ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8394 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 \times 3) - ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8395 &:= (((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8396 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8397 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((3 \times 4) \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8398 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((3 \times 4) \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8399 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8400 &:= ((Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) - Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8401 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((3 \times 4) \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8402 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times Q(Q(4)))) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8403 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8404 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8405 &:= (-1 \times (Q((Q(2 + 3) + Q(4))) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8406 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8407 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q((Q(4) - (5 + 6)))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8408 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8409 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + Q(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8410 &:= ((-1 - Q((Q(2 + 3) + Q(4)))) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8411 &:= ((Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) \times (4 + Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8412 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8413 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + (3^4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8414 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8415 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - 4))) \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8416 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)))) + (5 \times (Q(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8417 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8418 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) - ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8419 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) - ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8420 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4)))) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8421 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8422 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8423 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8424 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8385 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times Q(Q(6)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8386 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + Q(Q(Q(((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
8387 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7 + Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8388 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - ((6 - Q(5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8389 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + (7 + Q(6)))) + (Q(5 + 4) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8390 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8391 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8392 &:= (-9 \times 8 + Q(((7 \times 6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8393 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8394 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7))) + (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8395 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 + 7 \times 6)) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8396 &:= ((-9 + ((Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - 6)) \times 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8397 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (7 \times (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8398 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8399 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8400 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7 + 6)) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8401 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) \times Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8402 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + Q(7 + 6))) - (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8403 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7 \times (6 - Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8404 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) + ((Q(6) + Q(5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8405 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8406 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) + (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8407 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + Q(6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8408 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + ((Q(7) \times (6 + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8409 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((Q(7) \times (6 + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8410 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8411 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times Q(Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8412 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((7 + 6) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8413 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 + Q(7)))) - (6 + 5 - (4 \times Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8414 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - Q(6 + Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8415 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) - (7 - Q(6)))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8416 &:= (-9 - (((Q(8) - 7 + 6) \times Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8417 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + Q(6 + 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8418 &:= ((-9 - (Q(8) + Q(7))) \times (Q(6) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8419 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8420 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) + 7 + 6)) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8421 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) - (7 + Q((6 \times 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8422 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 - Q(6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8423 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) - (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8424 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (Q(6 + Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8425 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 8425 &:= (((-9 \times (8-7+6)) \times Q(5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8426 &:= (-1+2 - ((Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) & 8426 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7+6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8427 &:= ((-1 - (2+3)) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q((7+8+9)))))) & 8427 &:= (-9+8 - (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
8428 &:= ((-1+2-3) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 8428 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
8429 &:= (-1 - ((2-3) \times ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 8429 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + ((Q(6) + Q(5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8430 &:= ((Q(Q((-1 - (2 - (3+4)))))) + Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9) & 8430 &:= (((-9+Q(8)) \times (7 - Q(6))) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8431 &:= (((-1+2)^3) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 8431 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8+7) - (6 - Q(Q(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
8432 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) - 5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 8432 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + Q(7+6))) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8433 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + (Q(3) + Q(4+5)))))) - (6+7+8+9) & 8433 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7+6) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
8434 &:= (Q(((-1 + (2 \times Q(3+4))) - 5)) - (6+7+8+9)) & 8434 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (Q(6) + Q(5)))))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8435 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) & 8435 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + ((Q(6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
8436 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 8436 &:= ((-9+8 + (7 \times Q(Q(6)))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
8437 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 8437 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + ((Q(7) - Q((6 \times 5))) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
8438 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)) \times Q((5+6))) + Q((7+8+9)))) & 8438 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((Q(7) - Q((6 \times 5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
8439 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 8439 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times (7+6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8440 &:= (((-1+2+Q(3)) \times Q((4+Q(5)))) + 6+7+8+9) & 8440 &:= ((-9 + Q(((8 \times 7) + Q(6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
8441 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 8441 &:= (-9 + ((Q((Q(8) + (7-6)))/5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
8442 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) & 8442 &:= (-9 \times (Q(Q(8)) + (7 - Q((Q(Q(6)) - Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1))))))) \\
8443 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4)))) - (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) & 8443 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q((7 - (Q(6) + (5 - Q(4+3+2+1))))))) \\
8444 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)))) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 8444 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (7 + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
8445 &:= (((-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + Q(4))) \times Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)) & 8445 &:= (-9 - (Q(8+7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
8446 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 8446 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
8447 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 8447 &:= (-9 - 8 + Q(((7 \times 6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
8448 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 8448 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) \times (6+5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8449 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q(((3+4) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9))) & 8449 &:= (-9+8 + (Q(7+6) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
8450 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) + 4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) & 8450 &:= (((-9+8 - Q(7)) \times (6+Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8451 &:= (-1+2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 8451 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((7 \times Q(6+5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8452 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)) & 8452 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + Q(7+6)) - 5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8453 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)) & 8453 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (Q(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
8454 &:= (-1 + (Q(2+3) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 8454 &:= (Q(((-9 \times 8 + Q(7+6)) - 5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
8455 &:= (((Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9) & 8455 &:= (-9 + Q((Q(8) + (7+6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
8456 &:= (-1+2 + (((Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)) & 8456 &:= ((-9+8 + (7 \times Q(Q(6)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
8457 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) + (4 - (Q((5+6)) \times (7+8+9)))))) & 8457 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + ((Q(7) \times (6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
8458 &:= (Q((-1+2 \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q((7+8+9)))))) & 8458 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((Q(7) \times (6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8459 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2+3))) \times Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 8459 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + Q((6 \times 5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
8460 &:= ((((-1+2)^3) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) & 8460 &:= ((-9+8 + (7 \times Q(6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
8461 &:= (-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) & 8461 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
8462 &:= (-1 + ((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 8462 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
8463 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (Q(4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) & 8463 &:= (-9+8 + Q(((7 \times 6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
8464 &:= Q(((-1 + (2^{3+4}) - (5+6+7+8+9))) & 8464 &:= Q((-9 + (((8-7)^{65}) + Q(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$8465 := (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((4+Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8466 := ((Q((-1+Q(2+3))) \times Q(4)) - (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8467 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(4) + (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8468 := (-1 + (Q(((2 \times 3) + Q(4+5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8469 := (Q((-1-2+(Q(3)+Q(4+5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9))$$

$$8470 := (-1+2+(Q(3) \times (Q(4) + (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8471 := (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) - (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8472 := (((-1+Q(2+3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q((5+6)))) - Q((7+8+9)))$$

$$8473 := (-1 + (Q((2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4))) + (5 + Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8474 := (-1 - (Q(Q(2+3)) - (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8475 := (Q(Q((-1-(2+3)) + Q(4))) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8476 := ((-1 - (2 \times Q(Q(3)))) \times (4 \times ((5+6) - (7+8+9))))$$

$$8477 := (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) \times (Q((Q(4)+5)) + 6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8478 := (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + ((4 + (5+6)) \times Q((7+8+9))))$$

$$8479 := (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) - Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$8480 := (((-1+2+(Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4)))) \times Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)$$

$$8481 := ((-1-2+Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8482 := ((-1-2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) + ((4^5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8483 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) + ((4^5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8484 := (-1 + ((2 \times Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$8485 := (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + ((4^5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8486 := ((-1+2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) + ((4^5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8487 := (-1 + (Q((Q((2+3+4)) + (5+6))) + 7+8+9))$$

$$8488 := ((-1+2-3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8489 := (-1 + (((2 \times Q((3 \times 4))) - 5) \times (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8490 := ((-1 + Q(((2^3) + Q(4+5)))) - (6 - Q((7+8+9))))$$

$$8491 := (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8492 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) - 5))) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$8493 := (-1 + (Q((2 + (Q(3) + Q(4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$8494 := (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3+4))) - 5) + 6+7+8+9)$$

$$8495 := (-1+2+(Q((Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) - 5))) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$8496 := (Q(-1+2+3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8497 := (Q((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 + (5+6)))))) + Q((7+8+9)))$$

$$8498 := (-1 - (((2 - (Q(Q(3)) - 4)) \times Q((5+6))) + Q((7+8+9))))$$

$$8499 := (-1 - ((Q((2 \times Q(3))) + Q(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8500 := ((-1-2-(Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4)))) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8501 := ((-1-2+Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8502 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8503 := (((-1 - Q(Q(2 \times 3))) \times (4 - (5+6))) - Q((7+8+9)))$$

$$8504 := (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3+4))) - (5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8465 := (-9 - (Q(8+7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$8466 := (-9 - ((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times (6 - Q(Q(((5+4) - (3+2+1))))))$$

$$8467 := ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + Q((6 \times 5)))) + (4 - (3+2+1)))$$

$$8468 := ((-9+8+(7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5+4))) - Q((3+2+1)))$$

$$8469 := ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) + Q((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8470 := ((-9+Q(8)) \times (Q(7+6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8471 := (-9 + (8 \times (((7 \times 6) \times Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8472 := (-9 - (((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times (6 - Q(5+4))) - (3+2+1)))$$

$$8473 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (Q((6 \times 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8474 := (Q((-9 \times 8 + Q(7+6)) - 5) + 4+3+2+1)$$

$$8475 := ((-9 - (8 \times (7+6))) \times (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8476 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(((7 \times 6) + Q(5))) - Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8477 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) - Q(((5+4) + Q((3+2+1))))))$$

$$8478 := (-9 \times (8 - (((7 \times 6) \times Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8479 := ((-9 \times Q((8 + ((7-6) \times 5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8480 := ((-9 + ((Q(8) \times (7+6)) + Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))$$

$$8481 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8482 := ((-9 + ((Q(8) + 7) \times Q(6+5))) - Q(4+3+2+1))$$

$$8483 := (-9 + (8 \times Q(7) + Q((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8484 := (-9 \times 8 - (Q((Q(7) - (6+5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8485 := (((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) + Q((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8486 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$8487 := (-9 \times (Q(8) - (7 + (Q((6 \times 5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8488 := (Q((-9+8 \times 7)) - (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8489 := (((-9 - Q(8)) \times 7) + (Q((6 \times 5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8490 := ((-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7+6) + Q(Q(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1))$$

$$8491 := (-9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6+5))) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8492 := (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8493 := (-9 - 8 - ((Q(7) - Q((6 \times 5))) \times (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8494 := (Q((-9+8+Q(7))) - ((6 - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8495 := (-9 - (Q(8+7) + ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8496 := (-9 + (Q((8+7-6)) \times (5 + Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8497 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) \times (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8498 := (-9+8-((Q(Q(7)) - Q((6 \times 5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8499 := ((-9+8) \times ((Q(Q(7)) - Q((6 \times 5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8500 := (Q((-9+8 \times (7+6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8501 := (Q((-9+Q(8))) + Q((Q((7+6-5)) + 4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8502 := (-9 - (((Q(8) - Q(7+6)) \times Q(5+4)) - (3+2+1)))$$

$$8503 := (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8504 := ((-9 \times ((8+7) - Q(6+Q(5)))) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8505 &:= ((Q(((−1 + Q(Q(2 + 3)))/Q(4))) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8506 &:= (−1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(Q((4 + 5 − 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8507 &:= (((−1 + (2 \times Q(3 + Q(4)))) \times (5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8508 &:= (−1 − 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8509 &:= (Q((Q(−1 + 2 + 3) + Q(4 + 5))) − Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8510 &:= ((−1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) − (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8511 &:= (Q(Q((−1 + 2) \times 3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8512 &:= (−1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8513 &:= ((−1 \times 2) − ((3 − Q(4)) \times (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8514 &:= (Q((−1 − 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8515 &:= ((−1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8516 &:= (−1 + 2 − ((3 − Q(4)) \times (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8517 &:= (−1 − 2 + ((3 + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8518 &:= (−1 \times 2 + ((3 + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8519 &:= (Q(Q((−1 + 2 + Q(3)))) − (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8520 &:= (((−1 + 2) \times 3) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8521 &:= (−1 + 2 + ((3 + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8522 &:= (−1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q((4 \times (5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8523 &:= (((−1 + Q(2^3)) \times Q((Q(4) − 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8524 &:= ((−1 + ((Q(2 + Q(3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5))) − Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8525 &:= ((−1 − (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + Q(4))) \times (5 − (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8526 &:= (−1 − 2 − ((Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(4) − Q((5 + 6)))) − (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8527 &:= (−1 − (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) − Q((Q((5 + 6)) − (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8528 &:= (−1 \times (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) − Q((Q((5 + 6)) − (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8529 &:= (−1 + (((Q((2 \times Q(3))) + Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8530 &:= (Q((−1 + 2 + Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8531 &:= (−1 − 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) + (Q(5) − Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8532 &:= (−1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) + (Q(5) − Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8533 &:= (Q((−1 + 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8534 &:= (Q((−1 + (2 \times Q(3 + 4)))) + (Q(5) − Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8535 &:= (−1 + 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) + (Q(5) − Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8536 &:= (−1 \times ((2^{Q(3)}) − ((Q(Q(4)) + Q((5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8537 &:= (Q(Q(−1 + 2 + 3)) + Q((Q((Q(4) − 5)) − (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8538 &:= (((−1 − 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times Q((Q(4) − 5))) − Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8539 &:= (−1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) − (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8540 &:= ((−1 − 2 − (Q(3) − Q(Q(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8541 &:= (Q(((−1 − (2 + 3)) + Q(4 + 5))) + Q((Q(Q(6)))/(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8542 &:= (Q(Q((−1 + 2 + Q(3)))) + (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 − (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8543 &:= (−1 + (((2 − (3 + 4)) + Q((Q(5) − 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8544 &:= (Q((−1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) − (4 \times (Q((5 + 6)) − Q((7 + 8 + 9))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8505 &:= (−9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7 + 6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8506 &:= (((−9 − 8) \times Q(7)) − (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) − Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8507 &:= (−9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) − (6 − Q(((5 + 4) + Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))))) \\
8508 &:= (((−9 − 8 + Q(7)) \times (6 + 5 + Q(Q(4)))) − Q((3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8509 &:= (−9 + 8 − ((Q(7) − Q((6 \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8510 &:= ((−9 + 8) \times ((Q(7) − Q((6 \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8511 &:= ((−9 \times Q(8)) + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8512 &:= ((−9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) − (Q(6 + Q(5)) − Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8513 &:= (−9 − 8 − ((Q(7) \times (6 \times 5)) − Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8514 &:= (−9 \times ((8 + 7) − Q((Q(6) + (5 − (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8515 &:= ((−9 \times ((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8516 &:= (−9 − 8 − (7 \times (6 − Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8517 &:= ((−9 \times Q(8)) − ((7 + Q((6 \times 5))) − Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8518 &:= (Q((−9 + 8 + Q(7))) − (Q(6) − (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8519 &:= (−9 + (Q(8) + Q(((7 \times 6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8520 &:= (−9 + (((8 − Q(7)) \times Q(6)) + 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8521 &:= (−9 + ((8 + (Q(7 + 6) \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8522 &:= (Q((−9 \times 8 + Q(7 + 6))) − (Q(Q(5)) + (Q(Q(4)) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8523 &:= ((−9 \times ((8 + Q(Q(7)))/(6 − (5 + 4)))) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8524 &:= ((−9 \times (Q(8 + 7) − (Q(6) + Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8525 &:= (−9 + (Q(8) + (7 \times (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8526 &:= ((−9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8527 &:= (−9 − (8 \times (Q(7 + Q(6)) − Q(((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8528 &:= (((−9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7 + 6))) + Q(Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8529 &:= (−9 + 8 − ((Q(7) \times (6 \times 5)) − Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8530 &:= ((−9 + 8) \times ((Q(7) \times (6 \times 5)) − Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8531 &:= ((−9 \times Q(8)) + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) − (5 − (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8532 &:= (−9 + 8 − (7 \times (6 − Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8533 &:= (((−9 + 8) \times 7) \times (6 − Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8534 &:= (−9 − ((Q(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) − Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8535 &:= ((−9 + Q(8 + 7)) − (Q((Q(6) + 5)) − Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8536 &:= (((−9 − (8 + 7)) \times (Q(6) + Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8537 &:= (((−9 + Q(Q(8)) − 7)/6) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8538 &:= (−9 − 8 − ((Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))/5) − Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8539 &:= (−9 + ((Q(8) \times 7) + Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8540 &:= (((−9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times (Q(6) \times 5)) − Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8541 &:= (−9 + ((8 + (7 \times Q(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8542 &:= (−9 − (Q(8) − (Q(Q(7)) − (Q(6) − (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8543 &:= (−9 − 8 − ((Q(Q(7)) − Q(6 + Q(5))) − Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8544 &:= ((−9 \times (8 + 7)) − (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) − Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8545 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(3 + 4))) + ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8546 &:= (-1 + ((2 - Q(3)) \times (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8547 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8548 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (((Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)) \times Q(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8549 &:= (-1 - ((Q((2 \times Q(3))) + (Q(4) - Q(Q(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8550 &:= ((Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (4 + Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8551 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8552 &:= (Q((-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) - (Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8553 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8554 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8555 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8556 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - ((4 + (5 + 6)) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8557 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) - ((4 + (5 + 6)) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8558 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(3)) \times ((4 + 5) + Q(Q(6)))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8559 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8560 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times 3) \times Q(4))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8561 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8562 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4)) \times Q((5 + 6))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8563 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(((4 + 5) + Q(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8564 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) - (Q(4) \times ((5 + Q(6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8565 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3 + 4) - (Q((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8566 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) - Q((Q(4 + 5) + (Q(6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8567 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4 - 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8568 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q((Q(3) + 4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8569 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8570 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) + Q((Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8571 &:= (((-1 + Q((2 \times (3 + 4)))) \times (5 + Q(6))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8572 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + 4) \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8573 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4) \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8574 &:= (-1 + (((2 + Q(3)) - 4) \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8575 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8576 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + 4) \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8577 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q((5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8578 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q((5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8579 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8580 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3)))/4) \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8581 &:= (Q((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) - Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8582 &:= (-1 - (Q((2 + 3 + 4)) - (Q((Q(5) - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8583 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8584 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + Q(((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8545 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) - Q((7 \times 6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8546 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) + 6)) + Q(Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8547 &:= (-9 - (Q((Q(8) - (7 - 6 + Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8548 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (6 - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8549 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (6 + 5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8550 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + 6)) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8551 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8 + 7) + (6 + Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8552 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (((Q(7) + 6) \times Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8553 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (((Q(7) + 6) \times Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8554 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8555 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q((Q(7) - (6 + 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8556 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q((Q(7) - (6 + 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8557 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
8558 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q((7 + 6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8559 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(6 + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8560 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7) \times (Q(6) \times 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8561 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) \times (7 + 6)) + Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8562 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + Q((6 + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8563 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (7 \times (6 + 5) - (Q(Q(4)) \times Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8564 &:= (Q(((-9 \times 8 + Q(7 + 6)) - 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8565 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8566 &:= (-9 + ((8 - 7 + 6) \times Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8567 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q(7 + 6) - (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8568 &:= (-9 \times (Q(Q(8)) - (7 + Q((Q(Q(6)) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
8569 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + Q((6 \times 5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8570 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7 + 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8571 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + (Q(7 + 6) + Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8572 &:= ((-9 + ((Q(8) + 7) \times Q(6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8573 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) - (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8574 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - ((Q(Q(6)) - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8575 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times Q(7))) - Q(6)) \times Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8576 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q((7 \times (6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8577 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((7 \times Q(6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8578 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times Q(7)) + (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8579 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((Q(7 + 6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8580 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8581 &:= (Q((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7 + 6)))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8582 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + 7) \times Q((6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8583 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8584 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + (6 + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8585 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2^3) - Q((Q(4+5) + (Q(6) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
8586 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
8587 &:= (-1+2+(Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
8588 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{Q(3)}) - (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
8589 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 \times ((5+6) + Q((7+8+9)))) \\
8590 &:= (-1 + ((2+Q(3)) \times (Q((Q(4)+Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
8591 &:= ((-1+Q(Q(2^3))) - (4 - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
8592 &:= ((-1-2) \times (Q(Q(Q(3))) - (Q(4) + Q((Q((5+6) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
8593 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2^3))) + Q(((4 \times (5+6)) + 7+8+9))) \\
8594 &:= (Q((-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) - (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
8595 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
8596 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + (2+3+4)))) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
8597 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - ((4-5) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q((7+8+9)))) \\
8598 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times (Q(4) - (5 \times (6 - Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
8599 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
8600 &:= ((Q((-1 + (Q(2+3) + 4))) \times (5+6)) - (7+8+9)) \\
8601 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times ((5+6) - Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
8602 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q(3)) \times (4 + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
8603 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (4 + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
8604 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
8605 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + ((4+5) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q((7+8+9)))) \\
8606 &:= ((-1 - Q(2+3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - ((5+6) + Q((7+8+9)))) \\
8607 &:= (((-1+Q(2^3)) \times (Q(4) + Q((5+6)))) - (7+8+9)) \\
8608 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(((4+5) + Q(6))) + 7+8+9))) \\
8609 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q(((3 \times 4) + 5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
8610 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q((3 + (4+5)))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
8611 &:= (-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + ((4+5) \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
8612 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) - Q((Q(4+5) + (Q(6) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
8613 &:= (((-1-2) \times Q(3)) + ((4 + (5+6)) \times Q((7+8+9)))) \\
8614 &:= (Q((-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
8615 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+3) - ((4 + (5+6)) \times Q((7+8+9)))) \\
8616 &:= ((Q((-1+Q(2+3))) \times (4 + (5+6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
8617 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (3+4))) \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6))) + 7+8+9) \\
8618 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2 \times Q(3+4)) - 5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
8619 &:= (Q((-1+2+(Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) - 5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
8620 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2 \times 3) \times Q(4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
8621 &:= (Q((-1+2+(Q(Q(3)) + 4))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
8622 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + ((4 + (5+6)) \times Q((7+8+9)))) \\
8623 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+3) - Q((Q(4+5) + (Q(6) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
8624 &:= (Q((-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
8585 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - ((Q(7) \times (6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8586 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
8587 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + Q(7))) - (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8588 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) + ((Q(Q(6)) - 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8589 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times 7) - (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8590 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - ((6 - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
8591 &:= (-9 + ((Q((8+7-6)) + 5) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8592 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) + 7) \times Q(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
8593 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7))) + (Q(6+Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
8594 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) - ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8595 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) \times (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
8596 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8597 &:= (-9 - (Q(((8-7) + Q(6))) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8598 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
8599 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (Q(7+6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8600 &:= ((-9 + (((8+7) \times 6) + 5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
8601 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
8602 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 + Q(6)) \times (5 + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8603 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7 \times (6 - Q(5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8604 &:= (-9 \times ((8+7) - (Q(6+Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
8605 &:= ((-9 + Q((Q(8) - (7 - Q(6)))) - (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
8606 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
8607 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
8608 &:= (-9 - 8 - (((Q(7) + 6) \times Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8609 &:= (Q((-9+8 \times 7)) + Q(((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8610 &:= (((-9-8) \times 7) - ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8611 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - (Q((Q(7) - (6+5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8612 &:= ((-9+8+Q((Q(7) + ((6+5) \times 4))) - Q((3+2+1))) \\
8613 &:= (-9-8-(Q(7) + (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
8614 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times Q(7+6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8615 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + Q(Q(6))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
8616 &:= (-9 + (Q(((8+7) \times 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8617 &:= (-9 - (Q(((8-7) + Q(6))) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8618 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (7+6 - ((Q(Q(5)) \times Q(4)) - Q(Q((3+2+1)))))) \\
8619 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (7 + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
8620 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7) - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8621 &:= (((-9 - Q(8+7)) \times 6) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
8622 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times Q(7)) - (6 \times Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
8623 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 - Q(6)) \times 5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8624 &:= (-9 + 8 - (((Q(7) + 6) \times Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8625 &:= (Q((-1-2+(Q(Q(3))+(4+(5+6)))))-(7+8+9)) \\
8626 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((3+4)-(5 \times (Q(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
8627 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3))))-(4+Q((Q(5)+(Q(6)-(7+8+9)))))) \\
8628 &:= (-1-2-(Q(3)-((4+(5+6)) \times Q((7+8+9)))) \\
8629 &:= (-1+(Q((2+Q(Q(3))))+(Q((4+Q(5)))+Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
8630 &:= (-1-(2 \times Q(3)-Q((Q(4+5)+(Q(6)-(7+8+9)))))) \\
8631 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3)+((4+(5+6)) \times Q((7+8+9)))) \\
8632 &:= (-1+2-(Q(3)-((4+(5+6)) \times Q((7+8+9)))) \\
8633 &:= ((-1-(2 \times 3))+((4+(5+6)) \times Q((7+8+9)))) \\
8634 &:= ((-1-(2+3))+((4+(5+6)) \times Q((7+8+9)))) \\
8635 &:= (-1-(Q((2 \times Q(3)))-(Q(Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
8636 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 \times Q(3)))-(Q(Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
8637 &:= (-1-2-((Q(Q(3))+(Q(Q(4))-Q(Q(5)))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
8638 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3))+(Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5))-Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
8639 &:= (-1+(2 \times (Q((3+(4+5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
8640 &:= ((-1+Q(((2^3)+(4+5)))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
8641 &:= (-1+2-((Q(Q(3))+(Q(Q(4))-Q(Q(5)))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
8642 &:= (-1-2-((Q(3)-Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
8643 &:= ((-1 \times 2)-((Q(3)-Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
8644 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2+(Q(3)+Q(4+5))))+Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
8645 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3)+Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9) \\
8646 &:= (-1+2-((Q(3)-Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
8647 &:= (-1 \times 2+Q(((3 \times (Q(4)+Q(5)))-(6+7+8+9))) \\
8648 &:= (-1+Q(((2^{3+4})-(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
8649 &:= Q((-1+(2 \times ((3 \times 4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
8650 &:= (-1+2+Q(((3 \times (Q(4)+Q(5)))-(6+7+8+9))) \\
8651 &:= ((Q((-1+Q(2+3))) \times Q(4))+((5+6)-Q((7+8+9)))) \\
8652 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3)+Q((Q(4+5)+(Q(6)-(7+8+9)))) \\
8653 &:= ((-1+2+3)+Q((Q(4+5)+(Q(6)-(7+8+9)))) \\
8654 &:= (Q((-1-((2 \times Q(Q(3)))-Q(Q(4))))-(Q(5)-(6+7+8+9))) \\
8655 &:= (((-1+(Q(Q(2 \times 3))+Q(Q(4)))) \times 5)+Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
8656 &:= ((-1-2+Q((Q(Q(3))+Q(4))))-(Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
8657 &:= ((-1 \times 2+Q((Q(Q(3))+Q(4))))-(Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
8658 &:= ((-1-2+Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4+5)+6+7+8+9)) \\
8659 &:= (Q((-1+(2 \times Q(3+4))))-(Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
8660 &:= ((-1+2+Q((Q(Q(3))+Q(4))))-(Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
8661 &:= (-1-(2 \times (Q((Q(3)+4)-(5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
8662 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q((Q(3)+4)-(5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
8663 &:= (-1+(2 \times (Q((Q(Q(3))-(4+(5+6))))-(7+8+9))) \\
8664 &:= (Q((-1+(2+(3+(4+(5+6)))))) \times (7+8+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8625 &:= ((-9+Q((Q(8)-(7-Q(6)))))-(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
8626 &:= (-9 \times 8+(Q(7)+Q((6+(Q(5+4)+3+2+1)))) \\
8627 &:= (-9-((Q(((8-7)+Q(6)))-5)-Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8628 &:= ((-9-8+Q(Q(7)))-(6-(Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
8629 &:= (-9+8-(Q(7)+(Q(Q(6))+(Q(5)-Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
8630 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8))-(Q(7+6)+(Q(Q(5))-Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8631 &:= (-9-((8 \times (Q(7)+Q(6+5)))-Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8632 &:= ((-9 \times ((8+Q(7+6))-Q(5)))+Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8633 &:= (-9-8-(Q(7)+(Q(Q(6))+(5-Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
8634 &:= (-9-((8 \times Q(7+6))+(5-Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8635 &:= (-9+(Q((Q(8)-(7-Q(6))))+(5-(4+3+2+1))) \\
8636 &:= (-9-((Q(8+7) \times 6)+(5-Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8637 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8)))-(7+6-Q((Q(5+4)-(3+2+1)))) \\
8638 &:= (-9-(8 \times Q(7)+(Q(6+Q(5))-Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8639 &:= (Q((-9+(Q(8)+(Q(7)-(6+5))))-(4+3+2+1)) \\
8640 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8))+Q(((7-6-5)+Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8641 &:= ((-9 \times ((8-7)+(6 \times Q(5))))+Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8642 &:= (-9+(Q(Q((8-7+6)))+(Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
8643 &:= (-9-8-(Q(7)+((Q(Q(6))-5)-Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8644 &:= (-9-(((8 \times Q(7+6))-5)-Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8645 &:= ((-9+Q((Q(8)-(7-Q(6))))-(5-(4+3+2+1))) \\
8646 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7)))+(6 \times Q((Q(5)+4+3+2+1))) \\
8647 &:= (-9+Q(Q(8))-((Q(7+6)-Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
8648 &:= (-9+8+Q((Q(7)-(6-(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
8649 &:= Q(((9-8)/(7-6-5))+Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
8650 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8)))+Q(((7+6) \times 5)+4+3+2+1)) \\
8651 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8)))+(7-6+Q((Q(5+4)-(3+2+1)))) \\
8652 &:= ((-9+((Q(8)+(7+Q(6))) \times Q(5+4)))-(3+2+1)) \\
8653 &:= (-9+(Q(Q(8)+7)+(Q((Q(6)+Q(5)))-Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8654 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8+7)-6))+Q(Q(5)))+Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8655 &:= (-9+(Q((Q(8)-(7-Q(6))))+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
8656 &:= (-9+8+(Q(Q(7))+(6+(Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
8657 &:= (((-9-8) \times (Q(7)+6 \times 5))+Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8658 &:= (((-9-(Q(8)+Q(7))) \times (6+5))+Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8659 &:= (Q((-9+(Q(8)+(Q(7)-(6+5))))+4+3+2+1) \\
8660 &:= (((-9+Q(8)) \times Q(7+6))-Q(Q(5))+4+3+2+1) \\
8661 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7 \times 6))-Q(Q(5))-Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8662 &:= (-9-((8 \times (Q(7)-Q(Q(6))))+((5+4)+Q(Q((3+2+1)))))) \\
8663 &:= ((-9-8+Q(Q(7)))-(Q((Q(6)+Q(5)))-Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
8664 &:= (-9-(((8 \times Q(7+6))-Q(5))-Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$8665 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8666 := ((-1 + ((2 - Q(Q(3))) \times (4 - Q((5 + 6)))))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8667 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(((3 \times 4) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8668 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(((3 \times 4) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8669 := (-1 + (Q(((2^3) + (4 + 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8670 := (Q((-1 \times (Q(2^3) - Q(4 + 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8671 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8672 := (-1 + (Q(((2 - Q(3)) \times 4) + Q((5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8673 := (-1 - (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8674 := (Q((-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8675 := (-1 + (Q((2 \times (3 \times (4 + (5 + 6)))))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8676 := (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8677 := (-1 - (2 \times ((Q(Q(Q(3))) - Q((4 \times Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8678 := ((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3 + 4)))) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8679 := (-1 - (((2^3) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8680 := ((-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - Q(Q(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8681 := ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times Q(4)) + ((5 + Q(6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8682 := (-1 + (((2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q(4)) \times Q((5 + 6))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8683 := (((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) - Q(Q(4))) \times Q((5 + 6))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8684 := (Q((-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$8685 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8686 := (-1 - ((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8687 := ((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8688 := ((-1 + ((2 - (3 - 4)) \times Q((5 + 6)))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8689 := (-1 + (2 \times (((3 + 4) \times Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8690 := (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8691 := ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + 4) - (Q((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8692 := ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8693 := (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (Q(((4 + 5) + Q(6))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8694 := (((-1 - Q(2 + 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8695 := (((-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(4)))))) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8696 := (((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8697 := (-1 - 2 + ((Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8698 := ((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3 + 4)))) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8699 := (Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8700 := (((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times Q((4 \times 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8701 := (-1 + 2 + ((Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8702 := (-1 + (Q(((2 \times Q(3 + 4)) - 5)) + (Q(Q(6)) / (7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8703 := ((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(((3 \times 4) - 5)))))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8704 := (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3) + Q(4 + 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8665 := ((((-9 + (8 \times Q(7))) - Q(6)) \times Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8666 := (-9 - (((Q(8 + 7) \times 6) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8667 := (-9 - (Q(8) + ((7 \times (Q(6) \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8668 := (-9 \times 8 - ((7 \times (Q(6) \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8669 := (((-9 \times 8 - Q(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8670 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8 - 7) \times 6) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8671 := (-9 + 8 - 7 - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8672 := (((-9 + 8) \times 7) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8673 := (((-9 - (Q(8) \times 7)) \times (6 - Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8674 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + Q(((5 + 4) + Q((3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$8675 := ((-9 - (8 + 7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8676 := (-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) + (Q(6) - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8677 := (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8678 := (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 - Q(6))) + Q(Q(Q(((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$8679 := (-9 - ((8 \times (Q(7 + 6) - 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8680 := (-9 + (Q(((8 \times 7) + Q(6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8681 := (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8682 := (-9 + (((Q(8) + 7) \times Q(6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8683 := (-9 + (Q((Q(8) + (7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))))) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8684 := (Q((-9 \times 8 + Q(7 + 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8685 := (-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8686 := (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 + 6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8687 := (-9 - 8 - (Q(Q((7 - (6 - 5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8688 := (-9 - (((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8689 := (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8690 := (-9 - (Q(Q(8 - 7) \times 6) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8691 := (((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times (6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8692 := (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + Q((Q(6) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8693 := (((-9 - (Q(8) \times 7)) \times (6 - Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8694 := (-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8695 := (-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q((7 - (6 - 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8696 := ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + Q((6 + (Q(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8697 := (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 \times Q(6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8698 := (-9 \times 8 + ((7 \times Q(6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8699 := ((-9 - 8 + 7) - ((Q(Q(6)) - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8700 := ((-9 + (8 + 7 + 6)) \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8701 := (-9 + 8 - 7 - ((Q(Q(6)) - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8702 := (((-9 + 8) \times 7) - ((Q(Q(6)) - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8703 := (-9 \times (8 + ((7 + 6) \times (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8704 := ((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8705 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (Q((4 + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8706 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) - ((Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8707 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times Q(Q(5))) + (6 + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8708 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3 + 4))) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8709 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8710 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q((4 + Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8711 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q((3 \times 4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8712 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q((3 \times 4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8713 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (Q((5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8714 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (Q(3) - Q(Q(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8715 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8716 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + (Q(4) \times ((5 + 6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8717 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8718 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8719 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8720 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8721 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8722 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8723 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8724 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) + ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8725 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 \times 3))) + ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8726 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8727 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times ((Q(3) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8728 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3 + 4))) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8729 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8730 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8731 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8732 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8733 &:= (-1 - ((Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - Q((4 \times Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8734 &:= (-1 \times ((Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - Q((4 \times Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8735 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q((Q(Q(3)) - (4 + (5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8736 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(((2 + Q(3)) - 4))) + ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8737 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) + ((5 + 6) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8738 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8739 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8740 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + ((4 + (5 + 6)) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8741 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8742 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8743 &:= ((-1 + (Q(2^3) \times (Q(4) + Q(5 + 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8744 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + 3 + 4)) + (Q((Q(5) - 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8705 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8706 &:= (-9 + (Q(((8 + 7) \times 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8707 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (Q(7) \times (6 + 5))) \times Q(4))) - Q((3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8708 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8709 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8710 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + ((6 + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8711 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8712 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times (Q(7) - ((Q(6) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8713 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7) + 6 \times 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8714 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8715 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8716 &:= (Q((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7 + 6)))) - (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8717 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7 + 6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4))) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8718 &:= (((-9 - (Q(8) + Q(Q(7)))) \times (6 - (5 + 4))) + Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8719 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (Q((7 \times 6)) \times 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8720 &:= ((Q((-9 + Q(8)) - 7 - 6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8721 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8722 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) - ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8723 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((7 \times (Q(6) \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8724 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8725 &:= (((-9 - 8 + Q((7 \times 6))) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8726 &:= (-9 + (Q(((8 + 7) \times 6)) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8727 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8728 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + Q(((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8729 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + Q(((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8730 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 - (Q(6 + Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8731 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + (7 \times (6 + 5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8732 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(Q(8)) / (7 - 6 - 5))) - Q((Q(4) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8733 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) - (Q(7 + 6) \times (5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8734 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7) \times ((6 - Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8735 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8736 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8737 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((Q((7 \times 6)) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8738 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (Q((7 \times 6)) \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8739 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 \times (Q(6) \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8740 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (Q(6) \times 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8741 &:= (-9 - ((8 - 7 - Q(6)) \times (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8742 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times (Q(6) + (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8743 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8744 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7) + ((6 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8745 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 \times Q(3))) \times (Q(4) + (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8746 &:= (Q((-1 - ((2 \times Q(3)) - Q(Q(4)))) + (Q((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8747 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8748 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8749 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8750 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8751 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + 4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8752 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8753 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8754 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3 + 4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8755 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8756 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8757 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8758 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (Q(4) + (Q((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8759 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8760 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times Q(3 \times 4)) + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8761 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(Q(3))) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8762 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8763 &:= (((-1 + 2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4)) + ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8764 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3 + 4)) + (Q(5) - (Q(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
8765 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) + (Q(4 + 5) \times (Q(Q(6)) / (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
8766 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - (Q(4) \times ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
8767 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - (Q(4) \times ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
8768 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8769 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8770 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - ((Q(4) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8771 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8772 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times Q(((4 + 5) \times 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8773 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times Q(((4 + 5) \times 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8774 &:= ((-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8775 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q(4))) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8776 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 \times Q(3)) - (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8777 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + (6 + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
8778 &:= (-1 + (((2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4)) + ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
8779 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) + (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8780 &:= ((((-1 + 2 - 3) + Q(4)) \times Q(Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8781 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8782 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
8783 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8784 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8745 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8746 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
8747 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
8748 &:= (-9 - (((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times (6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8749 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (6 + 5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8750 &:= ((Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) - 6)) - Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8751 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + Q((7 \times 6))) \times 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8752 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (Q(7) - Q(Q(6)))) - (Q(5 + 4) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
8753 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 \times Q(6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8754 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (7 \times (Q(6) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
8755 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (Q(6) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
8756 &:= (((-9 + Q(8 + 7)) \times (Q(6) + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8757 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) - ((Q(Q(6)) - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8758 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((Q((7 \times 6)) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8759 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - (Q(Q((7 - (6 - 5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8760 &:= ((-9 - Q(8)) \times ((7 + 6 - Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8761 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) - ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8762 &:= (Q((-9 \times 8 + Q(7 + 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) + (Q(4) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8763 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - Q((Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
8764 &:= (-9 \times 8 + Q((Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
8765 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) - ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8766 &:= (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) - (Q((6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8767 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q((7 \times 6)) + Q(((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
8768 &:= (((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7))) - Q(6 + 5)) \times 4) + Q((3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8769 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 \times Q(6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8770 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7 + 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8771 &:= (-9 + ((8 - Q((7 \times 6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8772 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + 7)) + (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
8773 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + Q(6)))) + (Q((Q(5) + Q(4))) + Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8774 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8775 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times Q(Q(6)))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8776 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) + Q(6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8777 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) - ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8778 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) \times (7 + (Q(Q(6)) / Q(5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8779 &:= (-9 + (Q(((8 \times 7) + Q(6))) + ((5 + 4) \times Q((3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
8780 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8781 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8782 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) + (6 + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8783 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
8784 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8785 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8786 &:= (-1 + (((2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8787 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - (4 + Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8788 &:= (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - (4 + Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8789 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times Q(3 \times 4)) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8790 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times (4 - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8791 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8792 &:= (-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + Q((Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8793 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8794 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8795 &:= ((-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8796 &:= (((-1 - 2 - Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4) - Q((5 + 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8797 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8798 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8799 &:= (Q((-1 - (2 \times Q(Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8800 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8801 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8802 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8803 &:= (-1 + (((Q((2 \times Q(3))) - Q(Q(4))) \times Q((5 + 6))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8804 &:= (-1 + (((2 - 3) + Q(4)) \times ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8805 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8806 &:= (Q((-1 - (2 + 3)) + (4 \times Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8807 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8808 &:= ((-1 - 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8809 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + 4) \times Q(Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8810 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8811 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8812 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8813 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q((Q(3) - (4 - 5)) - 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8814 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3 + 4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8815 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8816 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(4) - ((5 + Q(6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8817 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) \times ((Q(4) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8818 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(3) + (Q(4) \times 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8819 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8820 &:= ((Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8821 &:= (Q((Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4))) + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8822 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(3) + (Q(4) \times 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8823 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8824 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8785 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times Q(6))) \times (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8786 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (((7 + 6) + Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8787 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8788 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + ((Q((7 \times 6)) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8789 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((Q((7 \times 6)) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8790 &:= (((-9 - 8 + 7) \times Q(6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8791 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8792 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + ((6 \times Q(Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8793 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (Q((7 \times 6)) \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8794 &:= (Q((-9 \times 8 + Q(7 + 6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8795 &:= (((-9 \times 8 - Q(7 + 6)) \times 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8796 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8797 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8798 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((7 - 6 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8799 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(Q((7 - 6) \times 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8800 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8801 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q(((7 - 6) - (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8802 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) - ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8803 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q((7 \times 6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8804 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) + ((5 + 4) - Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8805 &:= (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) + (Q(6 + Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8806 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7 + 6) - (5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8807 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8808 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8809 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (Q((7 \times 6)) \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8810 &:= ((Q((-9 + Q(8)) - 7 - 6)) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8811 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) + (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8812 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 + 6 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8813 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((Q((7 \times 6)) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8814 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + ((7 \times (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8815 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8816 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8817 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8818 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8819 &:= (-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8820 &:= ((Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) + Q(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8821 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times Q(Q(6)))) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8822 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8) + 7)) \times (6 - Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8823 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q(7) - (6 + 5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8824 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) \times 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8825 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8826 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8827 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8828 &:= (-1 - (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8829 &:= (Q((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8830 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8831 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8832 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3^4) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8833 &:= (-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3) + (4 - 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8834 &:= (-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3) + (4 - 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8835 &:= (-1 + Q((2 \times ((3 \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8836 &:= Q((-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8837 &:= (-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3) + (4 - 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8838 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8839 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8840 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8841 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8842 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8843 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2 \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8844 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - (4 + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8845 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - (4 + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8846 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - (4 + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8847 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3 + 4)))) - ((5 \times Q(6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8848 &:= ((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q((5 + 6)))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8849 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8850 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8851 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8852 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((3 - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8853 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((3 - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8854 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8855 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8856 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8857 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + Q((Q(Q(4) - 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8858 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3 + 4)) + ((5 \times Q(Q(6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8859 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3))) - Q((Q(4) + Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8860 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (4 + (5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8861 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8862 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4) \times Q((5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8863 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - (Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8864 &:= (-1 - ((Q(Q(2 \times 3)) - Q(Q(4 + 5))) - Q((Q(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8825 &:= ((-9 + 8 - Q((7 \times 6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8826 &:= (-9 - (((Q(8) + Q(7 + 6)) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8827 &:= (-9 + Q((Q(8 + 7) - (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8828 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8829 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((Q((7 \times 6)) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8830 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times Q(Q(6)))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8831 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - ((Q(7 + Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8832 &:= (((-9 - Q((8 + Q(7)))) / 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8833 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q((7 + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8834 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8835 &:= (-9 + 8 + Q((Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8836 &:= Q(((((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8837 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) + (Q(7) + (6 - Q(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8838 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5 + 4) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8839 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7 + 6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8840 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) + Q(((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8841 &:= (-9 + ((8 + Q(7 + 6)) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8842 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) - 7 - 6) + (Q(Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8843 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times Q(6 + 5)))) - (4 - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8844 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((Q((7 \times 6)) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8845 &:= ((((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - Q(6))) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8846 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times Q(Q(6)))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8847 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8848 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q(((Q(7) \times 6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8849 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((7 + 6) \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8850 &:= ((((-9 - 8 + 7) - Q(6)) \times Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8851 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8 + 7) + (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8852 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((Q(7) + Q(6)) \times (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8853 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8854 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 \times (6 + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8855 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (((7 \times 6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8856 &:= ((-9 + Q(8 + 7)) \times (Q(6) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8857 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7) + (6 \times (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8858 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((7 - Q((6 \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8859 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) - (6 - Q((Q(5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8860 &:= (((-9 - (Q(8 + 7) - 6)) \times 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8861 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((Q((7 \times 6)) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8862 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7))) - (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8863 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(Q(7)) + ((Q(6) / (5 + 4)) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8864 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$8865 := (-1 + (Q((2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) - 5)))))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8866 := (Q(((-1 - (2 + 3)) + (4 \times Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8867 := ((-1 \times 2) - ((3 + 4) \times (5 - (Q(Q(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$8868 := (((Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) - 4 - 5) \times Q(6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8869 := (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8870 := (((Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8871 := (Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8872 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 \times (Q((5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$8873 := (((-1 + 2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4)) + (Q((5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8874 := ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q((Q(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$8875 := (Q((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times Q(4)))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8876 := (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8877 := ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8878 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) \times (Q((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8879 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) \times (Q((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8880 := (-1 + 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8881 := (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(4) \times (Q((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8882 := (-1 + ((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$8883 := ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8884 := (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q((Q(6) + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$8885 := (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8886 := ((-1 - 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8887 := ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (((Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)) \times Q(6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8888 := (-1 + (((2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4)) + (Q((5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$8889 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8890 := (((-1 + 2 - 3) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8891 := (Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8892 := ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$8893 := (-1 \times (2^{Q(3)} + (4 - Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$8894 := (-1 - (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$8895 := (-1 - (Q(2^3) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8896 := (-1 \times (Q(2^3) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8897 := (((-1 + 2 - 3) \times Q(Q(4))) + Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8898 := ((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times Q((Q(4) - 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8899 := (-1 + ((Q((Q(2 \times 3) + 4)) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8900 := ((-1 + (Q(2 + Q(3)) \times Q(4 + 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8901 := (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3 + 4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$8902 := ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3 + 4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8903 := (-1 - (2 \times ((3 \times Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$8904 := (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$$

$$8865 := (-9 + (Q((Q(8) - (7 - Q(6)))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8866 := (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) + (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$8867 := ((-9 + (8 \times (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4)))) - Q((3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8868 := ((-9 \times (8 + Q(7))) + (6 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$8869 := (-9 + 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$8870 := ((-9 + (Q(8 + 7) + (Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8871 := (-9 + (8 \times (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$8872 := (-9 - ((Q(8) \times 7) + ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$8873 := (-9 - 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$8874 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((7 \times 6) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8875 := (((-9 \times Q(8 + 7)) + Q((6 \times 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8876 := (-9 + ((8 \times (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) + ((5 + 4) + Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$8877 := (-9 - (Q(8) + (((7 \times 6) \times Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$8878 := (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (Q((6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8879 := (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) - (Q((6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8880 := ((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8881 := (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (Q((6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8882 := (-9 - (Q((Q(8) - (7 \times 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$8883 := (-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$8884 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (6 + 5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8885 := ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((Q(7) \times (6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8886 := ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8887 := (-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q(7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$8888 := (-9 \times 8 - (7 \times ((Q(Q(6)) / Q(5 + 4)) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$8889 := (-9 + 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$8890 := ((-9 + 8) \times ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$8891 := (-9 + (Q(8) + Q((Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$8892 := ((-9 + Q((8 - (7 - (6 + (5 + 4))))) \times Q((3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8893 := ((-9 \times ((Q(8) - Q(Q(7))) / (6 - Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8894 := (-9 - (Q(8) - (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$8895 := (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8896 := (-9 - (((Q(8 + 7) - 6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8897 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(((7 + 6) + Q(5 + 4))) + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8898 := ((-9 \times (8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$8899 := (-9 + 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8900 := (Q((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6))) - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8901 := (((-9 \times 8 - 7) \times 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8902 := (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8903 := (-9 - 8 + ((Q((7 \times 6)) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8904 := ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (Q(6 + Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8905 := (-1 + (Q(Q(2+3)) + Q((Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6+7+8+9))))))$$

$$8906 := (Q((-1 + (Q(2+3) \times 4))) + (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8907 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times ((Q(4) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8908 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times ((Q(4) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8909 := (-1 + ((Q(2 \times 3) + (Q(Q(4)) + 5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8910 := ((Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + (Q(4) + Q(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))$$

$$8911 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times ((Q(4) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8912 := (((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3)))) \times Q(4)) + ((5+6) \times Q((7+8+9))))$$

$$8913 := (Q((-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9))))$$

$$8914 := (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(3) - Q(Q(4)))) + Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9))))))$$

$$8915 := (-1 + (((2 + (Q(3+4) \times 5)) \times Q(6)) + 7+8+9))$$

$$8916 := (((Q(Q(-1+2+3)) - 4 - 5) \times Q(6)) + 7+8+9)$$

$$8917 := (-1 + ((2 \times (3+4)) \times (Q(5) + (Q(6) + Q((7+8+9))))))$$

$$8918 := (-1 - (Q(2+Q(3)) + (Q(4) \times ((5+6) - Q((7+8+9))))))$$

$$8919 := (-1 \times (Q(2+Q(3)) + (Q(4) \times ((5+6) - Q((7+8+9))))))$$

$$8920 := (((-1 - 2 + Q(3+Q(4))) \times Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))$$

$$8921 := (Q((-1+2+(Q(Q(3))+4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8922 := (-1 + 2 - (((3+4) \times (Q(5) - Q(Q(6)))) - (7+8+9)))$$

$$8923 := (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8924 := (-1 + (((2-3) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8925 := ((-1 - ((2-3) \times Q(Q(4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$8926 := (Q((-1 + (Q(2+3) \times 4))) + (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8927 := (-1 - (2 \times ((Q(3) \times 4) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))))))$$

$$8928 := ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3+4) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8929 := (-1 - (((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) \times 5)) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$8930 := (((Q((-1+2+Q(3))) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)$$

$$8931 := ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 \times Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8932 := (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8933 := (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8934 := (-1 - (Q(2+3) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8935 := (-1 \times (Q(2+3) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8936 := (-1 + (Q((2+Q(3+4))) + ((5+6) \times Q((7+8+9))))))$$

$$8937 := (-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8938 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))))))$$

$$8939 := (-1 - ((2 - ((3 \times 4) \times Q(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8940 := ((Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) + (4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))$$

$$8941 := (-1 - (2 \times Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8942 := (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$8943 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) \times ((4^5) - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8944 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) \times ((4^5) - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$8905 := ((-9 - 8 - Q((7 \times 6))) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8906 := (-9 + 8 + ((7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5))) + 4+3+2+1))$$

$$8907 := (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8908 := ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 - 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8909 := (Q((-9 \times 8 + Q(7+6))) - (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8910 := ((-9 + Q(((8-7) \times (6 \times 5)))) \times (4+3+2+1))$$

$$8911 := ((-9 \times Q(((8-7) \times (6+5)))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8912 := (((-9 - 8) \times Q((7+6-5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8913 := (-9 - 8 - ((7 - Q((6 \times 5))) \times (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8914 := ((-9 \times (Q(8+7) - Q(Q(6)))) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8915 := ((-9 + Q(8+7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))$$

$$8916 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) - 7 - 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8917 := (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (Q(6+Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))$$

$$8918 := (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) + (Q(6+Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))$$

$$8919 := (-9 + 8 + ((Q((7 \times 6)) \times 5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8920 := (Q((-9 + 8 \times (7+6))) - (5 + Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8921 := ((-9 \times 8 - 7) + (Q((6 \times 5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8922 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7))) - (Q(6) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))$$

$$8923 := (Q((-9 \times 8 + Q(7+6))) - (Q(5+4) \times (3+2+1)))$$

$$8924 := (((-9 \times (Q(8+7) - Q(6))) + Q(Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8925 := (Q(((9 - Q(8+7)) - Q(6+5))) - Q(4+3+2+1))$$

$$8926 := (-9 - (((8+7) \times (Q(6) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8927 := (-9 + (((8 \times 7) \times (6 - Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8928 := ((-9 \times 8) \times (7 - (Q(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8929 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q((7+6-5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8930 := (Q((-9 + 8 \times (7+6))) + (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8931 := ((-9 + (8 \times (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1))$$

$$8932 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((Q(Q(7)) \times (6 - (5+4))) + Q(Q((3+2+1)))))$$

$$8933 := (-9 - 8 - (((7 \times 6) \times Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8934 := ((-9 \times Q((8-7+6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8935 := ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (Q((6 \times 5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8936 := (((-9 \times Q(8+7)) + Q(6+Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8937 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) - ((7+6) \times Q(5+4)))) + Q((3+2+1)))$$

$$8938 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(7) \times ((6-5) - Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8939 := (-9 \times 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + ((Q(6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$8940 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7+6) \times (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))$$

$$8941 := (-9 + (Q(((8 \times 7) + Q(6))) + (Q(5+4) \times (3+2+1))))$$

$$8942 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7))) - (Q(6) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))$$

$$8943 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q((Q(6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))$$

$$8944 := (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 \times (6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8945 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + Q(3 + Q(4))) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8946 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times ((4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8947 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) \times ((4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8948 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8949 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8950 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3 + 4)) \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8951 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8952 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8953 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8954 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8955 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8956 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) \times ((5 + 6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8957 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) \times ((5 + 6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8958 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8959 &:= (-1 - ((2 - 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8960 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8961 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8962 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8963 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8964 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8965 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8966 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8967 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8968 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (Q(4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8969 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8970 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8971 &:= (-1 + 2 + (((Q(Q(3)) \times 4) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8972 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - (Q((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8973 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - (4 \times (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8974 &:= (-1 + ((2 - Q(3 + Q(4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8975 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 \times 4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8976 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8977 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q(3) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8978 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + Q(3)) - (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8979 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) - 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8980 &:= (((-1 - 2 + Q(3 + Q(4))) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8981 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) + (Q((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8982 &:= ((-1 + (((2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4) \times Q((5 + 6)))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8983 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times Q(4))) \times Q((5 + 6))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8984 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8945 &:= ((-9 + Q(8 + 7)) - ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8946 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) + (6 - Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8947 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + (Q(6) + Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8948 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) + (Q(5 + 4) + Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8949 &:= (-9 + 8 - (((7 \times 6) \times Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8950 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8951 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) \times (Q(7) + (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8952 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6) - Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8953 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7))) - ((6 \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8954 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + Q((7 \times (6 - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8955 &:= (-9 + (Q(((8 \times 7) + Q(6))) + (5 \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8956 &:= (((-9 + Q(8 + 7)) \times (Q(6) + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8957 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8958 &:= (((-9 - (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))))/5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8959 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + ((7 + Q(6 + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8960 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) + (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8961 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + Q(Q(Q(((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8962 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8963 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 - Q((Q(Q(6))/Q(5 + 4)))) \times Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8964 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8965 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8966 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8967 &:= (-9 + ((Q(Q(8)))/(7 - 6 - 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8968 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7 + 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8969 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + (7 + Q(6)))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8970 &:= (-9 + ((8 - Q(7)) \times (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8971 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8972 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7))) - (6 + 5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8973 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7) + (Q(6 + Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8974 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (6 - 5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8975 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8976 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (Q((6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8977 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) + (Q((6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8978 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8979 &:= (((-9 - 8 - Q(7)) \times 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8980 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7) + (6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8981 &:= (-9 - ((8 - 7 - Q((6 \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8982 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7))) - ((6 - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8983 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7))) + Q(Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8984 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$8985 := (Q((-1 + 2 \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8986 := ((-1 \times 2) \times ((3 + 4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8987 := (-1 \times (Q(Q(2 + 3)) - (((Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times Q(6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$8988 := (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8989 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8990 := (Q((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8991 := (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8992 := (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8993 := ((-1 \times 2 + (Q(3 + Q(4)) \times Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8994 := (-1 - (((2 - 3) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8995 := (((-1 + 2)^3) + Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8996 := (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8997 := (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(3) + Q(4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8998 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(3) + Q(4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8999 := (-1 - ((2 - (3 + (4 + 5))) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$9000 := ((-1 \times (2 - (3 + (4 + 5)))) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8985 := ((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times Q(Q(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8986 := ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4)))) - (3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8987 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q((Q(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8988 := (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + Q((6 \times Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$8989 := (-9 + 8 - (Q(7) + (Q(6 + Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$$

$$8990 := (Q((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6))) - (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8991 := (Q((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7 + 6)))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8992 := (-9 + 8 - 7 + (Q((6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8993 := (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (Q((6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8994 := (((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7))) + (6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8995 := (-9 \times 8 + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8996 := (-9 + 8 + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8997 := (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 + Q((6 \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8998 := (-9 \times 8 + ((7 + Q((6 \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8999 := (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) + (Q(6) + 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$9000 := ((-9 + Q((8 - 7 + 6))) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$9001 := (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(3) + Q(4 + 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$9002 := ((-1 \times 2) \times ((3 - 4) - (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$9003 := (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) + (Q(4) \times ((5 + 6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$9004 := (-1 - (((2 - Q(3 + Q(4))) \times Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$9005 := ((-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$9006 := (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$9007 := (-1 - ((2^{Q(3)}) - (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$$

$$9008 := (-1 - ((2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$9009 := (Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$9010 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$9011 := (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) - ((Q(Q(4)) + Q((5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$9012 := (Q((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times Q(4)))) + ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$9013 := (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + 4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$9014 := ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) - (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$9015 := (((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$9016 := (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$9017 := ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$9018 := ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$9019 := (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q(4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$9020 := (-1 + 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$9021 := (-1 + ((2 \times (Q(Q(Q(3))) - (4 \times Q(Q(5)))))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$9022 := (((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times Q((Q(4) - 5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$9023 := (-1 + (Q(2^3) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$9001 := (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times Q(Q(6))) + Q((Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$9002 := (((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7))) - (6 - Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$9003 := ((-9 + (8 \times (Q((7 \times 6)) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$9004 := ((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - Q(Q(6)))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$9005 := ((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times Q(Q(6)))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$9006 := ((-9 + 8 + 7) + (Q((6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$9007 := (-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (Q(6) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$9008 := (-9 - (Q(8) + ((Q(7) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$9009 := (-9 \times ((Q(Q(8) + 7) - Q(6)) / (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$9010 := (Q((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$9011 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(Q(7)) - (6 - Q(Q(Q((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))))))$$

$$9012 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) + (7 + Q(6)))) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$9013 := (((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7))) + 6 \times 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$9014 := (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$9015 := (-9 \times 8 + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$9016 := (-9 + Q((8 + (7 \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$9017 := (((-9 - 8) \times Q(7)) - (6 \times Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$9018 := (-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + Q((Q(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$$

$$9019 := ((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 + 6)) + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$9020 := ((-9 + (Q(8) + (7 \times Q(6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$9021 := ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times Q(Q(6)))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$9022 := (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$9023 := (-9 + (8 \times (Q((7 \times 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9024 &:= (-1 + Q((2 - (3 \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9025 &:= Q((-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9026 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3 + Q(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9027 &:= (-1 - 2 - (((Q(Q(3)) \times 4) - Q(Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9028 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (Q(4) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9029 &:= (-1 - (((Q(Q(2 \times 3))/4) - Q(Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9030 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((3 \times 4) \times Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9031 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9032 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9033 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) - (Q(4) \times ((5 + 6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9034 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) - (Q(4) \times ((5 + 6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9035 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
9036 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) + (4 - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9037 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9038 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9039 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9040 &:= (Q((-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) + (4 - Q((5 + 6)))))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9041 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9042 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9043 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q((5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9044 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9045 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3 + Q(4)) - Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9046 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q((5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9047 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
9048 &:= ((Q(Q((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))))) + Q((5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9049 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 \times 4)) \times (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9050 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q(4)) \times (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9051 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) \times 4))) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9052 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q(3 + Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9053 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (Q(4) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
9054 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + 4) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9055 &:= (Q((Q((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q(4)) - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9056 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(3 + Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9057 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q((5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9058 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + Q(((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9059 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times Q(4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9060 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9061 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + Q(((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9062 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9063 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9024 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - Q(Q(6)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9025 &:= Q((-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9026 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 + 6)) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9027 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q((Q(7) + (6 - Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9028 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times Q(6))/5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9029 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) - (Q(6 + Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9030 &:= ((Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) - Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9031 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - (Q(6 + Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9032 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7) \times Q(6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9033 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) + Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9034 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9035 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8 + 7)) - Q(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9036 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) + (Q((6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9037 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7)/6) - ((5 - Q(Q(4))) \times Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9038 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9039 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9040 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9041 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + 7 \times 6)) - (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9042 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7) + Q(6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9043 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times (7 - (6 \times Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9044 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8) + Q(7))) + (Q(6) + Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9045 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7 + 6)) - (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9046 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times Q(7)) - (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9047 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) + (Q((6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9048 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (Q((6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9049 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9050 &:= ((Q((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) - 6)) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9051 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) + (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9052 &:= (-9 - ((8 - Q(7)) \times (Q(6 + 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9053 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 + Q((6 \times 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9054 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7 \times (6 + 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9055 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7 + 6) \times 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9056 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times Q(Q(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9057 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + Q(7)) \times (Q(6) + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9058 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) + ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9059 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) - 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9060 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6))) + (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9061 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (Q(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9062 &:= ((Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + (6^5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9063 &:= (-9 \times ((Q(Q(8) + 7) - 6)/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9064 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (4 - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9065 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9066 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9067 &:= (-1 - (Q((2 \times Q(3))) - (Q(4) \times ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9068 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9069 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9070 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q((4 \times (5 + 6))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9071 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (4 + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9072 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q((5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9073 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3)) + (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9074 &:= ((-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(4))) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9075 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q(4))) - (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9076 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) - (Q(4) \times ((5 + 6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9077 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - Q(Q(3))) \times 4) + Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9078 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - 4) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9079 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times Q(4)) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9080 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9081 &:= (((-1 + 2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4)) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9082 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9083 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q((5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9084 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (4 + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9085 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (4 + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9086 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4))) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9087 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (4 + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9088 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (4 + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9089 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times Q(4)) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9090 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9091 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - ((4 + 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9092 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9093 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9094 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q((4 \times Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9095 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q(4))) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9096 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - (Q(4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9097 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3 + 4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9098 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + Q((4 \times Q(5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9099 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2 + 3) \times (4 \times 5)))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9100 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9101 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - ((4 - 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9102 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9103 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9064 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - Q(6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9065 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9066 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9067 &:= ((-9 - 8 + ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(6 + 5)) \times 4)) - Q((3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9068 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7) \times (6 - Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9069 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) + 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9070 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7 + 6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9071 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) - (Q(6 + Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9072 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((Q(7 + Q(6)) \times 5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9073 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (Q(7 + Q(6)) \times 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9074 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) - (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9075 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9076 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9077 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9078 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) - ((Q(Q(6)) - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9079 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 - Q(6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9080 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + ((7 \times Q(6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9081 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((7 \times Q(6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9082 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (6 + 5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9083 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((Q(7 + 6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9084 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) - (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9085 &:= (((-9 + (Q(8) + Q((7 \times 6)))) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9086 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9087 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7) \times Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9088 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) \times (6 - Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9089 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(Q(7)) + Q((Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9090 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9091 &:= (Q((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7 + 6)))) - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9092 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9093 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) - (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9094 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(Q(7)) + ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9095 &:= (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) + ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9096 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9097 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6 + Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9098 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) - ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9099 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((7 + Q(6)) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9100 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9101 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + (7 \times Q(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9102 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9103 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + Q(7))) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9104 &:= ((-1+2+3) + (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9105 &:= (Q(Q((-1-(2+3)) + Q(4))) + (5 - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9106 &:= (-1-2 + (Q(3) + (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9107 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9108 &:= (((-1+Q(2+Q(3))) \times Q(4+5)) - (Q(6) + Q((7+8+9)))) \\
9109 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) + (4+5 - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9110 &:= ((-1+2+Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9111 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - (5 + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9112 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) + (((4-5) - Q(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
9113 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(Q(3)))) + (4 + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
9114 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3 - (Q(4) + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
9115 &:= (((Q(Q((-1+2 \times 3))) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6)) - Q((7+8+9))) \\
9116 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) + (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9117 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q(3) + (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9118 &:= ((-1-2+Q(Q(3))) - (Q(4) \times ((5+6) - Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
9119 &:= (-1 + ((Q((2 \times Q(3))) - (4 \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9120 &:= ((-1+Q(2+3)) \times ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9121 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
9122 &:= ((-1+2+Q(Q(3))) - (Q(4) \times ((5+6) - Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
9123 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times (Q(4) + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
9124 &:= (-1 + ((Q(Q(2+3)) \times Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9125 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times Q(4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
9126 &:= ((-1-2+Q(3)) \times Q(4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
9127 &:= (-1 - (Q(2+3) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9128 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2+3) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9129 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) + ((4+Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9130 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) - ((4+Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9131 &:= (-1-2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9132 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9133 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(((4+5) \times 6)) - (7+8+9))) \\
9134 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
9135 &:= (((-1+2 \times 3) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
9136 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(3))) + (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9137 &:= ((Q((-1+Q(2+3))) \times Q(4)) - (Q(5) + (Q(Q(6))/(7+8+9)))) \\
9138 &:= (((-1+Q(2+Q(3))) \times Q(4+5)) - (6 + Q((7+8+9)))) \\
9139 &:= (-1-2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9140 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9141 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9142 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9143 &:= (-1+2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9104 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9105 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9106 &:= (-9 - (((8+Q(7+6)) \times 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9107 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q(7+6) - Q(5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
9108 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - Q(6+5))) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9109 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times (7+6)) - 5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9110 &:= ((-9+8 - (Q(7) - Q(6+Q(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
9111 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 - Q(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9112 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9113 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (Q((7 \times 6)) - Q(Q(5)))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
9114 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8+7) - Q(Q(6)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9115 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) - Q(Q(6)))) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
9116 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(Q(8))/(7-6-5))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
9117 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (((Q(7) \times 6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9118 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (((Q(7) \times 6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
9119 &:= (-9+8 - ((Q(7) - Q(6+Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
9120 &:= (((-9 - (Q(8) + 7)) \times (6+5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9121 &:= (Q((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7+6)))) + (5 - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9122 &:= (-9+8 - (7 \times Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9123 &:= ((((-9+8) \times 7) \times Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9124 &:= (Q((-9-8+Q(7))) + Q((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9125 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8+7)) - Q(6+5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
9126 &:= ((-9+8+7) \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9127 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + (Q(6) + 5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9128 &:= ((-9-8 + (Q(7+Q(6)) \times 5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
9129 &:= (Q((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7+6)))) - (Q(5+4) + 3+2+1)) \\
9130 &:= (Q((-9+8 \times (7+6))) + (5 + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9131 &:= (((-9 \times 8 - 7) \times (6+5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9132 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9133 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7+6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9134 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7+6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9135 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9136 &:= (-9-8 - ((7 \times Q(6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9137 &:= (((-9-8) \times Q(7)) - ((6 \times 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9138 &:= (-9-8 - ((Q(7+6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9139 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8+7) - Q(Q(6)))) - (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9140 &:= (((-9+8+Q(7+Q(6))) \times 5) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
9141 &:= (Q((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7+6)))) + (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9142 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9143 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - Q(((7-6-5) + Q(4+3+2+1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9144 &:= ((Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + (4 + Q((5+6)))) \times (7+8+9)) \\
9145 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9146 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2+3) \times 4))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9147 &:= ((-1 - (2+3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9148 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3+4)) + (Q((5+6)) - Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
9149 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9150 &:= (((-1 + Q(2+3))/4) \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9151 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((Q(3+4) + Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9152 &:= (-1 + ((2-3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9153 &:= ((-1-2) \times (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9154 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9155 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + Q(3+4)) \times (5 \times Q(6)))) - (7+8+9)) \\
9156 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9157 &:= ((-1+2+3) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9158 &:= ((-1+2 \times 3) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9159 &:= (-1-2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9160 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9161 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2+3))) \times Q(4)) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9162 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9163 &:= (-1+2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9164 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 \times (3+4)) - (5 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
9165 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9166 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3^4)) + Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
9167 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q((5+6)))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
9168 &:= ((((-1-2) \times Q(Q(3))) + Q(Q((Q(4) - (5+6)))))) \times (7+8+9)) \\
9169 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
9170 &:= ((-1-2 + (Q(3) + Q(Q(4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
9171 &:= (-1 \times ((Q(2+3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)))) + (Q(Q(6))/(7+8+9)))) \\
9172 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(3+4))) + ((5 \times Q(Q(6))) + Q((7+8+9)))) \\
9173 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9174 &:= ((-1-2+Q(3)) \times (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9175 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times Q(4)))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9176 &:= (((Q((-1 + Q(2+3))) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6)) + 7+8+9) \\
9177 &:= ((-1 + Q(2+3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9178 &:= (-1-2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9179 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2+3) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9180 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2 \times 3) \times Q(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
9181 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2+3))) \times Q(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
9182 &:= (-1+2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9183 &:= ((-1-2 + (Q(3) \times (4^5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
9144 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
9145 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7+6 - Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
9146 &:= ((-9+8 + (7 \times Q(Q(6)))) - (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9147 &:= (-9 - (Q(8+7) - (6 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9148 &:= ((-9+8 + Q(7)) - (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9149 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9150 &:= (((-9+8 - Q(7+6)) \times 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9151 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (Q((Q(Q(6))/Q(5+4))) \times Q((3+2+1)))) \\
9152 &:= (-9+8 - ((7 \times Q(6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9153 &:= (-9 \times ((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9154 &:= (-9+8 - ((Q(7+6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9155 &:= ((-9+8) \times ((Q(7+6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9156 &:= (((-9-8) \times Q(7)) - (6+5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9157 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q((Q(6) + Q(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
9158 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - (7 - Q(6)))) - (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9159 &:= (Q((-9 \times 8 + Q(7+6))) - (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
9160 &:= (-9-8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9161 &:= ((((-9 - (8+7)) \times Q(6)) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9162 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9163 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (Q(7+Q(6)) \times 5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
9164 &:= (-9 - (((Q(8) \times (7+6)) - 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9165 &:= ((-9 \times ((8+7) \times 6)) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9166 &:= (Q((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7+6)))) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
9167 &:= (((-9-8) \times Q(7)) + Q(Q(((6-5) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9168 &:= ((((-9-8) \times Q(7)) + (6-5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9169 &:= (Q((-9 + Q((8-7+6)))) + Q((Q(5+4) + 3+2+1))) \\
9170 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7+6)) - (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9171 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times ((7 - Q(6)) \times 5)) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9172 &:= (Q(Q((-9+8+7))) + ((6^5) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9173 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7+Q(6)) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9174 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(7) + ((Q(6) + Q(5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9175 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9176 &:= (-9+8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9177 &:= (-9 - (Q(8+7) - (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9178 &:= ((((-9-8) \times Q(7)) + (6+5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9179 &:= (((-9 - Q(Q(8)))/(7-6) \times 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9180 &:= ((-9+8 + ((Q(7) \times 6) + Q(Q(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
9181 &:= (Q((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7+6)))) - (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
9182 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((Q(7+Q(6)) \times 5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
9183 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(7) + ((6+5) \times Q(4+3+2+1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9184 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) \times (4^5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 9184 &:= (Q((-9 \times 8 + Q(7 + 6))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9185 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(3) + 4))) \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 9185 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6)) - 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9186 &:= (Q((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + (Q(4) \times 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 9186 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 + 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9187 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (Q(3) \times (4^5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 9187 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7 - 6)) - (Q(5) - (Q(Q(4)) \times Q((3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9188 &:= ((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))))) & 9188 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) \times (Q(6) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9189 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times (Q((Q(4) - 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9189 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9190 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) \times (Q((Q(4) - 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9190 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7 + 6)) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9191 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times Q(4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9191 &:= (-9 - ((Q((8 \times 7)) - Q(Q(6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9192 &:= (Q((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (4 + (5 + 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) & 9192 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9193 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) & 9193 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) + (Q((Q(Q(6))/Q(5 + 4)) \times Q((3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9194 &:= (-1 - ((Q(2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 9194 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9195 &:= (-1 \times ((Q(2 + 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 9195 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6)) + 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9196 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 \times Q(3))) - (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9196 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9197 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q((Q(Q(6))/(7 + 8 + 9))))) & 9197 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q(7 + 6) - Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9198 &:= (Q((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + (Q(4) \times 5))) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9))) & 9198 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times Q(7)) + Q(6)) - (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9199 &:= (-1 + (((2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (4 \times Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9199 &:= (-9 - 8 + Q(((7 - 6 - 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9200 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times ((4 \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9200 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + Q(7 + 6)) - 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9201 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(Q(3))) - (Q((4 \times (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9201 &:= (Q((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7 + 6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9202 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2 \times 3) \times Q(4)) + ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9202 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (((7 - Q(6)) \times Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9203 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times Q(4)) + ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) & 9203 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (Q((7 \times 6)) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9204 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (Q(3) + Q(Q(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9204 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9205 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + Q(Q(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 9205 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9206 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) \times 4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9206 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(Q(8))/(7 - 6 - 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9207 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9207 &:= (-9 + Q((Q((8 + 7 - 6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9208 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) \times (Q((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9208 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - ((7 \times Q(6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9209 &:= (-1 + (((2 + Q(Q(3))) \times 4) - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 9209 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (((7 + Q(6)) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9210 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(4) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9210 &:= (-9 - (((Q(8) + 7) \times (6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9211 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times Q(4)) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9211 &:= (Q((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7 + 6)))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9212 &:= (-1 + ((2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9212 &:= (-9 - (((8 - Q(7)) \times (6 - Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9213 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 \times (3 + 4)) - (Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))))) & 9213 &:= (Q((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7 + 6)))) - ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9214 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) \times 4)) - ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9214 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9215 &:= (-1 + Q((2 \times (Q(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9215 &:= (-9 + 8 + Q(((7 - 6 - 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9216 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9216 &:= Q(((-9 + 8 + 7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9217 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(3) - (4 - (5 + 6))) \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9217 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (Q(7 + 6) - Q(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9218 &:= ((-1 + ((2 - Q(Q(3))) \times (4 - Q((5 + 6))))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) & 9218 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (Q(7 + Q(6)) \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9219 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9219 &:= ((-9 + Q(8) \times 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9220 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2 \times 3) \times Q(4))) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9220 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7 + 6)) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9221 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times Q(4)) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9221 &:= (Q((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7 + 6)))) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9222 &:= ((-1 - 2 + ((3^4) \times Q((5 + 6)))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))) & 9222 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9223 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + ((3^4) \times Q((5 + 6)))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))) & 9223 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (7 + 6 - Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9224 &:= (-1 - ((Q(Q(2+3)) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9225 &:= (-1 \times ((Q(Q(2+3)) - Q(Q(4))) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9226 &:= ((-1 + (Q((Q(2+3) + 4)) \times (5+6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
9227 &:= ((Q((Q((-1+2 \times 3)) + 4)) \times (5+6)) - (7+8+9)) \\
9228 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2 \times 3) \times Q(4)))) - ((5+6) - (7+8+9))) \\
9229 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2+3))) \times Q(4)) - ((5+6) - (7+8+9))) \\
9230 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2+3))) - Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\
9231 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9232 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9233 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - Q(3)) \times Q(4)) + Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9))) \\
9234 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2+3))) \times Q(4)) - (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9235 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9236 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2+3) \times 4))) + ((5+6) - Q((7+8+9)))) \\
9237 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + (4 + (5+6)))) + 7+8+9)) \\
9238 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + (4 + (5+6)))) + 7+8+9)) \\
9239 &:= (-1 + (((2^3) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
9240 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2 \times 3) \times Q(4)))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
9241 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2+3))) \times Q(4)) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
9242 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - Q(((4 \times (5+6)) + 7+8+9)))) \\
9243 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q(3) \times (4^5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
9244 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(3) \times (4^5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
9245 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9246 &:= (Q((Q(-1+2+3) + (Q(4) \times 5))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
9247 &:= (-1+2 + ((Q(3) \times (4^5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
9248 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) - ((Q(4) \times (5+6)) + Q((7+8+9)))) \\
9249 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
9250 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2 \times 3) \times Q(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
9251 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2+3))) \times Q(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
9252 &:= (((-1 - 2 - Q(Q(3))) \times (4 - Q((5+6)))) - Q((7+8+9))) \\
9253 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9254 &:= (-1 - ((Q(2+3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)))) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
9255 &:= (-1 \times ((Q(2+3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)))) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
9256 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9257 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9258 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + (Q(Q(4+5)) - (Q(Q(6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
9259 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3+4)))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9260 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9261 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9262 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
9263 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q((3 \times 4)) - Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9224 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9225 &:= ((-9+8+7 \times 6) \times Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
9226 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(Q(8)) / (7-6-5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
9227 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + ((Q(6) + Q(5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9228 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7+Q(6)) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9229 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (Q(7+6) - Q(5))) + (Q(4) + 3+2+1))) \\
9230 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7+6) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9231 &:= (Q((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7+6)))) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
9232 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9233 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 \times 6) - (Q(Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9234 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9235 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times (6+5)))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9236 &:= ((-9+8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
9237 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + Q(7)) \times 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9238 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((Q(7+Q(6)) \times 5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
9239 &:= (-9 + (8 \times Q((Q(7) - ((6 \times Q(5)) / (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9240 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + 7)) - (Q(6+5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9241 &:= (-9 + (((8-7) + Q(6)) \times (Q(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9242 &:= (-9 - (((Q(Q(8) + 7) - Q(Q(6))) / 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9243 &:= (((-9 - (Q(8) + Q(7))) \times 6) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9244 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7) \times (Q(6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9245 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7+6)) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
9246 &:= ((-9 \times Q((8+7-6))) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9247 &:= (-9 - ((Q(((8-7) + Q(6))) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9248 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) + ((6 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9249 &:= (((-9 \times 8 - Q(7)) \times 6) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9250 &:= (Q((-9+8 \times (7+6))) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
9251 &:= (Q((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7+6)))) + (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
9252 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q((7-6+Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9253 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (6 \times 5)))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9254 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (Q(6+5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9255 &:= ((-9 + Q(8+7)) - (Q(6+Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9256 &:= (((-9 - (8+7)) \times (6+Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9257 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) + Q(6+Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9258 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((7 - Q(6)) \times Q(5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9259 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (6 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9260 &:= (-9+8 - (Q(7) \times (Q(6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9261 &:= ((-9+8) \times (Q(7) \times (Q(6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9262 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + 7+6+5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9263 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7) + ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9264 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2+3)) + ((4 + (5+6)) \times Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
9265 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9266 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2+3) \times Q(4)))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9267 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + Q((5+6)))) + Q((7+8+9)))) \\
9268 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
9269 &:= (-1 + (((2 - Q(Q(3))) \times 4) + Q(Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9270 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9271 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2+3))) \times Q(4)) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9272 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q(3) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9273 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(3) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9274 &:= (-1 - (Q(Q(2+3)) - ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9275 &:= ((Q((-1 + 2) \times 3) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9276 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(3) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9277 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9278 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) - Q((Q(5+6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9279 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + Q((Q(5+6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9280 &:= (-1 + (((2 + Q(3)) \times Q((4 + Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9281 &:= ((Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) \times (4 + Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9282 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9283 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9284 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + Q(3)) + (4 - Q((Q(5+6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
9285 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q(4))) + (5 - (Q(Q(6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
9286 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2+3) \times 4))) + (Q(5) + (Q(6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
9287 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((3 \times 4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9288 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9289 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q((5+6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
9290 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times (4 + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9291 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (Q((5+6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9292 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(3) + 4)) \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9293 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(3) + 4)) \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9294 &:= ((-1 + 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) - 4) \times Q((5+6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9295 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9296 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(3) + 4)) \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9297 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(Q(3))) - (Q((4 \times (5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
9298 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(Q(3))) \times (4 + Q((5+6)))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9299 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) - Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9300 &:= (((-1 + Q((Q(2+3) + Q(4)))) \times 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9301 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(Q(3+4))) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9302 &:= ((-1 + (Q(Q(2+3)) \times Q(4))) - (Q((5+6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9303 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q(4))) - (Q((5+6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9264 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times Q(7+6)) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9265 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (((7 - 6) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9266 &:= (Q((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7+6)))) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9267 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((7 + (6 \times Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9268 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 + (6 \times Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9269 &:= (((-9 \times 8 - Q(7)) \times 6) - (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9270 &:= ((Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9271 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + Q(((7 - 6 - 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9272 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((Q(7 + Q(6)) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9273 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7) + (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))) \\
9274 &:= (((-9 - 8 - Q(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9275 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6))) + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9276 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9277 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) \times Q(7)) / Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9278 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 \times 6) \times Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9279 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (Q(7) - (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9280 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7 + 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9281 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9282 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + 7 + 6)) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9283 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4)))) + Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9284 &:= (Q((-9 \times 8 + Q(7 + 6))) - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9285 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9286 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 - Q(Q(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9287 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + Q(7)) \times (6 + Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9288 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times Q(7)) + Q(6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9289 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 + 6)) - Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9290 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7 + 6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9291 &:= (Q((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7 + 6)))) - (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9292 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + 7) \times (Q(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9293 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7) \times ((6 - Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9294 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 - 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9295 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) \times 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9296 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9297 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 + Q((Q(6) + Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9298 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7 + 6)) + ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9299 &:= ((((-9 \times 8 - Q(7)) \times 6) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9300 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (6 + 5)))) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9301 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + ((7 - 6 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9302 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + 7 + 6)) - (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9303 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(Q(((7 - 6) \times 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$9304 := (-1 + (((2+3) \times Q((Q(4) + Q(5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$9305 := (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$9306 := ((-1-2) \times (3 - (Q(Q(4+5)) - (6 \times Q((7+8+9))))))$$

$$9307 := (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) + (4 - (Q((5+6)) + Q((7+8+9))))))$$

$$9308 := (-1 - ((Q(2+3) \times 4) - Q((Q(5+6)) - (7+8+9))))$$

$$9309 := (-1 \times ((Q(2+3) \times 4) - Q((Q(5+6)) - (7+8+9))))$$

$$9310 := ((-1+2+(Q(3)+Q(Q(4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$9311 := (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3+4)) + Q((Q(5+6)) - (7+8+9)))$$

$$9312 := (Q((-1+(2 \times Q(3+4)))) - (Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))$$

$$9313 := (((-1 - (2+3)) \times Q(4)) + Q((Q(5+6)) - (7+8+9)))$$

$$9314 := ((-1+(2 \times Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q((Q(5+6)) - (7+8+9))))$$

$$9315 := ((-1 \times (2+3)) \times (4+5 - (Q(Q(6)) + Q((7+8+9))))$$

$$9316 := (-1+2+(3 \times (Q(Q(4+5)) - (6 \times Q((7+8+9))))))$$

$$9317 := ((-1 + ((Q(Q(2+3)) + 4^5) \times 6)) - Q((7+8+9)))$$

$$9318 := (-1 + (Q((2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$9319 := (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - (Q((5+6)) + Q((7+8+9))))))$$

$$9320 := ((-1+(2+3+4)) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (Q(6) - Q((7+8+9))))$$

$$9321 := (-1-2-(Q(Q(3)) + (4 - Q((Q(5+6)) - (7+8+9))))$$

$$9322 := (-1-2+(((Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$9323 := (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) \times (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$9324 := (-1 \times (Q(2 \times 3) \times (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$9325 := (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + Q((Q(4)+5+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$9326 := (-1+2+(((Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$9327 := ((-1-2+Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$9328 := (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3+4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$9329 := (((-1+Q(Q(2+3))) \times Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9))$$

$$9330 := (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)+6+7+8+9)))$$

$$9331 := (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$9332 := (((-1+2+3) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - 6))) - Q((7+8+9)))$$

$$9333 := (-1+2-(Q(Q(3)) - (4 + Q((Q(5+6)) - (7+8+9))))$$

$$9334 := (((-1-2) \times (Q(3) + Q(4))) + Q((Q(5+6)) - (7+8+9)))$$

$$9335 := (-1 + ((Q(((2+3) \times 4)) - (5+6)) \times (7+8+9)))$$

$$9336 := (((-1+Q(Q(2+3))) \times (4+(5+6))) - (7+8+9))$$

$$9337 := (-1 + (2 \times (Q((Q(3)+4)) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$9338 := (-1-2+(((Q(Q(3)) - 4) \times Q((5+6))) + 7+8+9))$$

$$9339 := (-1 + ((2 \times (Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) - 5)) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$9340 := (Q((-1+2+(Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))$$

$$9341 := (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) - (4 + (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)))$$

$$9342 := (-1+2+(((Q(Q(3)) - 4) \times Q((5+6))) + 7+8+9))$$

$$9343 := (-1 - (Q(2^3) \times (4 - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$9304 := (Q((-9 \times 8 + Q(7+6))) - (5 + Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9305 := ((-9 - (8+7)) - ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9306 := (-9 \times ((Q(Q(8))/(7-6-5)) - (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9307 := (-9 + ((Q(8) \times (Q(7+6) - Q(5))) + Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9308 := (-9 - (((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times 6) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9309 := (Q((-9 - (8+7)) + Q(6+5)) - Q(4+3+2+1))$$

$$9310 := (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7+6)) + 5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$9311 := (Q((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7+6)))) - (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9312 := (((-9 \times (Q(8) + 7+6)) + 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9313 := (-9 - ((8 \times (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5+4)))) + 3+2+1))$$

$$9314 := (Q((-9 \times 8 + Q(7+6))) + (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9315 := (-9 - (Q((8+7+6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9316 := ((-9 + Q(8)) - (Q(7) \times (Q(6) - Q(5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9317 := (-9 - (Q((8-7+6)) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9318 := (-9 - (((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times 6) - 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9319 := (-9+8 - (Q(7) + ((6 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9320 := ((-9+8) \times (Q(7) + ((6 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9321 := (Q((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7+6)))) + (5 + Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9322 := (((-9+8) \times 7) - ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9323 := (-9+8 - (Q((7-6+Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9324 := (-9 \times (Q(8+7) - (Q(6) + Q((Q(5)+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9325 := ((-9 \times (Q(8+7) - (6 \times Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9326 := (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 - (Q(6) + Q(5+4)))) + Q(Q((3+2+1))))$$

$$9327 := (((-9+8-7) \times 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9328 := (-9-8 + ((Q(7+Q(6)) \times 5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9329 := ((-9-8+7) - (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9330 := (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7+6)) + (Q(5) + 4+3+2+1))$$

$$9331 := (-9+8-7 - (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9332 := (((-9 \times (Q(8) + 7+6)) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9333 := (((-9+8) \times (7 \times 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9334 := (Q((-9 \times 8 + Q(7+6))) + (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9335 := ((-9+8+7) - ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9336 := (-9 - (Q(8) - Q((7 + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$9337 := (-9 \times 8 + Q((7 + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9338 := (-9 - (((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times 6) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9339 := (((-9 - Q(8)) \times 7) - (6 \times Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9340 := (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7) + Q(6+5))) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$9341 := (Q((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7+6)))) + (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9342 := ((-9 \times (Q(8) + 7)) + (6 - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9343 := ((-9 \times (8 + (7+6) \times 5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9344 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (Q(3) + Q(Q(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9345 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q(4))) - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9346 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) \times 4))) + (Q((5 + 6)) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9347 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times (Q((5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9348 &:= ((-1 - 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q((Q(4) - 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9349 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) + (4 - (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9350 &:= (((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(Q(4)))) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9351 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9352 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9353 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9354 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3 + 4)))) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9355 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9356 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9357 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9358 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9359 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4))) + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9360 &:= ((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9361 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9362 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) - 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9363 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + (Q(3) + Q(4 + 5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9364 &:= (Q(((-1 + (2 \times Q(3 + 4))) - 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9365 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) - 5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9366 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times Q(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9367 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) \times (4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9368 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) + (Q(4) - Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9369 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2^3))) + (Q((4 + (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9370 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) + ((4 - Q(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9371 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9372 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9373 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 \times 4)) + Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9374 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3 + 4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9375 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9376 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) - (4 + Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9377 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((Q(3) \times (4 - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9378 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((Q(3) \times (4 - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9379 &:= (Q((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + Q(4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9380 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) + (4 - Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9381 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9382 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9383 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (Q(4) \times ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9344 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((Q(7 + Q(6)) \times 5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9345 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7 + 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9346 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9347 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (7 \times (6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9348 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9349 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9350 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + 7)) - (6 + 5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9351 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (Q(7) + (6 + Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9352 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9353 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 + 6) \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9354 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9355 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + 6) \times 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9356 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9357 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7 - 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9358 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(Q(((7 - 6) \times 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9359 &:= (Q((-9 \times 8 + Q(7 + 6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9360 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + Q(7))) \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9361 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9362 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9363 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times 7) + ((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9364 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7) + (6 + 5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9365 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 + 7)) - ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9366 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + Q(7))) - (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9367 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - 7)^6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9368 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times 7) - (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9369 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (Q(7) + (Q((6 \times 5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9370 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7 + 6)) - (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9371 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7 - 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9372 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8) + 7)) + (6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9373 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 + 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9374 &:= (Q((-9 \times 8 + Q(7 + 6))) - (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9375 &:= (Q((-9 - 8 + 7 \times 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9376 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7)/6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9377 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7 \times 6) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9378 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 \times 6) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9379 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + (7 + Q(6)))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9380 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 \times 7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9381 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 + 7)/6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9382 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8) + 7) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9383 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(7))/6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9384 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3 + 4)))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9385 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9386 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9387 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q((Q(4) + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9388 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + Q(((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9389 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2 + 3))) \times Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9390 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9391 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 - (Q(4) - Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9392 &:= (Q((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) \times ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9393 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + (Q(4) \times ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9394 &:= ((-1 + ((Q(2 + Q(3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9395 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9396 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) + ((4 + 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9397 &:= (((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) \times (4 + Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9398 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + Q(3)) - (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9399 &:= (-1 + (((Q((2 \times Q(3))) + Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9400 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9401 &:= (((-1 + 2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9402 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9403 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (3 + 4)) + Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9404 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3 + 4)))) + (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9405 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q(4))) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9406 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) - (4 - Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9407 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((Q(Q(3)) - 4)) - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9408 &:= (-1 + Q(((2 \times (Q(3) \times 4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9409 &:= Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9410 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(4) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9411 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9412 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9413 &:= ((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))) + Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9414 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3 + 4)))) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9415 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9416 &:= (-1 + (((2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4)) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9417 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4)) + Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9418 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9419 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) - Q(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9420 &:= (((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3)))) - 4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9421 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9422 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3 + 4)))) - ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9423 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9384 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9385 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times 7) + (Q((6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9386 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((Q(7) - (6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9387 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (Q(Q(7)) - (6 \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9388 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - 7 + 6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9389 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((Q(7) \times (6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9390 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7 + 6)) - (5 - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9391 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) - (7 \times Q(6))) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9392 &:= (-9 - 8 + Q((7 + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9393 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times 7) + (6 \times Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9394 &:= (Q((-9 \times 8 + Q(7 + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9395 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times Q((Q(7) + 6)))/5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9396 &:= (Q(Q((-9 + 8 + 7))) + Q((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9397 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + (6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9398 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((7 - 6 + Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9399 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) \times (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9400 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7 + 6)) + (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9401 &:= (((-9 - 8 + 7) + Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9402 &:= ((-9 + Q(8 - 7) \times 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9403 &:= ((-9 + 8 - 7 + Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9404 &:= (Q((-9 \times 8 + Q(7 + 6))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9405 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (((7 + 6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9406 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((7 + 6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9407 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (((7 \times 6) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9408 &:= (-9 + 8 + Q((7 + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9409 &:= Q((-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (6 - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9410 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) + (7 - 6))) - (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9411 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9412 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 + 6 - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9413 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + (6 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9414 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - Q(Q(6)))) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9415 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9416 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((7 + 6 - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9417 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - (((7 + 6) + Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9418 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((7 - (6 - 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9419 &:= (Q(((-9 - (8 + 7)) + Q(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9420 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((7 - 6 - 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9421 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) + (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9422 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times 7) + (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9423 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8)) - (((7 - 6)^5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9424 &:= (-1 + (Q((2+3) \times Q(4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9425 &:= (Q((-1 + Q((2+3+4)))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9426 &:= ((Q((-1-2+Q(3))) \times (Q(Q(4)) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9427 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) + (Q(4) \times ((5+6) + Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
9428 &:= ((-1 + ((2+3) \times 4)) + Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
9429 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) + (4 + Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9430 &:= (((-1 + (Q(2+Q(3))) + Q(Q(4)))) \times Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9431 &:= ((-1-2+Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
9432 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
9433 &:= (Q((-1+2+(Q(Q(3)) + (4+(5+6)))))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9434 &:= (Q((-1+(2 \times Q(3+4)))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
9435 &:= ((-1+2+Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
9436 &:= (-1-2-(Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9437 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9438 &:= ((-1-2+Q(Q(3))) \times Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9439 &:= (Q((Q(-1+2+3) + Q(4+5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9440 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) - (Q(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
9441 &:= (-1-2+(Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
9442 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
9443 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(3) \times 4) + Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9444 &:= (Q((-1+(2 \times Q(3+4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
9445 &:= (-1+2+(Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
9446 &:= (-1+2+((Q(3) \times 4) + Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9447 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9448 &:= (-1 - ((2+Q(3)) \times (Q(4) + (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9449 &:= (-1 + ((Q((2 \times Q(3))) - 4 - 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9450 &:= ((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9451 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + ((5+6) - Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
9452 &:= (-1 + (((2+Q(3)) \times 4) + Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9453 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3+4)))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9454 &:= (Q((-1+2+(Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9455 &:= (-1 - (Q(2^3) - (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9456 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2^3) - (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9457 &:= (-1 - ((2^{Q(3)}) - (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9458 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{Q(3)}) - (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9459 &:= (-1+2+(Q(3+4) + Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9460 &:= ((-1-2-(Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(4)))) \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9461 &:= (-1-2+(Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9462 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9463 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(3)^4) + (Q((5+6)) \times (7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9424 &:= (Q((-9 \times 8 + Q(7+6))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9425 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q((Q(7) + (6+5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9426 &:= (-9 - (((8+7) \times Q(6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9427 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((Q(7) - (6+5)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - (3+2+1)))))) \\
9428 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) - 7 + 6 + 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9429 &:= (-9 + 8 + (Q(7) + (6 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9430 &:= ((((-9 + Q(8)) - Q(7+6)) \times 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9431 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + 7) + Q(Q((6-5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9432 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7+6-5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9433 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 \times 6) \times Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9434 &:= (Q((-9+8 \times 7)) + Q((Q((6+5-4)) + Q((3+2+1)))))) \\
9435 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7+6))) \times 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9436 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) - (7+6 - Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9437 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + 6)) - 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9438 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8) - 7 + 6)) + 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9439 &:= ((Q((-9+8+Q(7)))/Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9440 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8) + (7-6))) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9441 &:= (Q((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7+6)))) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
9442 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + 7 + 6 + 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9443 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7+6 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9444 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((Q(7) \times (6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9445 &:= (Q((-9+8+7)) + Q((Q(6+5) - (4 \times (3+2+1)))))) \\
9446 &:= (-9 - (((8+7) \times Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9447 &:= (Q((-9+8+7)) + (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9448 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) - ((7-6) - Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9449 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 \times 6) \times Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9450 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) - 7 - 6) \times Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
9451 &:= (-9 - (((8+7) - Q(6+Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
9452 &:= ((-9-8) \times (Q(7+6) - (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9453 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) - (Q(7+6) - (Q(Q(5+4)) + Q((3+2+1)))))) \\
9454 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q(7)) + (6 - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9455 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times ((7 \times 6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9456 &:= ((-9 + ((8+7) \times 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9457 &:= ((-9 \times (8+Q(7))) - ((6 \times 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9458 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8) - 7 + 6)) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9459 &:= (Q((-9 \times 8 + Q(7+6))) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
9460 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((Q(7) \times (6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9461 &:= ((-9+8) \times ((Q(7) \times (6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9462 &:= (-9 - ((8 - Q(7)) \times (6 + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9463 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q(7) - ((6-5) - Q(4+3+2+1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9464 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3 + 4)))) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9465 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9466 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(3)^4) + (Q((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9467 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 + (Q((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9468 &:= (((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times Q((Q(4) - 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9469 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9470 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 + (Q((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9471 &:= (-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9472 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (Q(4) - Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9473 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 + 3 + 4))) + Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9474 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - (Q(4) - Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9475 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (Q(4) - Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9476 &:= (-1 - (Q((2 + (Q(3) + Q(4)))) \times ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9477 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9478 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) + (Q((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9479 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times (Q(Q(4)) \times 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9480 &:= ((-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - Q((4 \times 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9481 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(4) + (Q((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9482 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) + (Q((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9483 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(3) \times ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9484 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9485 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times Q(3 + 4)) - Q(Q(5))) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9486 &:= (Q(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9487 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) \times ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9488 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times Q(4)) + Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9489 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) + Q((Q(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9490 &:= ((-1 - Q(2^3)) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9491 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9492 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(4) \times ((5 + 6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9493 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9494 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + 3) - (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9495 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) - (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9496 &:= (Q(Q(-1 + 2 + 3)) + ((Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9497 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + ((4 \times 5) + Q((Q(Q(6)) / (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9498 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((Q(Q(3)) \times (4 - Q((5 + 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9499 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + 3) \times ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9500 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) + (Q((4 \times 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9501 &:= (-1 - (2 \times Q(3) - (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9502 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9503 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) + Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9464 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + Q((7 + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9465 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9466 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7 + 6) \times Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9467 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + 6)) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9468 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (((7 \times 6) \times Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9469 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - ((7 - 6) \times 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9470 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9471 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6) \times 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9472 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q(7 + 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9473 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q(7)) + Q(Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9474 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (6 - 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9475 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (Q(6 + Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9476 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + Q(7))) - (6 + 5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9477 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9478 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times 7) - (6 + 5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9479 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times Q((7 + 6 - 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9480 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 + 6) \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9481 &:= (-9 + (Q((Q(8) + (7 - 6))) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) - Q(Q((3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9482 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8) + 7)) + Q(6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9483 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times Q(7))) - (Q((6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9484 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) + (6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9485 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9486 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (Q((Q(6) + 5)) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9487 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + Q(7))) + Q(Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9488 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q((7 + 6 - 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9489 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 + 6) \times 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9490 &:= ((((-9 - Q(8)) \times 7) + (6 - 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9491 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times 6) + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9492 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) - (6 - Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9493 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + ((6 + 5 + Q(Q(4))) \times Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9494 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - (Q(Q(6)) - 5))) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9495 &:= (-9 - ((Q(Q(8)) - Q((Q(7) + (6 + 5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9496 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7) - Q(6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9497 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6 - 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9498 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + Q(7))) + (6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9499 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + (7 + Q(6)))) - (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9500 &:= (((-9 + Q(8 + 7)) - Q(6 + 5)) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9501 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 \times (6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9502 &:= (-9 - (Q((Q(8) - (7 \times 6))) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9503 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9504 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3)))/Q(4)) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 9504 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9505 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) & 9505 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 \times 6) \times Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9506 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9506 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + Q(7))) - (6 - Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9507 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) + Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))))) & 9507 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9508 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) - (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) & 9508 &:= ((((-9 - Q(8)) \times 7) - (6 - Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9509 &:= (-1 - (((2 + Q(Q(3))) - Q((4 \times 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9509 &:= (Q(((9 - (8 + 7)) + Q(6 + 5))) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9510 &:= ((Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 9510 &:= (((9 - 8 + 7) + Q(6 + Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9511 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9511 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (Q(7) + (6 + 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9512 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) & 9512 &:= (((9 + 8 - 7) \times (Q(6) + Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9513 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9513 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times 7) + ((6 \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9514 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9514 &:= (Q((-9 \times 8 + Q(7 + 6))) + (5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9515 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9515 &:= (((9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9516 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))) & 9516 &:= ((9 + Q(8)) - ((Q(7) \times (6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9517 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) & 9517 &:= (((9 \times (8 + Q(7))) + 6 \times 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9518 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9518 &:= (((9 - Q(Q((8 - 7 + 6))))/5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9519 &:= (-1 - ((2 - 3) \times (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) & 9519 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9520 &:= ((Q(-1 + 2 + 3) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 9520 &:= (((9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7 + 6)) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9521 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9521 &:= (((9 + 8) \times (Q(Q(7)) - 6))/5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9522 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9522 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9523 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9523 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((7 - Q(6 + Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9524 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9524 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) \times 7 - (6 - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9525 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9525 &:= (-9 - (Q((8 + 7 + 6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9526 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) \times 4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9526 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7) \times (6 + 5 + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9527 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) & 9527 &:= ((9 - 8 + Q(7 + 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9528 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(Q(3))) \times Q((Q(4) - 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 9528 &:= (((9 \times (8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6) + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9529 &:= (Q(((9 - 2) \times 3)) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9529 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + (7 + Q(6)))) + (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9530 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(3) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) & 9530 &:= ((9 + 8 - 7 + Q(6 + Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9531 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 + 5 - (6 \times Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) & 9531 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) + Q(6)) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9532 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - ((4 - Q((5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) & 9532 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times 7) + (6 + 5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9533 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) + (Q((5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9533 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q((Q(7) + 6)) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) - Q((3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9534 &:= ((-1 + (((2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4) \times Q((5 + 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) & 9534 &:= (Q((-9 \times 8 + Q(7 + 6))) + (Q(5) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9535 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times Q(4))) \times Q((5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) & 9535 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (Q(7) - (Q(Q(6)) - ((5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9536 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9536 &:= ((9 \times (Q(8) - 7 - 6)) - (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9537 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q(3) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) & 9537 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (Q(7) - ((Q(6) + Q(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9538 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) \times ((4 \times Q((5 + 6))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) & 9538 &:= (((9 \times Q(8)) - (7 - Q(6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9539 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4 + 5) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) & 9539 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 - Q(6 + Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9540 &:= (((-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3))/4) - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 9540 &:= (-9 \times (((8 + 7) - Q(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9541 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4) + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9541 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9542 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q((4 \times Q(5))) + (Q(6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) & 9542 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times 7) + ((6 - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9543 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + Q(3)) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q((Q((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))))) & 9543 &:= ((9 + 8 + Q(7 + 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9544 &:= (-1 + (Q(2+3) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9545 &:= (Q((-1+2 \times 3)) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9546 &:= ((-1 - (2+3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) - (Q(Q(6)) + Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
9547 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + ((5+6) + Q((7+8+9)))) \\
9548 &:= (-1 + (Q(((2 \times Q(3+4)) - 5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9549 &:= (Q((-1+2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) - 5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9)) \\
9550 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((3 \times 4)) + Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9551 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) + (Q((5+6)) + 7+8+9))) \\
9552 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2 \times 3) \times 4) + Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9553 &:= (Q((Q(-1+2+3) - 4)) + Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
9554 &:= (Q((-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))))) + (5 + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9555 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(3) + Q(Q(4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
9556 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9557 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9558 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9559 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3+4)))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9560 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9561 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (4 \times (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9562 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 \times (Q(5) \times (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9563 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + (Q(Q(6)) + 7+8+9)))) \\
9564 &:= (((-1 - Q(2+3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
9565 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + Q((4 + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
9566 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9567 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((Q(Q(3)) - Q((4 \times 5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9568 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3+4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
9569 &:= (Q((-1+2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
9570 &:= (((-1 + Q(2+3)) \times Q((4 \times 5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
9571 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((Q(Q(3)) - Q((4 \times 5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9572 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + Q((Q(Q(6)) / (7+8+9)))))) \\
9573 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times Q((3 \times 4) - 5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
9574 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3) + Q(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
9575 &:= (-1 - (Q((2 \times Q(3)) - ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9576 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2 \times 3)) + Q((Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9577 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3)))) + Q((Q((Q(4) - 5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9578 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3+4))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9579 &:= (Q((-1+2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
9580 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
9581 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - Q(3)) \times ((4 + Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9582 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) - (4 - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
9583 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
9544 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8+7) - Q(Q(6)))) + (5 - Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9545 &:= (-9 - (Q((8+7+6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9546 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8) - 7 - 6)) + 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9547 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q(Q(7))) - (6 \times ((5+4) - Q(Q((3+2+1)))))) \\
9548 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + Q(7))) + (Q(6) + Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9549 &:= (-9 + ((8 + Q(7+6)) \times ((5+4) \times (3+2+1)))) \\
9550 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 - Q(6)) \times Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9551 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) + Q((6 \times 5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
9552 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 + Q(6+5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9553 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (Q(7) - (Q(6) \times 5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
9554 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times 7 - (6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9555 &:= (-9 - ((Q((8+7+6)) - 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9556 &:= (-9 + (((8+7) \times (6 + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9557 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (Q(6) + Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9558 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - 6 + Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9559 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (Q(Q((7 - (6 - 5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9560 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7+6) + 5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
9561 &:= ((-9+8) \times (Q(7) - (Q(6+Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9562 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times (7 - (6 - 5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9563 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + Q((Q((7+6-5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
9564 &:= ((-9 \times ((8+7) - Q(6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9565 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7 - (Q(6) + Q(Q(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
9566 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8) - 7 - 6)) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9567 &:= (((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) \times 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9568 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q(7+6)) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9569 &:= (-9 - (8 \times Q(7) + ((6 \times 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9570 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7+6) - (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9571 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) + (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9572 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((7 \times (Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9573 &:= ((((-9+8) \times 7) \times (Q(6) + Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9574 &:= (-9 + 8 - (((Q(7) + Q(6)) \times 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9575 &:= (-9 - ((Q((8+7+6)) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9576 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times (7 - (6 \times Q(5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9577 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - ((7 \times 6) - Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9578 &:= (Q((-9 \times 8 + Q(7+6))) + (Q(5) + (4 \times Q((3+2+1)))))) \\
9579 &:= (((-9 - 8 - Q(7)) \times 6) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9580 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7+6) + 5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\
9581 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + (7 + (6 \times Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9582 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - (((Q(Q(7)) - Q(6)) / 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9583 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (Q(Q(7)) - Q((6 + ((5+4) \times (3+2+1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9584 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2+3)) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
9585 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2 \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
9586 &:= ((Q(((-1+2) \times 3))^4) + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
9587 &:= (-1+2 + ((Q(3)^4) + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
9588 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
9589 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q(3) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
9590 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (4 + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
9591 &:= (-1+2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (4 + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
9592 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3) + Q(4+5)))) - (Q(6) - (7+8+9))) \\
9593 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) \times (4 + Q((5 - (6 - (7+8+9)))))))) \\
9594 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9595 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9596 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3+4)))) - (Q(5) + (6 - (7+8+9)))) \\
9597 &:= (-1 + (Q(2+Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4+5)) + Q((Q(Q(6)))/(7+8+9)))))) \\
9598 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3+4))) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9599 &:= (Q((-1+2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
9600 &:= (Q((-1 + (2+3+4))) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9601 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9602 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + (Q(4) + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
9603 &:= (-1+2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + (Q(4) + Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
9604 &:= Q(((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3))) - (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
9605 &:= (-1+2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + (4 - ((5+6) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9606 &:= ((-1 - (2+3)) + (((Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times Q(6)) + Q((7+8+9)))) \\
9607 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (Q(Q((Q(4) - (5+6)))) + Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
9608 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3+4)))) - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
9609 &:= (Q((-1+2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
9610 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3+4))) + (Q(5) + (6 - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9611 &:= (-1 + (2^{Q(3)} + (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9612 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q(4)) - (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9613 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (3+4)) \times Q(Q(5))) + (Q(6) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
9614 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4+5) + Q(Q(6)))) + 7+8+9)) \\
9615 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
9616 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3+4)))) - ((5+6) - (7+8+9))) \\
9617 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times Q(Q(3)))) \times (Q((4+Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9618 &:= (((-1+2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (Q(4+5) + Q(6))) + 7+8+9) \\
9619 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times ((4^5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9620 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) - ((Q(Q(4)) \times 5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9621 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - ((Q(4) + Q((5+6))) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
9622 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(4))) \times (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
9623 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(4))) \times (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
9584 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8+7) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
9585 &:= ((-9 + Q(8+7)) - ((6 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9586 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - (7+6+5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9587 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) + (Q(6+Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9588 &:= (-9 - (8 \times Q(7) + (6+5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9589 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + (7 + Q(6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
9590 &:= (((Q((-9+8+Q(7)))/6) \times Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
9591 &:= (-9 - (Q(((8-7-6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9592 &:= (((-9-8 - Q(Q(7)))/6) - (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9593 &:= (Q((-9+Q(8))) + (7 + Q(Q(Q(((6 \times 5)/(4+3+2+1))))))) \\
9594 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
9595 &:= (-9 + Q(((8/(7-6-5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9596 &:= (-9+8 + (7 \times (Q(Q(6)) - (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9597 &:= (-9 + (Q(8+7) + (6 - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9598 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7+6) + 5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9599 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (Q(7+6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9600 &:= ((-9 + ((8+7+6) \times 5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
9601 &:= (-9 + (Q(((8-7) + 6 \times 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
9602 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - ((7+Q(6)) \times Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9603 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7+Q(6)) \times Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9604 &:= Q(((-9+8 \times 7) + (Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9605 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - Q(7+Q(6))) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
9606 &:= (-9 - (((Q(8) + 7+6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9607 &:= ((-9 + Q((8 \times 7))) - (Q(Q(6)) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9608 &:= (((-9 \times (8+Q(7))) + Q(6+5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9609 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + (7 + Q(6)))) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
9610 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times 7) + Q(6+5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
9611 &:= (-9 + (((8-7) + Q(6+Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
9612 &:= (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9613 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8) + 7)) - Q(Q(6)))/5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
9614 &:= (Q((-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) + Q(6+5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
9615 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (Q(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9616 &:= (-9 + ((Q(8) + 7+6) \times (Q(5) + Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9617 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + Q(6+5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9618 &:= (-9 - (((Q(Q(8)) + 7)/(6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9619 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + (7 + Q(6)))) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
9620 &:= ((-9 + (Q(8) + (7 + Q((6 \times 5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
9621 &:= (Q(((-9+Q(8)) - 7 - 6) + (Q(Q(5+4)) + Q(Q((3+2+1)))))) \\
9622 &:= ((-9 \times ((8-7) + (Q(6) + 5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9623 &:= (-9 - (((Q((8 \times 7)) - Q(Q(6)))/5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9624 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) - Q(4)) \times (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9625 &:= ((-1+2 - (3 \times 4)) \times (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9626 &:= (-1+2 - ((Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(4))) \times (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
9627 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (4 + (5+6)))))) + 7+8+9) \\
9628 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3+4)))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
9629 &:= (Q((-1+2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
9630 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q((Q(3) + (4+5)))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
9631 &:= (Q((-1+2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4+5 - Q((Q(Q(6)) / (7+8+9)))))) \\
9632 &:= (Q((-1+2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 + (Q((5+6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
9633 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q((3 \times 4) - 5)))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
9634 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3) + Q(4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
9635 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2 \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (5+6))) + 7+8+9)) \\
9636 &:= ((Q((-1 - 2 + Q(3))) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (5+6))) + 7+8+9) \\
9637 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) - (4 \times Q(5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9638 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3+4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
9639 &:= (Q((-1+2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
9640 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 + Q(3)) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9641 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9642 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2+3))) \times Q(4)) - ((Q(5) \times 6) - Q((7+8+9)))) \\
9643 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3))) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + (6 + Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
9644 &:= (Q((-1+2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (Q((5+6)) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
9645 &:= (-1 - (Q((2 \times Q(3)) - (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9646 &:= (-1 \times (Q((2 \times Q(3)) - (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9647 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((Q(Q(3)) \times 4) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9648 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) \times (Q(4) + ((5+6) + Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
9649 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (3+4)) \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9650 &:= (((-1+2-3) + Q(4)) \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9) \\
9651 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2+3) \times 4))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9652 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2 + Q(3)))) - (((4+5) \times Q(6)) + 7+8+9)) \\
9653 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9654 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(3) - (Q(Q(4)) + Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9655 &:= (Q((-1 + Q(2 \times 3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9656 &:= (((-1 + Q((2+3+4))) \times Q((5+6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
9657 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9658 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3+4)) + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
9659 &:= (-1 - ((2 - Q((Q(3) + (4+5)))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9660 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(3) + (4+5)))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
9661 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2 + Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9662 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4+5) + Q(Q(6)))) - (7+8+9))) \\
9663 &:= (-1 + (Q(2^3) \times (Q((Q(4) - 5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
9624 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8+7) - Q(Q(6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
9625 &:= (((-9 - (8-7) \times 6) \times Q(5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9626 &:= ((-9+8 + (7 \times Q(6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9627 &:= (-9 + (Q(8+7) + (Q(6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9628 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + ((Q(7) \times 6) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9629 &:= (((-9 - 8 - Q(7)) \times 6) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
9630 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 - (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9631 &:= ((-9 \times (Q((8-7) \times 6) + 5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9632 &:= ((-9+8-7) \times (Q(Q(6)) - Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9633 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(7+Q(6)) + (Q(Q(5+4)) + Q(Q((3+2+1)))))) \\
9634 &:= (Q((-9 \times 8 + Q(7+6))) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
9635 &:= (((-9 - Q(8)) \times ((7-6) \times 5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9636 &:= ((-9 - Q(8)) \times ((Q(Q(7)) - Q((Q(6) + Q(5)))) / (4+3+2+1))) \\
9637 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + Q(7))) + (6 \times Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9638 &:= (-9+8 - (Q((Q(7) - (6 \times 5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9639 &:= ((-9+8) \times (Q((Q(7) - (6 \times 5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9640 &:= (Q((-9+8 \times (7+6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
9641 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((7 \times (Q(6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9642 &:= ((-9 \times ((8-7) + Q(6))) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9643 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (Q(7) - Q(Q(6)))) + ((5+4) \times Q((3+2+1)))))) \\
9644 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8+7) - Q(Q(6)))) - (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
9645 &:= (-9 - (Q(8+7) + (Q(6+5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9646 &:= (Q((-9+8+7)) + (Q(6+Q(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
9647 &:= (((-9+8 - Q((7 \times 6))) / 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9648 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) - Q(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
9649 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8) - Q(((7-6) \times 5)))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9650 &:= (((-9+8-7-6) \times Q(5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9651 &:= ((-9 \times Q(8-7) \times 6) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9652 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (Q(7) \times 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9653 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9654 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8+7) - Q(Q(6)))) + 5+4+3+2+1) \\
9655 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + (Q(Q(6)) + (5 - Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9656 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8+7)) + Q((Q(6) + 5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9657 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7 - (Q(Q(6)) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9658 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7+Q(6)) \times Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9659 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7+6+5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9660 &:= (Q((-9+8 \times (7+6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
9661 &:= (-9 + (((8+Q(7)) \times 6) + Q(Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
9662 &:= ((-9 \times ((8-7) + Q(6))) - (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9663 &:= (((-9+8+Q(7)) \times 6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9664 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9665 &:= (Q(Q((-1-(2-(3+4)))))) + Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9))) \\
9666 &:= ((-1 + ((Q(Q(2+3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
9667 &:= (((Q(Q((-1+2 \times 3))) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6)) - (7+8+9)) \\
9668 &:= (-1 - ((2+Q(3)) \times (Q(4) + (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9669 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - Q(3)) \times (Q(4) + (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9670 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) - ((Q(4) - 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9671 &:= (-1 - ((2^3) \times (Q(4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
9672 &:= ((-1+2-Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
9673 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9674 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times Q((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)))) + Q(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
9675 &:= (-1+2+(Q(3)+(Q(Q(4))+Q((Q((5+6))-(7+8+9)))))) \\
9676 &:= (Q((-1+Q(2+3))) + (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9677 &:= (Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4)+Q(5))) + (Q(Q(6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
9678 &:= (((-1 - (Q(Q(2+3)) + Q(Q(4)))) \times (Q(5) - Q(6))) - (7+8+9)) \\
9679 &:= (-1 - ((2+Q(3)) \times ((4 \times 5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9680 &:= ((-1+2 - (Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(4)))) \times (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
9681 &:= ((-1-2+Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9682 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9683 &:= (-1 + ((Q(Q(2 \times 3)) \times 4) + (5 \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9684 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3+4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9685 &:= ((-1+2+Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9686 &:= (-1 - (((2+Q(Q(3))) \times (4 - Q((5+6)))) + 7+8+9)) \\
9687 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) - Q(Q(3))) \times (4 - Q((5+6)))) - (7+8+9)) \\
9688 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4+5 - (6 \times Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
9689 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
9690 &:= ((-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) \times (4+5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
9691 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + ((5+6) - Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
9692 &:= (-1 - ((Q((2 \times Q(3))) - Q(Q(4+5))) - (6 \times Q((7+8+9)))))) \\
9693 &:= ((-1-2) \times (Q(3) - ((Q(Q(4)) - Q((5+6))) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
9694 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) - (4 - Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9695 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3^4) + Q((5+6))) \times (7+8+9)))) \\
9696 &:= ((-1+2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (4 \times Q((5+6)))))) \times (7+8+9)) \\
9697 &:= (Q(((-1+2-3) + Q(4+5))) + (6 \times Q((7+8+9)))) \\
9698 &:= (Q((((-1+2)^3) + Q(4))) + Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
9699 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(Q(3))) - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
9700 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3+4))) + (Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
9701 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) \\
9702 &:= ((-1 + Q(2^3)) \times (4 + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9703 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) \times Q((4 \times (5+6)))) + 7+8+9)) \\
9664 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times 7 - Q(6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9665 &:= ((((-9-8+7) \times Q(6)) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9666 &:= (-9 - (((Q(8) + (7-6)) \times 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9667 &:= (-9 - (Q((((8+7) \times 6)/5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9668 &:= ((-9+8 + (Q(7) \times 6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9669 &:= ((((-9 - Q(8)) \times 7) + (Q(6) \times 5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9670 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (Q(7+6) + 5)) + Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
9671 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) \times ((7-6) \times 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9672 &:= (((-9+8-7) \times (Q(6) + 5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9673 &:= ((-9-8) \times (7 - Q((Q(Q(6)) / ((5+4) \times (3+2+1)))))) \\
9674 &:= (-9+8 + ((7+Q(6)) \times Q(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9675 &:= (-9+8 - (Q(7+6+5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9676 &:= ((-9+8) \times (Q(7+6+5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9677 &:= (((-9-8) \times (Q(7) - (6 \times 5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9678 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times Q((Q(5) + 4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9679 &:= (-9+8 + ((7+Q(6+Q(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
9680 &:= (-9+8 - ((Q(7) \times 6) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9681 &:= ((-9+8) \times ((Q(7) \times 6) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9682 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 \times Q(6)) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9683 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (Q(7+Q(6)) - Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
9684 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + ((7 - Q(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9685 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) - ((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9686 &:= (-9+8 + ((7 \times Q(Q(6))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9687 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (Q(7) - (6+5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9688 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + Q(Q(Q(((6 \times 5) / (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9689 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7+6))) + Q(Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9690 &:= (((-9-8+7) \times (6+Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9691 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) + (Q(6) + 5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9692 &:= ((-9 + Q(((8 \times (7+6)) - 5))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
9693 &:= (-9 \times ((Q(Q(8)) - (7 - Q(Q(6)))) / (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9694 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7+6+5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9695 &:= (((-9+8 - Q(7)) \times 6) - (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9696 &:= (-9-8 - ((7 \times (Q(6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9697 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + (7-6)))) + Q(Q(Q(((5+4) - (3+2+1)))))) \\
9698 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - Q(7))) - ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9699 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) + ((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9700 &:= (((-9 - (8+7)) + Q(6+5)) \times Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
9701 &:= (Q((-9 + (((8+7) \times Q(6))/5))) - Q(4+3+2+1)) \\
9702 &:= (-9 - (Q((Q(8) - ((7 \times 6) + 5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9703 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times Q((7 - (6-5)))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

9704 := $(Q((-1-2+Q(Q(3)))) + (4 \times (5+Q(6+7+8+9))))$
9705 := $(-1 - ((Q((2 \times Q(3))) - Q((4 \times Q(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)))$
9706 := $(-1 \times ((Q((2 \times Q(3))) - Q((4 \times Q(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)))$
9707 := $((-1 \times (2+3)) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) + (6 - (7+8+9)))))$
9708 := $((-1 + Q(2+Q(3))) \times Q(4+5) - (Q(6) - (7+8+9)))$
9709 := $(Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9))$
9710 := $((-1+2+Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9)$
9711 := $(Q((-1-2+(Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (Q(5) - Q(6+7+8+9)))$
9712 := $(Q((-1-(2-(3+4)))) \times (Q(Q(5)) + (6 - (7+8+9))))$
9713 := $(-1 - (2 \times (3 + ((4+5) \times (Q(6) - Q((7+8+9))))))$
9714 := $(Q((-1-2+Q(Q(3)))) + (Q((Q(4) - 5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))$
9715 := $((Q(Q((-1+2 \times 3))) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5+6)) + 7+8+9$
9716 := $(-1 + (((2^{Q(3)}) \times Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))))$
9717 := $(-1 - 2 + (Q((Q(3) + (4+5))) \times (6+7+8+9)))$
9718 := $(-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(3) + (4+5))) \times (6+7+8+9)))$
9719 := $(-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) \times ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))))$
9720 := $((-1+2+3) \times (Q(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))$
9721 := $(-1+2+(Q((Q(3) + (4+5))) \times (6+7+8+9)))$
9722 := $(Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + Q((4 + (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9))))$
9723 := $((-1 + Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4+5) - Q((Q(Q(6)) / (7+8+9)))))$
9724 := $(-1 + (Q(Q(2+3)) + (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))))$
9725 := $(Q(Q((-1-(2+3)) + Q(4))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9)))$
9726 := $(Q(Q((-1-2+Q(3)))) + ((Q(Q(4)) + Q(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))$
9727 := $(-1 - ((2^{Q(3)}) \times (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))))$
9728 := $(-1 \times ((2^{Q(3)}) \times (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))))$
9729 := $(Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) + ((4 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)))$
9730 := $(Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) - ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))$
9731 := $(Q((-1-2+(Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (5 - Q(6+7+8+9)))$
9732 := $(Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) - (4 + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9))))$
9733 := $(Q((-1+2+Q(Q(3)))) - (Q(4) - Q(Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))$
9734 := $(-1 + ((2 - (Q(Q(3)) - Q(Q(4)))) \times (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))$
9735 := $(-1 + (Q((2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(4) - 5)))) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$
9736 := $(Q((-1-(2+3)) + (4 \times Q(5))) + Q(6+7+8+9))$
9737 := $(-1 + (2 \times ((Q(3) \times (Q(4) + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(6+7+8+9))))$
9738 := $((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6+7+8+9))$
9739 := $(Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))))$
9740 := $(Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) + (4 - ((5+6) \times (7+8+9))))$
9741 := $(Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6+7+8+9))))$
9742 := $((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3+4)))) - (5 - (6 \times (7+8+9))))$
9743 := $(-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9))))))$

9704 := $(Q((-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) + Q(6+5)))) + Q(4+3+2+1))$
9705 := $(((-9 \times 8 + 7 + 6) \times 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$
9706 := $(-9 + (((8+7) \times (6 - Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$
9707 := $((-9+8-7) \times Q(6)) - (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$
9708 := $(-9 - 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1))))$
9709 := $(-9 + ((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times (Q(6) + (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))$
9710 := $(-9 + 8 - (Q(((7 \times 6) - Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$
9711 := $(-9 + ((8+7) \times ((Q(Q(6)) \times 5) / (4+3+2+1))))$
9712 := $((-9 \times (Q(Q(8)) / (7 + Q(6+5)))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$
9713 := $((((-9+8) \times 7) \times (Q(6) + 5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$
9714 := $((-9 \times (Q(8+7) - Q(Q(6)))) - (Q(5) - Q(4+3+2+1)))$
9715 := $((-9 \times (8+7)) - (6 \times Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$
9716 := $(Q((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7+6)))) + (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))$
9717 := $((((-9+8-7) \times Q(6)) + 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$
9718 := $((-9 \times 8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$
9719 := $(-9 + ((8 \times (7 - (Q(6) + 5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$
9720 := $(-9 - (((8 \times Q(7)) - Q(6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$
9721 := $(-9 - (((Q(8+7) \times 6) / 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$
9722 := $(-9 + 8 - (7 \times Q(6) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))$
9723 := $((((-9+8) \times 7) \times Q(6)) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$
9724 := $(-9 + 8 + (Q((Q(7) + Q(6))) + Q(5 \times (4+3+2+1))))$
9725 := $(-9 - (Q(8+7) + (Q(6) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))$
9726 := $(-9 - 8 - (7 \times Q(6) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))$
9727 := $(-9 + (8 \times (7 + (Q(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))))$
9728 := $(-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (6 \times Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))$
9729 := $(-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) + (6 \times Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))$
9730 := $(-9 + (Q(8) + ((7 + Q(6)) \times Q(5+4+3+2+1))))$
9731 := $((-9 + Q(8)) - (Q(7+6+5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$
9732 := $(-9 + (((8-7 - Q(Q(6))) / 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$
9733 := $(-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7+6) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))$
9734 := $(-9 \times 8 - (Q(7+6) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))$
9735 := $(-9 - (Q(Q(((8+7) - (6+5)))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$
9736 := $(((-9 - (8+7)) \times (6+5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$
9737 := $((((-9+8-7) \times Q(6)) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$
9738 := $(-9 \times (8 - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1))))$
9739 := $(((-9 - Q(Q(8-7) \times 6)) / 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$
9740 := $((-9 + ((8 - Q(7)) \times 6)) - (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$
9741 := $(Q((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7+6)))) + (Q(Q(5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))$
9742 := $(-9 - ((8 \times (Q(7) - Q(Q(6)))) + Q(5+4+3+2+1)))$
9743 := $((((-9+8) \times 7) \times Q(6)) - (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$

$$\begin{aligned}
9744 &:= ((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9745 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 - Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9746 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) \times 4))) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9747 &:= ((-1 - (2^{Q(3)})) \times (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9748 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9749 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + (3^4))) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9750 &:= ((-1 + 2 + Q((Q(3) + (4 + 5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9751 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) - Q(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9752 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9753 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3 + 4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9754 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9755 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) \times ((4 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9756 &:= (-1 + (Q(Q(2^3)) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9757 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 + 4)) \times (Q((5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9758 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + Q(4)) \times (Q((5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9759 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(Q(3))) - Q((Q(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))) \\
9760 &:= ((-1 - Q(2 + Q(3))) \times (Q(4) \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9761 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9762 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times Q(4)) - ((5 \times 6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9763 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q((Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4) - 5))) + (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9764 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (Q(4 + 5) + (Q(Q(6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9765 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9766 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) \times 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9767 &:= (-1 - ((2^3) \times (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9768 &:= ((-1 + 2 - Q(3)) \times (4 - Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9769 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9770 &:= ((-1 + (Q(2 + Q(3)) \times Q(4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9771 &:= (Q((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4 \times 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9772 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) \times Q((Q(4) - 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9773 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times Q(4)) - (Q(5) - (6 + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9774 &:= (((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times (4 + Q((5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9775 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9776 &:= (Q(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (Q(4) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9777 &:= (Q((-1 + Q((Q(2 + 3) - (4 + (5 + 6)))))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9778 &:= (-1 - ((2 + Q(3)) \times (Q(4) - (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9779 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q(Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9780 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (4 \times (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9781 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (Q(3) - (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9782 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) - (4 \times Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9783 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + Q((Q(4 + 5) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9744 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9745 &:= (Q((-9 - (8 \times (7 - 6 - 5)))) + (Q(Q(4)) \times Q((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9746 &:= (-9 - ((Q((8 - 7 + 6)) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9747 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + Q(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9748 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q(7 + 6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9749 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + ((7 + 6) \times Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9750 &:= (Q((-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6))) + (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9751 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) + Q(6 + Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9752 &:= (((-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 + Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9753 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7 + 6) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9754 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6)) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9755 &:= (-9 - (Q(8 + 7) + (6 + 5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9756 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (Q(6) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9757 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9758 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) + (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9759 &:= ((Q((-9 + 8 + Q(7)))/6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9760 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) - (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9761 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times Q(6)) + Q(Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9762 &:= (-9 - 8 - (((Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))/5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9763 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + ((Q(7 + 6) - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9764 &:= (-9 \times 8 - ((Q(7 + 6) - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9765 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + 7) - ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9766 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 + 6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9767 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8 + 7) - (6 - 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9768 &:= (-9 - 8 - (((7 + Q(6)) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9769 &:= (-9 - 8 - (((7 + 6 - Q(Q(5))) \times Q(4)) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9770 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(7) + ((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9771 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) + ((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9772 &:= (-9 - (((8 + Q(Q(7)))/6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9773 &:= (((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times Q(6)) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9774 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - (Q(Q(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9775 &:= (((-9 + 8 + Q(Q(7)))/6) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9776 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + (Q(Q(7)) + (6 \times (Q(Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9777 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8 + 7) - (6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9778 &:= (-9 + 8 - (((Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))/5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9779 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))))/5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9780 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times (7 - 6 - 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9781 &:= (((-9 + Q(8)) \times Q(7 + 6)) + (Q(5 + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9782 &:= ((-9 + Q(((8 \times (7 + 6)) - 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9783 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + ((Q(7 + 6) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$9784 := (Q((-1-2+Q(Q(3)))) + (4 \times (Q(5) + Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$9785 := (-1 + (Q(2+Q(3)) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9))))))$$

$$9786 := (Q((Q(-1+2+3) + (Q(4) \times 5))) - (6 - Q((7+8+9))))$$

$$9787 := (((-1-2) \times Q(Q(3))) + Q((4 \times Q(5)))) + 6+7+8+9$$

$$9788 := (Q((-1 + (Q(2+3) \times 4))) + ((5+6) - (7+8+9)))$$

$$9789 := (-1 + (((2 \times Q(Q(3))) + Q(4)) \times (Q(5) + 6+7+8+9)))$$

$$9790 := (-1 \times 2 + (Q((Q(Q(3)) + (4 + (5+6)))) + Q((7+8+9))))$$

$$9791 := (-1 + (Q((2 \times (Q((Q(3) + 4) - Q((5+6)))))) + Q((7+8+9))))$$

$$9792 := (Q((Q(Q((-1+2) \times 3)) + (4 + (5+6)))) + Q((7+8+9)))$$

$$9793 := (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (4 \times Q(5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$9794 := ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - (4 \times Q(5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$9795 := (-1 - ((2 - Q(Q(3))) \times ((4^5) - Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$9796 := (Q((-1 + (Q(2+3) \times 4))) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$9797 := (Q((-1+2+(Q(Q(3))+4))) + Q(Q((Q(5)+(6-(7+8+9))))))$$

$$9798 := (-1-2+(Q(Q(3)) \times Q((Q(4)+(Q(5)-(6+7+8+9))))))$$

$$9799 := (-1 - ((2^3) - Q(4)) \times Q(5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$9800 := ((-1 + (2+3+4)) \times Q(5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$9801 := Q((Q((-1 + (2+3+4))) + 5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$9802 := (-1+2+(Q(Q(3)) \times Q((Q(4)+(Q(5)-(6+7+8+9))))))$$

$$9803 := ((Q((-1+Q(2+3))) \times Q(4)) + ((5+6) + Q((7+8+9))))$$

$$9804 := (((-1-2-Q(Q(3))) \times (4-Q((5+6)))) - (7+8+9))$$

$$9805 := (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (4 \times Q(5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$9806 := (Q((-1 + (Q(2+3) \times 4))) - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$9807 := (-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$9808 := (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$9809 := (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) + (Q(4) \times (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$9810 := ((-1+2+Q(3)) \times (Q(4+5) + Q(6+7+8+9)))$$

$$9811 := ((Q((-1+Q(2+3))) \times Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))$$

$$9812 := (-1 + ((Q(2+Q(3)) \times Q(4+5)) + (Q(6) - (7+8+9))))$$

$$9813 := ((-1 + Q((2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - ((5+6) - (7+8+9)))$$

$$9814 := (Q((-1 + (Q(2+3) \times 4))) - ((5+6) - (7+8+9)))$$

$$9815 := (-1 + (((2 \times Q((3 \times 4))) + Q((5+6))) \times (7+8+9)))$$

$$9816 := (-1-2-(Q(Q(3)) - ((Q(4)-5) \times Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$9817 := (-1 + (2 \times (Q(3) + (4 \times Q(5+6+7+8+9))))$$

$$9818 := (-1 + (((2 - Q(Q(3))) \times (4 - Q((5+6)))) + Q((7+8+9))))$$

$$9819 := (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(Q(3))) - (Q((Q(4) + Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9))))$$

$$9820 := (-1+2-(Q(Q(3)) - ((Q(4)-5) \times Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$9821 := (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) - (4 \times (5 - Q(6+7+8+9))))$$

$$9822 := (-1-2+(((3^4) \times Q((5+6))) + 7+8+9))$$

$$9823 := (-1 \times 2 + (((3^4) \times Q((5+6))) + 7+8+9))$$

$$9784 := ((((-9-8) \times (7+6)) + 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9785 := (-9 - ((Q(8+7) + (6 - Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9786 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9787 := (-9 + Q(Q(8)) - ((Q(7) + (6 - Q(Q(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9788 := (((-9 \times (Q(8) - (7 - Q(6)))) + Q(Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9789 := (-9-8-(Q(7+6) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9790 := (((-9+8) \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9791 := (Q((-9 + (((8+7) \times Q(6))/5))) - (4+3+2+1))$$

$$9792 := (-9 + Q(((8 \times (7+6)) + (5 - (4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9793 := (-9 + ((8 \times (Q(7+Q(6)) - Q(Q(5)))) + 4+3+2+1))$$

$$9794 := (((-9-8) \times (Q(7) - (6 + Q(Q(5)))) - Q(4+3+2+1))$$

$$9795 := (((-9+Q(8)) \times Q(7+6)) + (5 \times Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9796 := ((-9 - (8+7)) - ((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9797 := (-9 - ((Q(8+7) - Q(6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9798 := ((((-9-8) \times Q(7)) + (6 + Q(Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9799 := (-9 - (Q(8) + ((7 + Q(6+5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9800 := ((-9 \times 8 - 7) - (Q(6+5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9801 := Q((-9+8+(Q(7)+(Q(6)+5+4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9802 := (-9 + (Q(((8 \times (7+6)) - 5)) + 4+3+2+1))$$

$$9803 := (-9 + ((8 \times ((7 + Q(Q(6))) - Q(5+4))) + Q((3+2+1))))$$

$$9804 := ((((-9-8) \times (7+6)) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9805 := (-9+8-(Q(7+6) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9806 := (((-9 \times (8+7+6)) - 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9807 := ((-9 + Q((8+7+6))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9808 := ((-9 + Q(8) \times 7) - ((6 + Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9809 := (-9-8-(Q(7+6) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9810 := ((-9 - (Q((8+Q(7))) - Q(Q(6)))) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9811 := (Q((-9 + (((8+7) \times Q(6))/5))) + 4+3+2+1)$$

$$9812 := (-9+8-7-((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9813 := (-9-8-(Q(7) + (Q(6+5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9814 := ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) - (Q(6+5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9815 := (((-9 \times ((8+7) \times 6)) + Q(Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9816 := (((-9 \times (8+7+6)) + 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9817 := (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (Q(6) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))))$$

$$9818 := (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) + (Q(6) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9819 := (-9-8-((Q(7+6) - 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9820 := ((-9 \times ((8-7-6) + Q(5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9821 := ((-9 + ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times 5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))$$

$$9822 := (-9 - (Q((8 + ((7-6) \times 5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1))))$$

$$9823 := ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9824 &:= (-1 + (((2-3) + Q(4)) \times (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9825 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9826 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) \times 4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9827 &:= ((Q((Q((-1 + 2 \times 3)) + 4)) \times (5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9828 &:= ((-1 - 2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(4 + 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9829 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q((Q(4) - 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9830 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2 + Q(3)) \times Q(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9831 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (4 + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9832 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((Q(Q(3)) \times Q((Q(4) - 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9833 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times Q(4)) + (5 + (Q(6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
9834 &:= (-1 + ((Q(2 + 3) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9835 &:= ((Q((-1 + 2 \times 3)) + Q(Q(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9836 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) \times 4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9837 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(3) - ((Q(4) + Q((5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9838 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9839 &:= (-1 + ((Q((2 + Q(Q(3)))) - Q(Q(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9840 &:= ((-1 - 2 - Q(3)) \times ((Q(4) \times 5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9841 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9842 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9843 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (Q(Q(4)) + Q(Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9844 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) - Q(4)) \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9845 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (3 \times 4)) \times (5 - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9846 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (4 + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9847 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q((Q(4) + (5 + 6))) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9848 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 + Q(3)) - (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9849 &:= ((-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(4))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9850 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q(4))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9851 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (4 + (Q((5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9852 &:= (((-1 - 2 - Q(Q(3))) \times (4 - Q((5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9853 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times Q(4)) + (Q(5) + (Q(6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
9854 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) + (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9855 &:= (-1 + (Q(2^3) \times (4 + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
9856 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2 + 3) \times 4))) + (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9857 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - ((4 - 5) + (6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9858 &:= (((-1 - Q(2 + 3)) \times (4 - Q((Q(5) - 6)))) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9859 &:= (-1 - (((2 - Q(3)) \times (Q(Q(4)) \times 5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9860 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9861 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (4 \times (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9862 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4 + 5)) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9863 &:= (-1 - (Q(2 \times 3) - ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9824 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (Q(6) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9825 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(7 + 6) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9826 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9827 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8 + 7) - (Q(6) + Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9828 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (Q(Q(7)) - (Q(Q(6)) - (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9829 &:= (Q((-9 + (Q(8) + (7 + Q(6))))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9830 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) + (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9831 &:= (Q((-9 - (Q(8) - Q(7 + 6)))) + (Q(Q(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9832 &:= (((Q((-9 + Q(8))) - Q((Q(7) + Q(6)))) / Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9833 &:= (-9 - 8 + (Q(7) + Q((Q(6 + 5) - (Q(4) + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9834 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9835 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((Q(7 + 6) - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9836 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7 + 6)) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9837 &:= (-9 + (Q((8 \times 7)) + ((Q(Q(6)) - Q(Q(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9838 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6)) / 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9839 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((Q(7 + 6) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9840 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) - (6 \times Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9841 &:= (-9 - (((8 - 7) \times 6) \times Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9842 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - (6 \times Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9843 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) - (6 \times Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9844 &:= (Q((-9 + Q(8))) + ((Q(7) \times 6) + (Q(Q(5 + 4)) - Q((3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9845 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9846 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + 6) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9847 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) \times (Q(7 + 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9848 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) + ((6 \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9849 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) + ((6 \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9850 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (7 \times (6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9851 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - (7 \times (6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9852 &:= ((-9 - 8 + Q(7)) - ((Q(6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9853 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5))) \times Q(4)) + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9854 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9855 &:= (((-9 \times (Q(8) + 7)) + Q(Q(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9856 &:= ((-9 \times Q(((8 + 7) - (6 + 5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9857 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + Q(7)) \times 6) - (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9858 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6))))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9859 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (6 - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9860 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (Q(7) + (6 - (Q(Q(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9861 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9862 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (((7 + 6) \times 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9863 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q((7 + 6 - 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9864 &:= ((-1 + Q(2 + 3)) \times (Q((Q(4) + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9865 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9866 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9867 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((Q(Q(3)) \times 4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9868 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) \times Q(Q(3))) + Q((4 \times Q(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9869 &:= (-1 + (((Q(Q(2 \times 3))/4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9870 &:= (((Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times 4) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9871 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2 + 3))) \times Q(4)) + (Q(Q(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9872 &:= (Q((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) \times (5 + (Q(6) + Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
9873 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times Q(3)) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9874 &:= (Q((-1 - ((2 \times Q(Q(3))) - Q(Q(4)))) + Q(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9875 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 + 3) - ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9876 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - ((4^5) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9877 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times Q(3))) \times (Q(4) - ((5 + 6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
9878 &:= ((-1 + Q((2 \times Q(3 + 4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9879 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q(4)))) - (Q(Q(5)) - Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9880 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9881 &:= (-1 - (2 \times Q(3) - ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9882 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times Q(3)) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9883 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + Q((Q(4 + 5) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9884 &:= (Q((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) + (Q((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9885 &:= (((-1 + Q(2 \times 3)) \times Q(Q(4))) + (Q(5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9886 &:= (-1 - 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9887 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9888 &:= (-1 + ((2 + Q(3)) \times ((4 - 5) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9889 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (Q(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9890 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(Q(3)) - (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9891 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9892 &:= (-1 + 2 - (Q(3) - ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9893 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9894 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9895 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9896 &:= (-1 \times ((Q(2 + Q(3)) - Q(Q(4 + 5))) - (6 \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9897 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((Q(3) - (4 \times 5)) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9898 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9899 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (Q(Q(3))/4 + 5)) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9900 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 - 4 - 5))) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9901 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((Q(3) - (4 \times 5)) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9902 &:= ((-1 + (Q(Q(2 + 3)) \times Q(4))) - (Q((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9903 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9864 &:= ((-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - Q(Q(6)))) + Q(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9865 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + Q(Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9866 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7 - 6) \times Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9867 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) + (6 + 5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9868 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(7) + (6 + 5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9869 &:= ((-9 - 8 + 7) - (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9870 &:= (-9 - (Q(((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9871 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9872 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) - (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9873 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8) + (Q(7) - (Q(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9874 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (6 - 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9875 &:= (((-9 + Q(((8 \times 7) - Q(6)))) \times Q(5)) + Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9876 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9877 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(7) + ((6 - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9878 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((Q((Q(7) + 6))/Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9879 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times Q((Q(7) + 6)))/Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9880 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) - Q(Q(5)))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9881 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - (Q(7 + 6) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9882 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times (7 + 6)) + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9883 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times Q(6))/5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9884 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9885 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) - (Q(6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9886 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + 7 + 6) \times 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9887 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8 + 7) - Q(6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9888 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9889 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + ((Q(7) - (6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9890 &:= (((-9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9891 &:= (-9 \times (8 - 7 - ((6 + 5) \times Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9892 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 + 6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9893 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(7) + (Q(6) + (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9894 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7 - 6)) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9895 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + 6 - Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9896 &:= (((-9 \times Q((8 + 7 - 6))) + Q(Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9897 &:= ((-9 + 8 \times 7) - (6 \times Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9898 &:= ((-9 + 8 + Q(7)) - (6 \times Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9899 &:= ((((-9 \times 8 - Q(7)) \times 6) + Q(Q(5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9900 &:= ((Q((-9 + Q(8))) - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9901 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9902 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + (Q(((7 - 6) \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9903 &:= (-9 \times 8 - (Q(((7 - 6) \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9904 &:= ((-1+2+3) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6+7+8+9))) & 9904 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8))/(7 - (6 - 5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9905 &:= ((-1+2 \times 3) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6+7+8+9))) & 9905 &:= (-9 - (Q((8+7-6)) + (5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9906 &:= (-1-2 + (Q(3) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 9906 &:= ((-9-8 - (7 \times (6+5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9907 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 9907 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) \times Q(7))/Q(6)) + 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9908 &:= (-1 - ((Q(2+Q(3)) - Q((4 \times Q(5)))) - (6+7+8+9))) & 9908 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + ((Q(7) - (6 \times 5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9909 &:= (Q((-1+2) \times 3) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6+7+8+9))) & 9909 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) + ((7+6+5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9910 &:= (-1+2 + (Q(3) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 9910 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - (7+6+5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9911 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - Q(3)) \times ((4-5) - Q(6+7+8+9))) & 9911 &:= ((-9-8 + Q(7)) - (Q(6+5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9912 &:= ((Q((-1-2+Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q((5+6)))) \times (7+8+9)) & 9912 &:= (((-9+8-7) \times (6+5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9913 &:= (-1 + (Q((2+(3^4))) + Q(Q(5)+6+7+8+9))) & 9913 &:= ((((-9 \times (Q(8) \times 7))/Q(6)) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9914 &:= (Q((-1 \times 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + 4))) + Q(Q(5)+6+7+8+9)) & 9914 &:= (((-9 \times (8+7-6)) - 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9915 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - Q(Q(4)))) + Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))) & 9915 &:= (Q((-9+8+7)) - (Q(6+5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9916 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6+7+8+9))) & 9916 &:= (-9 + (Q(Q(8)) + (Q(7 \times (6+5)) - Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9917 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q(3) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 9917 &:= (-9 - (Q((8-7+6)) + (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9918 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (Q(3) \times (Q((Q(4) - (5+6))) - Q((7+8+9)))))) & 9918 &:= ((-9-8 - (7+6) \times 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9919 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) - Q((4 - (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) & 9919 &:= (-9-8 - (Q((7+6-5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9920 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) + (Q(4) \times (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 9920 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - (7+6-5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9921 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (Q(Q(Q(3))) - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9)))))) & 9921 &:= ((-9+8) \times (Q(7) + ((6 \times 5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9922 &:= ((-1+2+Q(Q(3))) \times Q((Q(4) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) & 9922 &:= ((-9+8 - (7 \times (6+5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9923 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((Q(3+Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 9923 &:= (((-9+8) \times (7 \times (6+5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9924 &:= (-1 + (Q(2+3) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 9924 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7-6-5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9925 &:= (Q((Q((-1 - (2+3)) + Q(4))) - 5) + Q(6+7+8+9)) & 9925 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + Q(Q(7))) + Q((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9926 &:= (-1+2 + ((Q(3+Q(4)) \times Q(5)) + Q(6+7+8+9))) & 9926 &:= ((-9+8 \times 7) - (Q(6+5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9927 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (Q(4) + Q(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 9927 &:= (-9 - (Q(8) - Q((Q(7) + (Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9928 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) - ((4+5-6) \times (7+8+9))) & 9928 &:= (-9 \times 8 + Q((Q(7) + (Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9929 &:= (((-1+Q(Q(2+3))) \times Q(4)) - (Q(5)+6+7+8+9)) & 9929 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + ((7-6)^5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9930 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) - ((4 \times Q(5)) - (6+7+8+9))) & 9930 &:= (((-9+8-7-6) \times 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9931 &:= (Q(Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) - 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 9931 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) + (7-6-5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9932 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) - ((4 \times (5+6)) + 7+8+9)) & 9932 &:= ((-9 \times 8 - 7+6+5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9933 &:= (((-1-2) \times (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)))))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 9933 &:= (((-9+8) \times (7 \times 6)) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9934 &:= (-1 \times (Q(2 \times 3) - (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 9934 &:= ((-9+8 - (7+6) \times 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9935 &:= (-1 + (Q(2 \times 3) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6+7+8+9)))) & 9935 &:= (-9+8 - (Q((7+6-5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9936 &:= (Q((-1-2+Q(3))) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6+7+8+9))) & 9936 &:= ((-9+8) \times (Q((7+6-5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9937 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) - (Q(4+5) + (6 - (7+8+9)))) & 9937 &:= (-9 - (((Q(8+7) \times 6)/Q(5)) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9938 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4)))) + Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))) & 9938 &:= (-9 - (((Q(8) + Q(7)) \times 6) - Q(Q(5))) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9939 &:= ((-1 + Q(((2+3) \times (4 \times 5)))) - (Q(6) + 7+8+9)) & 9939 &:= (-9+8 - (Q(7) + (6+5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9940 &:= ((-1+2+Q(3)) \times ((4^5) - (6+7+8+9))) & 9940 &:= ((-9+8) \times (Q(7) + (6+5 - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9941 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) + (Q((4+Q(5))) - Q(6+7+8+9))) & 9941 &:= (-9 + (Q(8) + (7 - (Q(6+5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9942 &:= ((Q((-1+Q(2+3))) \times Q(4)) + ((Q(5) \times 6) + Q((7+8+9)))) & 9942 &:= (((-9 \times (8-7+6)) + 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9943 &:= (((-1-2) \times Q(3)) + (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9))) & 9943 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 - (6-5)))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9944 &:= ((-1 + (Q(Q(2+3)) \times Q(4))) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9945 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - (2+3)) + Q(4))) - (Q(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9946 &:= (-1 - 2 - ((Q(Q(3)) - Q((4 \times Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9947 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((Q(Q(3)) - Q((4 \times Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9948 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) + (4 \times ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9949 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2+3))) \times Q(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9950 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - ((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9951 &:= (Q((-1 + (Q(2+3) \times 4))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9952 &:= (((-1 + 2 + Q(Q(3))) \times Q((Q(4) - 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9953 &:= (Q(Q(Q((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + ((Q(Q(4)) \times (5 + 6)) + Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9954 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) - Q(4)) \times (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9955 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + Q(4)) \times (5 + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9956 &:= ((((-1 + 2 + 3) + Q(Q(4))) \times Q(5)) + (6 \times Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9957 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (Q(Q(3)) - ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9958 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9959 &:= (((-1 + Q(Q(2+3))) \times Q(4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9960 &:= ((-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + (4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9961 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9962 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((4 \times Q(Q(5))) + Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9963 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + Q((4 \times Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9964 &:= ((-1 + (Q(Q(2+3)) \times Q(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9965 &:= (Q(Q((-1 - (2 + 3)) + Q(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9966 &:= ((Q((-1 + Q(2+3))) \times Q(4)) + (Q(5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9967 &:= ((-1 - 2 + Q(Q((Q(3) - (4 - 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9968 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + Q((4 \times Q(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9969 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9970 &:= (Q(Q((-1 \times (2 - (3 + (4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9971 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9972 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) + Q(4))) - ((5 + 6) - Q((7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9973 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9974 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9975 &:= ((Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3)))) - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9976 &:= (Q((-1 - 2 + Q(Q(3))) - 4) + (5 \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9977 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (Q(3) + (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9978 &:= (-1 - 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9979 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) + (4 + 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9980 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) + (4 \times (Q(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9981 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) + (Q(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9982 &:= (-1 + 2 + (Q(Q(3)) + ((Q(4) - 5) \times Q(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9983 &:= (Q(Q((-1 + 2 + Q(3)))) - (4 - ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9944 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7 - 6)) + Q(5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9945 &:= (-9 - ((Q(8) - (7 + 6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9946 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9947 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) - 7) / (6 + 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9948 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (Q(Q(7)) - Q(Q(6)))) - (Q(5) - Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9949 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(7) + ((6 - 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9950 &:= (-9 + 8 - (Q(7) - Q(Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9951 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (Q(7) - Q(Q(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9952 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (Q(7) - Q(Q(6)))) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9953 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times ((7 \times 6) + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9954 &:= (-9 \times (Q(8 + 7) - (Q(Q(6)) + (Q(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9955 &:= (-9 - (Q(((8 - 7)^6) + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9956 &:= (((-9 - Q(8 + 7)) / 6) - (5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9957 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7 - 6)) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9958 &:= (-9 - 8 - (Q(((7 - 6) \times 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9959 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 - 6 - 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9960 &:= (((-9 - 8 + 7) - (6 \times 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9961 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((Q(7) - (6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9962 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((Q(7) - (6 + 5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9963 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) + (Q(7) \times (6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9964 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9965 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7 + 6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9966 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + Q(7)) - (6 + 5 - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9967 &:= (-9 - ((Q((8 - 7 + 6)) - Q(5)) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9968 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8)) / (7 + 6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9969 &:= (-9 + 8 - ((Q(7) + (6 - Q(5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9970 &:= (-9 + (((Q(8) - Q(7 + 6)) / 5) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9971 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7 - 6)) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9972 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (Q(7) - Q(Q(6)))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9973 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + 7) \times 6) / 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9974 &:= ((-9 / (8 + 7 - 6)) - (Q(5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9975 &:= (-9 - (Q(((8 + 7) - (6 + 5))) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9976 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) - (6 \times 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9977 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + 7) - (6 - 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9978 &:= ((-9 + Q(8)) - (7 \times (6 + 5) - Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9979 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7 + 6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9980 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5))) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9981 &:= ((-9 + 8 - (7 + 6 + 5)) + Q(Q(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9982 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (Q(7) - Q(Q(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9983 &:= (-9 - 8 + Q((Q(7) + (Q(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9984 &:= (Q(Q(-1+2+3)) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9)) & 9984 &:= (((-9 \times Q(8))/Q((7-(6-5)))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9985 &:= (Q((-1+2+(Q(Q(3))+(4+(5+6)))) + Q((7+8+9))) & 9985 &:= (((-9+(8-7) \times 6) \times 5) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9986 &:= (Q(-1+2+3) + (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9))) & 9986 &:= (((-9 \times (8+7)) + Q(6+5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9987 &:= (-1 + (2 \times Q(3) + (Q((4 \times Q(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 9987 &:= ((-9 - ((8+7) - (6+5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9988 &:= (-1 + (Q((2 \times Q(3))) + (Q(Q(4)) + Q((Q((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))))) & 9988 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (Q(7) + (6+5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9989 &:= (-1 + ((Q((2 \times Q(3))) + (4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 9989 &:= ((-9 + (8/(7-6-5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9990 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) + ((4 \times 5) - (6+7+8+9))) & 9990 &:= (-9 - (((8-7)^{65}) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9991 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) + (Q(4) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) & 9991 &:= (-9 + Q(Q((8 - (7+6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9992 &:= (Q(Q((-1+2+Q(3)))) + (Q(Q(4)) - ((5+6) \times (7+8+9)))) & 9992 &:= ((-9 + ((8-7)^{65})) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9993 &:= (((-1-2) \times (Q(3) \times (Q(Q(4)) - Q(Q(5)))))) + 6+7+8+9 & 9993 &:= ((-9 - (8/(7-6-5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9994 &:= (-1 + ((Q(Q(2+3)) \times Q(4)) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 9994 &:= (((-9-8-Q(7))/(6+5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9995 &:= (Q(Q((-1-(2+3)) + Q(4))) + (Q(5) - (6+7+8+9))) & 9995 &:= (((-9+8+7) - (6+5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9996 &:= (Q((-1 + (2 \times Q(3+4)))) + ((5+6) + Q((7+8+9)))) & 9996 &:= (((-9 \times 8)/(7+6+5)) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9997 &:= (-1 - 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))))) & 9997 &:= ((-9/(8 - ((7-6) \times 5))) + Q(Q(4+3+2+1))) \\
9998 &:= (-1 \times 2 + Q((Q(Q(3)) - (Q(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))))) & 9998 &:= (-9 + 8 - (((7-6)^5) - Q(Q(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9999 &:= (-1 + Q((2 \times (Q(Q(3)) + (4 - (5+6+7+8+9)))))) & 9999 &:= (-9 + 8 + Q((Q(7) + (Q(6) + 5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
10000 &:= Q(Q((Q(-1 \times 2 + Q(3)) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)))) & 10000 &:= Q((Q((-9 + Q(8))) - ((7+6) \times Q(5+4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

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